

The Role of Local Political Leaders in Shaping the Planning and Implementation of Health and Social Care Integration: A Case Study from Scotland.

Awais Mashkooor

School of Education and Social sciences

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PhD Thesis

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Declaration

I hereby declare that:

This thesis is my own original work and has not been submitted, in whole or in part, for any other degree or award at any other university or institution. I have acknowledged all the sources of information that I have used in this thesis, both in the text and in the list of references, following the appropriate citation style. I have obtained the necessary permission from the owners of any third-party material that I have included in this thesis and have clearly indicated the source and extent of such material. I have complied with the Chapter 4 regulation on Research Degrees of the University of the West of Scotland, which covers the ethical and academic standards for conducting research.

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Abstract

This thesis examines the role of local political leaders in shaping the planning and implementation of Health and Social Care integration (H&SCI) in Scotland. H&SCI is intended to improve the quality and efficiency of care for individuals accessing both health and social care services, as outlined in the Joint Act of 2014. Within the Integration Joint Boards (IJBs), local councillors are an integral part of the broader 'integration network' responsible for overseeing H&SCI. However, the role and contribution of local councillors in H&SCI has not been subject to a sufficient level of research in this area. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the role and participation of councillors in IJBs, the leadership styles and approaches they employ, and the political context and environment that shapes their choices and actions. It also investigates the relationship between political representatives within health and social care areas and senior bureaucratic actors (such as chief officers and planners). A case-study approach was adopted to examine and refine the theoretical claims of the study. The study uses a qualitative approach, based on content analysis of policy documents and semi-structured interviews with councillors and other key stakeholders (senior officials) involved in H&SCI in eleven case study areas in Scotland.

The study uses an analytical framework that guides the analysis of the role of local political leaders in public sector reform initiatives. It draws on the theories of contingency and situational leadership, which suggest that political leadership styles articulate a choice of action that is influenced by their surrounding context. The analytical framework of this study integrates the literature on leadership styles and political context and uses them as lenses to explore and identify the main frames, themes, sources, and tones that the participants use to describe their roles, responsibilities, and leadership styles in H&SCI in relation to their political context. This allowed for the identification of the potentially relevant leadership styles and political contextual factors that could help to better understand the subjectivity of local political leaders' leadership approach choices within modern governance settings.

The research finds that local political leaders play a key role in the strategic decision making of H&SCI and they adopt different leadership styles that vary along the dimensions of cooperation, vision, teamwork, inclusivity, result orientation, direction, and initiative, depending on the political context and their personal preference. The research also finds that councillors face various challenges and opportunities in exercising their leadership roles within the IJBs, such as managing the conflicting interests and expectations of different stakeholders, coping with the financial and operational pressures of H&SCI, and navigating the complexity and uncertainty of the reform process. The thesis contributes to the literature on the politics and leadership aspects of public sector reform in Scotland, and offers new insights for improving the governance and performance of H&SCI. The thesis also has

significant implications for the integrated/collaborative governance literature, as it can inform the development of new theoretical frameworks and practical guidance for integrated governance.

Table of Contents

List of Tables and Figures	ix
Acknowledgements.....	x
Acronyms and abbreviations.....	xi
Chapter 1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background to the problem: Possible gaps in the public administration literature on the role of local political leadership in public policy	2
1.2 Focus and purpose of the study.....	4
1.3 Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions	7
1.4 Relevance of the study.....	8
1.5 Organisation of the thesis	9
Chapter 2 Analytical Framework and Key Themes in Political Leadership Analysis	11
Introduction	11
2.1 The Elusive Nature of Political Leadership: An Attempt at Definition.....	12
2.2 Understanding the Contextual Dynamics of Leadership.....	14
2.3 Operationalizing Leadership: Theoretical Perspectives and Practical Implications	17
2.3.1 Fiedler's Contingency Theory: the impact of contextual factors on leadership	21
2.3.2 Operationalization of situational leadership theory	24
2.4 Leadership Styles in the Context of Local Governance: A Framework.....	26
2.4.1 Contemporary Paradigms in Political Leadership: Exploring Modern Styles	29
2.4.2 An Exploration of Political Leadership Styles: Definitions and Characteristics	32
2.5 Political leadership	39
2.5.1 Local political leadership.....	40
2.5.2 Role of local political leadership	41
2.5.3 Contextualizing Local Political Leadership	44
Conclusion: Emerging themes from the leadership literature and research questions	49
Chapter 3 Validating the Conceptualisation and Navigating the Gaps: The Integration of Public Services and the Role of Political Leadership in Public administration	52
Introduction	52
3.1 Framing Leadership Styles in the Historical Context of Public Administration: Old Public Administration	53
3.2 New public management	54
3.3 New public governance.....	57
3.4 Exploring Collaborative Leadership Styles and Themes in Participatory Initiatives.....	62
Conclusion.....	65

Chapter 4 Contextualising the Study: Aspects of Public Service Reform in Scotland	66
Introduction	66
4.1 Scottish Devolution: Empowering Localized Approaches to Service Delivery.....	67
Shaping Governance in Post-Devolution Scotland: Continuity, Change, and Power Dynamics.....	67
4.2 Local Authorities and the Scottish Executive: Integrated Partnerships and Devolution.....	69
4.3 Enhancing Local Democracy and Political Leadership in Scotland: Recommendations and Reforms	70
4.4 Community Planning in Scotland: Empowering Communities, Legal Framework, and Governance Dynamics	72
4.5 Challenges and Limitations in the Integration of Services and Community Empowerment Initiatives: Disparity between Rhetoric and Reality	75
Conclusion.....	79
Chapter 5 A Methodological Approach: Exploring the Role of Local Political Leadership in Strategic Decision Making within the Context of Health and Social Care Integration in Scotland	81
5.1 Research approach.....	82
5.2 Using the Case Study research design	85
5.3 Sampling Strategy	87
5.4 Data collection and analysis.....	92
5.4.1 Data Collection methods.....	93
5.4.2 Data analysis methods	97
5.5 Research Validity	103
5.6 Ethical Considerations.....	105
Conclusion.....	105
Chapter 6 The Role and Contemporary Characteristics of Local Political Leaders in Modern Governance: A Thematic Analysis	107
Introduction	107
6.1.1 Governance Structure and Membership of Integration Joint Boards.....	108
6.1.2 Role and Challenges of Local Political Leaders.....	110
6.1.3 Institutionalized Role of Local Political Leaders	113
6.1.4 The Politics of Depoliticization: Balancing Neutrality and Constructive Political Engagement	117
Conclusion.....	119
6.2 The Role of Local Political Leadership in Navigating Complexity in Integrated Governance 121	
Introduction	121
6.2.1 Local Political Leadership in Navigating Governance Regulations, Constraints, and Limited Resources	121
6.2.2 Fostering Community Engagement and Co-Production: Navigating Challenges and Building Trust in Healthcare Service Delivery	126

6.2.3 Challenges in Creating a Transparent and Accountable Environment	129
Conclusion.....	136
Chapter 7 Contextual Analysis of Local Political Leadership in Scottish Health and Social Care	138
Introduction	138
7.1 The influence of financial and economic conditions.....	139
7.2 The Influence of Partisanship.....	146
7.3 The Influence of Political-administrative Relationships	152
7.4 Geographical Considerations	157
7.4.1 The influence of the size of an IJB.....	157
7.4.2 Influence of Geography (Urban/rural)	160
7.5 Influence of Frontline- workforce' expectations.....	167
Conclusion.....	171
Chapter 8 Main discussion and Conclusions	173
Introduction	173
8.1 The Role of Local Political Leadership in Strategic Decision Making.....	174
8.1.1 The Advantages and Power Imbalances in Integrated Governance.....	174
8.1.2 The Benefits, Drawbacks, and Remedies for Information Flow	176
8.1.3 Bureaucratic Constraints and Community Engagement: A Double-edged Sword	177
8.2: Assessing the Contextual Role of Local Political Leadership in Integrated Governance: A	
Typology Based on Political Context.....	181
8.2.1 Economic and Financial Context	181
8.2.2: Partisanship.....	188
8.2.3 Political-Administrative relationship	193
8.2.4: The Influence of IJB's Size	198
8.2.5: The influence of geography (Rural/urban).....	201
8.2.6: The influence of Frontline Workforce Expectations.....	207
8.3 Concluding reflections.....	211
8.3.1 The Role of Local Political Leaders in the Public Service Reform of H&SCI.....	211
8.3.2 The contextual role of local political leaders	214
8.3.3 Policy and Practice Implications.....	216
8.3.4 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research	219
Bibliography	223
Appendix A: List of interviewees.....	265
Appendix B: A copy of Consent form.	268
Appendix C: A Copy of Ethical approval.	270
Appendix D: A Copy of Invitation email.	271

Appendix E: A Copy of Freedom of Information request (FOI).....	272
Appendix F: A Sampling of Documents.....	273
Appendix G: IJBs reviewed meeting minutes.....	276
Appendix H: NVivo Screenshot.	279
Appendix I: Interview Schedules.....	280
Appendix J: NVivo Screenshot.	281
Appendix K: Themes, descriptions, and codes of the interview qualitative data analysis (Chapter 6).	282
Appendix L: Themes, descriptions, and codes of the interview qualitative data analysis (Chapter 7).	285

List of Tables and Figures

Tables

Table 2.1: Comparing perspectives- great man, behavioural and Contingency theories of leadership.

Table 2.2: Shows the components and characteristics of the respective leadership styles.

Table 2.3: Outlines the components, dimensions, and studies that have informed contextual factors selection.

Table 3: Comparing public administration perspectives- old public administration, new public management, and new public governance to support the distinction between old and modern political leadership styles.

Table 5.1: Characteristics of the selected IJBs.

Table 5.2: Themes, descriptions, and codes of the content analysis of documents..

Table 8.2.1: Relationship between Economic and Financial Governance and Leadership Styles.

Table 8.2.2: Relationship between Responsibilities Towards Political Party and Leadership styles.

Table 8.2.3: Relationship between Political-Administrative Context and Leadership Styles.

Table 8.2.4: Relationship between IJB's Size as Contextual Factor and Leadership Styles.

Table 8.2.5: Relationship between IJB's Geography (rural/urban) and leadership styles.

Table 8.2.6: Relationship between Frontline workforce expectations and leadership styles.

Figures

Figure 6.1: Study components– leadership preference.

Figure 6.2: Organisational chart of a typical IJB.

Figure 6.3: The accountability mechanism in the IJB.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

CC	Christie commission.
CEA	Community empowerment Act.
CO	Chief Officer.
FOI	Freedom Of Information.
H&SC	Health and social care.
H&SCI	Health and social care integration.
IJB	Integration Joint Board.
LPL	Local political leader.
MP	Member of Parliament.
MSP	Member of the Scottish Parliament.
NPF	National Performance Framework.
NPG	New public governance.
NPM	New public management.
PA	Public administration.
PBJA	Public bodies Joint Act.
SNP	Scottish national party.
SO	Senior Official.
UK	United Kingdom.

Chapter 1

Introduction

The main purpose of this thesis is to explore the role of local political leaders in shaping the planning and implementation of Health and Social Care integration (H&SCI) in Scotland. H&SCI is a major public sector reform initiative launched by the Scottish Government in April 2016. Prior to this initiative, rising healthcare costs and siloed services within the health and social care sectors prompted a need for more integrated and collaborative approaches (Scottish Government, 2016). H&SCI aims to address these issues by fostering cooperation among stakeholders, including local authorities, health boards, third-sector organizations, and service users, to better serve local communities (Joint Act, 2014; Scottish Government, 2016). A key aspect of H&SCI is the integration of budgets and services between the health and social care sectors. To facilitate these objectives, the Scottish Government established Integration Joint Boards (IJBs) – statutory entities comprising local political figures, health board members, and representatives from trade unions, the third sector, and the community (Joint Act, 2014). However, the implementation of H&SCI has encountered various challenges (Christie, 2011; Joint Act 2014; Connolly and Pyper, 2020; Keating, 2020). One of the key challenges to H&SC reform has been the role of local political leadership in this process. The Scottish Government has been clear that it intends to lead the reform process, but it has not always been clear how to do this effectively. In particular, the Government has struggled to balance the need for central co-ordination with the need for local flexibility and strengthened local leadership (Baylis, and Trimble, 2018; Connolly and Pyper, 2020; Connolly, 2022). This thesis argues that local political leadership of public sector reforms in Scotland is important for its success. Local political leaders serving in H&SCI hold a crucial position as principle political members appointed by elected councils to oversee the planning and implementation of H&SC in their respective local areas (Joint Act, 2014). Moreover, H&SCI is an innovative approach of the Scottish Government (Connolly and Pyper, 2020), and the role of local political leaders in this process is relatively new, and little is known about their influence and involvement. Therefore, this thesis will draw on the literature on leadership and public administration, in particular contextual leadership and new public governance, to argue that the Scottish Government needs to facilitate a more strategic and situational leadership approach to address its leadership challenges in this sector. This thesis will be one of the first studies to examine the role of local political leadership in H&SCI reforms in Scotland.

1.1 Background to the problem: Possible gaps in the public administration literature on the role of local political leadership in public policy

This study reviews pertinent public administration literature in order to address the theoretical gaps and challenges in understanding the interplay between local governance and political leadership. It also analyses how three major paradigms of public administration - traditional public administration, new public management, and new public governance - shape and are shaped by the dynamics of local governance and political leadership. The reviewed literature examines the influential role of political leadership in shaping governance changes within the context of the old public administration (Frederickson, 1997). While new public management emphasized managerial primacy and marginalized local political leadership in policy spaces at a local level, it also created a governance complexity that could hinder the implementation of political ambitions or goals (Sullivan, 2011; Stoker, 2017). This has led to a paradigm shift which has reintegrated local political leaders into the governance systems (Stewart, 1995; Karlsson, 2012; Stoker, 2017). This re-emergence of the role of local political leaders in policy spaces in the new governance is a significant development that warrants further research.

These specific gaps in the public administration literature are further evident in Scottish context. The literature on Scottish policy developments (see Chapter 4) has primarily focused on evaluating different approaches to decentralization and their impact on empowering local tiers of government. This review mainly covers the period since Scottish devolution (1999), and it seems that the election of the New Labour government in Scotland led to the continuation of some Thatcherite ideas such as the importance of market-based solutions to public problems (Cairney, 2012; Keating, 2020). During the period of Labour-dominated administration in Scotland from 1999 until 2007, although there had been some steps to empower local tiers of government and local political leaders by introducing different agendas to renewing democracy (McGarvey, 2002), there has still been a notable increase in central government regulation, monitoring, and ring-fencing of municipal activities, which has undermined democratic responsiveness and resulted in dilemmas experienced within Scotland (Cairney and McGarvey, 2013).

This centralization trend contributed to diminishing the role of local councillors in service delivery, exacerbating the democratic deficit (Pugh 2014; BBC, 2015). However, since 2007, efforts have been made in the Scottish policy context to address the need for clarity in the relationship between traditional structures of representative governance and the wider commitment to extending deliberative democracy (Scottish Government, 2023). The concerns of local politicians were acknowledged during this period, and the Scottish Government initiated a public service inquiry (the

Christie Commission) in 2011. This was an independent commission that reviewed the future delivery of public services in Scotland and made recommendations for reform. The Commission emphasized the inclusion of local councillors in 'joined-up' initiatives for local public service delivery, such as the H&SC Integration Joint Boards. The Commission argued that local leaders are one of the best placed to understand the needs of their communities and to make decisions that are in the best interests of those communities. These developments indicate an enhanced and renewed role for local political leadership within the new governance structure, exemplified by concepts such as localism, representative democracy, and empowerment. Therefore, transition from new public management to new public governance is also evident in the H&SCI reforms in Scotland, which afford local political leaders the opportunity to engage in policy spaces. By examining these developments, the study identifies that the role of local political leaders in the modern governance decision making process is complex and is still a little unclear. In this context, understanding the role of local political leaders in strategic decision-making processes within H&SCI areas in Scotland becomes crucial given their relatively recent emergence in this area (Connolly and Pyper, 2020).

Consequently, the question arises: What is the role of local political leaders in the strategic decision-making processes of H&SCI in Scotland? This question has the potential to explore the need to understand how local political leaders are involved in shaping governance changes in modern governance and their contributions to public sector reforms (e.g., H&SCI). This is aligned with the recognition of the evolving nature of public administration and the impact of leadership on this process. Although there is a growing body of knowledge or literature that seeks to understand this role (Lowndes and Leach, 2004; Getimis and Hlepas, 2006), this research aims to address these gaps by exploring the role of local leaders from a modern governance perspective, which is increasingly characterized by the focus on participation, complexity, empowerment and collaboration (McGarvey, 2002, 2012; Connolly and Pyper, 2020). Moreover, this thesis argues that context, the specific circumstances in which leadership takes place, is essential to understanding leadership (Fiedler, 1967; Shamir, 2012). This thesis focuses on factors such as the economy and finance, political-administrative relationships, and relevant partisanship. In an increasingly complex world, and given the growing importance of diversity and inclusion, it is difficult to apply a single leadership style or approach to all situations. Instead, leaders need to be flexible and adaptable, and they need to be able to tailor their leadership style to the specific context.

For instance, Connolly and Pyper, (2020) argue that leaders of public service reform in modern governance must be aware that strategic success depends on the effectiveness of multi-level leadership and governing context within which strategies are implemented. It is important to recognize that contextual conditions are negotiated by the actors involved and can differ both within and

between local authorities. Consequently, successful implementation of H&SCI may require different leadership role, approaches and styles depending on the specific context in which the leader is situated. Therefore, this research aims to evaluate the role of modern local political leaders by understanding their behaviours and styles throughout the H&SCI implementation process in relation to their political context. The goal is to complement existing H&SCI roadmaps (strategic plans, leadership framework) by considering the appropriate local political leadership style as a contingency issue dependent on the context, and situations encountered.

1.2 Focus and purpose of the study

As noted in the introduction, the political context plays a crucial role in shaping the leadership approach of local political leaders. This intricate relationship serves as the foundation for delving into theoretical concepts and crafting a research design to unravel the connection between political context and leadership approach, ultimately shedding light on the role of local political leadership in the realm of H&SC.

Despite the fundamental importance of contextual or situational leadership (Fiedler, 1967; Osborn, Uhl-Bien, & Milosevic, 2019), there is a little clarity on how the political context and the local political leaders of IJBs align their roles and goals. Local political leaders are influenced by a number of factors, including the economy and finance, partisanship, political-administrative relationships, geographical considerations (such as the size of the area and its urban or rural nature), and frontline workforce expectations. These factors, in turn, shape the role of political leaders and structures within which IJBs operate. This study reviews the literature on the link between political context and leadership approach in IJBs. It draws on two theories: the contingency theory, which argues that local political leadership style depends on the political opportunities and constraints (Fiedler, 1967), and the situational theory, which rejects the idea of a single optimal leadership style and instead advocates for flexibility and adaptation (Hersey and Blanchard, 1969).

This study uses a theoretical framework that combines these theories (Contingency and situational) or concepts of leadership to understand how local political leaders in Scottish H&SCI adapt to different contexts and situations. The framework considers both the political context and the frontline workforce expectations as key factors that shape the local political leadership in the integrated governance of Scottish Health and Social Care. This study focuses on the relationship of the political context only for leadership approaches or styles based on the local political leaders and senior officials' perceptions in analysing a theoretical claim of this study, which aims to explore the alignment of local political leaders' roles with political contexts and frontline workforce expectations.

From the contextual or situational standpoint of this thesis, potential policy process success in Scottish H&SC relies on the alignment of local political leadership with the specific community needs, socio-economic and political influences of the local context. To analyse the leadership role of these local politicians, it is essential to examine the political perspectives that are shaped by the actual situations and challenges faced by the local IJB areas. Therefore, through a careful analysis of policy documents and meeting minutes from H&SCI areas, this research has gained valuable insights into compelling evidence regarding the significance and relevance of contextual factors regarding the role and responsibilities of local leaders serving in the IJBs. Specifically, factors such as the economy and finance, partisanship, political-administrative relationships, geographical considerations, and frontline workforce expectations have emerged as the influential dynamics shaping their leadership approach and situations.

One important aspect of this research is the influence of the economy and finance on the decision-making processes of local political leaders. Discussions on budget allocations, funding constraints, and resource management highlight the complexities they face in delivering efficient health and social Care services. The meeting minutes and documents emphasize the direct relationship between financial considerations and the decisions made by local leaders. Moreover, partisanship within IJBs emerges as a significant factor influencing local political leaders. The minutes and documents reveal instances where political ideologies, affiliations and partisan dynamics affect decision-making, relating resource allocations, and policy priorities in the health and social care sector. This highlights the challenge for local political leaders to navigate these partisan landscapes while prioritizing community interests. However, further exploration is needed to understand how they respond to political influences and which leadership approaches they employ.

The intricate relationship between political and administrative spheres is difficult to unravel through the analysis of the policy documents. There are some audit reports produced by Audit Scotland which shed light on the challenges faced by local political leaders in managing the expectations of both political stakeholders and administrative stakeholders and staff (Audit, 2018; Audit, 2020a) but there seems to be no comprehensive evidence which indicates the nature of political-administrative relationships. Therefore, further exploration is needed to understand this relationship and how it shapes the leadership style of local political leaders in the strategic decision-making of H&SC. In addition, the influence of geographical considerations (urban/rural differences and size of area) explain the varying nature of demands depending on the dynamics of the area. The urban focus on more participation of communities in decision making (IJB area C minutes, 9 Dec 2016; IJB area C minutes, 9 May 2018) and the rural emphasis on issues ranging from workforce, transport, service accessibility characterise the urban/rural differences in H&SC Scotland (IJB area G minutes, 13 May 2015; IJB area

G minutes, 30 Aug 2017). This underlines the importance of geographical context in shaping the role of local political leaders in the decision-making process. However, their specific influence in enabling the leadership styles of local political leaders remains unclear. This indicates the need to further explore the political perspectives of local political leaders through a range of measure including actual interviews. It is the same with the needs and expectations of the frontline workforce as policy documents indicate the need of providing support to frontline workforce (IJB area B minutes, November 2016; IJB area E minutes, 27 Nov, 2019). However, the specific ways in which these pressures shape the leadership approaches of these leaders are not yet fully understood and warrant further research. These accounts on the one hand validated the significance and relevance of contextual factors to local political leaders serving in the IJBs and on the other hand, they offer limited guidance for local political leaders and IJBs Integration Joint Boards to effectively align their leadership styles to the prevailing context (Hartley, 2018). Against this background, a question arises for this study: What local political leadership styles are evident in the different political contexts of H&SCI processes?

To explore and evaluate local political leaders' leadership styles in the modern context of H&SCI, it is important to understand contemporary literature on leadership styles that captures the specific preferences and competencies exhibited by local political leaders in modern governance. This study conceives six leadership styles that reflect the characteristics and strategies aligning with collaborative, shared and participatory approaches to leadership. These six leadership styles (transformational, laissez-faire, democratic, servant and situational, collaborative, facilitative) are widely accepted in modern public organization in order to address the complexity of the modern arrangements (Amanchukwu et al., 2015; van der Hoek et al., 2021). In the modern local governance, political leaders are required to practise leadership styles or skills which are necessary to work in today's complex governance structure (Torning and Sørensen, 2015).

The leadership styles chosen in this study serve as frameworks for promoting public interest within the political and democratic systems of public organizations. These classified leadership styles reflect approaches that prioritise democratic values, collaboration, empowerment, participation, followership, and shared visions (Spears, 1995; Ensley et al., 2006). They are designed to foster multi-dimensional relationships between public leaders, street-level workers, and citizens to promote and safeguard democratic values aligned with the contemporary public policy agendas, such as H&SCI. These leadership styles have been classified based on literature that focuses on new public governance and the role of local political leadership (see Chapter 2). By integrating local political leadership with these values, these leadership approaches emphasize governance that is responsive to citizens' needs and that values democratic principles. One primary aspect of these styles is the decentralization of

decision-making, which enhances the visibility and importance of lower-level offices (Gortner et al., 1997) and involves the participation of subordinates in high-level planning (Selznick, 1957).

The chosen leadership styles are one of the primary lenses used for comprehending the role of local political leadership within varying political contexts. It is proposed that local political leaders' preferred leadership styles influence their actions, which are then reflected in the leadership approaches they adopt. In addition, an association is proposed between the political context and the approach of local political leadership. The initial relevance of this association was revealed through a content analysis of documents, highlighting the significance of political contextual factors on the decision-making processes of IJBs involving local political leaders. These insights guide the situational fit of local political leaders within the political context of IJBs that will be explored through interviews.

1.3 Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions

This study aims to explore the leadership styles of local political leaders in eleven different IJB areas through the role they play within the Scottish H&SCI, in relation to their political context.

Objectives:

- Investigate the role of IJB political members in strategic decision-making for H&SCI service delivery in Scotland.
- Examine how political, economic, political-administrative relationship and geographic factors intersect to influence leadership dynamics within H&SCI in Scotland.
- To compare the impact of these factors on different IJB areas in Scotland.
- Explore the perceptions of senior officials regarding the leadership styles of local political leaders and how these styles affect relationship between political-administrative spheres.
- Develop recommendations for strengthening the role of local political leaders within the IJB to promote efficient and collaborative governance of H&SCI services.

To achieve this, the research questions guiding the aims and objectives of the thesis are:

- What is the role of local political leaders, particularly IJB members, in the strategic decision-making process for H&SCI service delivery within Scotland?
- How do the following contextual factors influence the leadership styles employed by local political leaders in H&SCI decision-making processes:

1. Economic and financial landscape: The dominant economic conditions in the IJB territory and the way this impacts public finances in the area.
2. Partisanship: The responsibilities towards political parties of IJB members and its influence on decision-making.
3. Political-administrative relationships: Collaboration and power dynamics between political leaders and administrative officials.
4. Geographical considerations: Demographic and spatial attributes of the IJB areas, such as rural or urban settings, and the size of the IJB.
5. Frontline workforce expectations in health and social care: Needs, concerns, aspirations, and preparedness of health and social care stakeholders, particularly frontline workforces.

The literature reviewed in Chapters 2 and 3 further develops the themes and analytical direction needed to explore the questions. Chapter 3 also identifies the research gaps. Further details on each contextual factor are provided in Table 2.3.

1.4 Relevance of the study

This study is relevant because the key findings of this study will focus on understanding the role of local political leaders in the strategic decision making of H&SCI. This could offer a better understanding of the regenerated role of local leaders in strategic decision-making and present new insights into the challenges and opportunities facing local leaders, in relation to their political context. It explores the relationship between political contexts and the leadership approaches of local political leaders operating in H&SC. By constructing and utilizing a contemporary leadership style - local political contextual factors categories specifically tailored for political leadership - this thesis aims to generate valuable insights into the modern debates around integrated governance. These insights will focus on the contextual role of local political leadership operating in H&SCI. A better understanding of leadership is essential for effective governance design and implementation of integrated governance, especially in the light of the complex and challenging contexts in which they often operate. Studying leadership enables the identification of optimal practices and principles that can guide local councillors and other public service leaders in designing and executing integrated governance, a comprehensive and cooperative approach to public service delivery. Local councillors would benefit by pondering how leadership styles contribute to public service reform programs, as different leadership styles possess unique strengths and shortcomings, and may be more or less appropriate for varying contexts and challenges. For instance, on the one hand, some of these styles and practices have the potential to yield positive outcomes in integrated governance and, on the other hand, these practices expose the contributions of local political leaders that exacerbate the challenges of collaborative environment.

Moreover, this research helps to identify the political contextual factors that need to be considered when developing leadership strategies for integrated governance. It can also help to understand the political landscape or politics surrounding local leaders and provide insights into how politics unfold and influence the leadership practices of varying H&SC contexts. This contextual analysis can also offer practical insights for current and aspiring leaders in their self-assessment and personal growth. Building a contemporary combination of political context and corresponding leadership styles specifically designed for local political leadership can offer a potential framework that can be utilized by local councils to articulate expectations during the nomination process of local political leaders in the IJBs. These insights have the potential to contribute to the advancement and development of effective leadership within the realm of Scottish H&SC and enable local political leaders to better serve their communities. Furthermore, the insights gained from studying local political leadership will be instrumental for SG and local authorities in the development of some of the proactive and corrective strategies aimed at enhancing the collaboration between the political and administrative spheres.

The outcome of this study has implications for professional institutions and associations of local political leaders in Scottish Health and Social Care (H&SC), such as COSLA. It may encourage them to invest in professional development that enhances their skills and adapts to the changing political situations. It may also increase their awareness of the dynamic and contextual nature of local political leadership and their own roles in Scottish H&SC. Moreover, this study will add to the existing literature on situational leadership by providing new findings and methods for studying local political leadership.

1.5 Organisation of the thesis

This thesis consists of two parts. The first part explores the foundations of the research, explaining its rationale and approach based on the background, purpose, and problem statements presented in this chapter. Chapter 2 reviews the relevant literature on leadership, contextual leadership, leadership theories, local political leadership, leadership styles, and political context to develop a conceptual framework for analysing local political leadership in the strategic decision making of Health and Social Care (H&SC). Chapter 3 traces the evolution of political leadership in public administration to validate the conceptual framework and identify the gaps in the existing literature, while Chapter 4 contextualises these gaps in the Scottish setting. Chapter 5 describes the methods used to collect the data, such as content analysis of policy documents and meeting minutes, and interviews.

Part Two of the thesis details the findings from documentary analysis and interviews. Chapter 6 presents the first part of the thematic analysis, which explores the role development of local political leaders in the Scottish H&SCI. Subsequently, Chapter 7 synthesises the insights from both content and

thematic analyses to present a comprehensive examination of the contextual factors that impact the leadership style of local political leaders.

Chapter 8 serves as the main discussion and conclusion of the thesis, weaving together the content analysis, thematic insights, interview data, and relevant literatures. This chapter provides an answer to the Research Questions and highlights the key insights derived from the study. It concludes by analysing the key findings, exploring their implications for public administration literature and leadership theories. It also examines the impact on policy and practice, and suggests avenues for future research within the context of local political leadership in Scottish H&SCI.

Chapter 2

Analytical Framework and Key Themes in Political Leadership Analysis

Introduction

The literature review develops the analytical framework, providing a foundation for exploring local political leadership in public administration and in the unique political landscape of Health and Social Care integration areas in Scotland. Its purpose is to comprehensively review the existing literature, establish analytical themes that will guide the study, and demonstrate the study's contribution to the broader academic discourse. In this chapter, a multi-faceted approach is taken to investigate the phenomenon of political leadership. It begins by defining leadership and it delves into various leadership theories, with a specific focus on situational and contingency leadership theories, which have been operationalized to analyse political leadership in the Scottish H&SCI context. The core endeavour of this thesis is to explore the role of local political leaders in relation to their political context. These theories are helpful in accomplishing that and primarily encompass two key components: leadership styles and political context.

The literature review examines the relevant leadership styles that are pertinent to local political leadership within the contemporary policy landscape, particularly emphasizing participatory, and shared and collaborative leadership approaches. The chapter thoroughly examines political contextual factors that are relevant and influential for local political leadership, including partisanship, economy and finance, political-administrative relationships, and geographical considerations and it explores the literature on the role of local political leadership in the public sector reform initiatives. By synthesizing the existing literature, this chapter attempts to provide an analytical framework to achieve research objectives and it lays the groundwork for the subsequent analysis by identifying and exploring key themes within the leadership literature that will guide the study: The central premise of this chapter is that the role of local political leader and their leadership styles are intricately connected to the political context in which they operate. The surrounding political environment significantly influences the preferred leadership styles in various situations. Therefore, it is important to identify and analyse leadership within its specific context, recognizing the analytical significance of aligning leadership styles with the unique political context.

2.1 The Elusive Nature of Political Leadership: An Attempt at Definition

Leadership, as an indispensable element within organizations, holds a significance that should not be underestimated. As an historically concrete phenomenon, leadership structures and methods undergo changes over time. It encompasses a complex set of tasks that have evolved across various types, approaches, styles, models, and tools (Uhl-Bien and Marion, 2007; Trottier et al., 2008). Irrespective of cultural makeup and social order, leadership prevails in all societies. This complexity of leadership has given rise to many definitions that capture specific components of this multi-faceted concept (Trottier et al., 2008; Uhl-Bien and Marion, 2011). A useful starting point for understanding leadership is to recognize its three core elements: influence, group, and goals (Rost, 1991; Yukl, 2009; Northouse, 2010). Many leadership concepts provide explanations for these fundamental elements of influence, group dynamics, and goal attainment (Avery, 2009; Avolio et al., 2009; House and Antonakis, 2014; Northouse, 2021).

Avolio et al. (2009) argued that influence is the key component, while Bass and Avolio (2004) and House and Antonakis (2014) argued that all three components (influence, group, and goal) are important, but the relative importance of each component depends on the situation. Northouse (2021) took a similar view, arguing that leadership is a complex phenomenon that involves a variety of factors, including influence, goal, group, communication, trust, and decision-making. However, it is clear that all three components are important in some way. Influence is essential for leaders to get others to do what they want (Haymond, 2017). Goals are important for leaders to have a clear direction and purpose (Mawhinney and Ford, 1977; Price-Dowd, 2020). Group is important for leaders in order to have the support and resources they need to be successful (Sharpe, 2008; Dinh and Lord, 2012). In addition to these three components, other factors that can be important for leadership are communication, trust, and decision-making (Goodwin, et al., 2011; Asencio and Mujkic, 2016). Communication is essential for leaders to be able to effectively communicate their vision and goals to others. Trust is important for leaders to be able to build relationships with their stakeholders and to get them involved effectively in decision making. Decision-making is important for leaders to be able to make timely and effective decisions (Asencio and Mujkic, 2016).

Despite these vibrant debates, the existing reference literature lacks a definition that fully reflects the nature and complexity of leadership. Notwithstanding years of research, the exact essence of leadership remains elusive (Dion, 1968; Ulrich and Smallwood, 2012; Yukl, 2012). This persistent challenge has been exacerbated by political scientists' attempts to expand the conceptual framework by incorporating definitions used in other social sciences (Nunes, 2010). For example, the concept of power, which is central to political analysis, has been defined in various ways by different social sciences, such as sociology, psychology, and economics (Guzzini, 2022). This has resulted in a lack of

clarity and consensus on how to measure, compare, and explain power in different political contexts and situations. Moreover, the peer-reviewed literature has raised several questions regarding the understanding of leadership and the actions undertaken by leaders. Many definitions of leadership have been proposed, with many favouring concepts that emphasize the process of leading behaviours rather than relying solely on trait-based logic. The term "leadership as a process" emerges as a common theme in many definitions found in the literature (Yukl, 1989; Van Wart, 2013; Northouse, 2021). Specifically, leadership is often described as a social interaction process in which a leader influences others, typically within an organized group, to achieve shared goals (Northouse, 2021). Consequently, leadership can be understood as a process of social interaction that brings about change (Burns, 1978; Bass, 1990). This process can be seen in various manifestations, ranging from the art of persuasion and skilled negotiation to the complex task of resolving conflicts. Defining leadership as a process makes it accessible to individuals beyond those presumed to possess inherent qualities. Moreover, leadership extends beyond the confines of a single person with formal positional authority within a group (i.e., a formally appointed leader).

Political leadership, as a subset of leadership, poses additional complexities because of its lack of a universal definition. Political scientists, driven by their individual perspectives and areas of interest, have yet to reach a consensus or establish a comprehensive treatment of the subject. Thus, political leadership often takes on an abstract nature, subject to social construction and contestation. Its intricate connections with terms such as "influence," "power," and "authority" further contribute to the plethora of competing definitions (Rost, 1991). The multi-arena nature of political leadership, operating across diverse settings simultaneously, makes it a complex and challenging phenomenon to define. This is because its meaning varies depending on the context in which it is exercised and is influenced by institutional, historical, and cultural contexts (Dion, 1968; Hockin, 1977).

Furthermore, exercising influence constitutes a fundamental component of political decision-making, even within contemporary democracies that prioritize collaborative approaches in the pursuit of leadership (Nunes, 2010). Political leaders hold a significant position in shaping the political landscape by actively engaging in the generation of alternatives and exploring diverse options amid the presence of competing strategies within the public realm (Nunes, 2010; Christie, 2011). However, this multi-faceted task requires a careful consideration of the extent to which political leaders should exercise their influence. There are varying perspectives regarding the appropriate level of influence exerted by political leaders. One perspective contends that political leaders have a duty to assume top-down guidance and exert influence, drawing upon their expertise and authority to navigate complex decision-making processes (Weber, 1971; Burns, 1978; Nye, 2010). Conversely, an alternative perspective posits that political leaders should embrace an empowering approach, facilitating citizen

engagement and enabling them to autonomously make decisions (Sharp et al, 2022). Determining the most suitable approach necessitates a nuanced evaluation of contextual factors, as the optimal balance between top-down influence and citizen empowerment may differ depending on specific circumstances. The strategies chosen by leaders to attain their top-down or bottom-up leadership approaches are pivotal in determining what this study will subsequently refer to as "leadership styles".

Against this background discussion on the definition and brief contextual aspects of leadership, revealing commonalities among various definitions, this thesis adopts the following working definition:

"Leadership is a process that occurs in a context. It has the capacity to motivate and inspire others to work towards a common goal. It is a process that involves influence, collaboration, and empowerment. Leaders create a shared vision, build trust, and create a positive environment where people can thrive."

Defining leadership as a process-based practice between leaders and stakeholders within a particular context implies the following:

- (a) leadership is not an exclusive trait confined to a select few individuals,
- (b) leadership is a transformational and transactional event characterized by negotiation and interaction between leaders, stakeholders, frontline workforce, and the political context, and
- (c) leaders both exert influence on, and are influenced by, their context and expectations of the frontline workforce, with outcomes varying from positive to negative.

For example, political leaders in democratic states must collaborate with various parties, including members, colleagues, coalition partners, other branches of government and stakeholders. It is crucial to note that political authority alone does not guarantee leadership. While authority may be conferred based on rules, norms, institutional contexts, or historical determinants, true leadership surpasses mere power and authority. To be a political leader, one must possess additional qualities. Authority ultimately rests on the consent of others (Nunes, 2010).

2.2 Understanding the Contextual Dynamics of Leadership

"Context counts" (Heifetz et al., 2009, p. 209). Both leadership and institutions operate within specific organizational and external contexts, rather than in isolation. When the context changes in terms of societal norms or expected behaviours, the shared understanding of what constitutes effective leadership also evolves and is redefined by the emerging context. Extensive research has explored the impact of the organizational context on leaders' behaviour and the success of their leadership endeavours. During the 1970s, leadership scholars were prompted to consider context as a potential

factor that could influence leadership and its effectiveness (Fiedler, 1967; Hannah, Uhl-Bien et al., 2009; Porter & McLaughlin, 2006). Theorists approached this topic from different angles, investigating both the influence of contextual factors on leadership and the influence of leadership on shaping the context. Within the field of leadership, three distinct assumptions or perspectives regarding the interplay between context and leadership can be identified.

One perspective suggests that astute leadership can circumvent the influence of context (Bass & Avolio, 1994). However, this study does not make such an assumption; instead, it considers the impact of contextual factors on leadership. This view is consistent with the second and third perspectives, which highlight context as the dominant factor that defines the boundary conditions for leadership and its effectiveness (Fiedler, 1967; Uhl-Bien, 2006; Fairhurst, 2009). Contextual approaches emphasize how the specific context shapes the type of leadership displayed. A third perspective recognizes that context modifies the influence of leadership on various criteria, often presenting a causal relationship involving leadership, context, and criteria (Fiedler, 1967; House, 1971; Liden & Antonakis, 2009). The contingency and situational approaches to leadership have been influential in understanding how leadership varies by context and the extent to which leadership style matches the context (Fiedler, 1967). Associated with the contingency movement is the contextual school of leadership (Porter & McLaughlin, 2006; Hannah et al., 2009), which emphasizes that contextual factors can facilitate or inhibit specific leadership behaviours and their underlying dispositional factors (Liden & Antonakis, 2009).

Despite the historical consideration of human behaviour in both nature and nurture, several prominent leadership theories have overlooked the examination of leaders themselves in relation to their context (Grint, 2005). Zaccaro and Klimoski (2002) expressed their concern that leadership is often studied without sufficient attention being paid to the structural considerations that influence and moderate its conduct. This lack of understanding of contextual factors may contribute to the confusion in the literature on leadership measurement. Grint (2000) emphasized the importance of context to such a degree that he categorized theories of leadership based on their attention to, or neglect of, context. For instance, he criticized the trait approach for disregarding context, while Liden and Antonakis (2009) highlighted the shortcomings of charismatic-transformational theories for not considering context. Thus, there is relatively limited research on the interactions between leadership and context, despite their crucial significance and there is an increasing call for the inclusion of context in empirical research on leadership in recent times (Liden and Antonakis, 2009; Fairhurst, 2009; Nunes, 2013; Bennister, 2016).

This thesis has, therefore, considered operationalized leadership by adopting a contextual standpoint, highlighting that effective leadership is contingent upon the prevailing context and situation. The scope of leaders' activities is influenced by their institutional and non-institutional environment. The institutional environment, including constitutional and legal arrangements, customs, conventions, and the role expectations inherited from previous leaders, defines the matters within a leader's province (Heifetz, 2009). Conversely, the non-institutional environment, such as economic problems, social demands, and internal or external crises, can constrain or provide opportunities for leaders. In these situations, leaders' perspectives, and capacity to respond become crucial. Understanding the contextual factors that shape leadership is essential for a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. However, it poses challenges in conceptualizing the relationship between political leaders and their surroundings and devising research projects that accurately capture the relevant concepts and variables involved in this relationship.

In this context of understanding the interplay between leadership and contextual factors, a comprehensive examination of existing leadership theories and operationalization of relevant theories has been a useful step. The evolution of leadership theory provides valuable insights into the subject. These theories have been recounted many times, with varying levels of depth, following a chronological order that begins with Great men and trait theory and progresses through different conceptualizations such as behavioural and style-related theories, transactional and transformational models, as well as situational and contingency approaches. Some academics have explored these theories in the specific context of network management or integration (Silva and McGuire, 2010; Greasley and Stoker, 2008).

By examining these leadership models within their theoretical frameworks, this thesis can better address the current challenge of exercising leadership styles in diverse political contexts. This analysis is crucial to the Research Questions as it seeks to explore the relationship between leadership styles and the contextual factors that influence the leadership process. Furthermore, this examination will enable this research to evaluate the suitability of existing leadership theories and shed light on their applicability in this specific research context. In light of the significance of contingency and situational leadership approaches, which elucidate the interdependence between political context and local political leadership, this study aims to identify prevalent local political leadership styles within specific political contexts. This study does not assume that a certain context guarantees leadership effectiveness, but rather recognizes that particular contexts shape the type of leadership style that emerges. Specifically, this research focuses on the implementation of the H&SCI agenda in Scotland.

2.3 Operationalising Leadership: Theoretical Perspectives and Practical Implications

Leadership theory aims to explain factors related to the emergence and nature of leadership (Stogdill, 1974; Bass, 1990). It encompasses various aspects such as the traits, behaviours, styles and characteristics of the leader, organizational context, and the interactions between leaders, stakeholders and followers. Early theories focused on identifying qualities associated with effective leadership, while subsequent theories explored different factors such as situational variables and ability levels. The study of leadership has produced theories covering attributes, situational associations, work, behaviour, power, qualities, vision, insight, and charisma. Stogdill and Bass (1990) explained that the multitude of leadership definitions is comparable to the number of attempts made to explain them. Up until 2000, more than forty leadership theories have been published (Edwards, 2000), accompanied by over 1,500 different definitions (Bass, 1990). It was stated almost four decades ago that "leadership is among the most observed and least understood phenomena on earth" (Burns, 1978 P.,2).

Therefore, understanding the complexities of leadership theories is crucial in unravelling the intricate dynamics of effective leadership. This literature review critically examines the various leadership theories, evaluating their strengths, weaknesses, and controversies, to gain insights into the key elements that contribute to effective leadership.

The development of leadership theories can be traced back to the emergence of four predominant theoretical genres that aim to explain the nature and process of leadership (Jogulu and Wood, 2006). These genres are:

- **Great Man Theory:** this theory posits that exceptional leaders possess innate personal qualities that set them apart from others. These distinctive characteristics define the leader's effectiveness. Additionally, trait theories extend the concept of the Great Man theory by identifying specific personality traits associated with effective leadership.
- **Behavioural Theories:** researchers recognized that traits alone were insufficient to explain leadership and turned their attention to studying the interactions between leaders and followers. This shift led to an emphasis on leadership behaviours that can be learned, rather than being innate. Three major leadership styles have been identified within behavioural theories: democratic, autocratic, and laissez-faire.

- Contingency Theories: these theories propose different leadership styles and behaviours, appropriate in varying leadership contexts. Contextual theories build upon the significance of traits and behaviours. They suggest that effective leadership is a result of aligning the prevailing context with the appropriate leadership style.
- Situational Theories: these theories aim to establish a match and that match is between the leadership situation and the individual leader. These theories recognize that effective leadership is contingent upon various factors, such as the characteristics of the situation, the traits of the leader and the needs of the followers.

This study examines three broad and indicative leadership approaches to analyse local political leadership and its context. The first approach, known as the Great Men and trait categories, offers insights into the leadership process by establishing a connection between personality and the emergence of a leader within a group without a formally appointed leader. Personality measures can be valuable for organizations to enhance their selection processes (Dinh and Lord, 2012). Trait approaches view the leader as essential but do not consider the contextual factors. According to Morrel and Hartley (2006), in the trait school of thought, a leader is seen as a leader in any circumstances. While the trait approach focuses on the leader component of leadership, it has been criticized for neglecting the impact of situational factors. Trait representation accounts are limited because they overlook the significance of leaders' interdependence. Political leadership involves complex relationships between leaders, organizations, and the context (see Section 2.0). Defining 'leader' and 'context' separately can be restrictive (Morrel and Hartley, 2006; Yulk, 2012). Effectiveness and identity for political leaders are not solely determined by character but are socially constructed within a dynamic context, influenced by structural constraints and opportunities. Thus, flexibility is crucial for political leaders as they are often required to adapt their approach depending on the situation (Northouse, 2010). The trait theory is considered "too one-dimensional to account for the complexity of leadership" (Van Wart, 2003, p. 217). Leaders must be able to adjust their leadership approach based on the circumstances they encounter (Northouse, 2010). Therefore, this study adopts a theoretical analytical framework that moves away from the trait theory, which assumes a fixed approach to problem-solving, and instead embraces the dynamic nature of leadership.

The behavioural approach to leadership is an alternative to trait theory, which failed to identify universal attributes contributing to leader effectiveness. Behavioural theories focus on identifying

different leadership styles, such as autocratic, democratic, task-oriented, and person-oriented (Gill, 2011). These styles are defined by the leader's focus on tasks and relationships. According to Northouse (2007), behaviour theories encompass task behaviours and relationship behaviours. Task behaviours are those that focus on getting the job done, while relationship behaviours are those that focus on building and maintaining relationships with stakeholders and followers. These theories propose that leadership behaviours and styles can be learned through training and are significant because they explain how leaders can use different behaviours to be effective in different situations (Northouse, 2021; Yukl, 2013). For example, a leader may need to be more task-oriented in a crisis situation, while they may need to be more relationship-oriented in a more stable situation. However, they do not fully embrace the prevailing consensus that leadership should be contingent upon the environment. Dissatisfaction with the focus on individual leaders' traits and styles led to the development of alternative theories, which will be explored in the Sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2. Consequently, this study focuses on contingency and situational leadership theories rather than the trait or behavioural approaches.

A third approach to analysing local political leadership and its context is the situational leadership approach, which is consistent with the theoretical framework of this study. Situational leadership theory has contributed to the understanding of leadership by highlighting the importance of situational factors (Yukl, 2010). Many contingency and situational theories build upon behavioural theories, utilizing leader behaviour dichotomies such as democratic, laissez-faire, autocratic, task-oriented, and relationship-oriented as a starting point. However, they also suggest a mechanistic relationship between leadership style and context, emphasizing concepts of "matching" and "fit" (Hartley and Morel, 2006). Contingency and situational approaches consider both the leader and the context as essential and ascertainable elements. Thus, among the approaches presented, contingency and situational leadership theories appear to offer the most suitable framework for understanding local political leadership as a process that occurs in its context. The rapidly changing landscape of modern democracy necessitates a more dynamic comprehension of leadership within the political context. It cannot be assumed that the nature of such dynamic leadership roles remains consistent in an increasingly complex and collaborative environment of public leadership.

The three perspectives discussed in this section stem from profound philosophical differences, as shown in Table 2.1. Each perspective constructs its own understanding of leadership based on these theoretical foundations and establishes the criteria for selecting leadership styles.

Table 2.1: Comparing perspectives- great man, behavioural and contingency theories of leadership.

	Trait and great man theory	Behavioural theory	Contingency and Situational theory
Primary theatrical and epistemological foundations	Trait theory, rooted in the Great Men theory, posits that leaders are born with innate characteristics that distinguish them.	Behavioural theory is primarily based on the leader's behaviours rather than their social, physical, and mental features, emphasizing the importance of studying the actions and conduct of leaders.	The primary foundations of situational analysis suggest that there is no singular approach to leadership, and each style is contingent upon specific circumstances.
Conception of leadership	Individuals, through their knowledge, skills, experience, and persistent efforts, establish themselves as great leaders.	Leaders adopt specific behaviours that stem from a logical assessment of different leadership styles.	There is no universally applicable leadership style that is effective in all situations. Leadership effectiveness depends on the interplay between behaviours, traits, and various situational factors.
Mechanism for achieving or performing leadership	Tireless energy, penetrating intuition, uncanny foresight, and irresistible persuasive powers.	Leaders to adopt their styles with the behavioural magnitudes.	The leadership has to adapt, accommodate, and respond to certain contexts and situation and eventualities may comprehend followers' potentials.
Selection basis of the	Leader under any circumstances.	Individuals are believed to acquire leadership skills through	Flexible enough to generate a repertoire of styles.

leadership styles		observation and experiential learning, enabling them to become great leaders.	
Approach to surrounding environment of leadership	Certain birth qualities enable leaders to face any situation.		Defines which leadership style is well-matched for a specific situation.
Assumed organizational leadership.	“Talkativeness,” “duration of verbal excitation,” and “vividness and originality of expression and facility of conversation.”	Two dimensions of leader behaviours: those oriented toward task and structure and those oriented toward people and relationships. The former drives the progression of work tasks, and the latter maintains the social cohesiveness of a unit.	Leadership can look at a situation, decide what style of leadership is needed by the group, and act accordingly. A variety of leadership styles may be needed to lead different groups.

2.3.1 Fiedler's Contingency Theory: the impact of contextual factors on leadership

Contingency theories of leadership emphasize the importance of matching the leader's style with the context or situation. Fiedler's contingency model (1967) is one such theory. It suggests that the best leadership style depends on the level of leader-member relations, task structure, and position power. The contingency theory considers the political environment, a political leader's motivation, and the current group and stakeholders' situation in its dynamic model (Herman, 2013). This model acknowledges that different settings require different skills, which increases the likelihood of individuals with relevant skills assuming and consolidating political leadership positions. Leadership styles can also adapt differently to various situations, with some styles being more effective than

others (Fiedler, 1967). In the political realm, contingency theory has been used to understand the success of different leaders. Various academics have noted that voters place varying demands on political leaders in response to changing circumstances (Hargrove, 1989; Hermann & Gerard, 2009). For example, some leaders may be more effective in situations with high levels of conflict, while others may be more effective in situations with high levels of co-operation (Fiedler et al., 1984; Hargrove, 1989; Hermann, 2003). During times of crisis, constituents and committees seek leaders who possess the necessary skills to navigate turbulent periods, taking responsibility and instilling a sense of security, if not optimism, in the public. Conversely, once the crisis subsides and relative calm returns, constituents seek inclusion in the decision-making process and express discontent when their views and interests are disregarded. They desire political leaders who excel in day-to-day politics, actively listen, and foster consensus building (Hermann, 2013).

Within the political context, various components impose limitations on leaders, necessitating the selection of specific leadership styles that align with the given circumstances. For instance, Hlepas et al. (2018) conducted a study that revealed the strong influence of the local political context on leadership styles among local political leaders. They found that favourable economic conditions and leaders' control over spending are associated with a visionary leadership style, while financially challenging situations often lead to a more strategic approach. The study also highlighted a significant relationship between the mayor's party affiliation and their leadership style. Specifically, political leaders belonging to parties with strong structures and high party membership percentages tend to choose styles influenced by their party's reliable backing (Gertmis and Hlepas, 2006). The political context acts as a mediating variable that directly affects leadership dynamics.

Building upon these insights, it becomes evident that successful political leadership is intricately tied to a nuanced understanding of individual capabilities and the contextual nuances of the political landscape. This understanding goes beyond the skills and traits of individual leaders. Some historical evidence also demonstrates that the trajectory of leadership success is not a straightforward path, as evidenced by notable leaders such as Jimmy Carter and Gordon Brown who attained achievements in specific capacities but encountered difficulties and constraints in other contexts (Bass, 1985; House and Aditya, 1997). For example, Jimmy Carter, who was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 2002 for his humanitarian and diplomatic efforts, faced many challenges and criticisms during his presidency, such as the Iran hostage crisis, the energy crisis, and the economic recession (Forbes, 2021). Brown was known for his competitive leadership style, which involved creating and promoting choice, diversity, and innovation in public service provision, such as through outsourcing, privatisation, and marketisation. He was also a strategic and analytical leader, who had a strong grasp of economic and financial matters and was able to respond swiftly and decisively to the global financial crisis (Theakston,

2011). However, he lacked the charisma and emotional intelligence to inspire and motivate others, and he was perceived as aloof and distant by the public and the media. He also faced criticism for his domestic policies, such as his decision to raise taxes on low-income earners, and his handling of the 2009 expenses scandal that rocked Parliament (Theakston, 2011). He lost the 2010 general election to David Cameron's Conservative Party, ending thirteen years of Labour rule. Moreover, an illustrative example is the case of German Chancellor Helmut Kohl, whose effectiveness as a leader fluctuated within his tenure. After several years of domestic policy stasis, Kohl displayed remarkable international statesmanship following the collapse of the Berlin Wall in November 1989. This unexpected display of leadership enabled him to secure the unification of Germany, strengthen its ties with the European Union, and extend his hold on the office for another two terms (Zelikow with Rice, 1995).

These examples emphasize the complex interplay between leaders and their contextual surroundings, but contingency and situational theories have faced critique for their limited applicability in assessing the role of local political leaders. This stems from the fact that these leaders, in their overall council role, contend with a multitude of simultaneous issues, often functioning in diverse roles (Hartley and Morrel, 2006). For example, talking to leaders about the influence of financial and economic conditions on their institutional role might lead to them pondering under which capacity they should respond. Capturing the multi-faceted context of local political leaders becomes intricate, given the fluid nature of their broad roles. However, this study asserts the suitability of contingency and situational leadership theories, adapting them as pertinent constructs. This narrows its scope to the role of local political leaders within the H&SCI Partnership, where their engagement is confined to a singular capacity (Moore, 1995). Their primary responsibility lies in championing the collective interests of the partnership or IJBs, eliminating the complexities of juggling various roles or managing overarching council pressures. This specific role configuration provides an opportune avenue to scrutinize the local leaders' functions within their context. It enables an exploration of how their distinct involvement in delivering H&SC services intersects with contextual factors.

In this respect, local political leaders in H&SCI have an important role to play in promoting the interests of Integrated Joint Boards with shared goals (Audit Scotland, 2018). Their responsibilities go beyond maintaining control; they are expected to build effective regimes, facilitate networks, and bring stakeholders together under a common vision for the locality's Health and Social Care integration agenda (Christie Commission, 2011). Section 2.5.3 demonstrate that the role of local political leadership is influenced by various contextual factors, including partisanship, economic and financial conditions, political-administrative relationship, and geographical considerations. These factors create opportunities and constraints that shape the role of leadership adopted by local political leaders. Recognizing that each local authority and IJB context presents unique challenges, it becomes clear that

a one-size-fits-all leadership style may not be suitable for all situations. Instead, success hinges on the ability of leadership styles to align well with the specific challenges inherent to each local authority's political context. This also shows the interdependence of local actors on the surrounding environment in integrated governance. This indicates their contextual role. In this respect, this thesis argues that studying political leadership in Scottish H&SC as a contextual process can be persuaded by using contingency and situational leadership theory concept.

For instance, an assessment of local governments or IJB areas based on various dimensions, such as demography, political control, and economy, could be conducted to understand the situational specificity of political leadership (Morrel and Hartley, 2006). This approach would shed light on the varying leadership approaches of local leaders depending on the issue area or specific moments of intervention. Indeed, the geographical location of a local authority can significantly influence the challenges faced by leaders and the requisite skills needed, considering factors such as demography, technology, and social cohesion (Morrel and Hartley, 2006). By embracing a contingency approach, this thesis can enhance our understanding by taking into account the diverse contextual factors at play. Therefore, this study institutes a theoretical framework based on Fiedler's contingency theory and the situational leadership theory of Hersey and Blanchard (1969). These theories provide a foundation for examining the interaction between political leadership styles and contextual factors. By incorporating a contingency approach, it is possible to develop framework that explore the relationship between leadership styles and the political context.

2.3.2 Operationalisation of situational leadership theory

The situational leadership theory (SLT) was developed by Hersey and Blanchard in 1969. It acknowledges that there is no one-size-fits-all leadership style and that leaders need to adapt their style to the specific needs of the situation (Fiedler and Chemer, 1974). The needs of the stakeholders create these different situations that require different leadership styles (Northhouse, 1997). The essence of SLT is aligning the leader's style with the needs, characteristics, competence, and expectations of the stakeholders to foster success (Hersey and Blanchard, 1969; House and Mitchell, 1974; Van Wart, 2013). However, it is important to note that, while situational leadership theory is intuitively appealing, its empirical examination remains limited (Antonakis and Day, 2018) Situational approaches, similar to contingency approaches, acknowledge the significance of context and offer advantages over descriptive accounts. This makes them suitable for local political leadership, as they recognize the interdependence between local political leaders and stakeholders such as street level bureaucrats or frontline workforce (Grint, 2005; Hartley and Morell, 2006; Lipsky, 2010).

Local political leaders play a significant role in shaping policy goals. Their influence on policy outputs and outcomes is also significant (Langbein, 2000; May and Winter, 2009; Hlepas et al., 2018). They exercise this influence through street level bureaucrats or frontline workforce (Lipsky, 2010). The frontline workforce is one of the channels for local political leaders to implement their political ambitions. Several studies demonstrate that this channel is used to influence policy outcomes, such as Latino school board members impacting Latino educational achievement in Texas (Meier, O'Toole, and Nicholson-Crotty, 2004), partisan makeup of politicians influencing regulatory enforcement in New York (Scholz et al., 1991), and bureaucratic discretion in child support enforcement (Keiser and Soss, 1998). However, it is important to recognize that these studies primarily focus on aggregate outcomes rather than the street-level behaviours of frontline workers (Meyers and Vorsanger, 2003). This limitation prompts further investigation into the specific mechanisms through which political leaders and their context affects the actions of street-level bureaucrats.

Researchers have explored the influence of political context on street-level bureaucrats and their ability to shape frontline service delivery behaviours (Keiser and Soss 1998; Langbein 2000; Wimmelman et al., 2018). These studies highlight the interplay between political factors and bureaucratic actions in policy implementation. For example, Jones (1985) looked at the impact of local partisanship on metropolitan bureaucracies. This revealed potential hierarchical channels through which political influences are transmitted. This research has identified how local elected officials exert influence over frontline workers, particularly in implementing nationally issued guidelines. The rhetoric to adhere to central party plans can influence the decision-making processes of frontline workers, despite their own discretionary logic (Jones, 1985; Lipsky, 2010). Conversely, Winter (2007) extends this notion, suggesting that caseworkers are more likely to diverge from national goals when endorsed by their immediate political principals (local political leaders). Moreover, the control of financial resources by elected officials plays a significant role in shaping frontline worker behaviour and their adherence to central guidelines (Wimmelman et al., 2018). Wimmelman (2018) found that political parties, municipal size, and economic resources all influenced the frontline workforce, and, in turn, the choice of leadership styles adopted by local political leaders. In addition, Langbein (2000) found that the degree of agreement among policy principals is crucial in shaping the influence of political signals. When signals are inconsistent across different levels of government, frontline workers have less discretion and tend to follow the preferences of their immediate elected officials. This shows that understanding these working patterns and tailoring the interaction between elected officials and frontline workers is crucial for effective service delivery.

This analysis of implementation practices reveals significant variations, and these variations are influenced by contextual factors experienced by local frontline workers including the instruction of

their political masters and different factors shaped the attitudes and interpretations of the frontline workforce towards policy guidelines. This highlighted the diverse individualities within this group. Therefore, it could be argued that political context plays an important role in policy implementation at local level, and this can lead to local political leadership adopting different leadership styles. Therefore, application of situational approaches in examining leadership behaviours can provide valuable insights into the suitability of certain behaviours within the regulatory role of political leaders across different contexts in Scottish H&SC.

This study argues the adoption of a situational approach to thoroughly analyse the multi-faceted leadership behaviours of local political leaders in their representative regulator role in H&SCI. By carefully examining the interplay between situational factors, stakeholder expectations, and the political context, this thesis attempts to unravel the complexities that underpin political leadership within the H&SCI areas of Scotland. By precisely integrating situational approaches and scrutinizing leadership behaviours within this specific contextual framework, this study aims to provide invaluable insights into the dynamic influence of situational factors and contextual dynamics on leadership styles.

Building upon the contingency and situational leadership theory discussed earlier, this study shifts its focus and now focuses on operationalizing two important concepts that underpin these theories: leadership styles and political context. This study operationalises these two concepts within the context of local governance because the research participants of this study are local political leaders operating in H&SCI, in Scotland. While situational approaches have laid the groundwork for understanding the multifaceted behaviours exhibited by local political leaders, examining leadership styles in the next section provides a deeper understanding of their actions and how they influence decision-making processes in the complex landscape of local politics.

2.4 Leadership Styles in the Context of Local Governance: A Framework

Leadership style and leadership theory are distinct yet interconnected aspects of leadership. Leadership theory explores the characteristics and essence of individuals in positions of leadership whereas leadership style delves into their behaviours and actions. Leadership style plays a crucial role in shaping how leaders provide direction, execute plans, and influence individuals (Weller & Stevens, 2015). As the policymaking landscape is becoming increasingly complex, local political leaders must overcome challenges in maintaining policy control, delegating authority, and shaping the policy agenda in the face of external influences, the demands of constituents, and the constraints of limited resources (Hermann, 2010). Leadership style in this context becomes instrumental in navigating these challenges and influencing the decision-making process. It encompasses their interactions with stakeholders,

advisors, and subordinates, as well as the establishment of rules, principles, and structures governing these interactions (Hermann, 2010). Simultaneously, leadership involves motivating others to assume responsibility and fulfil their potential in pursuing a shared vision with integrity and passion (Michael, 2010). The selection of a leadership style significantly impacts the relationship between a leader and their effectiveness in this process.

However, leaders often face a notable challenge when their personal ideals of moral leadership do not align with the expectations set by the organization or community, necessitating the adoption of alternative styles (Greenleaf, 1995). The complexity surrounding the adoption of leadership styles is influenced by a multitude of contextual factors and the wide array of variations that exist (Grønn, 2002; Page and Wong, 1998). These variations have been dealt with by a spectrum of approaches, ranging from traditional authoritarian models to styles that emphasize empowerment, participation, transformation, servanthip, and situational adaptability - all of which integrate the concept of service into the philosophy of leadership. As we navigate the 21st Century, the language used to describe leadership has expanded, introducing terms such as democratic, decentralized, distributive, co-operative, collective, and co-ordinated (James, 2011). Among these expressions, transformative leadership, democratic, servant, collaborative, and situational styles emerge as particularly relevant for this study.

Building upon this exploration of diverse leadership styles, extensive research has been conducted to understand successful leadership within the realm of local governance. Getimis and Heinelt (2004) argue that academic research has shifted from focusing on the institutional role of political leaders to the active and dynamic ways they exercise leadership. Several researchers, such as Kotter and Lawrence (1974), John and Cole (1999, 2014), Lowndes and Leach (2004), Getimis and Hlepas (2006), and Hlepas et al. (2018), have proposed different frameworks to classify these leadership styles and understand the complex dynamics of local political leadership. Another important aspect of the literature is the impact of leaders' attitudes and behaviours on change and problem-solving. Dahl's (1961, 2005) 'broker' and Banfield's (1961) 'entrepreneur' are two influential models of mayoral leadership. The broker protects their power by avoiding conflict and implementing consensual decisions, while the entrepreneur shapes the community's preferences and expectations to achieve their policy goals (Kearney, 2020). However, Levine (1980) points out the limitations of these models, such as their outdatedness and their inapplicability to non-pluralist systems, lacking a suitable approach for leaders whose actions extend beyond the consensual implementation of policy initiatives.

In response to these limitations, John and Cole (1999) conducted a study focused on leadership styles within the context of local governance, specifically addressing the challenges faced by leaders in adapting to complex networks. Their research resulted in the development of a comprehensive typology comprising four distinct styles: the visionary, consensual facilitator, city boss, and caretaker. These styles capture various aspects of leadership, such as strong leadership and the ability to unite diverse actors, reliance on persuasion, adaptability in complex network environments and the inclination to avoid change. In a similar vein, Lowndes and Leach's work (2004) has provided a comprehensive and intriguing approach to understanding leadership styles. Their work explored the interactions among constitutions, contexts, and capabilities, shedding light on how different institutional rules, external environments, and the skills and capacities employed by political actors shape diverse experiences of political leadership. This comprehensive approach provides intriguing insights into the multi-faceted nature of leadership within local governance systems. It is worth noting that individuals may respond differently to the constraints they face, perceiving them either as limitations or as catalysts for progress.

Expanding upon the knowledge of leadership styles within local governance, Getimis and Hlepas (2006) built upon the foundational work of Leach and Wilson (2000) and the approach developed by John and Cole (1999). Their study delved into the realm of political leadership styles in the context of local government and European mayors, emphasizing the personal enactment of leadership within specific environments. By analysing leadership predispositions and attitudes towards the exercise of power, they constructed a comprehensive framework consisting of two dichotomies and four categories. These categories encompass the dimensions of exercise of power and leadership predisposition, encompassing strategic/reproductive orientation and authoritarian/co-operative attitudes. Interestingly, their typology aligns with John and Cole's framework, revealing how attitudes towards the exercise of power are manifested in the four distinct leadership styles.

Understanding the evolving nature of leadership styles is crucial, particularly as we consider the complexities of contemporary local government environments and the demands faced by mature democracies (Greasley and Stoker, 2008). The traditional typology that once categorized leadership into boss and entrepreneurial styles no longer adequately addresses these challenges. Instead, modern leadership approaches, such as facilitative, transformational, servant, and situational styles have emerged as purposeful and adaptive frameworks that can effectively address the diverse range of local problems and challenges (Greasley and Stoker, 2008). As we delve deeper into the evolution and determinants of leadership styles, it becomes evident that they are shaped by a combination of individual characteristics, contextual factors, institutional norms, and governance rules (Stogdill, 1948; Fiedler, 1967; Lowndes and Leach, 2004). While exploring these evolutionary trends provides a

broader understanding of prevailing research trends, it is important to recognize their limitations in explaining the complex trajectories of modern leadership styles (Hartley, 2018).

This thesis aims to critically examine the role of modern local political leadership, revealing its relationship with deterministic political contextual factors and institutional constraints. While acknowledging the valuable insights and analytical tools provided by the existing body of work, it is evident that it falls short in adequately addressing the intricate realm of modern local political leadership styles (Hartley, 2018). As the focus shifts towards contemporary governance tendencies and constraints, there is a pressing need to delve deeper into the dynamics of modern political leadership styles. Therefore, the next section endeavours to explore the emergent paradigms and approaches that delineate modern leadership, shedding light on their impact and potential explanatory capacity within local political contexts.

2.4.1 Contemporary Paradigms in Political Leadership: Exploring Modern Styles

In contemporary public institutions, the integration of collaborative and participatory approaches plays a vital role in effectively navigating the complex landscape of governance arrangements (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Emerson, Nabatchi, & Balogh, 2012; Douglas et al., 2020). These approaches encompass a range of leadership styles, including transformational, democratic, servant, laissez-faire, situational, collaborative, and facilitative (Svara, 1994; Avolio & Bass, 2004; Spears, 2001; Northouse, 2021; Yukl, 2013). These leadership styles are vital skills for local political leaders within the modern local authority governance structure and they have a potential to effectively navigate the challenges of contemporary governance (Torfing and Sørensen, 2012). The recognition of collaborative and participatory approaches as essential in modern public organizations not only provides a foundation for exploring their practical implications but also reveals the challenges that local leaders might come across within the context of contemporary governance.

For instance, Bochel's interviews (2010) with leadership positions in UK local authorities shed light on the specific skills deemed crucial for effective leadership in modern governance. Local political leaders have highlighted the need for managerial skills in order to prioritize, think creatively, and address pressing issues within local authorities (Conservative, county council). Strategic thinking, especially in planning and prioritizing, and managing colleagues to foster a sense of teamwork were emphasized (Independent, Welsh council). Additionally, managing officers and avoiding distractions were seen as crucial (Labour, unitary council). These findings not only reveal the convergence between government aspirations and the narratives of local political leaders but also highlight the relevance of these leadership skills in navigating the complexities of new public governance (NPG).

NPG is a transformative paradigm in public administration emphasizing collaborative decision-making and service delivery. It is designed to foster collaboration among government entities, civil society organizations and stakeholders, departing from hierarchical models to embrace a networked and interactive approach (Klijn & Koppenjan, 2002; Osborne, 2010; O'Toole Jr, 2017). Local political leadership within the context of new public governance faces the challenge of managing a complex environment with multiple stakeholders and pressures on public services. The NPG movement emphasizes three characteristics of public administration that are crucial for establishing trust and legitimacy which align with the leadership demand. First, NPG is value-centred, advocating for the promotion of the common good rather than solely focusing on programme effectiveness, efficiency or responsiveness (Alford, 2002; Moore, 1995; Stoker, 2017). This aligns with an emphasis on prioritization, creative thinking and addressing pressing issues within the authorities as highlighted by the councillors in Bochol's (2010) study. Another key aspect of NPG is its emphasis on creating government processes that facilitate the formation of sustainable agreements among major stakeholders, even when there are disagreements with regards to the approach that generates the greatest public value (Larsen, 2008). This resonates with the importance of managing colleagues and fostering teamwork identified in Bochol's 2010 findings.

The role of local political leadership is crucial in the context of NPG as elected politicians derive their mandates from citizens within their jurisdictions, granting them legitimacy as key actors in NPG-based reforms. NPG perceives politics, not as the mere aggregation of individual preferences, but as a politically mediated expression of collectively determined preferences (Alford, 2002; Moore, 1995; O'Flynn, 2007). This perspective also aligns with the role and functions of political leaders as they are responsible for identifying and addressing the problems and challenges within the political community and ensuring that the political process reflects the collective preferences of the public. Moreover, the NPG movement recognizes the importance of co-production of the public good, involving the collaboration of the public, private market, and non-profit sectors (Crosby & Bryson, 2005; Larsen, 2008; O'Toole, 2010). Government's role in this model extends beyond regulation and distribution of public benefits, to serving as a catalyst for engaging private and non-profit stakeholders in the shared ownership of the public good. This can range from community policing programme to more intricate forms of networked governance (Bao et al., 2013). The alignment between this perspective and the role of political leaders is exemplified by the UK's recent reforms in social, educational, medical, and judicial service delivery at the local level. In these reforms, the government's representation is viewed as a process of political mediation, acknowledging legitimate differences in public values (Brookes & Grint, 2010).

In the context of partnerships, local political leaders are often responsible for representing diverse interests to central government to secure resources. This task necessitates leadership skills and highlights the importance of locally elected individuals who possess sufficient political legitimacy (John, 2010). Success in these partnerships relies on political leaders striking a balance between being representative and fulfilling their roles within the partnership setting to safeguard shared interests. However, politics has been historically perceived as either illegitimate or dysfunctional in general management theory and public administration (Hartley et al., 2015). Nevertheless, this viewpoint is undergoing a rapid transformation, with an increasing recognition of the constructive potential of politics in management (Bochol, 2010), including within the realm of public management and administration. Leadership that incorporates political astuteness - also referred to as political savvy or having political antennae - entails the utilization of political skills to navigate situations involving diverse and sometimes conflicting interests and stakeholders, aiming to align interests and achieve desired outcomes (Hartley et al., 2015).

The utilization of diverse leadership styles in contemporary public organizations acknowledges the complexities and interdependencies at play. Instead of relying on a singular leadership approach, there is an understanding that varying situations and challenges demand different strategies. Moreover, the integration of multi-level and multi-territorialized public and private organizations within the public policy process highlights the necessity for adaptive and context-specific leadership (Stoker, 2006). Leaders must possess the ability to navigate the intricacies of collaborating with diverse actors across different levels of government and territories (Selznick, 1957). Effective communication, negotiation, and alignment of interests are essential skills for leaders to achieve collective goals. These participatory and collaborative approaches are particularly relevant in the context of political leadership within modern public organizations, including Health and Social Care Integration, where multiple agents are involved, and public policy processes involve multi-level and multi-territorialized public and private organizations (Christie, 2011).

By incorporating participatory and collaborative approaches, political leaders can tap into the expertise and perspectives of various stakeholders, promoting inclusivity and shared decision-making (Douglas et al, 2020; Ansell and Torfing, 2021). This can not only enhance the quality of decision-making but also helps in building trust and legitimacy within the organization and among the public. These styles encompass democratic values, collaboration, empowerment, participation, followership, and shared visions (Ensley et al., 2006). They are specifically classified in this study because they have a potential to foster collaborative and democratic values in the collaborative governance. One of the major responsibilities of local political leaders in H&SCI is to practice shared leadership and collaborate effectively with involved stakeholders (Christie, 2011). Thus, this study utilizes these lenses of

leadership style literature to explore the role and leadership approaches of local political leaders in managing multi-level relationships, relationship with bureaucratic stakeholders, communities, frontline workforce and responsibilities towards their political parties in the modern context of H&SCI. The utilization of diverse leadership styles acknowledges the complexities and interdependencies within contemporary public organizations. It recognizes that different situations and challenges demand context-specific strategies, particularly in the context of multi-level and multi-territorialized public and private organizations involved in H&SCI (Christie, 2011; Nunes, 2015).

Therefore, the adoption of various modern leadership styles can provide an important lens to explore the role of political leaders in modern public organizations (e.g., H&SCI). These approaches recognize the complexity of the environment, the involvement of multiple stakeholders, and the need for adaptive and context-specific leadership to effectively address public policy challenges and promote integration.

2.4.2 An Exploration of Political Leadership Styles: Definitions and Characteristics

This section will explore six distinct leadership styles that can potentially assist political leaders in navigating the complexities and uncertainties of modern governance. These are: transformational, democratic, facilitative, servant, laissez-faire, and situational leadership styles. These leadership styles have been utilized in this study to explore the leadership of local political leaders through the role they play in H&SCI. Each style has its own definition, characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages. The section will also examine some of the political leaders who demonstrate these styles and how they affect their political outcomes.

2.4.2.1 Transformational

Transformational leadership is a leadership approach that focuses on motivating and inspiring followers to achieve shared goals. It was introduced in the late 1970s as a more powerful form of transactional leadership, which focuses on the needs of stakeholders and followers (Singh, 2011). The term "transformational leadership" was coined by James Downton in 1973, but its significance in leadership studies gained traction when James McGregor Burns extended his political leadership theories in 1978. Burns highlighted the leader's ability to motivate others towards shared goals, and this became a key characteristic of transformational leadership (Northouse, 2013). Transformational leaders are considered visionaries who set goals for the organization and develop plans to achieve them (Northouse, 2006). They also effectively communicate and connect with followers, which helps to motivate and inspire them (Northouse, 2013). In this situation, the leader serves as an ideal role model for followers. They lead by example and are admired for it. This is known as idealized influence.

Another key aspect of transformational leadership is inspirational motivation (IM), which is the ability to inspire and motivate followers (see Table 2.2) (Givens, 2008). IM can be seen in the leadership style of many successful leaders, such as Tony Blair, Mahatma Gandhi, Martin Luther King Jr., and Nelson Mandela. These leaders were able to inspire their followers to achieve great things by articulating a clear vision, providing meaning and purpose to their work, and building trust and rapport (Woolpert, 1998). For instance, the leadership style exemplified by Blair himself, with the shift from 'old' to 'new' Labour reflects the transformation of traditional bureaucratic companies into mission-driven, customer-focused, and flexible enterprises, as described in the new public governance literature (Torfing and Sorsen, 2019). Moreover, transformational leaders embody not only the charisma that captivates but also the traits of Intellectual Stimulation and Individualized Consideration. The hallmark of their leadership lies in their authentic concern for the well-being and sentiments of their stakeholders and followers, fostering an environment that enables them to unleash their potential. In the realm of creativity and innovation, these leaders wield their influence by challenging their stakeholders and followers to break boundaries and envision novel solutions. A common misunderstanding or many people wrongly assume that transformational leaders are not tough enough, but in reality they always push their followers to achieve more. This is shown by Riggio (2009), who argues that transformational leaders inspire, motivate, and empower their followers to reach their full potential.

2.4.2.2 Democratic

Democratic political leadership, according to Gastil (1994), is behaviour that aligns with, and fosters, basic democratic principles and processes, such as self-determination, inclusiveness, equal participation, and deliberation. Gastil (1994) further emphasizes the importance of distributing responsibility, empowering individuals, and facilitating deliberation in his definition. However, he acknowledges that not all situations are suitable for democratic leadership, such as when the expertise of judges is required or when decisions should be left to individuals' privacy and personal choice. On the other hand, Northouse (2016) characterizes democratic leadership as the behaviour of leaders who support the organization and assist stakeholders and followers in achieving their personal goals and agenda objectives. Unlike autocratic leaders, democratic leaders adopt a non-one-sided approach and aim to reach a consensus by involving the group in ongoing activities, as presented in Table 2.2. This study defines democratic political leadership as an inspirational approach that encourages increased participation of individuals in shaping a new vision. It promotes inclusion, equal consideration, fairness, and enhanced opportunities for individuals to pursue their mutual self-interest (Hendriks and Karsten, 2014). Democratic leaders actively encourage group members to provide constructive criticism and to collaborate in order to prevent negative outcomes that may arise from

individual independent actions and to enhance the efficiency of problem-solving processes (Weber, 2010; Beerbohm, 2015).

2.4.2.3 Facilitative

Facilitative leadership operates within the contours of democratic principles, with team members actively engaged in shaping decisions. At its core, both facilitative and democratic leadership epitomize traits of consideration, consultation, consensus-building, stakeholder-centricity, and a profound concern for interpersonal dynamics, thus nurturing harmonious work relations. Facilitative leadership for political leaders, as defined by Svava (1994), involves collaboration and the promotion of a shared vision and he presents case studies that redefine leadership in council-manager governments. He highlights the role of facilitators as successful elected council members. According to Svava, a facilitative mayor leads by empowering others instead of seeking personal power, achieving objectives by enhancing the performance of others and he identifies dimensions of the facilitative mayor's role. Firstly, the facilitative mayor contributes to co-ordinating efforts among officials and improving communication between them and the public. Secondly, the facilitative mayor provides guidance in policy formulation, and he emphasizes the importance of the interaction process and the shared purposes among the facilitative mayor, public officials, and citizens.

While facilitative leadership may appear to reject the acquisition and use of power from a hierarchical position, it still relies on power and position within a hierarchical perspective. Svava (1994) argued that facilitative leadership aims to establish broad networks of relationships, regardless of formal powers, to promote communication and co-operation. According to Bussu and Bartels, (2014) the facilitative leader's role is to engage and empower other stakeholders in the decision-making process rather than dominate or ignore them. The essence of facilitative leadership, as emphasized by Bussu and Bartels, lies in creating a collaborative culture and a shared vision. Facilitative leadership recognizes the integral governing process, which involves the trust-based interaction between public officials and citizens in policy formulation and fosters co-operation and communication to achieve shared outcomes.

2.4.2.4 Servant

In the jurisdiction of political leadership, the paradigm of servant leadership has emerged as a compelling approach, encapsulating the essence of prioritizing the needs of constituents and society above personal ambitions. Servant leadership, by its very nature, does not seek power or personal gain, but rather focuses on empathetically guiding and motivating followers through genuine connections and empowerment (Ellis, 2015). It emphasizes the significance of pursuing moral goals that bring meaning and satisfaction to work. Servant leaders act as stewards who garner commitment from both their followers and the organization, (see Table 2.2). However, it is important to

acknowledge that servant leadership may not be suitable for every circumstance and carries the risk of serving misguided causes or providing imprudent service. There have also been assumptions that it conveys a negative undertone (Ellis, 2015). The servant leadership approach is paradoxical in a sense. On one hand, individuals must strive to attain positions of public service, showcasing their talents, skills, and knowledge, to surpass others. Ambition is necessary. On the other hand, these positions of public service can entail considerable influence over others. However, this apparent paradox finds resolution in the underlying motivation of service that distinguishes the servant leadership model.

Moreover, there are many similarities and parallels between transformational and servant leadership. They share many traits, such as influence, vision, trust, respect, credibility, risk-sharing, integrity, and modelling, according to Stone, Russell, and Patterson (2004). The main difference is that servant leaders put the collective welfare above their own interests, while transformational leaders focus on motivating followers to achieve organizational goals (Stone et al., 2004).

2.4.2.5 Laissez-faire

Political leadership encompassing the laissez-faire classification prioritizes the granting of maximum freedom to individuals. Within this style, each person is granted autonomy to act independently, and the cumulative outcome arises from the separate actions of individuals (Robert and Vandenberghe, 2021). It is worth noting that laissez-faire leadership styles diverge from democratic forms, although democratic societies may still exhibit a degree of respect for laissez-faire leadership (Weber, 2010), which is characterized by a hands-off approach, whereby leaders establish goals but offer limited or no guidance to their followers or stakeholders (Weller & Stevens, 2015). According to Northhouse (2016), this approach entails minimal impact and direction. Weller and Stevens (2015) provide evidence showcasing how this leadership style empowers employees, as they assume ownership of their efforts, leading to heightened motivation among followers. An appropriate leadership style aligned with this perspective often prioritizes the process rather than a specific vision or solution when tackling political problems.

2.4.2.6 Situational leadership style

Situational leadership is considered a universal leadership style, (see Table 2.2). Political situational leadership entails a dynamic approach that hinges on the ability of leaders to keenly assess the prevailing circumstances and tailor their leadership style accordingly (Herman, 2013). This multi-faceted approach involves a tripartite process: firstly, leaders meticulously assess the situation at hand and the specific requirements of the team or stakeholders they are working with (Salagean, 2014). Following this, they deploy a chosen leadership style, coupled with the provision of guidance, support, constructive feedback, and the infusion of motivation. As the journey progresses, leaders undertake a

comprehensive evaluation of the outcomes achieved, allowing them to discern the effectiveness of their particular leadership style. In the face of evolving situations, leaders remain poised to adeptly adjust their approach, ensuring alignment with the ever-changing demands and needs of the political landscape (Kareem, 2016). This dynamic interplay between assessment, application, and evaluation forms the essence of political situational leadership, enabling leaders to navigate complexity and uncertainty while fostering optimal outcomes.

With regard to situational leadership, qualities that contribute to leadership success in one set of circumstances may be counterproductive in another. For instance, Winston Churchill’s Tory party lost the British national elections after the end of World War II in Europe. The electorate preferred Clement Atlee, the leader of the Labour party, whose characteristics suited the peacetime better than Churchill’s wartime traits (Herman, 2013). Therefore, a leader’s charisma may depend on the context and change over time. (e.g., Churchill during the darkest hours of World War II).

Table 2.2: Shows the components and characteristics of the respective leadership styles.

<i>Styles</i>	<i>Habitual way of performing</i>	<i>Strategies to influence and interaction</i>
Transformational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Idealized influence • Inspirational Motivation • Intellectual Stimulation • Individual consideration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage in proactive communication and motivate personnel. • Emphasize the collective objective. • Hold high expectations for both employees and oneself. • Require meticulous individuals on their team to provide assistance.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation • Inclusiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seek collective input for decision-making.

Democratic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empower • Aid in decision making failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide leadership, assistance, and support. • Promote engagement and consensus. • Hasty decision-making is a vulnerability and can result in organizational detriment.
Facilitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teamwork • Willingness • Learning • Sharing task 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitment to participation in problem solving. • Gets all the stakeholders to explore their concerns in a constructive way to build consensus. • Requires trust and mutual respect in organizational culture
Servant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empathy • Stewardship • Respect and Empower • Commitment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritize the empowerment of employees. • Service is priority. • Place high importance on ethical conduct and inclusivity in decision-making processes.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shape the style to corporate culture.
Lassies fare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delegate responsibility. • Hands-off • Non-interventionist. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowers stakeholders to make decisions and perform tasks autonomously while maintaining accessibility for guidance when required. • Insufficient guidance may result in subpar performance and diminished motivation.
Situational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessing the situation and the needs of the team or individual • Applying the chosen leadership style and providing the necessary guidance, support, feedback, and motivation • Evaluating the results and adjusting the leadership style as needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapting the leadership style to the situation and the needs of the team or individual, rather than using a one-size-fits-all approach • Assessing the competence and commitment of the team or individual, and choosing the appropriate level of direction and support

(Created by author)

Following a comprehensive analysis of the definitions and distinctive attributes of diverse leadership styles, it becomes imperative to investigate their convergence and practical application within the domain of political leadership. Thus, the following section embarks on an exploration of political leadership within the specific framework of this thesis, aiming to illuminate the intricate dynamics through which the various leadership styles are utilized and customized to navigate the intricate terrains of political landscapes. By delving into the multi-faceted nature of political leadership, this study endeavours to acquire profound insights into the underlying mechanisms governing power dynamics, decision-making processes, and the proficient mobilization of resources in the pursuit of collective objectives.

2.5 Political leadership

The traditional role of elected officials as "sovereign rulers" in politics undergoes a transformation into that of an NPG participant, exerting influence over complex networks of interacting actors through flexible leadership strategies (Sørensen, 2006; Torfing et al., 2012). This shift necessitates a comprehensive reevaluation of the essence of political leadership. Accordingly, this study explains political leaders as democratically elected representatives who operate, and exert influence over, a constitutional and legal framework. These leaders engage in partnerships to pursue shared interests and advance their agenda. Furthermore, by adapting the fundamental conceptual underpinnings of leadership studies to the empirical conditions of this research, local political leadership is conceived as a contextual process involving influence. Thus, empirical research supports the argument that the role of political leaders is transforming in modern policy spaces, and they face challenges in relying solely on wielding power.

The 21st Century presents difficulties in persuading the public to embrace new ideas because of decreased trust in political leaders and the expectation that their views will be acknowledged (Hartley and Bennington, 2011). Society is witnessing a shift in governance, moving towards a more dynamic and interactive process involving various public and private actors (Sorensen, 2006; Stoker, 2017) and this transformation indicates new modern governance challenges for political leaders. In encountering these challenges, various conceptual strategies, models, and leadership approaches have been proposed in the literature. These include broker, chameleonic, charismatic, consultative, entrepreneurial, managerial, mobilizing, reactive, servant, and visionary leadership (Elgie, 1995). Research emphasizes specific skills such as agenda setting, effective communication, strategic manoeuvring, adaptability, self-awareness, and engaging with followers (Boin, McConnell, & t'Hart, 2010; Burns, 1977). Non-political literature suggests alternative approaches such as transformational

leadership, servant leadership, facilitative leadership, and shared, participative, delegation, or empowerment leadership theories as well as situational leadership.

2.5.1 Local political leadership

Local political leaders, primarily occupying positions within local executive bodies, operate at the convergence of two distinct domains of influence. The first encompasses the interface between the jurisdictions of politics and administration, whereas the second concerns the linkage between the local community and central government (Copus and Leach, 2014). The first aspect revolves around the demarcation between the domains of politics and administration, which defines the unique roles and responsibilities within each realm. Politics encompasses the complex processes of decision-making, policy formulation, and the interplay of political forces that shape the landscape of local governance (Peters and Pierre, 2016). On the other hand, administration encompasses the practical implementation of policies, effective management of resources, and the operational aspects that are crucial for the functioning of local government entities (Hood, 1991; Bovaird, 2016). This boundary signifies the importance of striking a harmonious balance between political considerations and administrative efficiency, highlighting the challenges faced by local political leaders as they navigate the intricate dynamics of policy development and implementation (Bryson et al., 2014; O'Toole et al., 2010).

The second aspect revolves around the complex interaction between the local community and central government, with local political leaders assuming the role of intermediaries who bridge the divide between the local populace and the higher levels of governmental authority (Lonsdale, 2009). These leaders serve as conduits of communication, facilitating the exchange of information, interests, and concerns between the community and the central government, while also advocating for the needs and aspirations of the local residents (Hendriks and Karsten, 2014). This connection between the local community and central government is crucial for effective governance, as it ensures that local perspectives and needs are considered in decision-making processes and that local governments are aligned with broader national objectives.

Extensive empirical research in the field of political leadership studies has contributed to the development of an analytical framework that explores the tasks, styles, contexts, and behaviours associated with local political leadership (Leach & Wilson, 2000; Lowndes and Leach, 2004; Morrell & Hartley, 2006; Hlepas et al., 2018). These approaches consider the impact of structural factors across different local government systems, emphasizing the indispensability of local political leadership in fostering effective governance and enhancing local government performance. However, it is important

to acknowledge that the understanding and manifestation of local political leadership can vary across different contexts and models of local government (Morrell & Hartley, 2006; Lowndes and Leach, 2004; Hlepas et al., 2018). Various approaches to political leadership emphasize different influential factors that shape the contextual framework within which leaders develop their styles. Contextual factors encompass policy characteristics and organizational elements, and their importance in relation to local political leadership has been recognized in previous research and existing literature (Elgie, 1995; Northouse, 2004).

Elgie (1995) argued that two key factors affect political leaders: institutional structures and societal needs. John and Cole (1999) added two more factors: party-related and external factors. Judd (2000) focused on how local leaders respond to national and local pressures, while Svava (1994) stressed the importance of the relationships between mayors, councils, and administrations. These diverse models or traditions of local government shape the conceptualization of local political leadership and the manifestation of political leadership processes within the local arena.

In this thesis framework, we consider the specific external environment of H&SCI for local political leadership. To develop a typology of contextual factors, this study will explain different features that shape the domains within which politicians operate. The policy and academic literature dealing with local government, such as Leach and Wilson (2000, 2002), Lowndes and Leach (2004), and Getimis and Hlepas (2006), Hlepas et al., (2018) and Heinelt et al., (2018) provide clarity and sufficient detail and this maintains a consistent level of analysis offering an in-depth description of contextual complexity. In addition, the logic informing this account of political leadership applies at regional and local levels, making it transferable to these contexts. The focus of this study is on several political contextual factors, namely partisanship, local authority size, economy of the local authority, urban/rural nature, and the relationship between elected members and managers. Before delving into the contextual factors of local political leadership, the role of local political leadership is examined.

2.5.2 Role of local political leadership

Local political leaders are political individuals who are elected by citizens for authority positions, are accountable to the voters, engage in political debates, and are exposed to political processes involving demands, pressures, and protests (Hollis, 1994; Lowndes and Leach, 2004; Morrell and Hartley, 2006). According to Kotter and Lawrence (1974), local leadership focuses on three main tasks. Firstly, they establish a programme for developing strategic and political leadership. Secondly, they commit to building and maintaining both internal (cohesiveness) and external networks (representational). Thirdly, they are concerned about implementing directives to ensure task implementation (Steyvers et

al., 2008). Ivanisevic's theoretical framework further expands on the functions and roles of local leaders, including administrative co-ordination, political integration, decision transfer, isolation between politics and administration, vertical integration of the political system, and representation of local interests (Ivanišević, 1987).

Likewise, councillors assume multiple functions that can be categorized into institutional roles, stemming from their electoral mandate, and organizational roles, pertaining to the effective functioning of the local authority (Stewart, 1998). As elected representatives and political figures, councillors bridge societal needs and problems with political actions, establishing an effective relationship between citizens and politics (Heinelt et al., 2018; Armenia, 2016). These institutional roles are assumed through municipal council elections, representing the functions of the municipality as a political institution based on representative democracy (Stewart, 1998, Orr and McAteer, 2010).

Several studies have found that municipal councillors play an organizational role or representative aspect that extends beyond the local government. For example, Stewart (1998) showed that UK councillors advocate for constituents on issues that are not directly related to local government. Similarly, Lowndes and Gardner (2016) explored how councillors in the UK engage with different types of networks, such as local, regional, national, and international ones. They found that councillors use networks to advance their community's interests, share knowledge and best practices, and influence policy agendas (Lowndes and Gardner, 2016). External orientation is considered as one of the tasks of leaders which allows them to offer perspectives beyond community organization (Lowndes and Leach, 2004) The nature of this perspective varies among individuals, influenced by their party affiliation, geographic area, and personal experience (Van der Walldt and Hembold, 1995), Some leaders demonstrate a more externally focused approach (Kickert and Koppenjan, 1997), while others prioritize the local community preferences (also observed by Baldersheim, 2003) If leaders have an external orientation, they may recognize the challenges of finding development opportunities within a close-knit community and, therefore, collaborate with external stakeholders on behalf of the community. Acting as a representative, which is a common function among all political leaders, requires empathy, active listening, and a service-oriented mindset. This representative aspect is also evident in the roles of councillors within the institutional framework of the council.

In summary, councillors can assume various organizational roles, such as council leader, committee chair, or committee member (Orr and McAteer, 2010) and they can act as representatives of the authority to external organizations, spokespersons for the authority, advocates for their represented areas, or caseworkers. Some of these functions are formally defined by municipal organizations and are carried out within the local authority or externally. Others, such as the roles of advocate and

caseworker, are developed by councillors themselves, expressing aspects of their representative role but recognized by the organization to the extent that it responds to them. The organizational roles are inherent to the councillor position and form its essential character (Hollis, 1994).

However, councillors face emerging challenges and opportunities in the 21st-Century context, requiring them to adapt their roles and behaviours. Literature shows that councillors have diverse and multi-faceted responsibilities, such as representing, facilitating, advocating, scrutinizing, and leading their communities (Stoker, 2006). Nonetheless, not all councillors adopt the same approach to their role. Some may prioritize their formal skills and hierarchical position, following the will of political parties, supporters, and other dominant actors. Others may involve the community in political decision-making and agenda-setting, using their influence and networks to address complex social issues and improve local governance (Hambleton and Bullock, 1996). The latter approach reflects a shift from local government to local governance, which emphasizes the role of local leaders in developing partnerships (Moore, 1995). It also indicates a more interactive public administration (Torfing et al., 2012), where citizens become more assertive (Dalton and Welzel, 2014). For instance, interactive governance involves elected politicians engaging in defining policy problems, designing innovative solutions, and generating support through dialogue with relevant stakeholders, including citizens, civil society actors, interest organizations, and private firms (Sørensen, 2018). This trend fosters a modern form of political leadership that requires different qualities and skills from councillors.

As an example of modern public administration, H&SCI in Scotland is not only a tool for public managers to mobilize local resources for service production, but also a means for elected politicians to enhance their political leadership by developing new policy solutions with broad ownership (Christie, 2011). One of the institutional platforms for H&SCI are the Integration Joint Boards, which involve elected councillors in a local stakeholder engagement body. This involvement provides them with an opportunity to exercise political leadership by contributing to problem-solving, innovation, and implementation in H&SCI (Christie, 2011). However, this research conceptualises their role, and their influence may vary depending on different contextual factors, such as political parties and economic resources (Hlepas et al., 2018). To explore this variation, the next section reviews how political contextual factors shape local political leaders. This review informs the analytical framework, which guides the data analysis. The study findings will enhance the understanding of the political-contextual-leadership nexus.

2.5.3 Contextualizing Local Political Leadership

In the sphere of local government leadership, the concept of the "political context" encompasses various dimensions that contribute to the leader's day-to-day operations. The definition and operationalization of this broad concept in this thesis involve the selection of specific measures that capture pertinent components of the political arena. Any aspect of a locality, such as its institutional structure, and external influences can be argued to have political significance and influence on local leaders (Hlepas et al., 2018). To maintain both simplicity and practicality, this thesis takes a more restricted approach to delineating and operationalizing the political context. The research focuses on some of the components that are relevant and influential for local political leadership, as indicated by previous studies. They are argued to be directly associated or closely relevant with the local political landscape, such as the relationship between local political leaders and senior officials. These components are selected based on a review of the literature on local governance and a research of local political leaders in public administration. These factors are categorized into five dimensions: economy and finance, partisanship, geographical considerations (such as the size of the area and its urban or rural nature), and frontline workforce. The table below summarizes the components, dimensions, and studies that have informed this selection.

Table 2.3 outlines the components, dimensions, and studies that have informed contextual factors selection.

Component	Dimension	Studies
Economy and finance	State of local public finance and, deprivation levels.	Hlepas et al., (2018), Chapman, (2018) and Lupton (2003).
Partisanship	Ties and loyalty to party or other political bodies.	Hlepas et al., (2018); Leach and Wilson (2002); and Getimis and Hlepas (2006).
Geographical considerations (such as the size of the area and its urban or rural nature)	Population served, number of stakeholders, governance arrangements impact. Social diversity in communities, service delivery challenges, geographical factors.	Copus and Leach, (2014) and Hambleton et al. (2022).

Political-administrative relationship	The degree of collaboration, trust, and influence between the political and administrative leaders	Forbes, (2008), Kane and Patapan, (2009) and Svava, (2003).
Frontline workforce	The needs, concerns, and readiness levels of frontline workforce.	Wimmelmann et al., (2018); May and Winter (2009) and Langbein (2000).

(Created by author)

This focused approach aligns with the categorization found in significant scholarly works, such as Hartley & Benington (1998), Wilson & Leach (2002), Wilson (2004), and Getimis and Hlepas (2006). However, the conceptualization of the political context in this thesis is constrained by a notable factor: the UK level political arrangement and context, which could have a significant impact on local political leaders. This restriction to the local components is primarily driven by practical considerations. Given the limitations of a single project, it is necessary to prioritize and to avoid expanding the scope to unmanageable proportions by incorporating UK level measures of the political context. The primary motivation behind this choice is parsimony. This research aims to examine the unambiguous political components within the environment of political leaders that are believed to impact their leadership style. Once this relationship is thoroughly investigated, subsequent projects can explore additional areas of interest as independent variables.

Even with this narrower conceptualization of the political context, there still remains a plethora of potential independent variables that address components of that political context. One way to structure both the search for relevant variables, as well as the analysis of the data, is to organize the political context into five different categories. Four categories are discussed below and one category of the expectations of frontline workers has been outlined in section 2.4.2.6 where situational leadership theory has been implemented using that literature.

2.5.3.1 Partisanship

Political parties play an important role in shaping the role of political leaders. The relationship between both political party and political leader is a symbiotic one, in which each has influence on each other (Elgie, 1995). Local political leaders often exhibit varying political interests and priorities in preserving and strengthening their autonomy, personal integrity, and networks within their political group, as well as promoting the well-being of their communities. Some leaders align themselves closely with their political party's agenda, potentially driven by prospect of progress in their political careers (Hlepas et al., 2018). The leadership style of mayors and councillors are further influenced by their partisan

affiliations and levels of independence (Leach, 2004; Getimis and Hlepas, 2006: 121; Hlepas et al., 2018). For instance, Hlepas et al (2018) conducted research on European local political leadership and found that independence status and political party affiliation played a role in shaping leadership styles. Their empirical findings indicated that Communist local political leaders tended to adopt a visionary style more frequently than other groups. Conversely, 'independent' political leaders were inclined towards a co-operative style, since political leaders forming part of this group cannot rely on party support, they can hardly afford to be authoritarian, and are therefore more likely to enforce co-operation. Thus, independent LPL often serve as consensus facilitators. Moreover, Copus (2004) explored how political parties in the UK shape the behaviour and performance of local political leaders. He argued that local political parties have a strong impact on the selection, training, and support of local leaders, as well as on their policy agenda and accountability. He also suggested that local leaders rely on their party affiliation to build their legitimacy and authority in the local context. In addition, John (2010) observed that political parties in the UK endorse specific styles of local political leadership and that they hold significant influence compared to their counterparts in other countries (John and Saiz, 1999), and that they help leaders gain power through party connections. He also points out that some local leaders have become influential political figures in the UK, such as Herbert Morrison in 1930s' London, John Braddock in 1940s' and 1950s' Liverpool, and T. Dan Smith in 1960s' Newcastle. However, he does not explain how these examples relate to his main argument or research question.

Another dimension to consider is the level of party politics' influence from the national level to the local level. Partisan policies are also important to consider, as concerns about excessive influence from national political parties on local political leaders are common (Kasapović, 2004: 81). Local political leaders may exhibit ambivalence and act in different ways. On one hand, they may prioritize adherence to the formal authority structure of the state, viewing local authority as a product of the central state constitution and legislation - a form of political decentralization. A pragmatic argument supports this perspective, suggesting that central governments possess the necessary financial resources to support various local projects (Ivanišević, 1987). Local political leaders can also establish political connections with members of the governing political party at the central state level, remaining loyal to the party's internal directives. On the other hand, local political leaders may perceive local citizenship and the local community as primary sources of legitimacy and prioritize service orientation. Meeting the needs and satisfying the local citizens becomes crucial for the political success of these local actors, with a significant portion of the population primarily interested in receiving quality services (Swianiewicz, 2001: 27, 30).

2.5.3.2 Geographical considerations

The geographical considerations in this research are broadly divided into two categories: the population size of the IJB area and urban/rural community needs. It has been argued that these considerations of local leaders' constituency can have a significant impact on their role and the way they shape their priorities. First, the population size of a local authority significantly influences the behaviours of local political leadership, and an organizational size has been identified as an explanatory variable in various studies (Child, 1984). According to the Local Government Association (2019), the population size of the local authority translates into the number of councillors that are elected to represent the area in local government. For instance, in Scotland, the largest community, Glasgow, comprises over half a million inhabitants and is represented by approximately eighty elected politicians. In contrast, smaller communities such as the Shetland Islands have twenty politicians and a population of fewer than 20,000. This shows that population size potentially translates into the size of the governing body of the respective local authorities. Such diversity not only impacts the organizational structure but also influences government regulations and administration (Fawcett Society, 2019).

Moreover, the urban and rural divide has long been recognized as a significant determinant shaping the role of local political leaders in the United Kingdom (Copus and Leach, 2014). The unique challenges and opportunities posed by differing urban and rural contexts have implications for leadership styles, decision-making processes, and community engagement. In urban areas, local political leaders often face a dynamic and diverse landscape. Urban environments are marked by higher population densities, greater economic activities, and intricate social structures (Myers, 2020). This complexity requires local political leaders to adopt flexible and adaptive leadership styles. For instance, Hambleton et al. (2022) examined the impact of mayoral governance and leadership innovation in Bristol, UK. The authors argue that the directly elected mayor model has enabled a more transformational and democratic style of leadership in the city, resulting in improved civic engagement, collaboration, and innovation and coming to terms with national growth plans, economic migration, and the influx of asylum seekers. Similarly, there is typically a greater number of medium and large private companies, along with a diverse range of public and private stakeholders who collaborate to enhance the city's competitiveness. In these contexts, the presence of local political leaders is found to be closely tied to intense competition for investment and employment opportunities (Getmis and Hlepas, 2006). Consequently, mayors in such contexts are more inclined to adopt an entrepreneurial style to tackle these challenges, although some may opt for a laissez-faire approach (Getmis and Hlepas, 2006).

On the other hand, some local authorities in Scotland experience relatively stable populations with slow demographic changes, as some are rural areas with limited internal migration. In areas where a strong sense of community exists, political leaders can operate smoothly and reinforce existing networks (Savara, 1994). Conversely, establishing and fostering a sense of community can be challenging in other areas. Consequently, the styles and challenges faced by political leaders differ across these diverse circumstances (Leach et al., 2000). These varying dynamics exert pressure on the provision of local public services and necessitate different political decision-making (Audit Scotland, 2018).

2.5.3.3 Political- Administrative relationship

In addition to these factors, local political leadership in Scotland is also influenced by the politics-administration dichotomy, which is the idea that political leaders should be responsible for making decisions, while administrative officials should be responsible for implementing those decisions (Forbes, 2008). This politics-administration dichotomy refers to the relationship between administrators, political leaders, and the public (Svara, 2003). Political administrative relations have been a subject of debate and research for over a century now, with Woodrow Wilson's famous words "administrative questions are not political questions" (1887), marking the beginning of this discussion. The traditional debate on political domination over the bureaucratic domain serves as a framework for analysing these roles. The division of labour between politics and administration has become the normative ideal in Western society. The relationship between politicians and administrators is a topic of constant debate and is examined from both normative and descriptive perspectives (Svara, 1990; Svara, 2003).

The normative ideal of a strict division between politics and administration is contrasted with empirical studies that reveal a more complex interaction and the diversified roles of both groups (Kane and Patapan, 2009). Administrators actively participate in formulating visions and objectives at the political level, going beyond mere means but also influencing ends. In essence, administrators play an active role in politics. Similarly, politicians recognize the importance of direct involvement in administrative affairs. For instance, Forbes (2008) conducted research on the health and social care partnership agenda in Scotland. They found the interactive relationships between officer and politician during the H&SC decision making process different from normative accounts. The study noted the existence of "cultural and political differences" as potential stumbling blocks to effective partnerships, although their significance was often exaggerated. Practitioners focused on the benefits of Community Health Partnerships and were generally able to overcome any cultural differences. However, challenges remained in the relationship between councillors and officers during the implementation of health and social care agendas. This shows that these contextual factors are important influences on the role of

local leaders in the decision-making process. This research aims to study the dynamics between these two actors to understand how they shape the choice of local political leadership style.

2.5.3.4 Economy and finances

The economic and financial conditions of local policy spaces and communities had wide-ranging effects on local governance, leading to financial challenges faced by numerous municipalities. This holds true even in prosperous countries where the overall fiscal situation of the government appears favourable (Stolzenberg et al., 2016) The socio-economic status of a community partially shapes the perception of the role and orientation of elected local leaders (Chapman, 2018). Since council members come from diverse social backgrounds and communities, they bring a range of prior experiences to their positions. For instance, communities grappling with high unemployment, social deprivation, and associated issues such as low educational attainment and crime (Lupton, 2003) may require political leaders to focus on attracting additional resources. In addition, certain indicators found in the literature highlight economic variations among Scottish local authorities, which align with the financial challenges discussed above. For instance, North Ayrshire Council has achieved a 25% reduction in its base budget over the past eight years, affecting various services differently. Specifically, they have implemented savings of 16% in education, 20% in social care services, and 50% in the economy and communities during this period. In contrast, Inverclyde Council has successfully decreased its staff by more than 500 employees (13% of the workforce) over the past seven years (Yamazaki, 2004). The council estimates the need to reduce staff by an additional eighty to 130 employees over the next two years (equivalent to 2 to 4% of the workforce) (Gordon, 2002). Similarly, East Renfrewshire Council aims to reduce its workforce by an average of 100 employees annually over the next three years, which constitutes around 3% of its workforce in the first year. These diverse experiences in response to these financial challenges, have led to the development of distinct internalized values, suggesting that council members in municipalities of different social ranks perceive their institutional and representational roles in distinct ways. Consequently, a crucial question arises regarding the impact of a local authority's financial situation on leadership approaches of local leaders.

Conclusion: Emerging themes from the leadership literature and research questions

In conclusion, this chapter is the first of two phases in the analytical framework. It has provided a comprehensive overview of the literature on leadership, encompassing its understanding, theoretical frameworks, political leadership styles, and contextual factors. The first chapter identifies the key leadership literature themes that guide the analysis of local political leadership in the context of Health and Social Care integration areas in Scotland. One of the central themes is that leadership is not a fixed

trait or position, but rather a dynamic process that involves influencing and collaborating with others to achieve a common goal (Northouse, 2021). This process is shaped by and adapted to the specific situation and environment in which it occurs, highlighting the importance of contingency and situational theories as a framework for understanding effective leadership styles and strategies in relation their political context. Leadership outcomes are determined by the actions and strategies (leadership styles) employed by leaders and can be measured by the impact they have in collaborative setting by interacting with partner organizations, communities, and the policy issues they address. The local political context, which includes factors such as the political party, institutional structure, economy, size, and manager-political relationship, serves as an independent variable that shapes the opportunities and challenges for local political leaders (Pearson and Watson, 2018; Leach and Wilson, 2002; Getimis and Hlepas, 2006).

These themes serve as a potential foundation for investigating the role of local political leadership in the Scottish Health and Social Care context. They are used in structuring and analysing the interview questions and approach to content analysis of policy documents in H&SCI. This analytical framework allows the exploration of the following Research Questions.

What is the role of local political leaders in the strategic decision-making of Scottish H&SCI?

What are the distinct local political leadership styles observed within different political contexts of health and social care integration (H&SCI) processes in Scotland?

Throughout Chapter 2, leadership has been consistently defined and conceptualized as a contextual process that involves influence exerted over others to guide, structure, and facilitate activities and relationships within a group or organization. Moreover, contextual factors surrounding leadership significantly shape leadership processes and outcomes. Thus, it is essential to examine how these elements affect the local political leaders in the case of Scottish H&SCI. This chapter has provided an in-depth analysis of leadership styles related to local governance. It has discussed the different leadership styles used by local political leaders and the different leadership theories that have been operationalised in the context of local political leaders. Contingency and situational leadership theories are applied in studying local political leadership in relation to their context. The literature suggests that the role of local political leaders is impacted by the political context i.e., partisanship, economy, and finance, political administrative leadership, and geographical considerations. In this context, to exercise leadership effectively, leaders have to reconcile with political contextual factors when performing their duties. This thesis specifically focuses on the leadership style as a key strategy employed by local political leaders to guide their actions in the policy process and deal with contextual influences. Thus, this chapter also outlined the evolutionary conceptualisation of leadership styles in

the literature. It has discussed the different definitions of leadership styles, the different dimensions of leadership styles, and different typologies of leadership styles. The chapter has argued that conceptualisation of leadership styles in the literature is important for understating the role of local political leaders in modern policy spaces.

This reinforces the argument that local political leaders' roles can be understood using leadership style as a 'key concept' to explore their role. The purpose of the next chapter is twofold; it is to validate the conceptualisations of leadership this research drew in Chapter 2, and it will re-assess to what extent the role of local political leaders can be navigated in the public administration literature with reference to their leadership styles. The role of local political leaders is examined in conjunction with their leadership styles as they fulfil their responsibilities in public administrative matters across three distinct paradigms. This will help to understand how different leadership styles played out in the different paradigms of public administrations and how local leaders played their role choosing a leadership style as a strategy to perform their actions. This exercise has the potential to strengthen the analytical framework of this study by contributing further into a mechanism of studying local political leadership using leadership styles as one of the main concepts. The second purpose is to provide a comprehensive perspective on the basis of the Research Questions. Its purpose is to delve into the literature on the evolution of the role of political leadership within three major paradigms of public administration. This will offer detailed insights into how the role of local political leadership has evolved over time. This exercise will help to evidence the strengths, weaknesses and controversies related to local political leaders in the public administration literature and to demonstrate to what extent their role has been explored in the evolution of public administration, and what are the key areas that need more attention for further research. By doing so, this thesis aims to demonstrate the necessity of conducting research on the role of local political leadership and will seek to fill an important research gap.

Chapter 3

Validating the Conceptualisation and Navigating the Gaps: The Integration of Public Services and the Role of Political Leadership in Public administration

Introduction

This chapter highlights the gradual evolution of public administration and its interplay with political leadership. It focuses on how the leadership practices of political leaders have shaped governance changes and contributed to public sector reforms across three major paradigms of public administration: 'old public administration, new public management and new public governance'. By analysing how leadership styles have influenced governance changes across different paradigms of public administration, the chapter highlights the need for further research on the role of local political leaders in the new public governance paradigm. The analysis highlights that the role of political leadership in shaping governance changes has been significant in old public administration and new public management and has reduced their role in the decision-making process, where managerial dominance has marginalized local political leadership in policy spaces. The emergence of the new public governance paradigm has led to a recognition of the importance of local political leadership in policy spaces, including Health and Social Integration in Scotland. The role of local political leadership is altered and regenerated compared to NPM in the current paradigm of NPG in public administration (Stoker, 2006; Sullivan, 2011). Building upon this foundation, Chapter 4 examines Scotland's policy context post-devolution 1999. It specifically explores how the developments in Scottish public administration resonate with NPG principles, highlighting the evolving role of local political leadership within the context of H&SCI implementation. This is how exploring the historical development of public administration, particularly in the UK can provide valuable insights for identifying and examining current research gaps in the literature. This recent development serves as a catalyst for investigating the extent of the role local political leadership played in strategic decision making of H&SCI areas in Scotland. Therefore, within the context of H&SCI, this study explores the local political leadership styles, through the role they play in strategic decision making of H&SC. Leadership styles serve as a framework to perform their actions for political leaders in this case study. Consequently, this chapter provides detailed discussions on leadership strategies in old public administration and leadership styles in the new public management paradigm, and offering insights into the expected leadership styles in new public governance and participatory initiatives such as H&SCI.

3.1 Framing Leadership Styles in the Historical Context of Public Administration: Old Public Administration

Public administration combines theory and practice to enhance the understanding of government and its relationship with society (Bapuji, 1989; Denhardt and Denhardt, 2015). Public administration has experienced fluctuating trends influenced by political sentiments, institutional conditions, and cultural traditions (Hood, 1991). Three paradigms have significantly influenced the organization, governance, and management of public organizations. The intellectual founding of the field of public administration can be traced to Wilson (1887) - "The Study of Administration," - where he identified two crucial aspects of government. The first aspect focused on determining who should create laws and their content, which had been extensively explored by political philosophers. The second aspect, however, received less attention and involved the practical details of administering laws with enlightenment, equity, efficiency, and minimal friction. By addressing these questions, Wilson inadvertently established the field of public administration with a dichotomous framework that attempted to distinguish politics from administration.

In the context of old public administration, political leaders have exercised their influence over public administration in a variety of ways over time, through legislation, appointments, budgets, and oversight (Frederickson, 1997). The policy goals were initially established by elected political leaders and subsequently refined by technical experts and bureaucracy to align with political directives. This centralized approach to political leadership indicates a domineering leadership style, where decision-making authority is concentrated at the top (Frederickson, 1997). In this context, government agencies played a critical role in delivering public value by translating political objectives into tangible outcomes (Salamon, 2002). Emphasizing efficiency in government operations, the old public administration, prioritized the effective implementation of policies. During this period, citizens were primarily regarded as voters or constituents, reflecting the limited engagement of the public in decision-making processes. However, it is important to recognize that traditional public administration, in practice, was more intricately intertwined with politics than its idealized form suggested (Waldo, 1948/2007; Denhardt and Denhardt, 2011). Government agencies were not immune to failures and challenges (Wolf, 1979).

According to Frederickson et al., (2018):

"(E)arly attempts to establish a legitimate role for administration in governance focused on addressing the accountability of non-elected administrators in democratic societies. These attempts acknowledged the inherent connection between politics and administration in practice, although indirectly grappled with the issue of how to conceptualize this relationship" (p., 32). Scholars such as

Carl Friedrich and Herbert Finer engaged in a debate concerning the legitimacy and function of public administration. According to Friedrich, responsible administrators possess broad discretion to anticipate political and technical challenges, striving to ensure the effectiveness of legislation. Friedrich recognized that laws do not embody fixed and universal truths, but rather represent pragmatic policies that are subject to continuous change (Friedrich, 1940). Administrators are expected to act in the public interest, guided by a sense of the common good rather than direct accountability to legislators. While this behaviour cannot be compelled, it should be elicited through an understanding of commonly shared needs and desires (Friedrich, 1940).

This Friedrich and Finer debate highlights the tension between the role of political leaders and the role of public administrators in the old public administration paradigm. On one hand, practical administration necessitates "political" decisions and actions but on the other hand, elected representatives must retain hierarchical control over political decisions. Political leaders were seen as influential actors in old public administration because they were seen as the ultimate decision-makers, the ones who held public administrators accountable, and the ones who represented the interests of the public.

This centralized command and control of political leadership led to questions about the extent and power of government. As a response, calls for a more decentralized government emerged. This shift aimed to leverage economic market forces in order to enhance the delivery of public services (Kettle, 2002). Consequently, a political shift occurred, leading to a return to the concept of decentralized governance. The emergence of new public management was driven by concerns over government failures, a belief in the effectiveness and efficiency of markets, a commitment to economic rationality, and a desire to move away from large, centralized government agencies towards devolution and privatization. Waldo (1948) predicted the replacement of old public administration with a more adaptable and democratic organizational model. The subsequent new public management movement advocated for the superiority of private-sector managerial techniques compared to those of public administration (Osborne, 2010).

3.2 New public management

The second paradigm is the new public management, which emerged in the mid-1980s and introduced market logic and strategic performance management into the public sector. This shift in paradigm had an insightful impact on governance structures and was accompanied by changes in leadership practices. Stewart and Walsh (1992) note that, prior to the 1970s, the British welfare state followed principles of hierarchy, planning, direct control, self-sufficiency, centralism, and professionalism. The

public sector approach during that time heavily relied on traditional notions of public administration, reflecting Taylor's top-down management ideas. These ideas refer to principles and approaches to management, which emphasize a hierarchical structure where decision-making authority and control are concentrated at the top levels of an organization (1911).

In the trajectory of UK public administration, a notable juncture emerged during the mid-1970s, marked by the demise of the post-war settlement grounded in Keynesian economic and social policies (Marsh and Stoker, 1995). Subsequently, another wave of changes unfolded in the late 1970s as the Conservative Party spearheaded a series of transformative measures that fundamentally reconfigured the state's role, redefined the delineations between the public and private spheres, and curtailed the expanse of the public domain (Gray, 1996). Consequently, extensive reforms have been instituted across public services, encompassing multi-faceted dimensions such as structure, organization, administration, and management. These reform initiatives, led by Conservative governments from 1979 to 1997 (some of which found endorsement from New Labour), revolved around the fundamental conviction that augmenting the quality, efficacy, and value of public services necessitated the cultivation of competition, commercialization, and the adoption of management techniques and personnel inspired by the private sector (Walsh, 1995).

Gray (1996) characterizes this significant shift as "ideological radicalism," also known as Thatcherism or the New Right agenda, signifying a departure from traditional Conservatism. Defining Thatcherism has proven challenging, yielding various interpretations. However, it generally denotes a governmental promotion of neoliberal public policies (Hall, 2011).

The rise of "anti-government parties" and leaders, particularly in the United States and Great Britain, coincided with public sector reforms following the elections of Ronald Reagan in 1980 and Margaret Thatcher in 1979 (Steger and Roy, 2010). While some argue that the Conservative government's restructuring of local government in the 1970s and 1980s, exemplifying the New Right, influenced changes in public administration, a more significant shift occurred with the advancement of far-right policies that aimed to redefine the relationship between policymaking and service delivery. Advocates assert that traditional policy approaches were discredited as effective resource allocation tools because of their susceptibility to "producer interests" and a lack of necessary discipline for ensuring allocative efficiency (Sullivan, 2011).

Consequently, politicians have redirected their focus away from citizens as taxpayers and service users, acknowledging the market as a suitable disciplinary mechanism to challenge the protected interests of producers within local government bureaucracy and better serve the interests of taxpayers and customers (Walsh, 1995; Hood, 1994). In practice, this approach aimed to isolate local politics from

service decisions to ensure their efficient delivery. Sullivan (2011) explained that the emphasis on keeping politics at bay was driven by the objective of establishing a new role for local government. Nicholas Ridley (1988), the key proponent of this new role, called it "empowerment."

Strengthening local authority epitomized their aspiration for a smaller state at the local level, albeit within a framework of strong central direction. This vision was accompanied by the introduction of a mixed economy, tendering processes, and public-private partnerships, as well as greater involvement of the Third Sector as service providers. Citizens were identified primarily in their roles as consumers or taxpayers. Consequently, various local government activities could be outsourced to external entities, enhancing the efficiency of service provision in alignment with taxpayers' preferences. This approach entailed reducing the number of local government employees and, notably, the number of elected councillors on the ground. The elected council's role, as often reiterated, would be limited to convening annually to agree upon a contractual framework (Sullivan, 2011).

This interpretation of local governance operated under the conviction of market primacy, the pursuit of individual citizen freedom from state intervention and the view that all council activities should be subject to calculation to render them negotiable or dispensable. The political-democratic dimension of local government found expression in electoral processes and the representation of the people's will through contract awards. However, the assumption was never made that the electorate desired an alternative through elections. This trajectory signalled a period characterized by what Hirst (2000) referred to as the 'post-political,' wherein democracy was perceived to serve the market rather than being served by it.

Therefore, departure from the new public management has not been immune to criticism. Opponents argued that the government's adoption of this form of management has led to a centralization of power rather than its decentralization, as decision-making authority becomes concentrated in the hands of a select group of government administrators overseeing the contracting process (Mongkol, 2011). Similarly, Christensen et al. (2007) contended that new public management is a broad and somewhat contradictory concept encompassing various administrative doctrines. This inherent complexity can impede the realization of political ambitions or goals. For local councillors, it necessitates self-restraint, as they are expected to align their activities with public objectives and to overcome their entrenched inclination to intervene in specific and minute matters of local administrative decision-making, instead focusing on broader issues (Van Thiel et al., 2007). Van Thiel et al. further asserted that new public management is a highly ambiguous concept, exhibiting the characteristics of a "chameleon." The new public management agenda faces challenges regarding a specific accountability model that involves reconciling conflicting community values and the

government's approach to serving the public interest (Morgan & Cook, 2014). One of the concerns arises from its tendency to blur the distinction between the public and private interests, often leading to a conflation of the conditions of a democratic state with matters of liability. According to Morgan & Cook (2014), democratic values should take precedence over cost reduction and speed. Furthermore, new public management fails to acknowledge that performance is an integral component of a broader range of governance issues that are essential for establishing public trust and legitimacy in governing institutions and their leaders (Morgan & Cook, 2014).

Amidst the widening social inequalities and the persistence of unresolved "wicked issues," (Brookers and Grint, 2010) the emergence of new public governance has sparked debates and discussions. While ongoing debates surround the essence of new public governance and its departure from new public management, it is evident that integration, collaboration, and community empowerment are increasingly being embraced (Glasby and Dickinson, 2014; Elliott et al., 2019). It does not seek to replace previous models entirely, as elements from previous frameworks will continue to co-exist, but it does go beyond internal management processes by addressing the intricate interplay between organizations and the political and administrative context in which they operate.

3.3 New public governance

According to Osborne (2010), the rise of new public governance reflects a shift from a centralized, elite-controlled, and homogenizing regime towards a more decentralized, pluralistic, and community-powered system that values democratic participation and collaboration. It has placed greater emphasis on democratic participation and involvement of the Third Sector, and it encourages co-production, a decentralized public service delivery approach involving citizens and local stakeholders. It has been used in a variety of contexts, such as education, healthcare, and social services (Pestoff, 2011, Connolly and Pyper, 2020). The contemporary reform of new public governance highlighted the inherent challenges in achieving operational efficiency in public administration practices. These challenges included meeting performance expectations within government agencies, but traditional hierarchical and rigid government bureaucracies are often slow to respond to change. They can also be unresponsive to the needs of citizens. This has created a demand for greater focus on problem-solving, transparency, and citizen engagement (Morgan and Cook, 2015). This realization of the need for enablement emerged in the 1990s as a response to the growing complexity and formidable nature of governance, where conventional market-oriented or bureaucratic approaches were proved to be inadequate. Instead, a governmental mechanism was sought that could effectively address the diverse local interests and the intricate nature of "wicked problems" (Perry, 2017).

A wicked problem transcends mere complexity, necessitating holistic and comprehensive governance approaches for effective resolution (Perry, 2017). These multi-faceted and interconnected challenges lack clear cause-and-effect relationships and often pose intractable difficulties. For instance, the endeavour to develop a National Health Service based on a scientific approach proves unattainable because of factors such as an ageing population, advancing medical interventions, unlimited demand and finite resources. Consequently, political decisions become imperative for resource allocation. These inherently contested issues exemplify wicked problems. Moreover, the challenges faced by the NHS, including obesity, drug abuse, and violence, extend beyond the realm of health and encompass complex social problems that transcend departmental boundaries. Knife crime serves as a prime example, intertwining medical, legal, and social aspects, thereby demanding comprehensive approaches beyond a single institutional framework (Brookers and Grint, 2010).

In 1995 John Stewart had an important contribution to this discourse, particularly in regard to the concept of enabling. Stewart equated enabling with empowered leadership and community empowerment, emphasizing the importance of responsive and attentive local government (Stewart, 1995). It entails actively listening to, and taking action based on, the opinions and aspirations of the local community, thereby representing the collective will of the community. Within this framework, citizens are regarded as stakeholders, alongside other local service providers whose actions necessitate coordination and alignment with community goals. This perspective of empowerment envisions service provision as an outcome of expressing the will of the community within a local democratic context.

This alignment of community and political participation with the core principles and existing institutions of representative democracy has been recognised as important in these initiatives (Teorell, 2006). This alignment with the principles and institutions of representative democracy is essential in assessing the relationship between these initiatives, established institutions, and actors within the representative democratic system. Political representatives play a key role as gatekeepers, influencing the political impact of participatory initiatives on policy decisions. Local political representatives possess the authority to implement these initiatives, even if they are not always the primary initiators" (Karlsson, 2012 p., 4). Often, such initiatives are driven by the local bureaucratic executives in the public administration, but it is the official decisions of the local council that enable these initiatives to take shape (Åström, Freschi, and Montin, 2010). In this context, Stoker (2006) emphasizes that both elected officials and public managers bear the responsibility of creating public value by effectively addressing the concerns of the public and pursuing actions that serve the public interest. Although this shift in the role of public managers raises pertinent questions regarding democratic accountability, it is important to recognize that this change primarily acknowledges the

longstanding significance of managers in goal setting, given the advice they provide to elected officials and the need to take action despite often ambiguous policy directions.

Therefore, political leaders and public managers are encouraged to work together and thoroughly assess and select from various alternative delivery mechanisms based on pragmatic criteria. This often entails fostering cross-sector collaborations and actively involving citizens to collectively attain mutually agreed objectives (Agranoff and McGuire, 2001). The role of public managers also changes in the new approach to public administration. In the old approach, they had little freedom to make decisions. In the emerging approach, they have more freedom to be innovative and efficient. However, they still have to follow the law and respect democratic and constitutional values. This is different from hierarchical structures (as observed in traditional public administration) or market-driven mechanisms (as emphasized in New Public Management).

Consequently, this displays a renewed role of democratic values and role of local political leaders in these initiatives, which extends well beyond the confines of traditional public administration or new public management, as they are expected to possess the ability to establish and guide networks that facilitate deliberation and service delivery (Moore, 1995; Christie, 2011; Stoker 2017). Their responsibilities also encompass maintaining and enhancing the overall effectiveness, capacity, and accountability of the system (Bryson et al., 2014). However, new forms of public participation present both opportunities and challenges for political representatives. For example, local politicians may be reluctant to let citizens influence, evaluate, or propose political decisions through participatory initiatives, as this deviates from the usual norms of representative democracy. Furthermore, participatory initiatives mean that councillors have a more prominent role in new public governance, but also face more scrutiny for their political actions between elections and may have to bypass traditional representative institutions for some projects (Koopman, 2004).

The instructional exercise, (see Table 3) served as a concluding comparison to the three foundational perspectives in public administration:

- (1) Old public administration
- (2) New public management; and
- (3) New public governance.

Denhardt and Denhardt (2003) revealed that the concepts of centralised and domineering leadership find a more seamless fit within the realm of old public administration. On the other hand, the concept of collaborative leadership aligns with the principles of new public governance and readily adapts to its perspective. This observation holds particular significance, especially when considering that, while

old public administration and new public management assume that control and authority reside within the organization (as exemplified by old public administration leadership), the organizational structure of new public governance is characterized by participation, collaboration, shared leadership, and transcending organizational boundaries.

Table 3: Comparing public administration perspectives- old public administration, new public management, and new public governance to support the distinction between old and modern political leadership styles.

	Old public administration	New public management	New public governance
Primary theoretical foundations	Political theory, social and political commentary augmented by naïve social science	Economic theory, more sophisticated dialogue based on positivist social science	Sophisticated dialogue based on positivist social science Democratic theory, varied approaches to knowledge including positive, interpretive, critical, and postmodern
Prevailing rationality and models of human behaviour	Synoptic rationality, 'administrative man'	Technical and economic rationality, 'economic man' or the self-interested decision maker	Strategic rationality, multiple tests of rationality (political, economic, organisational)
Mechanisms for achieving policy objectives	Administering programmes through existing government agencies	Create mechanisms and incentive structures to meet policy objectives through private and non-pro fit agencies	Building coalitions of public, non-pro fit and private agencies to meet mutually agreed needs
Conception of Public interest	Politically defined and	Represents the aggregation of	Result of a dialogue about

	expressed in law	individual interest	shared values
Motivational basis of public servants	Pay and bene fits, civil-service protection	Entrepreneurial spirit, ideological desire to reduce size of government	Public service, desire to contribute to society
To whom are public servants responsive?	Public	Clients, customers and Citizens	Citizen
Approach to accountability	Hierarchical – administrators are responsible to democratically elected political leaders.	Market-driven – the accumulation of self-interest will result in outcomes desired by broad groups of citizens (or customers).	Multi-faceted – public servants must attend to law, community values, political norms, professional standards, and citizen interests.

(Source: Denhardt and Denhardt, 2003).

After examining these three paradigms of public administration and their impacts on leadership, this section concludes with specific focus on the new public governance paradigm, known for emphasizing community participation and revitalizing the role of local political leaders. The following section will explore leadership approaches closely aligned with this evolving framework of NPG. Although modern leadership styles associated with this modern paradigm have been discussed Chapter 2, this section will extend that discussion by examining participatory and collaborative approaches to modern leadership. Departing from the traditional command and control style that dominated old public administration and the subsequent marginalization of local political leaders during the new public management era, new public governance advocates for leadership styles that actively cultivate participation, empowerment and collaboration. The new public governance paradigm places significant value on the utilization of participatory and collaborative approaches to leadership, aligning with its core principles of inclusive decision-making and citizen engagement in shaping public policies. This section examines the distinctive characteristics and consequential implications of these leadership

approaches, illuminating their suitability and effectiveness within the context of new public governance, particularly in the context of H&SCI.

3.4 Exploring Collaborative Leadership Styles and Themes in Participatory Initiatives

Contemporary public governance aims to enhance co-ordination, integration, and the efficiency of public services while prioritizing citizen-centred and client-focused approaches (Pollitt and Bouckaert, 2011). Achieving these objectives necessitates collaborative efforts between individuals and organizations to collectively address and manage common challenges. Consequently, when implementing the new public governance framework in diverse contexts, it becomes crucial to establish a clear understanding of the leadership framework (Reid, 2014). This involves transitioning from individualistic to collaborative leadership, which generates public value, and this refers to the societal benefits and outcomes generated through collaborative and participatory processes involving government entities, civil society organizations, and stakeholders (Bevir et al., 2003). Moreover, leadership responsibilities are often distributed horizontally and vertically, involving community, private-sector, Third Sector and political leaders (Reid, 2014; Hartley, 2018). These new forms of co-operation are expected to foster equal participation among collaborative partners, leading to joint governance, meaningful dialogue, and consensus-based decision-making processes. This can lead to new models of co-operation that transform previous hierarchical and authoritarian political governance structures (Rhodes, 1997). However, traditional leaders can play a valuable role in collaborative arenas, but they may need to adapt their leadership style to be effective. In particular, they may need to be more open to different perspectives and more willing to compromise. In addition, they may need to develop new skills, such as conflict resolution and consensus-building (Bassu, 2011). When the leaders are not able to compromise in a collaborative setting, these instances may lead to governance Inertia and deadlock (Bodin, 2017).

A clear distinction emerges when comparing modern collaborative leadership with traditional hierarchical leadership. In the world of collaboration, traditional hierarchical leadership is often portrayed as a command-and-control affair, where authority reigns supreme within leadership positions (Feldman and Khadadian, 2001; Innes and Booher, 2010; Walker, 2002). According to Walker, traditional leadership is known for its ability to enhance efficiency, maintain a clear chain of command, and operate through established communication and decision-making channels. It emphasizes the leader's control over the involvement of others in decision-making and implementation. However, this form of leadership tends to shoulder the entire burden of decisions and outcomes, offering limited

flexibility in the decision-making and implementation process. This stands in stark contrast to the collaborative nature of leadership, a key aspect highlighted by, Vangen and Huxham (2005).

Collaborative leadership stands apart from traditional leadership models, emphasizing the facilitation of collaborative processes rather than wielding power and authority. As Innes and Booher (2010) describe, collaborative leadership adopts a generative approach that fosters collective learning, collaborative problem-solving, and the exploration of creative solutions. By empowering stakeholders, collaborative leadership enables consensus-building and the identification of shared solutions that address the complex challenges faced by diverse groups. Silvia and McGuire (2010) insightfully point out that the dynamics of collaboration differ from those encountered in traditional public administration settings. The stakeholders involved, the collaborative structure itself, and the challenges presented are often more complex and nuanced in collaborative environments. This necessitates a shift in the skills, behaviours, and approach of collaborative leadership, requiring leaders to adapt their strategies to effectively navigate these unique dynamics.

In traditional representative democracies, incentive structures and institutionalized perceptions of roles and practices present challenges for politicians' involvement in interactive governance. Competitive incentives within party systems limit politicians' allocation of time outside political spheres and internal party matters. Moreover, the conventional perception of politicians as authoritative lawmakers and visionary leaders restricts their potential for innovation and collaboration (Stoker, 2006; Helms, 2012). Hence, the deterioration of political leadership are serious challenges in polarized and fragmented Western societies. Politicians need to step forward and embrace collaborative processes to address these challenges. The traditional notion of democratic leaders as exclusive decision-makers is becoming increasingly outdated. This is because cross-border collaborations and participatory democracy are gaining more prominence (Torfing et al., 2012). Citizens are becoming more informed and seeking alternative ways to navigate politics beyond traditional party influence (Dalton and Welzel, 2014).

Participatory models of democracy place a strong emphasis on citizen engagement in the policy development process outside of election periods (Greasley and Stoker, 2008; Connolly et al., 2021). This approach recognizes the value of involving citizens in shaping policies by leveraging their knowledge, identifying valuable resources, and fostering community engagement (Smith, 2009). Participatory democracy fosters active engagement, learning, and the incorporation of diverse knowledge and resources to enhance governance effectiveness (Chambers, 2006; Haus and Sweeting, 2006). Political leaders are required to collaborate with stakeholders beyond formal structures to set agendas, find solutions, and mobilize resources for policy implementation. The growing emphasis on

collaboration is driven by the increasing need for politicians to mobilize resources and gain support from diverse groups to address the rising costs of public services (Leach and Wilson, 2002; Morrell and Hartley, 2006; Sørensen and Torfing, 2016). This evolution highlights the changing role of political leaders in facilitating collaboration, building alliances, and leveraging external networks to effectively tackle complex societal challenges and deliver public services.

Political leadership in a collaborative context can also be characterized as leaders augmenting their influence through power-sharing mechanisms (Dyhrberg-Noerregaard and Kjær, 2014), and aligning with the notion of facilitative leadership as described by Svaara (1990). Facilitative leadership enables political leaders to achieve objectives by harnessing the efforts of others (Svaara, 1990) and fosters constructive interactions and communication between local government officials and the broader public, while providing guidance in goal setting and policy formulation (Svara, 2003). This democratic ethos promotes the idea of shared or distributed leadership, as every citizen has the right to participate in decision-making processes and mobilize support based on reason and preferences (Kane, Patapan, and Hart, 2009). Consequently, there are discernible trends toward power diffusion, not only across political sectors and stakeholders (Kane, Patapan, and Hart, 2009), but also within the political realm itself, with decision-making authority being shared among defined groups of citizens (Bolden, 2011; Grønn, 2002; Pearce).

Similarly, Kane, Patapan, and Hart (2009) describe the evolution of leadership in liberal democracies as "dispersed democratic leadership." Public leadership is no longer solely confined to the elected political sphere; it has permeated various societal domains, including politics, administration, justice, social affairs, and economics. The diversification of public leadership poses challenges for elected politicians in effectively responding to problems and seizing opportunities as they, then, lack the sole power and authority to make binding decisions. Masciulli, Molchanov, and Knight (2009) offer a compelling perspective, suggesting that the interaction between political leaders and their stakeholders or subordinates should be viewed as an ongoing process of mutual adaptation. As leaders navigate the intricacies of local and political contexts, they must engage in discourse with their supporters, fostering a dynamic exchange of ideas and perspectives. This dynamic interaction not only influences the attitudes and beliefs of both leaders and followers but also creates an environment conducive to innovation. Within this innovation process, political leaders leverage their charisma and persuasive abilities to drive change and inspire stakeholders and subordinates towards the attainment of new objectives. Furthermore, the collaborative process is most effective when political leaders adopt a shared leadership approach and actively facilitate the process (Linden, 2002). By engaging in constructive dialogue and nurturing collaborative relationships, political leaders can effectively

navigate complex governance dynamics and foster an atmosphere of creativity and collective problem-solving.

Conclusion

The purpose of this chapter has been twofold; first to expand on the analytical framework established in Chapter 2 and secondly to evidence the under-researched area of political leadership in public administration. The chapter has also provided a detailed account of leadership dynamics in a major school of thoughts in public administration. The examination of three major paradigms of public administration highlights the evolving role of political leaders and the gap in research regarding their power and influence. Traditional public administration enabled a command and control, centralized leadership style, where political leaders held significant power. They were treated as political masters between 1900 and the 1950s and bureaucracy was treated as a mechanism to deliver on political promises. However, with the emergence of the New Right and managerial primacy in the UK, the role of local political leaders diminished to mere contract approvals on an annual basis. This indicated local political leaders' "hands off" approach in policy spaces. The subsequent rise of the new public governance paradigm revitalized the role of local political leaders in strategic decision-making processes at the local level. This paradigm shift recognized the importance of collaborative and participatory approaches, with political leaders once again playing a crucial role in shaping policies and initiatives along with civil branch and third sector. The Scottish H&SCI agenda serves as an example of this new public governance model, demonstrating innovative approaches in the Scottish context (Connolly and Pyper, 2020) that involve local political leaders in the decision-making process of H&SC.

This means that the renewed role of local political leaders in contemporary public sector reforms are relatively new phenomena which indicate a need for more research. The next chapter will evidence these identified gaps which are related to local political leaders' roles in Scottish H&SC by examining the key development in Scottish politics that led to renewed role of local political leadership in H&SCI. This exercise will further reinforce and contextualize this gap, shedding light on the specific dynamics and opportunities for local political leaders in Scotland.

Chapter 4

Contextualising the Study: Aspects of Public Service Reform in Scotland

Introduction

The health and social care agenda are the main premises of this study, and the entire case study is based on this. This chapter provides a comprehensive background on the role of local political leadership in public service reform, with a specific focus on H&SCI. It begins by exploring the public sector landscape in Scotland, and then discusses the political dynamics that have shaped reform efforts in the country.

The chapter will explore the following:

- The underlying ideas that have shaped the reform agenda in Scotland since devolution.
- The changes in the decentralized policy framework over the past two decades.
- The influence of these changes on governance approaches and structures.
- How these ideas align with the evolving role of local political leadership.

The chapter explores the impact of Scottish devolution on the empowerment of localized approaches to service delivery. It does this by dissecting the key dynamics and developments resulting from the devolution of powers to the Scottish Parliament and the subsequent implications for local government and service provisioning. In particular, the discussion centres on how devolution has catalysed a transformative shift toward localized decision-making within the Scottish political landscape. It scrutinizes the policies and initiatives advanced by the Scottish Government to bolster community empowerment and local autonomy, with a specific emphasis on their application in service delivery. Moreover, this chapter critically assesses the effectiveness and outcomes of these localized approaches to service delivery in Scotland. By considering the triumphs, hurdles, challenges, and limitations encountered in the implementation of empowerment approaches and their subsequent impact on local governance and local communities, this analysis irradiates the complex interplay between local political leadership role and the evolution of service provision, in Scotland.

The themes covered in the previous chapter provide valuable context for understanding Scottish policy dynamics during the post-devolution period. Particularly noteworthy is the transition from New Labour's efforts until 2007, which marked a shift from new public management principles towards the promotion of empowerment, participatory, collaborative, and decentralized practices in Scottish public

governance. These evolving governance paradigms, closely aligned with new public governance principles, have persisted since 2007 under the SNP's leadership. This transition is not only significant ideologically but also demonstrates a political consensus that transcends traditional left-right divisions, as argued by academics such as Stoker (1996) and Morgan and Cook (2015). Understanding this context is essential for analysing the Scottish Government's 2014 initiative to establish H&SCI, which marked a significant shift in public health policy. The initiative sought to involve local stakeholders, including political leaders, in delivering Health and Social Care services, thus decentralizing power, and promoting community engagement. However, the role of local political leaders, as community representatives in contemporary public sector reforms, has not been subject to sufficient level of research. Therefore, this thesis aims to bridge this gap by examining the strategic decision-making role of local political leaders within the H&SCI framework. The study will examine how local political leaders have contributed to the integration of health and social care by working to improve co-ordination, communication, shared decision making between health and social care providers, and by developing new services that meet the needs of people with complex health and social care needs. The study will also take into account the unique local political context and the leadership approaches adopted by local councillors.

4.1 Scottish Devolution: Empowering Localized Approaches to Service Delivery.

Shaping Governance in Post-Devolution Scotland: Continuity, Change, and Power Dynamics

Constitutional, political, and administrative factors have consistently shaped the governance of Scotland, with a heightened focus on these themes since 1999 (Arnott, 2020). The post-devolution era in Scotland ushered in a significant shift in institutional arrangements. While the devolution of legislative powers to the Scottish Parliament and the establishment of devolved governance brought about new governance structures, there remained elements of continuity in governance approaches compared to the pre-1999 period, which had been referred to as the 'administrative devolution' phase (McGarvey, 2012). McGarvey has said that, prior to devolution, discussions on UK politics often depicted the United Kingdom as a unitary state, assuming that Scotland mirrored the broader UK political landscape. However, while acknowledging differences in structure, policy agenda, process, and output, McGarvey (2002, 2005) argued that the similarities outweighed the differences. Scottish politics has maintained a degree of continuity in various aspects, such as the powers of well-being, best value implementation, and retention of business rates at the centre. These aspects reflect the central priorities of the Scottish government, which also supports citizen participation and seeks to

increase electoral turnout. McConnell (2004) provides an analysis of these aspects and their implications for Scottish governance.

However, the devolution of new powers to the Scottish Parliament in 1999 has also had significant implications for the governance structures and political dynamics in Scotland. One of the main effects has been the attempt at increased scrutiny and accountability of the Scottish Executive/Government by the Scottish Parliament (Arnott, 2020). Nevertheless, the relationship between the two institutions has not always been smooth, as they have had to balance their roles and responsibilities over the past two decades (Arnott, 2020). Another notable change has been the transformation of electoral politics, which has led to diverse approaches to forming the devolved government. Unlike the traditional Westminster model that favoured a majoritarian and adversarial style of politics, the Scottish Parliament aimed for a more consensual and co-operative approach (McGarvey, 2003). This has resulted in different types of coalitions and minority governments over time.

In this context, the process of Scottish devolution and the establishment of the Scottish Parliament in 1999 further provided Scotland with the opportunity to pursue its own approach to public policy, addressing Scottish issues with Scottish solutions rather than relying on the UK government to decide for it (Cairney, 2013). The Scottish Executive (Labour Government) has consistently emphasized the importance of community involvement in executive policy, launching various initiatives to enhance the participation of marginalized communities in the democratic process (Arnott, 2020). This period of democratic renewal witnessed reforms in local political decision-making processes, focusing on collaborative approaches to revitalizing geographic communities through partnerships and community participation. However, devolution on the other side has also challenged the assumption that power was centralized in Westminster and Whitehall before 1999. McGarvey (2012) argues that Scottish local government had a degree of autonomy and influence through the Scottish Office in Edinburgh, which was responsible for administering most domestic policies in Scotland. Therefore, devolution has not simply shifted the centre of central-local relations, but rather reconfigured them in complex ways (Kelly, 2007; McGarvey, 2012).

Furthermore, the impact and potential of decentralization also varies among stakeholders. In Scotland, devolution has introduced changes to the political landscape, fostering a distinct Scottish political atmosphere in certain policy domains, such as education, health and social care. Moreover, devolution has created political and legislative capacities, offering multiple avenues to address complex issues in Scotland, such as education, and health and social care among others (Bennett et al., 2002). As a result, research on the effects of decentralization on local government in Scotland has indicated positive outcomes (Keating, 2010). However, decentralization has also created a tension

between the need to ensure the autonomy and accountability of the devolved institutions, and the desire to maintain the coherence and coordination of the public sector in Scotland (Torrance, 2006; Keating, 2010).

This tension resulted in the emergence of internal centralising dynamics, whereby the Scottish Government used its powers to influence and regulate the local authorities and public bodies that deliver public services in Scotland. For instance, the Scottish Government can freeze the council tax, which may limit the ability of local authorities to raise their own revenues (Scottish Government, 2023). This measure increased the central control over local finances, possibly affecting local service delivery and independence. The Scottish Government also imposed the Best Value regime that was part of Local Government Act (2004), which subjected the local authorities and public bodies to regular audits and inspections, and to a duty to secure continuous improvement in their performance. These internal centralising dynamics have had significant implications for the political landscape and the policy domains in Scotland, as they have affected the balance of power, the distribution of resources, the diversity of interests, and the quality of services in the devolved system (Keating, 2010).

4.2 Local Authorities and the Scottish Executive: Integrated Partnerships and Devolution

Following devolution, local authorities in Scotland serve as a central institution of the Scottish Executive (Labour government), which has the responsibility of enhancing the well-being of ordinary citizens (McGarvey, 2012). The partnership between local government and the Scottish Executive (Labour Government) plays a crucial role in realizing the government's social justice agenda and establishing a comprehensive framework. Local authorities often uphold the Executive's commitments by aiming to foster strong communities, cultivating a skilled workforce, and facilitating sustainable development (NPF, 2021; Scottish Government, 2018). In addition, local authorities play a vital role in advancing the objectives of devolution, encompassing democratic control and political accountability across Scotland (McGarvey, 2002). However, during the New Labour Government, local government in Scotland has been facing similar pressures and policies as other parts of the UK, including local government restructuring in the mid to late 1990s which reduced the number of local authorities from 65 to 32 and a decline in central-local government dynamics (though not as severe as in England) (Allmendinger, 2003; McGarvey, 2008). The policies implemented in the 1980s and 1990s, along with the establishment of a new level of accountable government, presented challenges for central government in managing the local tier. Addressing this issue became a priority in Scottish parliamentary discussions. To examine the relationship between the Scottish Parliament and local authorities, the Scottish Office commissioned the McIntosh Report, which made comprehensive

recommendations on parliamentary and ministerial relations, electoral agreements and reforms, council activities, and the role of local councils (McGarvey, 2008).

The White Paper on Devolution (Office of Scotland, 1997) emphasized co-operation in fostering effective relations between the two tiers of government. McIntosh's report, "Forward: Local Government and the Scottish Parliament" further advocated a strategic alliance between the Parliament and local government, with equal consideration given to both levels Scottish Executive, 1999a,. As explained by McGarvey (2002), the White Paper on Devolution (Office of Scotland, 1997: paragraph 6.7) explicitly outlined that the national efforts to improve central-local relations were not aimed for a Parliament to assume control over the powers of local authorities. In this regard, a permanent joint conference, the Community Leader Forum, was created to facilitate dialogue between ministers and council leaders, examining best practices and leadership changes. However, academics raised concerns about decentralization's impact on local government in politically oriented village life in Scotland (Alexander, 1997; Sinclair, 1997). While both Parliament and local government possess democratic foundations, the ultimate authority to determine the fate of local government rests with the UK Parliament (McIntosh Commission, 1999).

In the light of the recommendations put forth by the McIntosh Commission, the Scottish Executive was seen to embrace the suggestions, resulting in the creation of several new entities dedicated to addressing various aspects of the central-local relationship. Some of the initiatives that were launched to promote local governance were the Community Leadership Forum, the Renewable Local Democracy Working Group (also known as the Kerley Group), and the Leadership Advisory Board. These initiatives aimed to enhance the role and capacity of local authorities and communities in decision-making and service delivery. McIntosh (1999) provides a detailed account of these initiatives and their outcomes.

4.3 Enhancing Local Democracy and Political Leadership in Scotland: Recommendations and Reforms

The Working Group for Renewing Local Democracy, established on the recommendations in the McIntosh report, aimed to enhance local democracy in Scotland. Chaired by Richard Kerley, an academic from Edinburgh, the group published its report in June 2000, presenting a number of recommendations (Kerley, 2000). These recommendations sought to foster accountability within local government by establishing external mechanisms that facilitated public access to, and comprehension of, local governance processes. They included implementing a proportional voting system, remunerating council members, adjusting the election cycle, and promoting clear lines of responsibility to ensure the compatibility of participatory processes with the roles of elected officials. However, the

literature highlights challenges in achieving accountability and tensions between representative democracy and participatory approaches (Stoker, 1999; Stoker, 2000; McGarvey, 2001b). McAteer and Orr (2006) argued that the promotion of participatory processes by Scottish central government has impacted traditional structures of local political participation, raising concerns about the impact of the participatory agenda on governance structures and the authority of councillors.

Notably, the Kerley Report (2000), which focused on local political leadership, aligned with the broader UK agenda for local councils. It recommended equal pay for top local political executives (councillors) and Members of the Scottish Parliament (MSPs), aiming to enhance the leadership role of elected leaders (Leach and Wilson, 2000). In addition, the report proposed higher compensation for councillors with additional responsibilities, particularly those from non-majority parties. It suggested eliminating the wage threshold for politically restricted jobs and provided guidance on the composition of boards, emphasizing proportionality, and recommending a range of nineteen to fifty-three members (except for the Highlands Council). The report also emphasised the need for a strong link between ward and councillor, fair representation for independents, geographic diversity, and alignment of council wards with natural communities. To enhance accessibility, it recommended reviewing business procedures, providing administrative support for part-time councillors, and encouraging more participation from under-represented groups on councils. Furthermore, it proposed lowering the age limit for standing as a councillor from 21 to 18 (McIntosh, 1999). These recommendations aimed to strengthen local political leadership and broaden representation within councils, complementing the objectives of the working group's report on renewing local democracy.

Fostering greater public participation is a desirable outcome for addressing the democratic deficit between leaders and the public. This objective is particularly relevant in the context of local government in Scotland, as highlighted by both the McIntosh (1999) and Kerley (2000) reviews of local councils. These reviews called for increased engagement with under-represented groups and emphasized the importance of sustained public debate, review, and questioning of local authority policies.

The impact of these ideas is evident in the approaches taken to report on legislative developments. For example, the Scottish Government's launch of the 'National Conversation' on devolution in August 2007 exemplifies the use of deliberative processes to engage the public in discussions on highly political issues. In addition, community planning and the H&SCI agenda emphasizes the collaborative process of empowering communities to effect change and have more influence over matters that are important to them. It recognizes the potential of Scotland's communities as a valuable source of talent

and creative solutions to local challenges, highlighting the role of community empowerment in stimulating and harnessing local people's energy (Scottish Government, 2009).

4.4 Community Planning in Scotland: Empowering Communities, Legal Framework, and Governance Dynamics

It is evident that the implementation of community planning in Scotland has aimed to address the involvement of neglected stakeholders and prioritize local issues. The McIntosh Commission's recommendation of community planning as a mechanism for developing and implementing strategic plans demonstrates the initial commitment and attempt of the Scottish Executive to empower communities. This empowerment is emphasized by the Scottish Government, which recognizes the importance of tailoring the level of empowerment to each community's specific needs (Scottish Executive, 2001c; CEA 2015). Building upon this context, the attention given to community planning in 1998 through the establishment of Pioneer Councils, Pioneer councils in Scotland in 1998 were a group of 12 local authorities that volunteered to participate in a pilot scheme to test new ways of delivering public services. The scheme was launched by the Scottish Office in 1997, as part of the Modernising Government agenda, and aimed to promote innovation, partnership, customer focus, and best value in local government. This further highlights the commitment to inclusive governance in Scotland. This approach aligns with the concept of "joined up government" proposed by Lloyd and Illsey (1999), emphasizing collaboration between the council and other organizations to promote community well-being. By providing a comprehensive framework, community planning strives to encompass the efforts of various institutions involved in community development and skill-building (Forester, 2009; Forester, 2019). According to Cairney and McGarvey (2013), the need for a strategic structure and shared vision among existing partnerships, as emphasized in the 1998 report by the Community Planning Working Group, underpins the importance of effective coordination and collaboration. Local committees play a pivotal role as intermediaries, facilitating the alignment of strategies, activities, and resources to collectively pursue objectives in local governance.

The Local Government Act enacted in Scotland in 2003 provided a solid legal foundation for community planning.

“This legislation extended the statutory obligation of citizen engagement for service improvement beyond local authorities to include chief constables, police boards, NHS boards, enterprise agencies, fire services, and transport agencies. It introduced the discretionary power to advance well-being, granting local authorities the authority to undertake actions aimed at promoting or enhancing the well-being of their area and residents “(Albert and Passmore, 2008).

The enactment of the Local Government Act further fortified community planning, endowing it with statutory powers to promote well-being, achieve best value for money and engage a wider range of public entities in the process. This legal framework expanded the scope and influence of community planning, reinforcing its commitment to inclusivity, collaboration, and the enhancement of local services. As highlighted in the Scottish Government document (2008), the Guidance on Best Value highlights the importance of authorities being responsive to the diverse needs of communities, citizens, customers, employees, and other stakeholders. This entails developing plans, priorities, and actions that are informed by a deep understanding of these needs, and maintaining an ongoing dialogue with public sector partners, as well as the local business, voluntary, and community sectors. Moreover, consultation arrangements are expected to be open, fair, and inclusive (Scottish Government, 2008). In current terms, this proposal materialized in the form of the 2015 Community Empowerment Act, which granted councils the authority to engage in community initiatives, empowering them with greater autonomy to serve the interests of their communities. COSLA, which represents Scottish local authorities and is a longstanding advocate for recognizing the pivotal role of communities, welcomed this development, perceiving community initiatives as a means to empower councils (COSLA, 2010). Reforms targeting specific services, such as the Health and Social Care Integration Act 2014, further necessitate the active involvement of local authorities, local political leaders, communities, senior officials, and other stakeholders in service delivery (Pearson and Watson, 2018; Christie, 2011).

Therefore, a prevailing theme that begins to emerge from this ongoing discourse is the significance of community planning. This emphasis on community planning resonates with the principles of New Public Governance (NPG) as it promotes collaborative decision-making, citizen engagement, and the empowerment of local actors, underscoring its value as a mechanism for coordinating and implementing policy initiatives at the local level (Community Planning Working Group, 1998; Stoker, 2006; Christie, 2011). Several evaluations conducted by reputable organizations such as the Scottish Convention on Local Government (COSLA), the Scottish Executive (Scottish Executive, 1999), and the Community Planning Working Group (2001) have consistently provided evidence of the positive outcomes associated with community planning. These benefits encompass the provision of a local strategic vision, increased participation at the local level, effective partnerships, and community leadership. Notably, the development of H&SCI in Scotland has garnered considerable attention beyond its borders (Freeman and Moore, 2008; Pearson and Watson, 2018). It is widely recognized that this approach significantly differs from the one adopted in England. In the context of H&SCI, the role of leadership has been identified as a critical factor influencing its success (Pearson and Watson, 2018).

However, the fundamental question that warrants emphasis is whether community empowerment signifies a transition towards governance characterized by equitable negotiation of power and responsibility in local partnerships with communities, or if it involves processes that manipulate communities into assuming additional responsibilities (Tabner, 2020; Connolly et al., 2020). Upon initial examination, policy plans may appear as indications of a shift from government-centric approaches to governance, recognizing the constraints of top-down interventions and aiming to leverage community resources. Nevertheless, an alternative viewpoint posits that the discourse on power distribution serves as a governmental tactic, employing an illusory incentive that places greater responsibility on communities (McGarvey, 2003; Connolly and Pyper, 2020). In fact, the initial political rhetoric surrounding this programme explicitly refers to communities assuming increased responsibility (Scottish Government and COSLA, 2009). Despite the Scottish approach emphasizing communities gaining power, there are likely to be underlying political conceptions shaping these assumptions. The Scottish Government's emphasis on partnership signifies a notion of positive sum, whereby communities and the state engage in a collaborative endeavour to generate collective power (Lowndes and Pratchett, 2012; Rolfe, 2016). This approach highlights the potential for mutually beneficial outcomes, as stakeholders work together to address societal challenges and pursue shared goals.

In this context, Pratchett (2004) and Ilsley and Coles (2009) conducted an analysis of local government reforms in United Kingdom, focusing on local autonomy and democracy, and argued for their practical implications. In the British context, the authors highlighted that, despite the Labour government's strong commitment to democratic renewal, the initial phase remains highly centralized. Theoretically, the new reforms present a way to address these challenges by establishing a framework of nationally agreed policy outcomes that allow local institutions to implement context-specific solutions. Pratchett (2004) highlights that there is some evidence that councils have gained more decision-making flexibility at the local level, leading to steps being taken to empower local authorities to benefit the community. However, the extent to which community empowerment initiatives can effectively cultivate a sense of local ownership remains uncertain. Local democracy can be enhanced by empowering communities, for example, by involving non-elected actors in decision-making. Nevertheless, the lack of a clear agreement on democratic principles and values creates doubt about whether this can achieve the desired outcomes. This concern about the new localism plan is echoed by several authors, such as Walker (2002), Beecham (2003), Wadhams (2007), and Connolly and Pugh (2016). Sir Jeremy Beecham, for instance, expresses unease regarding the Government's inconsistent approaches, citing instances where local elected representatives have been deprived of power. Others

draw attention to the multitude and intricacy of community initiatives, accompanied by administrative and funding requirements (Hunt, 2005).

Moreover, in their examination of embedding co-production in leading integration, Connolly et al. (2020) delve into the challenges and issues faced by individuals within the policy system tasked with spearheading H&SCI. Their findings indicate limited relevance of local political leaders in the process, as they focus on evaluating the experiences of those responsible for managerial and bureaucratic leadership. Taking a more critical stance, Wadhams (2007) expands on these concerns and asserts that localism, despite its merits, possesses inherent limitations. These include a misalignment between national and local priorities difficulties in managing neighbourhoods with varying levels of responsibility, lukewarm enthusiasm among many local governments, and the potential for raising community expectations that cannot be met. Wadhams argues that unless these barriers are recognized and addressed, local communities may lose confidence in the localism approach and there are continuing challenges which are part of the process. Consequently, these changes are likely to have a significant impact on how local actors in Scotland have implemented public sector reforms.

4.5 Challenges and Limitations in the Integration of Services and Community Empowerment Initiatives: Disparity between Rhetoric and Reality

The era of the Scottish National Party (SNP) in power in Scotland has witnessed significant developments in the integration of services and community empowerment programmes. Since 2007, the SNP Government has introduced new powers to grant local stakeholders and communities participation rights in service improvement and particularly expand community rights regarding land and property control and ownership (CEA, 2015). The Public Bodies Joint Act (2014) and Community Empowerment Act (2015) reinforces the obligations of public sector authorities to involve local municipalities and address diverse planning and service delivery needs. These developments align with previous strategic guidelines emphasizing joined-up government and community empowerment in addressing various challenges (Scottish Government and COSLA, 2009), as well as the emphasis placed on community assets and co-production, as underscored in the review of public services by the Christie Commission (Public Services Commission, 2011) and the 'Scottish Approach to Government' outlined by Ferguson (2015), which sheds light on the importance attributed to these principles within the Scottish context.

The recommendations put forth by the Christie Commission (2011) underscored the importance of collaboration among local stakeholders and active community involvement in shaping the provision of local services, challenging the traditional top-down administrative approach. The Commission

advocated for a model of community empowerment that not only emphasizes community participation but also seeks to enhance their influence in the design and delivery of public services, including integrated delivery. While the language used in the Christie Commission recommendations and Community Empowerment Act (Scotland) 2015 aligns with this rhetoric, the extent to which these ideals have been effectively translated into practice needs to be critically evaluated. The Scottish Community Empowerment Action Plan (Scottish Government, 2009) defines community empowerment as a collaborative process that empowers individuals to bring about meaningful change in their communities by exerting greater power and influence over matters important to them. In addition, the integration of services highlights the inclusion of all concerned stakeholders in the decision-making process of delivering public services at a local level. While this approach holds promise in invigorating democracy” it is essential to consider the potential challenges and limitations that may arise in its implementation.

The further significance of these participatory, collaborative and community empowerments is evident in the National Performance Framework (NPF) established by the Scottish Government. Launched in 2007, the NPF serves as a strategic tool to align public sector organizations with the government's overarching purpose, five strategic objectives, and sixteen national achievements (Connolly and Pyper, 2020). The alignment between national goals and local contexts is facilitated by the utilisation of Single Outcome Agreements (SOAs), as highlighted by Elliot et al. (2018). These agreements serve as a mechanism for demonstrating how the outcomes outlined in the national performance framework are realized, effectively translating central government objectives into specific local contexts (McGarvey and Cairney, 2008). Consequently, the entire government has embraced a joined-up and performance-based approach (Connolly and Pyper, 2020).

In light of these developments, particularly the Christie Commission (2011) recommendations, the Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014, which became operative in April 2016, mandates that each Health Board and its associated local authorities collaborate to formulate an integration scheme outlining the adopted integration model, delegated functions, and positions of the delegated individuals. The composition of the newly established Integration Authorities is mandated through an Order, guaranteeing equitable representation through a combination of nominated councillors from the local authority and members (preferably non-executive) from the Health Board, with a minimum of three representatives from each entity. These boards also include citizen representatives and members representing Third Sector organizations. In addition, the Joint Strategic Commissioning Plans, which are obligatory for a three-year period, incorporate a Contribution Statement, thus incorporating strategic considerations within the broader framework of strategic planning and coordination (Kaehne et al., 2017). The Act delineates these "integration planning principles," highlighting the primary

objective of integrated provision to enhance the well-being of service users. In this context, it can be argued that the alignment of the national performance framework, the utilization of single outcome agreements (SOAs), and the enactment of the Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014 underscore the Government's commitment to community empowerment and participation (Connolly and Pyper, 2020). By incorporating performance-based approaches, integrating services, and fostering collaborative decision-making, the Scottish Government seeks to improve the well-being of service users and achieve the desired outcomes outlined in the national performance framework. This holistic approach reflects the evolving nature of governance in Scotland and the recognition of the value of community involvement in shaping and delivering public services. This focus on collaboration and community empowerment aligns closely with the principles of New Public Governance (NPG), which advocate for network governance, participatory decision-making, and a shift in power towards local actors (Stoker, 2006; Sullivan, 2011).

This transformation of Scottish planning has been motivated by multiple factors, including the necessity to adapt to decentralization and promote integration. Equally significant are the imperatives of expediency and effectiveness, which are inherent in the government's overarching modernization agenda (Allmendinger, 2010). The modernization programme encompasses streamlining plans and strategies and reducing redundancies, thereby shifting planning from its narrower focus to assume a broader strategic role that is, however, subordinate to local community plans. While these developments present challenges, they are emblematic of Scotland's overarching trajectory towards modernizing governance and incorporating an integration of a novel accountable and representative entity into the existing institutional structures and policy processes (Connolly and Pyper, 2020). Consequently, the outcomes can sometimes appear chaotic and ambiguous (Connolly and Pyper, 2020), particularly in the realm of planning, where shifting attitudes and the varying influence of central and local governments significantly impact planning practices.

Another key consideration is the potential disparity between rhetoric and reality. While the language used in policy documents and legislation may highlight the importance of integrated services and community empowerment, practical implementation may face hurdles and obstacles that hinder genuine participation and influence (Tabner, 2020). It is necessary to critically evaluate the mechanisms in place to ensure that relevant stakeholders and community voices are heard, respected, and meaningfully integrated into decision-making processes. Furthermore, while recognizing the abundant talent and creative potential within Scotland's communities is important, it is equally crucial to acknowledge the potential barriers and inequalities that may limit the effectiveness of community empowerment initiatives. Factors such as socio-economic disparities, power differentials, and unequal access to resources and opportunities must be carefully examined to ensure that community

empowerment initiatives truly empower all individuals and communities, including those that may face systemic disadvantages (Keating, 2020). Moreover, while community empowerment is often associated with innovative and successful solutions to local challenges, it is vital to critically examine the factors that contribute to these outcomes (Tabner, 2020). Evaluating the extent to which community-led decision-making processes foster collaboration, inclusivity, and effective resource allocation can shed light on the true impact of community empowerment initiatives.

The existing research highlights a common limitation of community strengthening initiatives, namely the lack of meaningful community participation in policy spaces (Adamson and Bromley, 2013). Contrary to the intended goal of empowerment, power often remains concentrated within governing bodies, hindering genuine community strengthening. Empowerment, by definition, necessitates a connection between action and dialogue (Fung and Wright, 2001). Academics in this field frequently emphasize that the efficacy of participatory initiatives is contingent upon the unwavering dedication demonstrated by local politicians (Klijn and Koopenjan, 2000; Copus, 2003; Granberg and Åström, 2010; Geurtza and Van der Wijdeven, 2010). Participatory initiatives seldom establish direct channels for citizens to exert influence over policy decisions. Consequently, the political implications of these endeavours are typically conveyed by councillors who possess the political authority to transform citizens' policy proposals into tangible local reforms or may, regrettably, disregard their contributions to the political process in Scotland and beyond (Albert and Passmore, 2008; De Groot, Denters, and Klok, 2010). Therefore, the role assumed by local political leaders in community empowerment and participatory initiatives, such as those within the Scottish Health and Social care context, is of paramount importance. The emphasis on the critical role of local political leadership closely aligns with the principles of New Public Governance, which advocates for empowered local actors and collaborative decision-making (Osborne, 2010). Within the context of H&SCI, local political leaders serve as conduits between communities and policymakers, facilitating citizen participation and ensuring that their voices are heard (Christie, 2011). This highlights the synergy between local political leadership and community-led initiatives, which are fundamental to the NPG framework.

Building upon this perspective, Pandey and Moynihan (2006) highlighted elected officials as the most invested group of political actors in the activities of public organizations. They possess the opportunity and capability to gain a comprehensive understanding of the internal functioning of public bodies in Scotland through various formal and informal hierarchical mechanisms (Albert and Passmore, 2008). Recognizing the significance of actors operating at the partnership or meso-level in Scotland, Connolly and Pyper (2020) emphasize the importance of comprehending their experiences. In fact, the policy strategy of the Scottish Government relies on network actors operating across boundaries and partnerships as instrumental agents for achieving success.

Consequently, empirical research is crucial to examine the relationship between participatory initiatives and the attitudes, practices, and leadership roles within public administration (Connolly and Pyper, 2020). The recent inclusion of local political leaders in the Integration Joint Boards of the H&SCI area in Scotland is a testament to the recognition of their pivotal role. However, there remains a significant knowledge gap in the public administration literature regarding the precise role of local political leaders in strategic decision-making processes within the context of Health and Social Care in Scotland. Addressing this gap is essential to advancing our understanding and informing effective governance in the field.

Conclusion

This chapter examined Scotland's public sector reform journey, culminating in the innovative concept of H&SCI. This ambitious initiative arose from a progressive decentralization process that began with devolution in 1999. Notably, Scotland has advanced in promoting community engagement and distributing decision-making authority since that pivotal year (Ritchie and Haggith, 2012; Elliot et al., 2019). Over time, Scottish Government has undertaken various reforms to establish a terrain conducive to these goals prior to the establishment of Integration Joint Boards in the H&SC sector. The enactment of key legislative measures such as the Community Empowerment Act (2015), and Local Governance (Scotland) Act (2004) has been instrumental in advancing the agenda of localism and community empowerment. These reforms have aimed to empower local actors and local communities, strengthen their role in decision-making processes, and improve the delivery of services at the grassroots level.

The emphasis on community empowerment, tailoring services to local needs, and the growing autonomy of local authorities converged to create an environment conducive to the innovative concept of H&SCI. This ambitious initiative inherently required extensive collaboration and coordination among diverse stakeholders. Navigating potential conflicts, such as resource allocation disagreements or differing priorities between national healthcare visions and local needs, presented an ongoing challenge (Audit, 2018; Scottish Government, 2019). This is where effective leadership became paramount in bridging these divides and fostering a collaborative spirit. The Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014 played a key role by empowering local leaders with voting rights on IJBs, allowing them to strategically influence H&SCI plans and resource allocation. They also took on an advocacy role for local interests and the responsibility to foster partnerships. Moreover, their mandate to represent the broader community charged them with tailoring service delivery models to

local needs, effectively bridging the gap between national directives and community requirements (Scottish Government, 2015).

Thus, the collaborative ethos underpinning H&SCI calls for strong leadership to establish partnerships across various sectors, including social care, private, third sector, and NHS boards (Audit Scotland, 2018). Such alliances are essential for leveraging collective strengths and delivering effective services. In essence, local political leaders serve as conduits and guides, drawing upon their leadership skills to bridge divides, build consensus, and realize the vision of integration (Scottish government, 2019).

It is within this context that the empowered role of local political leaders emerges, signalling a significant shift in the governance landscape. The pronounced role of these leaders marks a departure from conventional public administration, leading towards a more integrated and cooperative model. This evolution was previously explored in the last chapter, where the increasing relevance of local political leadership was highlighted within the framework of New Public Governance (NPG). Despite this, a notable gap persists in our understanding of the mechanisms by which these leaders tackle the complex decision-making processes inherent in H&SCI. Of particular interest is how they incorporate and tailor the aforementioned leadership styles to address the complexities of this dynamic environment. Transformational, servant, and facilitative leadership styles, as discussed in both Chapter 2 and 3, are deemed crucial for navigating the complexities of H&SCI. These styles emphasize empowering stakeholders, fostering collaboration, and building relationships – all essential for successful integration across diverse participants. While previous chapters explored various leadership styles relevant to local political leaders, the current understanding may not fully capture how these leaders adapt their styles to the specific challenges and opportunities presented by H&SCI.

This study thus aims to address this gap by examining how local political leaders in the selected case studies strategically employ and adapt different leadership styles, or combinations thereof, to navigate the complexities of H&SCI decision-making. Moving forward, the subsequent chapters will build upon the analytical groundwork laid out in the preceding literature chapters, including the typology of leadership styles (as presented in Table 2.2) and the typology of political contextual factors (as depicted in Table 2.3). These theoretical frameworks, given their significance in shaping the research approach, design, and analytical framework, will be instrumental in interpreting the data collected from local political leaders. The study will employ a thematic interpretation utilizing these frameworks to illuminate the nuanced role of local political leadership in H&SCI. By informing the research process with these frameworks, this study aims to bridge the current research gaps by examining the leadership strategies and practices that facilitate successful service integration, taking into account the unique political landscape of Scotland.

Chapter 5

A Methodological Approach: Exploring the Role of Local Political Leadership in Strategic Decision Making within the Context of Health and Social Care Integration in Scotland

This research explores the role of local political leadership in the strategic decision-making processes of H&SCI in Scotland. The study focuses on two Research Questions:

- What is the role of local political leaders, particularly IJB members, in the strategic decision-making process for H&SCI service delivery within Scotland?
- How do the following contextual factors influence the leadership styles employed by local political leaders in H&SCI decision-making processes:
 1. Economic and financial landscape
 2. Partisanship
 3. Political-administrative relationships
 4. Geographical considerations (rural vs. urban, size of the IJB area)
 5. Frontline workforce expectations in health and social care.

This thesis has followed the qualitative exploratory case study design (Creswell, 2003, 2007; Stake, 1995; Yin, 1994, 2003) focusing on Scottish H&SCI policy area as a case study. It has employed the theoretical framework based on contingency theory by Fielder (1967) in conjunction with the situational leadership theory by Hersey and Blanchard (1969) to address the Research Questions. This chapter initially explains the research approach and design, elaborating on the reasons behind selecting a qualitative case study method for this research. The next section outlines the sampling strategy and criteria, presenting the cases and participants carefully selected for this research. The fourth section details the data collection methods and procedures used and discusses the types and sources of data that were collected and analysed for this research. It explains the two-pronged approach of reviewing policy documents in order to understand the contextual factors in each area and conducting semi-structured interviews with local leaders in order to understand their leadership styles within their respective political contexts. The fifth section explains the data analysis methods and techniques and describes how the data were coded, categorised, and compared using content and

thematic analysis. This is followed by the discussion of the validity, ethical considerations, and data validation protocols. Finally, the concluding section offers a brief summary of the key methodological aspects contained in this chapter.

5.1 Research approach

The intricate and nuanced nature of local political leadership in the context of H&SCI in Scotland calls for a research approach that aligns with the complexities of the phenomenon. A deductive qualitative approach has been deemed most suitable for this research. Qualitative research happens in real-life situations. This helps the researcher to learn more about the place or person and to share the experience of the people involved (Creswell, 2003; Rossman and Rallis, 1998). In a deductive qualitative approach, the researcher focuses on understanding the meanings held by participants, guided by an existing theoretical framework that still enables the emergence of novel insights (Miles and Huberman, 1994). The role of local political leaders in the policy process is a relatively new and an under-researched area in the context of H&SCI. A predetermined framework can provide the researcher with a literary direction to explore certain aspects of leadership phenomena that they want to initially focus on. For example, the researcher can identify and understand the key actors and factors that influence the leadership practices and outcomes of local political leaders in H&SCI, given that their basic role is a currently understudied area. The deductive qualitative knowledge claim identifies knowledge as an evolutionary process, in that the reality exists, and it evolves (Hyde, 2000). When it comes to phenomena about which very little is known, it might be a wise decision to identify a framework that can serve as a starting point for exploring this phenomenon. A deductive approach, based on the synthesis of existing literature, can be helpful to determine what basic questions need to be addressed first, before moving to more critical aspects of that phenomenon or what matters the most, which is subjective, should be considered as a starting point. This approach is particularly suitable for exploring complex and nuanced phenomena such as local political leadership in H&SCI in Scotland.

Local political leaders play a crucial role in the planning, implementation, and impact of H&SC initiatives, as well as the decisions that affect the lives of their communities (Christie, 2011; Joint Act, 2014). However, they face a complex set of challenges and opportunities as they navigate the dynamic and interconnected landscape of H&SCI (Connolly et al, 2022). They often have to balance the competing interests of multiple stakeholders involved in the decision-making process, adapt their leadership styles to suit the unique context of their communities, and navigate the ever-evolving policy landscape. These factors make the leadership practices of local political leaders a rich and multifaceted

phenomenon that requires a deeper understanding. Therefore, this study adopts a qualitative research approach that can examine the lived experiences of local political leaders and uncover the nuances of their leadership practices, as well as the factors that influence them.

The predetermined framework, derived from a synthesis of relevant literature, serves as a foundation for the research, ensuring that the findings are grounded in existing knowledge. It also provides a lens through which to interpret the data collected from participants, allowing for a deeper understanding of their perspectives within the context of the established framework (Miles and Huberman, 1994). In this study, the contingency and situational theories of leadership inform the theoretical framework of this research (See Sections 2.2 and 2.3). These theories suggest that the effectiveness of leadership styles may depend on the alignment between the leader, the context, stakeholders, and the situation. This aligns with the research interest in exploring how local political leaders adapt their leadership approaches to the diverse contextual factors that influence H&SCI in Scotland. The contingency and situational theories of leadership consist of two main dimensions: the political context and the leadership styles of local political leaders in H&SCI. The political context is defined and operationalized as the main contextual factor that influences the leadership styles of local political leaders in H&SCI (see Section 2.5). The political context is composed of five dimensions: economy and finance, partisanship, the political-administrative relationship, geographical considerations (such as the size of the area and its urban or rural nature), and the expectations of the frontline workforce (as earlier presented in Table 2.3). These dimensions are derived from the academic literature on local political leadership and H&SCI, and they align with the research objective and questions. The political context dimensions provide analytical tools to identify patterns, themes, and underlying motivations in the data. These predefined political contextual factors are the basis for selecting a variety of research participants from local IJB areas.

The leadership styles dimension is based on the techniques that local political leaders employ to perform their actions and interactions with stakeholders and frontline workers effectively and to navigate complex environments. The leadership styles dimension is operationalized as six types of leadership styles including transformational, democratic, servant, facilitative, laissez faire, and situational leadership style (as earlier presented in Table 2.2). These types of leadership styles are derived from the academic literature on leadership theories and models, and they reflect the main focus of the Research Questions and their aim. The leadership styles dimension serves as an analytical tool to examine how local political leaders enact their contextually dependent role in H&SCI. These themes and issues underscore the necessity for insight into the various leadership styles employed by the leaders themselves, necessitating an exploration and understanding of the diverse meanings that individuals or local political leaders assign to specific issues or experiences.

In this regard, the qualitative approach emerges as indispensable. As Creswell (2013) explained, 'throughout the qualitative research process, the researcher keeps a focus on learning the meaning that participants hold about the problem or issue' (p. 47). An interpretive knowledge claim to qualitative research, as advocated by Creswell (2007), is inherently subjective and context-bound, concerned with the understanding and interpretation of human experiences and actions. This philosophy aligns with our endeavour to explore the nuanced landscape of local political leaders in H&SCI. The qualitative approach, underpinned by the interpretivist paradigm, resonates with the research aim of understanding the meanings and experiences of local political leaders. It serves as the methodological linchpin, allowing us to explore the role and leadership styles of local political leaders in depth and detail. This approach enables an examination of the complex and dynamic interactions between the leaders, their contexts and their integration partners. Furthermore, the interpretivist paradigm facilitates an acknowledgment and respect for the diversity and complexity inherent in the role and leadership styles of local political leaders, capturing their views and voices in an authentic and empathetic manner.

While the interpretivist paradigm is suitable for case study design, it is crucial to acknowledge its inherent limitations and challenges. These include the potential for researcher bias, the subjectivity of participants, and the specificity of the context (Yin, 2018). These challenges are met with a commitment to reflexivity, transparency, and rigor throughout the research process. Furthermore, critics have argued that a deductive approach may restrict the exploration of novel themes because of its reliance on a predetermined framework (Thomas and Magilvy, 2011). It is, therefore, important to stress that a qualitative deductive approach does not preclude openness to data that challenges, or contradicts, the theory (Yin, 2009). A qualitative deductive approach does not impose a predefined theory on the data, but rather uses the theory as a guide or a lens to explore the data. The theory is not taken as a given or a final truth, but rather as a tentative or provisional framework that can be modified, refined, or challenged by the data (Bryman, 2016). A qualitative deductive approach does not ignore or discard data that do not fit the theory, but rather acknowledges and examines the discrepancies, contradictions, or anomalies in the data. A qualitative deductive approach does not claim to produce objective or neutral knowledge, but rather to produce situated and reflexive knowledge (Bryman, 2016; Yin, 2018). Furthermore, to mitigate these concerns, the researcher has maintained a reflexive and critical stance, utilizing multiple data sources, methods of analysis, and triangulation to enhance validity (see Section 5.2). The predetermined framework serves as a guide and provides empty boxes while allowing both deductive and inductive reasoning to fill them in.

5.2 Using the Case Study research design

The selection of an appropriate research design is essential when conducting a rigorous study that focuses on intricate phenomena such as local political leadership in the context of H&SCI. This study adopts a case study design, which is a suitable and effective method for an immersive and comprehensive exploration of unique projects, policies, institutions, programmes, or systems (Stake 1995; Yin, 2014). It is also meticulously grounded in order to investigate a contemporary phenomenon in its real-life context, encompassing all aspects of the research process, from design to data collection and analysis (Yin, 2003). It also allows the researcher to focus on the unique characteristics and experiences of a particular case, which is consistent with the interpretivist emphasis on understanding individual meanings and perspectives. According to Yin (2003, p., 13; Yin, 2014), a case study is:

‘an empirical inquiry that allows for an in-depth and holistic investigation of a phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident.’

A case study approach is particularly suitable for this research as it facilitates the investigation of local political leaders, a phenomenon where the boundaries between leadership styles and political context are intertwined. Therefore, case study design facilitates an in-depth examination of the complex and dynamic interactions between local political leaders, bureaucratic leaders (senior officials), and other stakeholders (frontline workforce) in the H&SCI policy area in relation to their political context. In addition, case studies can also be used to study causal and proximate relationships between different variables (Yin, 2008). This research studies the relationship between political contextual factors and the leadership styles of local leaders. Given the need for a holistic understanding of this intricate relationship, a qualitative case study design is deemed most appropriate for this research.

Case studies are a type of research methodology that can be classified into different categories based on their objectives and methods. Some of the common types of case study design are:

- **Explanatory case studies** which aim to explain the causal mechanisms and processes behind a phenomenon or a problem, often using a theory or a model as a framework.
- **Theory testing case studies** which aim to test the validity and applicability of an existing theory or a hypothesis in a new or different context, often using multiple cases for comparison and contrast.
- **Descriptive case studies** which aim to describe the features and characteristics of a phenomenon or a problem in detail, often using rich and thick descriptions to provide a comprehensive understanding.

- **Exploratory case studies** which aim to explore the nature and scope of a phenomenon or a problem, often using open-ended and flexible methods to generate new insights and questions (Baxter and Jack, 2008; Yin, 2018).

This research has employed a qualitative exploratory case study design to explore how local elected political members of the Integration Joint Boards in Scotland exercise their roles and leadership styles within the H&SCI context, taking into account their political environment. An exploratory case study design is particularly effective for examining new or under-researched phenomena (Yin, 2014). Given the relatively nascent and understudied nature of local political leadership in the H&SCI context of Scotland (Connolly and Pyper, 2019), this design choice is particularly appropriate. By adopting a case study approach, the research generates richer and more meaningful data compared to a narrower quantitative study (Bass, 1990; Creswell, 2013; Hesse-Biber, 2010; Ridder, 2017).

This study examines the subjective perceptions of research participants through broad and general questions to construct situational meanings, given that they have subjective interpretations of their leadership experiences. It primarily focuses on specific contexts in which the subjects operate and interact within the political landscape, and it seeks to interpret the subjects' understanding of their work environment and their preferences and practices regarding leadership styles, while considering their individual worldviews in relation to the impact of political contextual factors. This method allows researchers to focus on a particular example of a policy process and to investigate the basic questions of how, what, and why (Hallingberg et al., 2018). The exploratory feature of the research design also allows it to identify key factors related to political leadership within the specific contexts of H&SCI, gain insights into the variety of leadership styles practised by the leaders themselves and explore and understand the diverse meanings that individuals or local political leaders assign to specific issues or experiences. This design aligns with the interpretivist paradigm that this research followed to uncover the socially constructed reality of the role of local political leaders. This design is particularly well-suited for addressing the Research Questions, which seek to explore the multiple, subjective, and socially constructed realities and context-dependent nature of how local political leaders adapt their leadership styles to the dynamic H&SCI political landscape.

Furthermore, this approach is particularly valuable for exploring phenomena that are considered "unique" or "atypical" (Lee & Saunders, 2017), such as the H&SCI policy area, which involves multiple actors, levels, and sectors (Joint Act, 2014) and that has undergone significant changes and challenges in recent years (Connolly et al, 2022). A population study of all H&SCI services in Scotland has the potential to overlook the intricate nuances and contextual factors that shape the experiences and perspectives of local and bureaucratic leaders in this complex policy area. Therefore, the case study is

a good method for qualitative research because it studies a specific phenomenon, such as local political leadership, in depth and detail (Stake, 1995). It shows the researcher's interest in the context and meaning of the phenomenon, rather than the size and representativeness of the sample, which are more important for statistical research.

In this case its use of multiple sources of evidence, such as documents, interviews and observations, allowed the researcher to gain a comprehensive understanding of the role of local leaders in the reform process. While critics argue that the case study approach lacks scientific rigor and introduces subjective bias (Diamond, 1996), the data collected using multiple sources are helpful in addressing concerns related researcher' bias, reliability, and validity through collecting data from diverse sources, including triangulating via data derived from multiple stakeholder perspectives and the relevant policy documents. With regard to concerns about generalization, it is true that case studies do not aim to achieve statistical generalization; however, their strength lies in generating rich and context-specific knowledge that can inform theory development, contribute to the understanding of specific cases, and provide insights into similar contexts (Merriam, 2015). In this study, the focus on local political leaders across Scotland allows for an exploration of their experiences and perceptions within a specific political and policy context, which can contribute to a deeper understanding of local political leadership dynamics in the H&SCI areas. This case study approach has been motivated by the public administration literature that highlights the need to study local political leaders in the modern paradigm of new public governance (Sullivan, 2011; Stoker, 2017). The principle of new public governance (NPG) has been applied in different developed countries around the world to deliver public services. The Scottish H&SCI is one example of reform that lies in the ideas of NPG. Therefore, the evidence and themes derived from this case study of H&SCI could potentially have implications for other policy spaces which are built on these principles.

5.3 Sampling Strategy

The selection of participants for this study followed a purposive sampling approach (Patton, 1990; Bloomberg & Volpe, 2012). Purposive sampling is commonly employed in qualitative research to identify individuals or groups with specific characteristics or circumstances relevant to the phenomenon under investigation (Patton, 1990) or based on specific criteria or characteristics that are relevant to the research question and objectives (Bryman, 2016). In this study, the focus is on individual political leaders and senior officials in the H&SCI field operating within a specific IJB area. This targeted approach enabled a more focused and precise examination of each participant's qualifications for inclusion in the study. To expand the sample size, a snowball strategy was employed (Patton, 1990).

Participants were asked to provide referrals and suggest other individuals who they believed would be of interest for the study. This snowball recruitment method involves leveraging the network of participants in order to identify additional suitable candidates (Patton, 1990; Bloomberg & Volpe, 2012). This was helpful in finding interested research participants suggested by their colleagues.

The criteria for selecting the cases were based on the following factors:

- The size and population of the IJB area
- The urban or rural nature of the IJB area
- The political composition of the IJB board
- Broad economic and financial conditions of IJB area.

The research participants consisted of local councillors and senior officials from eleven local authorities' H&SC Integration Joint Boards, selected based on diverse and specific political contextual factors as previously explained. For instance, the research selected few urban IJBs as the initial sample, considering elected members' political affiliation, economic and financial conditions of the area, and geographical considerations. Subsequently, the researcher included a selection of participants from rural IJBs, following a similar pattern of considering elected members' political affiliation, economy, geographical considerations. These various urban and rural settings provided a range and depth of experiences relevant to the research areas of interest. This means that participants were selected based on the analytical direction provided in Chapter 2, aiming to reflect diversity in political party affiliation, the economy and financial conditions, size, and the rural-urban nature of the IJB area. This strategy was adopted to ensure that the cases were not biased or skewed towards a particular type or category of the political context, but rather that they reflected the diversity and heterogeneity of the political context in the H&SCI policy area. A list of local councillors was obtained online from the local H&SCI joint board authorities, and suitable participants were invited to take part in the study.

Moreover, the inclusion of senior officials in this study played a crucial role in exploring the intricacies of 'political' leadership within local political contexts. The rationale behind their inclusion was twofold: first, to examine the political-administrative relationship, which was one of the contextual factors in this study. Their firsthand experiences working alongside local political leaders provided valuable insights into working relationships, decision-making processes, and potential areas of collaboration or tension. This information enriched the understanding of the political context within which leaders operated and how these dynamics influenced their leadership styles.

In addition, the inclusion of senior officials was designed to triangulate data on local political leadership styles practiced within their political context. Their perspectives complemented the self-reported approaches of leaders. Interviewing these officers allowed for a more nuanced and potentially more realistic understanding of leadership styles in practice—how they were perceived and experienced by those working directly with the leaders. By comparing and contrasting data from both groups, researcher was able to strengthen the validity and reliability of their findings. However, there was one strategic change that needed to be discussed in this study. The rationale for choosing a case study did not incorporate the contextual factor of the relationship between political leaders and senior officials, as this was unlikely to be identified prior to conducting the research. Nevertheless, the relationship between managers and political leaders remained an important contextual factor for this study and was included in the justification for selecting participants.

Against this background, the selected IJB or local authorities where this study was conducted, exhibited diversity in economic and financial conditions and different party-political affiliations. They also demonstrated a range of urban and rural trajectories, with some having stable (positive) political-administrative relationships while others experienced frequent changes in political-administrative relationships (nuanced). This group serves as a specific, finite, and unique unit of analysis, increasing the credibility of the sample by establishing a defined domain to which the study's findings can be related (Yin, 2003; Universal Teacher, 2015). Moreover, the selection of multiple IJB areas allowed for diversity among councillors.

The contextual factors were considered in the breakdown of the sample as shown earlier in Table 2. 3. Specifically, it focused on the factors of economy and finance, partisanship, and geographical considerations. However, the economy and financial section in Table 2.3 was complimented by the economic data gathered through IJB meeting minutes and these helped to further clarify the categories where IJBs are facing 'less challenging', 'challenging' and 'more challenging' economic and financial conditions. The economic and financial dimension was approached very broadly and refrained from asserting controlled measurement of economic and financial circumstances. Instead, the objective lies in generating a comprehensive differentiation across various levels of economic and financial conditions which Integration Joint Boards confront. The intent was to delineate between contexts of heightened difficulty, those that posed challenges, and those that presented comparatively lesser challenges. This approach acknowledges the complexity of economic and financial dynamics within IJBs, while emphasizing the delineation of diverse conditions without rigid quantitative categorization. This involved categorizing them into three groups: small deficit (less deprived), deficit (medium deprived), and challenging (deprived), with each IJB's information presented comprehensively. The cases were selected from a list of thirty-one IJBs in Scotland, using publicly

available information from the Scottish Government, Audit Scotland, National record Scotland (NRS) and the IJB websites. The final sample of eleven IJBs is shown in Table 5.1 along with their characteristics.

Table 5.1: Characteristics of the selected IJBs.

IJB	Size and Population	Urban/Rural	Political Composition	Economy and finance
IJB A	Large, 230, 000	Urban	Conservative	Unknown
IJB B	Small, 96,000	Rural	SNP	Challenging: 2018-2019 gap 3.3M (2.8%).
IJB C	Large, 0.5million	Urban	Labour-SNP	Challenging: Projected deficit £15-20M.
IJB D	Medium, 198,000	Urban	SNP	Less challenging: 2019-2020 deficit £1.2M out of £279M.
IJB E	Small, 51,000	Rural	SNP	Challenging: In fiscal year 2019/20, £6.2M in savings required to break even.
IJB F	Large, 600,000	Urban	SNP	Challenging: Approved £1.2B budget with

				planned savings of £19.5M.
IJB G	Medium, 148,000	Rural	Labour-	Very challenging: Approved 2019/20 budget OF £389M with planned savings IN 2020/21 of £19.5M.
IJB H	115,000	Rural	Conservative with independents.	In 2019/20, IJB ended the year with a surplus of £2.477M.
IJB I	Small, 120,000	Rural	SNP	Less challenging: In 2019/20 had underspend of £1M.
IJB J	Medium, 151,290	Rural	Conservative	Challenging: In fiscal year 2018/19 budget overspent was 1.16M.
IJB K	Medium 164000	Rural	Labour minority	Unknown

The criteria for selecting the units of analysis (local political leaders and bureaucratic leaders) were based on the following factors:

- The position and role of the leader in the IJB board or management.
- The availability and willingness of the leader to participate in the research.

These factors were considered in order to ensure that the selected leaders were knowledgeable and influential in the strategic decision making of the H&SCI policy area. The local political leaders were the elected councillors who represented the local authorities on the IJB board. The bureaucratic leaders were the senior officials who were appointed by the IJB board or the partner organisations (NHS boards and local authorities) to manage the H&SCI services. The participants were identified from the IJB websites, annual reports, and minutes of meetings, and contacted by email or phone to invite them to take part in the research. The final sample of twenty-two leaders is shown in Appendix A, along with their positions and roles. The leaders were labelled alphabetically (A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J) to ensure the anonymity of the research participants. Senior officials were named A1, B1, and C1, respectively (See Appendix A).

5.4 Data collection and analysis

The theoretical framework of contingency and situational leadership theories provided a guiding lens for data collection and analysis, ensuring that the gathered information aligned with the theoretical constructs. The study adopted an ontological position that views local political leaders as social actors who are inextricably linked to their political environment. Ontology, the study of being or existence, guides researchers in understanding the nature of reality, or the object of their investigation (Bryman, 2016; Yin, 2018). This research embraces a subjectivist or interpretivist ontological position, which holds that reality is socially constructed, subjective, and multifaceted, rather than objective, independent, and singular (Baxter & Jack, 2008; Simons, 2009). This position underscores the dynamic and adaptive nature of local political leadership, where leaders constantly adjust their strategies and approaches in response to contextual factors and stakeholder expectations. This study focused on the leadership styles of local political leaders as a manifestation of their ability to perform their actions and adapt their political environment. This focus was grounded in two key assumptions:

(1) the role of local political leaders is intrinsically intertwined with the political factors that influence their environment, such as economic and financial conditions, partisan dynamics, geographical considerations, relationships with officials, and expectations of the frontline workforce; and

(2) the hallmark characteristic of a contingent and situational leadership style is the ability to adjust strategies according to the context. In line with these assumptions, studying local political leadership styles entails examining how they enact their role in relation to their political environment and the needs of their stakeholders.

5.4.1 Data Collection methods

The data collection methods employed in this study were document analysis and semi-structured interviews. Document analysis is a method of collecting and reviewing documents that are relevant to the research topic and questions (Bowen, 2009). This serves as a valuable research method, particularly within the realm of qualitative case studies, which aim to provide comprehensive and detailed descriptions of specific phenomena, events, organizations, or programmes (Stake, 1995; Yin, 1994). In such academic investigations, researchers can use different kinds of evidence. Some evidence is technical, such as scientific papers, data sets, or experiments. Other evidence is non-technical, such as reports, letters, emails, and internal correspondences, and possesses significant promise as a valuable source of empirical data, capable of enhancing the depth and complexity of the analysis. By examining these documents, researchers can gain valuable insights into the contextual factors that shape the participants' experiences (Mills, Bonner, and Francis, 2006). Merriam (2015) highlighted the significance of documents in uncovering meaning, fostering understanding, and offering insights relevant to the research problem. Documents can also stimulate the formulation of new research questions and guide researchers in identifying relevant situations for observation. For example, Goldstein and Reiboldt (2004) utilized document analysis as a methodological approach within their longitudinal ethnographic inquiry into service utilization patterns among economically disadvantaged urban families. Through this approach, they effectively generated new interview questions that complemented their primary data collection method. The researchers elucidated the interconnectedness of different methods, whereby interview data informed participant observation activities, document analysis prompted the formulation of novel interview questions, and participant observation at community events facilitated the collection of additional documents (Goldstein and Reiboldt, 2004).

Document analysis was useful for this research because it provided contextual information about the H&SCI policy area, the IJBs, and the leaders. It also helped to triangulate and validate the data obtained from the interviews. The types of documents that were analysed in this study include:

- Policy documents and reports from the Scottish Government, Audit Scotland, and other national bodies on the H&SCI policy area
- Annual reports, and minutes of meetings from the IJBs.

These documents are specified and outlined in Appendices F and G. In addition, to select the IJB meeting minutes for content analysis, a systematic approach was used based on two criteria: the timing of the meetings and the relevance of the information. Particular focus was placed on the meetings that took place before and after the IJB budget announcements every year from 2015 to

2021; for instance, two meetings before the budget and two meetings after each budget and the meetings prior to, and after, the local government elections in 2017 and before 2022 local elections. The rationale was that much discussion about key issues was likely to occur during these times. The researcher also excluded the meetings that did not contain any discussion about the political contextual factors which were relevant to this research. This process was time-consuming and required several attempts, but it did help to narrow down the data from the eleven different IJB areas. Many of these documents can be accessed through online sources and local councils' websites. By reviewing evaluation reports and other relevant documents, the researcher gained specific contextual information about H&SCI that may not have been uncovered through interviews alone. The documents were selected based on their relevance, credibility, and availability.

However, the literature on research methods acknowledges the shortfalls in the reliability and validity of documentary materials in terms of the potential for bias and in terms of the researcher's approach and the publishers' agenda (Norris, 1997; Connolly, 2009; Yin, 2016). Connolly (2009) warned that "caution should thus be used when deducing meanings or truths from documents. Indeed, documentary sources must have a limited worth in explaining the intricates of the policy process and as noted above this is where interviews have an important function." (p. 8). To address the issue of validity, the documentary evidence has been analysed alongside interview data, but the documentary materials drawn upon in this study have significant value. First, the study relies on independent inquiries and meeting minutes to give perspective to the contextual aspects of a local political leader's role. Secondly, the identification of gaps and forming interview questions in the specific Scottish context have enriched the research objectives in this study in order to understand the local political leadership styles through the role they play in H&SCI. Thirdly, it was useful in finding the correct information when interviewing local Scottish political leaders, as the researcher was more familiar with the current situations around their role in H&SCI in order to constructively discuss their leadership styles/behaviours.

Furthermore, in terms of accessing the documents, certain IJBs have made their attendance records, meeting minutes, and reports accessible online, while for other IJBs, the researcher had to resort to Freedom of Information (FOI) requests to obtain the necessary documents (See Appendix E). Although the process of obtaining these documents was not without challenges, it provided valuable learning experiences. When making FOI requests, it is crucial to keep the research objective in mind. When contacting IJB co-ordinators or local authorities via email, it is essential to introduce oneself as a researcher and clearly articulate the nature of the research in straightforward language, while also requesting the specific documents needed. This approach is likely to facilitate a prompt processing of the request, recognizing the importance of the research endeavour. In addition, the documents were

analysed using a content analysis approach (see Section 5.4.2.1), which involves a descriptive approach to code and interpret the content of documents. It is useful in order to measure and compare the occurrence and distribution of specific categories, concepts, and codes in the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The document analysis also informed the design and conduct of the semi-structured interviews, which were the primary data collection source for this research. This approach of complementing has been adopted to ensure that respondents are not treated as mere objects of study. By actively involving respondents in the research process, the aim was to enhance the quality of the study through ongoing discussions regarding the identified themes and issues with those who are directly engaged in the practices being researched. This collaborative approach recognized the importance of engaging with practitioners to gain a deeper understanding of the role of local political leadership, aligning with the overall research objective. By valuing the insights and perspectives of the respondents, this approach seeks to generate a more comprehensive and nuanced analysis of the topic at hand.

Semi-structured interviews are a method of collecting data from the participants through a flexible and interactive conversation, guided by a set of open-ended questions (Bryman, 2016). Twenty-two interviews were conducted with local political leaders and senior officials in order to gather insights into the role and leadership styles of participants in the context of H&SCI (see Appendix A). The interview questions focused on their role in shaping and implementing H&SCI, decision-making processes, regulatory discretion, and their overall leadership style. The questions were asked in a semi-structured manner because they allow for the exploration of the perceptions, experiences, and opinions of the local political leaders and the bureaucratic leaders in the H&SCI policy area. Pre-determined semi-structured questions served as a framework, with additional probing and follow-up inquiries exploring specific areas in depth.

The interviews were carried out between September 2021 and May 2022, either face-to-face, by phone, or by video call, depending on the preference and availability of the participants. The duration of each political interview was 45-60 minutes and senior official interviews lasted 30-45 minutes. Potential participants were identified and contacted via email to be included in the study (Yin, 2009). However, accessing research participants was a challenge. The email invitation was crafted, conveying the research's nature, purpose, and significance. Contact details were gathered through online research, including diary secretaries' and officials' email addresses and office phone numbers. Initial contact was made with participants' diary secretaries, and if there was no response, the main department co-ordinator was contacted. In this instance, the co-ordinators of IJBs served as gatekeepers, requiring professional and courteous communication. In certain cases, persistent follow-

ups proved instrumental in securing interviews. For example, the initial invitation was sent a month before, and agreement was reached within five weeks. When support staff did not respond, direct invitations were extended to research participants, encompassing local political leaders and senior officials. This approach highlighted that relying solely on contacting diary secretaries is not always effective. Furthermore, interviews were rescheduled multiple times in certain instances because of participants' packed schedules. For those facing time limitations, written responses were requested, which yielded results in one reply.

The interviews were based on an interview guide with both local political leaders and senior officials containing multiple questions (See appendix I). The guide consisted of two main sections. Section 1 was for local political leaders questions and Section 2 was for the senior officials' questions:

1. The interviews with local political leaders aimed to extract insights on participants' backgrounds, roles, involvement in strategic decision-making for H&SCI policy, and their perspectives on leadership styles. The interview began with a few more open and general questions along the lines of "what motivated them to choose this career and How they view their leadership style?".

Subsequently, their leadership styles were assessed questioning on how contextual factors (e.g., economy, partisanship, relationship with officers, urban/rural nature, frontline workforce expectations) influenced their leadership style choices. The probing and follow up questions were derived from the document analysis, which provided evidence of the contextual factors' relevance of the H&SCI policy area and the IJBs. The questions were also tailored to the specific characteristics and circumstances of each case and each participant, based on the information obtained from the document analysis.

2. The interviews with senior officials aimed to assess the nature of the relationship between local political leaders and senior officials. They were also asked at the beginning of the interview about their views on the progress of H&SCI and the leadership styles of local political leaders they worked with in the IJBs. The senior officials were asked to explain their relationship with local political leaders and how these relationships were impacted by political contractual constraints. The questions in this section were also informed by the document analysis, which provided evidence of the political contextual factors that influenced the leadership styles of the participants.

The sequencing of questions plays a crucial role in the interview process. To elicit responses that captured participants' personal behaviours and experiences (Breugh, 2006), interviews commenced with non-controversial questions. These opening questions facilitated participants' engagement in a descriptive narrative style. Then, the questions shifted to probe more deeply into participants' opinions, feelings, and experiences related to the Research Questions and sub-questions (El-Zayaty, 2016). This approach enabled a comprehensive understanding of the lived experiences of the participants. Throughout the interview process, the researcher-maintained flexibility while adhering to the established interview protocol. To align with the research objectives and questions, an interview guide was meticulously crafted (see Appendix I). It included open-ended questions that allowed participants to share their personal perceptions, ideas, feelings, emotions, and stories related to different leadership styles and work-related leadership experiences. This encouraged participants to share insights and knowledge about leadership and managerial situations that they participated in or observed. They also described the results of their actions (Creswell, 2009; Patton, 2002).

The interviews were transcribed verbatim and analysed using a thematic analysis approach, which involves identifying, coding, and categorising the key themes and patterns that emerged from the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). These themes and patterns were compared and contrasted with the themes and patterns from the document data, using a triangulation protocol, as explained in the next section.

5.4.2 Data analysis methods

This study employed two qualitative data analysis methods: content analysis for documents and thematic analysis for interviews.

5.4.2.1 Content analysis

The purpose of this content analysis was to establish the foundations for understanding the contextual conditions of H&SCI areas to help with identifying the analysis of local political leaders. Content analysis involved analysing and interpreting the meaning of text data, focusing on both explicit and implicit content, themes, patterns, and categories (Elo et al., 2014). There are two types of qualitative content analysis: conventional and directed. Conventional content analysis is an inductive approach that allows the researcher to derive codes and categories from the data, without using any pre-existing theory or framework. Directed content analysis is a deductive approach that uses existing theory or prior research to guide the coding and categorization of the data (Bowen, 2009; Elo et al., 2014). In this study, the deductive approach has been used, guided by existing theory to categorize text that matched predefined categories (Elo et al., 2014). This analytical approach was based on the key concepts outlined in the Literature Review (see Section 2.5). The following contextual factors and their

description provided deductive lenses for the analysis. These included the economic and financial challenges faced by the IJBs, the geographical implications of urban and rural local communities, the political divisions, and dynamics within the IJBs, and the needs and readiness of the frontline workforce to implement the new IJB structure. For a more detailed description of these factors, (see earlier presented Table 2.3).

This framework facilitated the measurement of the relevance and prominence of specific political contextual categories, concepts, and codes related to the role of local political leaders in the H&SCI policy area. According to Cardno (2018), the content analysis process involved systematically addressing the following questions in relation to each facet of the policy documents:

1. What aspects (that you are looking for) are evident in the language of the policy?

The policy language was analysed to identify specific terms, phrases, or concepts related to political contextual factors, such as the economy and finance, partisanship, stakeholder engagement, and urban/rural community needs.

2. Does the policy language refer to these aspects directly or indirectly?

The examination focused on how the policy document addressed political contextual factors, both explicitly and implicitly. Direct references to these factors were identified, as well as indirect implications or suggestions. For example, economic and financial considerations were evident in some instances through the presentation of financial data, while other instances included discussions on cost-saving measures.

3. What is specifically stated in the policy?

Specific statements or provisions in the policy relating to political contextual factors were identified. The analysis considered how these statements influenced the role of local political leaders in the H&SCI policy area. For instance, a provision in the policy that grants local political leaders more autonomy in decision-making could empower them to take a more proactive approach. This was more relevant when analysing legislation relating to the IJBs and financial governance systems.

Subsequently, the researcher developed a comprehensive codebook (See Appendix H) that defined the categories, concepts relevant to the Research Questions and objectives, drawing upon existing literature and theory (see Table 5.2). The researcher then examined documents; firstly, legislation to determine the existing legal framework relevant to the subject, encompassing political arrangements and financial governance arrangements of IJBs. This was followed by the audit reports produced at national level that utilized some of the sampled IJBs in their national reporting. The relevant contextual

data have been extracted from these for the respective IJBs - F, C, G, and I. The legislation and national audit reports were read in full to understand the legal framework and national dynamics. However, the meeting minutes were not read in full, but a skimming and scanning strategy was employed to trace relevant instances (Cardno, 2018; Kuckartz, 2019) related to the contextual factors of the economy and finance, geographical considerations, partisanship, political-administrative relationships, and frontline workforce expectations. In addition, the meeting minutes of the IJBs, which are one of the main sources of this content analysis, have been analysed by using a predetermined framework of contextual factors and utilized NVivo software to create a hierarchical coding structure. This structure consisted of main nodes for each IJB area, sub-nodes for the political contextual factors, and further sub-nodes for specific aspects of each factor (see Appendix H). The political contextual factors that were coded and analysed included the economy and finance, partisanship, geographical considerations (such as the size of the area and its urban or rural nature), and expectations of the frontline workforce. The researcher meticulously traced instances within the documents that evidenced the relevance of these factors to the role of local leaders (see the table 5.2) The data collected from content analysis were enhanced and triangulated during the interview data at analysis stages and have been used for this purpose. This is one way to justify the validity of this data set (Elo et al., 2014).

The main results to emerge from the content analysis are summarised below. The document data analysis identified four main themes that related to the political contextual factors that are relevant to the role of local political leaders an in the H&SCI policy area.

Table 5.2: Themes, descriptions, and codes of the content analysis of documents.

Theme	Description	Codes
Economy and finance	The economic and financial conditions and constraints that affected the H&SCI policy area.	“Budget pressure”, “funding uncertainty”, “efficiency target”, “budget deficit”.
Partisanship	This factor refers to the political divisions, factions, and group dynamics within the IJB, as well as the interactions between political parties and the leadership role.	“Political conflict”, “political instability” “lack of direction” “political compromise”, and “political consensus”.

Urban/rural nature of the area	The geographical characteristics and diversity of the IJB areas, and how they affected the needs and preferences of the communities and the stakeholders in the H&SCI policy area.	“Deprivation levels” “citizen representation” “Transport issues”, “workforce shortage”, “citizen engagement”, and “service integration” “lack of skilled workforce” “large board”.
Frontline expectations	The expectations and demands of the frontline workforce in the H&SCI policy area, and how they influenced the decision making and the performance of the local political leaders.	“Logistical support”, “appreciation”, “workload formula”, “capacity issues”, “feedback”, and “evaluation”.

5.4.2.2 Thematic analysis

The data analysis process entailed a systematic approach to organizing, integrating, and scrutinizing the data, seeking patterns and relationships that addressed the Research Questions and objectives. As Jackson, Gillies, and Verberg (2011) noted, “analysis is a continuous process that starts from the first data collection and goes on until the end of the study.” (Jackson, Gillies, and Verberg, 2011, p. 242). Similarly, Neuman (2011) emphasized that “analysis helps us to link data and concepts, make generalisations, and find patterns and themes. Analysis also helps us to deepen our understanding, develop our theory, and increase our knowledge.” (Neuman, 2011, p. 341).

The researcher used NVivo software (see Appendix J) to manage, code, and visualize the qualitative data (Bazeley and Jackson, 2013). In qualitative data analysis, three steps are crucial: coding, concept development, and linking to theoretical frameworks. Coding involves assigning labels or categories to data segments that were relevant to the research question and objectives. The researcher used both deductive and inductive coding, depending on the purpose and approach of the study. Deductive coding applied pre-existing codes based on a theory or a framework, while inductive coding created new codes based on the data itself (Bryman, 2016; Yin, 2018). The researcher coded the interview data on the role and practices of local political leaders in the H&SCI context using contingency and situational leadership theories as theoretical lenses. The codes were based on two dimensions: leadership styles and political context (see earlier presented Table 2.2 and 2.3). The coding process

aimed to identify, categorize, and link patterns and themes from the data that answered the research question and objectives.

Concept development involved refining and clustering the codes into broader and more abstract concepts that captured the essence of the data. The researcher then linked the refined concepts to existing theoretical frameworks relevant to the research objectives and questions. The conceptual framework, anchored in Neuman (2011), presented a lens through which to understand the data and address the research questions. Neuman argued that a conceptual framework is essential for interpreting the findings and generating meaningful insights. He highlighted the role of a conceptual framework in guiding data analysis and connecting empirical evidence to the theoretical literature (p. 344). By using this framework, the researcher was able to explain how and why the study's findings supported or contradicted the existing theories in the field. By doing this, the researcher captured both the expected and the unexpected aspects of the data and enriched the analysis with both confirmatory and exploratory insights.

The analysis was comprised of six steps:

- Familiarisation with the data: The researcher read and reviewed the data to gain an overall understanding of the content and context.
- Coding: During coding, the researcher adopted a pragmatic approach, allowing the data to guide the process while maintaining a focus on the established coding categories. This strategy ensured that the analysis remained grounded in the data while also being guided by the theoretical framework. The researcher assigned codes to segments of data that were relevant to the research question and objectives, using descriptive labels that captured the essence of the data, such as "role of local leaders" "political context," "leadership style," and "leadership challenge". For instance, in an interview with a local political leader, the phrase "We need to empower our frontline workforce to deliver the best possible care" was identified. This statement was coded under the leadership styles category - specifically the "transformational leadership" subcategory - as it highlighted the leader's focus on motivating and empowering others to achieve shared goals.
- Theme review: The researcher checked the themes for coherence, consistency, and distinctiveness, and refined them accordingly. The researcher also mapped the relationships between the themes and subthemes.
- Theme development: The researcher reviewed the codes and grouped them into potential themes. The themes were broader categories that represented the main topics or issues that

emerged from the data, such as “role and responsibilities” “IJB board” “political instability”, “transparency” “IJB Chair” “financial pressure”, “motivation” “community engagement” “deprivation” “accountability” “committees” “transformation” “consensus” “limited autonomy” “frontline domestic abuse”, “stakeholders engagement” “Coordination” “Cooperation”, and “facilitation” “compliance” “resistance” “workload” “participation” “political harmony” and “vision” among others.

- The researcher defined and named the broader themes and gave a clear and concise description of what each theme was about, and how it related to the Research Questions and objectives. The researcher also gave an informative name to each theme, such as “Governance Structure and Membership of Integration Joint Boards”, “Role and Challenges of Local Political Leaders” “The Politics of Depoliticization: Balancing Neutrality and Constructive Political Engagement” “Challenges in Creating a Transparent and Accountable Environment” “The impact of political context on leadership”, and “The Influence of Political - Administrative Relationship on leadership styles choices” among others.
- Data analysis and interpretation: This study used the illustrative pattern matching method (Neuman, 2010) to analyse how theoretical concepts are supported by empirical evidence. This method uses a pre-existing framework that can be filled with evidence from the data (Neuman 2011). The researcher matched the patterns or concepts identified in the case studies to those derived from the literature review such as the role of local political leaders in the public sector reform initiatives and contingency and situational leadership theories, which were the theoretical propositions of this study (Yin, 1994). The interviews were first transcribed, and the interview data analysis identified twelve main themes that related to the perceptions, experiences, and opinions of the local political leaders and the bureaucratic leaders on their role and leadership styles in the H&SCI policy area.

The following themes have been identified for this study:

(A) Governance Structure and Membership of Integration Joint Boards

(B) Role and Challenges of Local Political Leaders

(C) Institutionalized Role of Local Political Leaders

(D) The Politics of Depoliticization: Balancing Neutrality and Constructive Political Engagement

(E) Navigating Governance Regulations, Constraints, and Limited Resources in Local Political Leadership within Integrated Governance

(F) Fostering Community Engagement and Co-Production: Navigating Challenges and Building Trust in Healthcare Service Delivery

(G) Challenges in Creating a Transparent and Accountable Environment

(H) The Influence of Financial and Economic Conditions

(I) The Influence of Partisanship

(J) The Influence of Political - Administrative Relationship

(K) The Influence of Geographical Considerations and

(L) The Influence of Frontline Workforce Expectations.

The detailed coding process has been presented in Appendices J, K and L. These appendices provide a comprehensive overview of the coding process, including the coding categories, subcategories, and the description of themes and codes. Appendix K focuses on the role development of local political leaders, analysing the evolving nature of their roles and the factors that shape their leadership practices (Chapter 6). Appendix L delves into the impact of political contextual factors on leadership styles, examining how the political environment influences the leadership approaches of local political leaders (Chapter 7).

Open coding was performed at the first stage of coding where the researcher allowed the data to speak for itself and organized it into segments. At the later stages of theme development and refining the themes or renaming them for the final presentation, themes were guided by the theoretical framework of the study. For instance, when the second stage themes started to emerge by highlighting “frontline workforce job security”, “frontline mental health” and “frontline domestic abuse”, the theoretical framework helped to group them under one of the main themes of the “expectations and needs of frontline workforce”. This was similarly applied to the major thematic groups.

5.5 Research Validity

Validity is a concept that addresses the truthfulness, credibility, and trustworthiness of the findings (Neuman, 2010; Stebbins, 2002). In exploratory research, validity hinges on the researcher's ability to accurately grasp the essence of a phenomenon, whether it is a group, a process, or an activity (Stebbins, 2001). This accuracy is often guided by the concept of authenticity, which emphasizes presenting a fair, honest, and balanced account of social life from the perspective of those directly involved (Neuman, 2011). While traditional quantitative research prioritizes the establishment of a

singular, objective truth, qualitative studies often embrace a more nuanced epistemological stance. Qualitative researchers acknowledge the existence of multiple, relative, and contextual realities or truths, contingent upon the perspective and position of the person with that knowledge (Lather, 1993). This relativistic perspective challenges the notion of a single, universal truth and recognizes the influence of factors such as personal experiences, cultural background, and social context on individual perceptions.

In this study of leadership within H&SCI settings, the researcher employed a combination of deductive and relativist approaches to enhance the validity of the findings. Deductive reasoning involves drawing upon existing theoretical frameworks, such as contingency and situational leadership theories, to provide a structured framework for analysing the data. These theories guided the identification and interpretation of patterns or themes within the diverse experiences of participants from eleven different IJB areas. However, the researcher also recognized the limitations of deductive reasoning and acknowledged the subjective nature of leadership experiences. A relativist approach was adopted to acknowledge the multiple realities and meanings constructed and expressed by participants during their interviews. This approach fostered a deeper understanding of how leadership was perceived and enacted within the specific contexts of each IJB area.

By embracing this blend of deductive and relativist approaches, the researcher was able to achieve a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of leadership within integrated H&SCI settings. The study provided a rich and detailed description of leadership practices, while also acknowledging the diverse perspectives and experiences of participants. The researcher's reflection on their own role, biases, values, and relationships as a researcher further enhanced the validity of the findings, demonstrating a commitment to transparency and reflexivity throughout the research process.

Furthermore, triangulation was employed in multiple ways to strengthen the validity of the findings. The researcher employed multiple data sources, including in-depth interviews with local political leaders and stakeholders (senior officials), and policy documents (independent inquiries and meeting minutes). This triangulation of data allowed for a comprehensive examination of leadership practices from diverse perspectives, capturing both the subjective experiences of participants and the broader context within which these experiences unfolded. In addition, the researcher employed triangulation theory, drawing upon two complementary theoretical lenses – contingency leadership and situational leadership – to provide a multifaceted understanding of leadership practices. Contingency leadership theory emphasizes the importance of adapting leadership styles to the specific demands of the situation, while situational leadership theory focuses on the leader's ability to adjust their behaviour based on the readiness of their followers. By incorporating these two theories, the researcher gained

a deeper understanding of how leadership practices evolve and adapt within the complexities of integrated H&SCI settings.

This use of triangulation across data sources and theoretical frameworks significantly enhanced the validity of the study's findings. This cross-referencing approach ensured that the findings were grounded in multiple perspectives and aligned with established theoretical principles, providing a more robust and reliable representation of leadership practices within integrated H&SCI settings.

5.6 Ethical Considerations

This study followed the ethical principles and guidelines of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), as well as those of external bodies, such as, the Social Research Association (SRA, 2021), and the National Committee for Research Ethics in the Social Sciences and the Humanities (NESH, 2021). These bodies provide ethical guidance for social research, covering issues such as informed consent, confidentiality, anonymity, data protection, participation, and harm prevention. The researcher obtained informed consent from the participants before conducting the interviews, and explained the purpose, objectives, methods, benefits, and risks of the research. The participants were also assured that they could withdraw from the research at any time and without any negative consequences. The researcher provided the participants with a consent form, which they signed and returned to the researcher. The consent form also explained how their data would be protected, confidential, and anonymous, and how they could contact the researcher and the supervisors if they had any questions or concerns. The researcher ensured the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants and the data, and used pseudonyms and codes to identify the participants and the IJBs and removed any identifying information from the documents and the interview transcripts. The researcher stored the data securely, using password-protected devices and encrypted files. The researcher also obtained permission from the participants and the IJBs to use and publish the data and ensured that the data was used only for the purposes of the research. The researcher treated the participants and the data with respect and sensitivity, and respected the views and opinions of the participants, and avoided any judgement, bias, or coercion. The researcher addressed these issues by adopting a reflexive and critical approach, and by seeking guidance and support from the supervisory team.

Conclusion

This chapter has outlined the methodology of this thesis, which adopted a case study approach to examine the role and practices of local political leaders in the H&SCI context. The chapter has justified

the choice of the case study method and explained how it aligns with the Research Questions and objectives. It has described the research design, including the selection of the research site and the sampling programme, which aimed to ensure the representativeness and diversity of the participants. The chapter has further discussed the data collection and analysis procedures, which involved a combination of deductive and inductive coding, concept development, and linking to theoretical frameworks. It has also presented the research validation and methodology validity protocols that were implemented to ensure the quality and rigor of the research, such as triangulation. The chapter has also reflected on some of the strengths and limitations of the methodology and how they influenced the interpretation and generalization of the results, such as the depth and richness of the data, the potential bias and subjectivity of the researcher, and the contextual specificity of the case. Finally, this chapter has addressed some of the ethical issues and challenges that emerged during the research process and how they were resolved or mitigated, such as informed consent, and confidentiality. The methodology chapter has thus set the stage for the next chapter, which will present and analyse the findings of the data collection and analysis.

Chapter 6

The Role and Contemporary Characteristics of Local Political Leaders in Modern Governance: A Thematic Analysis

Introduction

This chapter examines the role of local political leaders and their leadership styles in Scottish Health and Social Care. Using interview data, it analyses the leadership component of the contextual-situational leadership construct presented in Figure 6.1 and assesses its compatibility with the leadership style matrix outlined in Chapter 2. It provides a nuanced understanding of the factors that contribute to the development of local political leadership roles, including the leadership styles preferred or evidenced by local political leaders, by drawing on the latest empirical research and theoretical insights. It applies the leadership styles typology (Chapter 2) with forty-one strategies and characteristics to analyse the interview data. It then contrasts the local political leadership strategies for H&SCI with the typology.

This chapter consists of two sections. Section 6.1 covers four key areas: 1) The structure and membership of IJBs, 2) The role and challenges of local political leaders in H&SCI, 3) The institutional role of local political leaders as board members and IJB chairs, and 4) The balance between neutrality and political engagement. The chapter provides a detailed overview of the IJBs and analyses the roles and responsibilities of local political leaders as members of these boards. It explores the challenges that local political leaders face in navigating complex structures, managing workloads, and maintaining positive relationships with stakeholders. Additionally, it examines the politics of depoliticization in H&SCI, addressing the delicate balance between neutrality and constructive political engagement. Section 6.2 evaluates the difficulties and prospects of local political leadership in integrated governance frameworks for health and social care. It shows how local political leaders adapt to the complex and dynamic environment, make decisions under resource and regulatory constraints, and engage with the community in a transparent way. It also reveals the strategies they use to build trust and accountability within and outside their governance system. This section demonstrates the diverse and crucial role of local political leaders in delivering effective healthcare through integrated governance.

Figure 6.1: Study components-leadership preference

6.1.1 Governance Structure and Membership of Integration Joint Boards

The Scottish Government implemented a significant public sector reform in 2014, with the ultimate goal of improving the participatory and collaborative nature of policy development for local actors working on Health and Social Care issues (Joint Act, 2014). One of the aims of the reform was to create opportunities for local political leaders to engage more effectively with local stakeholders and the public, thereby facilitating the development and implementation of policies that better reflect the needs of the local community. In order to facilitate this process, the Scottish Government established thirty-one IJBs, which are statutory bodies composed of elected local political leaders, bureaucratic leaders, 'citizen representatives, care representatives, and clinical professional representatives and third sector representatives' (Joint Act, 2014; Interviewee C1, 2022). These IJBs were created to provide a platform for local policy actors to collaborate on the most pressing issues related to Health and Social care in their local communities. The membership of the IJBs usually consists of the local council, the health board, bureaucratic leaders, medical professionals, and third-sector organizations including, charities and trade unions (typically four politicians and four members of health board and as well as Third Sector stakeholders). Local political leaders and members of the Health Board hold voting rights within the IJBs. On the other hand, bureaucratic leaders, citizen or carer representatives and Third Sector organizations participate as non-voting members. However, despite the defined membership, the IJB members have the autonomy to plan their own meetings and activities, and to engage additional citizens and stakeholders through sub-committees, social media, online platforms,

and public hearings (IJB, 2015; Interviewee I1, 2022; Interviewee C1,2022). This structure provides a glimpse into the integrated governance model of the IJBs, which is designed to be inclusive and cross-party, with representation from various political parties including the Scottish National Party, Conservative, and Scottish Labour.

Figure 6.2: Organisational chart of a typical IJB

Source: (Audit Scotland - Health and Social Care Integration, December 2015).

In conjunction with the organizational chart, this research finds that the IJBs in Scotland receive support from a variety of committees, including the Audit Committee and Strategic Planning Committee. According to the Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Integration Joint Boards) Scotland Order 2014, each IJB has the authority to determine the number of supportive committees they deem necessary for the smooth functioning of their operations (Joint Act, 2014). This discretionary power allows IJBs to tailor their committee structures to suit the specific requirements and complexities of their respective areas. These committees play a significant role in the integration process (Interviewee

F, 2022). The committees concentrate on overall policy performance, rather than the day-to-day operations of health and social care administration.

These committees are chaired by the local politicians, and members representing NHS, appointed by the IJBs. Within the committees, political leaders collaborate with other participants, managers, and administrators to combine overall strategic goals with concrete experiences and ideas (IJB meeting minutes, 2018; Interviewee H, 2021). The committees meet regularly in a flexible manner to gather information, identify and frame issues, search for policy solutions and discuss their practical and political feasibility. However, the role of committees is to support the effective working of the IJB on matters which have been devolved to them by the IJB. This may be in advisory capacity or, depending on the remit given by the IJB, the sub-committees may have decision-making powers to carry out certain functions of the IJB (Joint Act, 2014).

6.1.2 Role and Challenges of Local Political Leaders

This section examines the role and challenges of local political leaders in the IJBs. The previous section described the structure and membership of the IJBs, as well as the role of committees in facilitating discussion and decision-making among various stakeholders. Local political leaders and NHS non-execs are channelled through committees in order to provide a forum for discussion and decision-making. This ensures that a variety of perspectives are represented in the decision-making process. The members of the committees are appointed by the IJB's voting members, who originate from the local authorities and the health boards (Joint Act, 2014). The IJB's voting members can also make recommendations to the associated organisations about who should be appointed to the committees. Elected politicians play a crucial role in the committees by exercising political leadership and initiating and participating in the discussions. However, in one of the IJB areas, local political leaders have expressed concerns about the limited number of committees, with only one for audit and performance scrutiny and another for public engagement. They suggest that additional committees, such as one focused on initial strategy, may be necessary to reduce the workload faced by IJB members in reviewing a large amount of paperwork.

“Currently, there are only two committees, and I think it might be worth considering the possibility of having a third. Sometimes, important work can be done in committees. There is currently an audit and performance scrutiny committee and a public engagement committee. It might be worth considering adding a committee that can provide an initial review of the strategy” (Interviewee F, 2022).

Local political leaders play a significant role in creating and functioning committees for decision-making in the H&SC system in Scotland. The limited number of committees raises questions about the

efficiency and effectiveness of the current system in some areas. Interviewee F suggests that more committees, or re-evaluating existing ones, might be needed. The suggestion of a new committee focused on strategy shows local political leaders are actively seeking ways to adapt and improve the system. Continuous evaluation and adaptation in leadership are crucial to ensure that the H&SC system is effective and responsive to community needs (McGowan et al., 2020).

In addition, the role of Integrated Joint Board member is critical in the process of integration. The political members of the board set the strategic direction and aim to allocate resources and services to best meet community needs (Interviewee F, 2022). They also scrutinize proposals by officers, who manage day-to-day H&SC services. This scrutiny aims to ensure that proposals align with strategic direction, community needs and priorities. Local political leaders are expected to balance their role as strategic decision-makers with their responsibility to ensure that proposals put forward by officers are thoroughly evaluated and meet the needs of the community. This is done by “ensuring that there is enough evidence to support decisions and that there are sufficient mechanisms in place to evaluate performance and outcomes” (Interviewee F, 2021).

Despite the importance of this role, local political leaders participating in the IJBs face significant challenges in providing adequate scrutiny because of a high volume of papers that come for review. The sheer amount of paperwork involved in these meetings can make it difficult for local political leaders to give the necessary attention to each proposal, leading to concerns about the level of scrutiny being applied. As one interviewee noted, “I think I am concerned that whether there is, in some cases, adequate level of scrutiny because of the nature and amount of the papers that come to the board.” (Interviewee F, 2022). This challenge underscores the importance of finding a balance between the need for scrutiny and the need for efficient decision-making in the complex environment of integration.

The qualitative interviews indicate the importance of preparation and due diligence for local political leaders in an integrated environment, by mentioning their personal approach of doing homework and reading papers before the IJB meeting. It shows the importance of adequate preparation and pre-meeting review by political leaders to ensure effective and efficient governance. The local political leaders also indicate their willingness to intervene in the meeting and ask officers to remove any item that does not fit, which shows a proactive approach to ensuring effective governance.

“I do my homework by reading the papers before the IJB meeting and we have a pre-meeting. During the pre-meeting, I ask the officers to remove any irrelevant material. When I first became chair, I was surprised to see a 450-page document for an IJB meeting. It's difficult to give such a large amount of papers proper scrutiny, and I think it inhibits scrutiny to some extent.” (Interviewee E, 2022).

They do their homework by reading the papers presented by the officers, but they also gain further insights into the content when the papers are presented. They say that what they read may not always align with the intent of the authors, and that this often prompts them to ask questions and potentially change their approach.

“I can read a paper. I can get one view from it. But then I will pick up other nuances when the thing is presented. So that will prompt me to ask questions. Because sometimes what you actually read is not what people have necessarily intended. So, that might change my approach depending on what I have heard.” (Interviewee A, 2021).

Interviewee A highlights the significance of local political leaders' involvement in the integrated governance process. Active engagement and flexibility in approach are essential to enable effective integration and governance (Department of Health and Social Care, 2021). This research indicates that by actively participating in the discussions and interactions with officers, leaders can gain a more complete understanding of the situation and make informed decisions. Relying solely on written materials may have limitations, as there may be difficulties in giving papers proper scrutiny when meetings have a large volume of papers to read. Therefore, local political leaders must ask questions, clarify, and understand different points of view, and remain engaged to ensure effective integration and governance.

Moreover, according to Interviewee C1, a senior official, local political leaders contribute to the decision-making process by asking good questions and participating in various committees and meetings. They also have opportunities to engage in public debates and help make decisions on the board. To ensure informed decision making, it is important that “they are familiar with the subject matter and are able to ask questions privately, by meeting each other in outside the IJB” meetings” (Interviewee C1, 2022). The Integrated Joint Board also values open debate and discussion and prides itself on having those debates publicly. This is demonstrated by the fact that they webcast their meetings. Interviewee C1 (2022) believes that good decision making is the result of good engagement, good information, and a willingness to have open debate and discussion.

The senior official perspective emphasizes the pivotal role of local political leaders in effective integrated governance. It highlights the importance of formulating relevant inquiries, understanding the subject matter, and addressing concerns for informed decision-making. Encouraging active engagement and fostering an environment conducive to open debate enhances transparency, while webcasting meetings enable public scrutiny. However, it is essential to acknowledge that characterizing leaders primarily as questioners, rather than as leaders themselves, may limit their full potential and influence in the governance landscape. The senior official may recognize the crucial role of local political leaders in their perspective.

On the other hand, one senior official G1, (2021) offers a different perspective on the role of local political leaders in integrated governance. The actor emphasizes the importance of political leaders possessing strong leadership skills and navigating complex decision-making, beyond being informed questioners. The actor acknowledges the challenges faced by the IJB in transforming community Health and Social Care services, foreseeing the need for difficult decisions. They cited past examples, such as “closing dental and GP practices, which proved challenging for elected members due to their democratic role within local communities” (G1, 2021). This senior official predicts further tough decisions and underscores the indispensable role of local political leaders in effectively transforming Health and Social Care services and expects that the leadership approach of the IJB elected members should be transformational and strategic, focusing on developing a shared vision and empowering others to deliver. However, in practice, the leadership styles of IJB elected members can be transactional, autocratic, and less collaborative, which is not ideal for the IJB (G1, 2021). Despite variations in perspectives among senior officials, it is evident that leadership skills, subject matter expertise, and a commitment to transparency and public debate are essential for successfully navigating integrated governance.

6.1.3 Institutionalized Role of Local Political Leaders

The leadership role in the IJBs has been institutionalised in a number of ways. First, the Chief Officer position, which is the primary leading position of the IJBs, is appointed by the IJB board, but Scottish Government provide guidance on this appointment (Joint Act, 2014). Secondly, the chair of an IJB is a non-partisan position which comes through consensus between different political parties and is considered to be the second leading position in the IJB. This means that the chairs are not beholden to any particular political party or interest group. For instance, some local political leaders do not view their role as one of leading staff and sees the notion of leadership as more appropriate for the chief officer, high level staff, and possibly the chair of the board.

“The board is responsible for setting strategic direction. It is responsible for setting a budget. It is responsible for making sure that budget is adhered to and looking at high level performance against that strategy. So, it is the responsibility of a board member. It is not leading staff. So, I think the notion of leadership is probably more appropriate to the chief officer, to some of the high-level staff and possibly to the chair of the board in the way that he or she chairs the board.” (Interviewee F, 2021).

The political perspective highlights a distinction in the roles of local political leaders and staff members within the Integrated Joint Board. According to interviewee F, board members are primarily responsible for setting strategic direction and ensuring adherence to the budget, rather than directly

leading staff. In this perspective, the role of leadership is more fitting for the chief officer, high-level staff, and possibly the political chair of the board, who facilitates and guides discussions during board meetings. The emphasis lies in clearly defining roles and responsibilities within the IJB where board members monitor performance while staff members are responsible for service operations. The distributed nature of leadership across different levels reinforces the importance of efficient board operation facilitated by the chair, who plays a vital role in discussions and decision-making. This gives the chair a great deal of influence over the direction of the board's work.

However, this perspective can be critically examined from a political standpoint. Constraining the role of local political leaders to that of board members fails to fully comprehend their impact and influence. These leaders bring a distinct viewpoint influenced by the aspirations and needs of their constituents, which can significantly shape governance proceedings. Furthermore, the categorization of the board's role and the members' role by local political leaders may overlook the complexity of decision-making in integrated governance. Successful governance necessitates the integration of various functions, perspectives, and competencies (Ansell and Gash, 2008). This research finds that effective collaboration between the board and personnel is crucial to make informed decisions and implement policies that serve the best interests of all relevant parties.

In addition, interviewee A (2021) highlights the dominance of NHS staff in managing the IJB as elected members play a limited role, "primarily offering a slightly different perspective on various issues". This perspective raises further questions about the level of influence and decision-making power that elected members hold within the IJB, especially compared to the dominant presence of NHS staff. It raises concerns about the balance of power and the representation of diverse perspectives within the governance process. The characterization of elected members as simply providing a "slightly different view" raises questions about the extent of their influence and participation in the IJB's decision-making. This raises concerns about adequate representation for constituents in the integrated governance process and emphasizes the necessity for a more comprehensive and inclusive approach to decision-making. However, it is important to note that, despite some arguing their limited role in some areas, some local political leaders argued they still retain authority within the IJB and have the ability to exercise their influence when necessary.

Local political leader E (2022) recounts a meeting where officers presented a proposal to establish a grant fund for staff-wellbeing purpose. However, questions arose regarding the tax implications and whether the fund would be inclusive of all staff, including those working in remote healthcare settings. The concern was that the proposal seemed to prioritize the hospital, potentially neglecting equitable treatment across different healthcare settings. To address these concerns, E, (2022) who has the

“authority” within the IJB over financial matters, proposed an agreement in principle to establish the grant and allocate funds but requested officers to provide further details and clarity on tax and revenue implications. This exercise of authority demonstrates their ability to pause the meeting and demand further work and examination before proceeding. By doing so, they emphasize the importance of fairness and inclusivity in decision-making, ensuring that decisions made with public or patient funds are comprehensive, just, and beneficial for all stakeholders. Despite their limited role, local political leaders have the authority to exercise their influence and advocate for equitable decision-making processes within the IJB.

Effective governance thrives on the integration of diverse roles, perspectives, and expertise, promoting collaboration between the board and staff (Douglas et al., 2020). The inclusion of elected political leaders and professional staff enables the incorporation of various viewpoints, leading to well-informed decisions that prioritize the interests of all stakeholders. Political leader A (2021) was keen to highlight the value of diverse perspectives, as evidenced by their different approach to solving a problem during a flu outbreak. Although initially overlooked by National Health staff, their bottom-up approach based on local knowledge, grounded in local practical calculations, acknowledged by the national authorities and later proved to be correct. This experience highlights the significance of integrating diverse perspectives in governance and emphasizes the need for effective communication and negotiation skills to successfully incorporate these perspectives. While divergent viewpoints do not guarantee immediate acceptance, they underscore the importance of robust communication and negotiation in fostering collaboration within a governance framework. Furthermore, the leader's pragmatic and hands-on approach underscores the importance of practicality in solving complex problems within governance. These contributions are further commended by senior officials, recognizing the crucial and non-political role of local political leaders in the decision-making process (Interviewee A1, 2022).

Moreover, the role of the political IJB chair is particularly important in terms of leadership. The chair has certain additional leadership aspects, such as the ability to build consensus, make efficient decisions, and avoid political divisions. This is because the chair has to work with a diverse group of stakeholders and ensure that everyone's needs are met. Interviewees C1, G1, C, E, and F affirm the value of diversity in political representation, which fosters a shared sense of ownership and contribution among committee members. They acknowledge the chair's success in keeping party politics separate from their discussions. However, they also acknowledge that political considerations can sometimes impede progress and should be avoided. Local political leader C (2021) concurs with this perspective, as an IJB chair, emphasizing the need to prioritize collective interests over party

politics. The chair's main role encompasses creating an environment of collaboration and ensuring that decisions are made in the best interest of the constituents.

“As the chair of the IJB, my responsibility, like any committee chair, is to efficiently conduct the business at hand. It is impossible to tell people to talk for hours without reaching a conclusion. I've always tried to work on the basis of achieving as much consensus as possible to include that as many people and discussion and debate in a way that everybody's views are taken. We have made conscious efforts to prevent political divisions, despite having five elected members from different political parties in Scotland. It was more by accident than business. Each member's representation has been valuable, contributing to a collective sense of ownership and making joint contributions.” (Interviewee C, 2022).

The chair's focus on achieving consensus and conducting business efficiently also reflects the bureaucratic perspective on the role of political leaders in governance, which emphasizes the importance of informed decision-making and open debate (Preston and 't Hart, 1999; Morais and Kakabadse, 2020). By striving for consensus and avoiding political division, the political chair of the IJB is working to ensure informed and transparent decision-making, which is crucial to the success of the integration process. This approach by the chair seems to prioritize efficient and effective decision-making over political considerations. The phrase "more by accident than by design" raises questions about the intentionality behind inclusive representation and avoiding political biases in the Integrated Joint Board.

Senior officials also acknowledge the significance of effective communication and collaboration when local political leaders assume the chair or vice-chair roles within the Integrated Joint Board. According to interviewee G1, (2021) elected members demonstrate support and attentiveness towards operational challenges in their chair roles. Another senior actor, C1 (2022), emphasizes the role of a competent chair in promoting respect, reminding members of their responsibilities, and ensuring accountability. However, the alternating presence of a non-executive from the NHS and an elected member as the IJB chair can introduce political dynamics and potential politicization. The chair position alternates between NHS and local authority every two years (Joint Act, 2014). As noted by C1, (2022) the involvement of politicians may sometimes lead to political rivalries, party-political point-scoring, and strained relationships within the IJB. Furthermore, the overlapping roles of elected members in the IJB and local authority can result in a focus on local details rather than strategic service commissioning (Interviewee D1, 2021; Interviewee G1, 2021).

6.1.4 The Politics of Depoliticization: Balancing Neutrality and Constructive Political

Engagement

The political makeup of the local authority can significantly impact the ability of elected members to separate their roles in the IJB from their political affiliations (Interviewee D1, 2021; Interviewee H1, 2021). In some cases, political discussions and blame games related to Scottish Government agendas and policies may permeate the IJB. However, senior official interviewee H1 (2021) asserts their strength in not engaging in such discussions, highlighting the importance of personal strength and leadership qualities for navigating these challenges. This underscores the significance of strong bureaucratic leadership in the role of local political leaders in integration governance. The ability to maintain neutrality, refrain from political discussions, and remain focused on the community's goals are essential skills for successful integration within complex governance environments (Fawcett et al., 2017). However, it is important to recognize that not all leaders may possess these qualities, and other factors such as political context, culture, and stakeholder collaboration can also influence the effectiveness of local political leadership in collaborative governance. While Interviewee H1 emphasizes the importance of bureaucratic leadership and refraining from political discussions, it is essential to consider that politics can also have positive effects within the context of integrated governance. Bringing politics into the decision-making process can increase accountability and transparency. When political leaders engage in discussions related to agendas and policies, they provide a platform for public scrutiny and hold each other accountable for their actions. Political debates can shed light on different perspectives and foster a healthy exchange of ideas.

Research supports the notion that incorporating politics in governance processes can lead to positive outcomes. As highlighted by Peters and Pierre (2016), political dynamics and interactions among various actors can help to expose hidden agendas, challenge dominant narratives, and promote a more inclusive decision-making process. In their study on collaborative governance, Emerson et al. (2012) argue that political engagement allows for a broader range of voices to be heard, leading to more informed and robust decisions. Furthermore, Sørensen and Torfing (2018) contend that politics in governance can enhance democratic legitimacy by ensuring that decisions are shaped by diverse perspectives and interests. Moreover, the inherent nature of governance processes necessitates the consideration of politics. In systems where multiple stakeholders with differing interests and ideologies are involved, political dynamics are almost unavoidable. As observed by Kooiman (2003) and McMillan (2021), governance is characterized by complex interactions and power struggles between actors, and politics is an integral part of these interactions. Attempts to ignore or avoid politics may hinder effective decision-making and limit the diversity of perspectives considered. Therefore, effective leadership should not shy away from politics but instead focus on managing and harnessing political

dynamics to promote constructive dialogue and collaboration. By acknowledging the role of politics and providing a space for political debates, leaders can foster transparency, accountability, and the representation of diverse viewpoints in integration governance (Sorensen et al, 2020; Douglas et al., 2020).

Building upon this understanding, it is evident that local political leaders in integration governance can play a constructive role in promoting collaboration and reaching consensus. According to I1 (2022), political leaders in the integrated governance do not see the IJB as a political game and do not bring their political views to the IJB, which is considered "unusual" (Interviewee I1, 2022). These leaders are described as working collaboratively and constructively, even when faced with conflicting views, in order to determine the best course of action for the communities they represent. For example, despite clear differences on the National Care Service policy at the national level, local political groups such as the Labour group, Scottish Conservatives and SNP political group do not engage in these debates when making decisions within the Health and Social Care setting (Interviewee I1, 2021; Interviewee I, 2022; Interviewee I2, 2022). This co-operative approach allows the IJB to focus on addressing important issues and contributes to effective governance. The fact that local political leaders handle differences of opinion respectfully suggests their capacity to engage in constructive debates and reach compromises, which is crucial in a democratic system.

In addition to the positive role played by local political leaders, the perspective of a senior official (A1, 2021) in integrated governance sheds light on the decision-making process and efforts to avoid political influences. The senior official acknowledges the potential for political sensitivity, particularly during election periods, and takes proactive steps to mitigate such challenges. They invest in seminars and development days for IJB members to promote an understanding of their role and cultivate a culture that discourages politicization. By emphasizing the importance of avoiding politicization, the senior official demonstrates their commitment to maintaining the integrity of the decision-making process within integrated governance. Furthermore, the actor recognizes the significance of education and training in equipping IJB members with the necessary knowledge and skills to navigate the complexities of collaborative governance effectively. Through these measures, the senior official displays a proactive approach to addressing potential challenges and upholding decision-making integrity.

At the same time, local political leaders play a vital role in integrated governance through their interest and focus on community needs. These leaders try to prioritize the welfare of vulnerable individuals who depend on public services, recognizing that their concerns outweigh political scores or agendas.

Their practical approach to addressing difficult and contentious issues is commendable, fostering collaboration with other stakeholders.

“We try and keep in mind that the most important thing here is people that are serving the community. And those people who use the services and depend on the services, many of them are very, very vulnerable. So, with that, I think the, these considerations are far more important than policy work or points.” (Interviewee C, 2021).

In the context of integrated governance, the leader's focus on the community is a sign of good leadership. However, their role as an IJB member has certain limitations. Because of procedural requirements, they are unable to address direct constituent issues during IJB meetings but choose to raise them with officers outside of the meeting (Interviewee F, 2021). It is important to acknowledge the constraints of their position within the IJB. While their dedication to serving the community is admirable, their reliance on addressing issues outside of formal meetings raises concerns about their ability to actively contribute to the decision-making process in the complex environment of integrated governance. Finding a balance between their community-centric approach and active engagement in governance processes is crucial to ensure that their constituents' voices are adequately represented and considered.

On the other hand, local political leaders play a valuable role in fostering transparency and accountability within integrated governance. They ask questions at IJB meetings to ensure information is communicated to the public and to gain a deeper understanding of the situation. They approach concerns raised directly by members of the public with a willingness to ask questions, “even if they may seem trivial” (Interviewee I, 2021). However, it is important to acknowledge that relying solely on asking questions may have limitations. This approach may not capture the needs and perspectives of the broader community, especially those who are less likely to voice their opinions. In addition, complex, and nuanced issues may require more than just questioning to ensure thorough and effective resolution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this section has explored the intricate role development of local political leaders in strategic decision-making within integrated governance settings. The governance structure, as outlined, places local political leaders alongside senior officials, NHS representatives, and Third Sector counterparts. It is evident that local political leaders, vested with voting powers, contribute significantly to the IJBs' functioning, but not without encountering challenges. Workload issues and time-consuming tasks often hinder their scrutiny and questioning of presented documents. Yet, the insights gathered from senior officials reveal a multi-faceted role, from raising pertinent queries to

participating in transformational decision-making. This shows that integrated governance is a complex process that requires multiple parties with different roles, interests, and perspectives to work together to make decisions and implement policies. The presence of both elected political leaders and professional staff in the IJB provides an opportunity for the integration of different viewpoints and ideas, which can lead to more informed and effective decisions.

The institutionalized role of local leaders was also explored, showcasing the diversity of perspectives within this group. While some perceive their function as offering alternative viewpoints, others assert their authority in shaping strategic plans and their implementation. Leadership positions are predominantly held by chief officers and Board Chairs, who effectively navigate the complex dynamics of integrated governance. Notably, it was suggested that local political leaders in chair positions play a pivotal role in enhancing communication and collaboration within these structures. Furthermore, the impact of politicization on their roles was also discussed, revealing a spectrum of experiences. While instances of blame games resulting from political party affiliations can arise, the prevailing sentiment appears to be one of political harmony, where local leaders prioritize the interests of their communities. Overall, this section has provided a comprehensive insight into the various dimensions of local political leadership within integrated governance and their crucial role in navigating its complexities. It becomes evident that the importance of local political leadership in navigating the complexity of integrated governance cannot be overstated.

The next section delves into the strategies employed by local political leaders to effectively manage their roles within the intricate landscape of integrated governance.

6.2

The Role of Local Political Leadership in Navigating Complexity in Integrated Governance

Introduction

The following sections demonstrate that local political leaders play a critical role in navigating the complexities of H&SC system by circumnavigating governance regulations, constraints, and limited resources within integrated governance. They are potentially known for being close to their communities and possessing an understanding of their constituents' needs and concerns, as well as the challenges and opportunities in their local area (Downes, 1968). This knowledge enables them to address complex problems and promote community well-being, acting as a liaison between communities and different levels of governance, integrating their constituents' needs and perspectives into decision-making processes. Hence, this section will also be looking at their role in fostering community engagement and co-Production as well as navigating challenges in maintaining transparent and accountable environment.

Despite their essential role, local political leaders face challenges and limitations, such as balancing conflicting interests and priorities and facing pressure from different groups to make certain decisions (Agranoff and McGuire, 2001; Emerson et al., 2012). Moreover, navigating the complex nature of contemporary governance requires a deep understanding of policies, regulations, and processes at different levels, which can be daunting. Therefore, identifying leadership strategies of local political leaders in integrated governance is critical to explore their role in addressing complex problems, promoting well-being, facilitating communication and collaboration between different levels of governance, and helping local political leaders navigate complex systems.

6.2.1 Local Political Leadership in Navigating Governance Regulations, Constraints, and Limited Resources

In the role of local political leadership, navigating complexity is a persistent challenge. This is especially true in discussions held by the IJB where political perspectives can greatly vary among members. One such example is seen in the allocation of the budget, where the Council is responsible for allocating a global sum of money for the IJB to distribute. Despite slight variations in budget allocation between political parties such as the SNP, Labour, and Conservatives, the IJB must come together as a united body to make decisions on how to allocate the funds. Local political leader (F, 2022) states:

“There have been obvious differences in political perspective in IJB discussions. A lot of people coming from different directions and therefore having different views on a particular issue. I mean, some examples in relation to budget potentially. largely what the Council does is to allocate a global sum of money and then it is for the IJB to decide how to spend that. So, the global sum of money may slightly vary in the SNP budget to the Labour budget or to this Conservative budget, but it's a global sum of money. The SNP to my mind did something which was totally inappropriate on the last budget where they didn't ask, they didn't allocate additional money, but they asked the IJB to act in a particular way which the IJB then as a united body did not agree that that should have been done and actually ask the chair who happens to be an SNP member, to write back to the council and say they thought it was inappropriate because the responsibility for allocating the budget is the IJB's.” (Interviewee F, 2022).

This shows the challenges faced by the IJB in reconciling the diverse political priorities of its members to underscore the complexity of local political leadership within integrated governance. The potential for disagreements, particularly in budget allocation, can hinder the IJB's effectiveness in addressing community needs. The interference by the SNP serves as a reminder of the importance of maintaining the autonomy and unity of the IJB as a cohesive entity dedicated to the responsible distribution of the budget. For example, when a community is grappling with healthcare, social care, and public service issues, the IJB's diverse membership, with its varied backgrounds and expertise, becomes crucial in making well-informed decisions on budget allocation. However, succumbing to political pressure and deviating from responsible budget distribution potentially risks misrepresenting the community's needs and compromising resource utilization (Hood, 1995; Alsharari, 2022). On the other hand, a united IJB that operates free from political influence has a potential to foster transparency, fairness, and community trust, while enabling its members to make informed decisions on fund allocation. It is therefore incumbent upon the majority of the IJB to provide the necessary guidance and direction for the partnership or network. While elected political leaders and chief officers may hold influential positions, the leading role in this context is unequivocally attributed to the IJB as an autonomous and cohesive entity. Through their collaborative decision-making on budget allocation, the IJB strengthens its position as a responsible and effective governance body, striving to meet the diverse needs of the community while upholding transparency and accountability.

Local political leaders assume a crucial role as public servants within the governance structure of IJBs. Integration Joint Boards They bear the responsibility of prioritizing the voices and needs of the community they serve, representing the interests of the constituents who have elected them. Their role extends beyond partisan politics and self-interest, requiring a steadfast commitment to serving the entire community, irrespective of age, gender, socio-economic status, or political affiliation. As public servants, local political leaders are expected to be accessible, transparent, and accountable to their constituents, engaging in active and meaningful dialogue with the community. When talking to

local political leader (E, 2022), their dedication to fulfilling this public servant role is evident. They emphasize the importance of prioritizing community interests and engaging in open communication, fostering a sense of trust and collaboration. By embodying these qualities, local political leaders contribute to the effective functioning of IJBs and the promotion of integrated governance.

“We are engaged as public servants. I'm elected to serve whether that public's in my village, whether it's in another town or another community, my heart is in communities and maybe I'm different, I'm not a huge believer in governance, rules, and regulations. I'm here because people want me to represent them. If I can do that to the best of my ability, I will do so. Sometimes you can't, sometimes it's impossible, but to me, you should strive for that. You should strive for all ages and generations, so it should be right across the whole, the whole population that we represent, we are there to do a whole population service. We have too Otherwise not done our job.” (Interviewee E, 2022).

This exemplifies a leadership style that prioritizes public service and community needs over bureaucratic constraints of governance rules and regulations. This approach emphasizes empathy, inclusivity, and democratic decision-making, where all voices are heard and considered. The leader's focus on serving all ages and generations underlines the critical importance of considering the long-term impacts of decisions, which can assist in navigating the complex and often conflicting nature of integrated governance. Further, this finding and approach redefines the traditional understanding of democratic accountability as a question of voters holding elected politicians to account on election day and is replaced with emphasizing a horizontal form of accountability, where all those involved in politically initiated processes of collaborative policy evaluate their separate and joint efforts to enhance public value production and produce accessible narrative accounts of their deeds to facilitate public scrutiny (Wondolleck and Yaffee, 2000; Erkkilä, 2007). This means that all stakeholders are accountable to each other and there is a shared responsibility for ensuring that the collaborative process is heading in right direction.

However, within the framework of integrated governance, local political leaders face the challenge of balancing competing interests, reconciling conflicting priorities, and ensuring fairness and equity for all stakeholders involved (Agranoff and McGuire, 2001; Emerson et al., 2012). On the one hand, this community-based leadership style can foster a strong relationship with the community, promote unity, common purpose, trust, and accountability but on the other hand, the community-based leadership style adopted by local political leaders in integrated governance can pose challenges. Within the complex realm of IJB, leaders face a range of obstacles, including budget constraints, stakeholder conflicts, and adherence to the IJB rule book. Local political leader (F, 2022) shared one of these examples:

“I do represent individuals who approach me, who live in my ward. If somebody is having problems with social work, I would approach social work on their behalf, for example, if somebody had an issue about, why is Health Centre X, not open at a convenient time of day? The IJB is not the place to take that up. You take it up with officers, but not at an IJB meeting. That is not what we are there for as a IJB member.” (Interviewee F, 2022).

Notably, F (2022) provides evidence of being well-versed in the appropriate protocols, procedures, and forums for raising issues and addressing constituent concerns. This shows a deep understanding of the interplay between the IJB and other governance structures, as well as situational awareness, strategic thinking, and political savvy to navigate these channels and work within the existing structures for positive outcomes for constituents. Therefore, instead of prioritizing communities blindly over bureaucratic constraints, local political leaders are expected to possess the necessary skills to effectively navigate the challenges of regulatory framework and represent the best interests of their constituents. Furthermore, successful local political leaders foster a collaborative approach to governance, working closely with partners to find mutually agreeable solutions. This necessitates excellent communication, co-ordination, and co-operation among stakeholders (Ansell et al., 2008). Mediating diverse perspectives and ensuring collective efforts towards shared goals are crucial responsibilities from local political leaders. By raising issues at the appropriate time and venue, local political leaders optimize the decision-making process. Their ability to navigate complexities and work towards solutions that serve the best interests of their constituents is crucial for their effectiveness in this role.

While local political leaders play a crucial role in serving their communities, their leadership approach can further be challenged by governance regulations and constraints. This is particularly true in the case of the regulatory framework of H&SC governance, which can present considerable challenges to local leaders. The interaction between Scottish Government financial allocations and local council financing provides a complicated problem that calls on local leaders to distribute resources in a fair and equitable way. The Scottish Government's allocation of increasing funds for health services and decreasing funding for council social care services has caused noticeable strain on local leaders, who must reconcile competing demands. In the context of those challenges, it becomes even more crucial for local political leaders to navigate these regulatory constraints while ensuring the community's needs are met.

“I think the main issue is that, on the health side, the Scottish government's allocation to health boards and, in turn, the health board's allocation to IJB. The Scottish government has increased its funding for health over the last ten years, but it has decreased council funding over the last nine ten years. In our council, it has decreased by about 7% in real terms, and that's not including the pressures of demographic demand and pay levels. So, that is the context in which you are operating, where the Scottish government is giving more money for

some things, and the things which the council is responsible for have less money, and that restricts choice hugely. If money is stable or going down, it limits its choice, and to some extent, you are off.” (Interviewee F, 2021).

The local political leader's perspective highlights the challenge of balancing competing priorities and managing limited resources within the regulatory framework of governance. The funding allocation between the Scottish Government and local councils creates a significant challenge for local leaders, as funding for health services has increased while funding for council services has decreased, putting a strain on local leaders who are trying to reconcile the demands of different stakeholders.

When funding is reduced, local councils are forced to make difficult decisions about which services to cut or reduce, leading to conflicting demands from different groups, such as residents, businesses, and special interest groups, each with different needs and priorities (Lowndes and Gardner, 2016). Local political leaders are expected to balance limited resources with the diverse needs of their constituents while maintaining stability and continuity in their communities. The decrease in council funding restricts their choices, and limits their ability to effectively serve their communities, exacerbating the challenges they face in navigating financial governance and regulatory constraints (Lowndes and Gardner, 2016). The leadership challenge lies in striking a delicate balance between fulfilling the needs of the community and adhering to the rules and financial regulations imposed by Health and social care governance framework.

A key aspect of this leadership style involves effectively addressing practical, day-to-day issues while concurrently considering the broader objectives of their position. C (2022), acknowledges the reality of limited resources and the need for difficult decisions,” if you don't want to be faced with difficult decisions, then don't get involved in local government.” This pragmatic and determined attitude enable them to navigate the complexities of integrated governance by emphasizing the importance of working with available resources and making progress within challenging circumstances. By acknowledging the reality of constrained resources and the need for difficult choices, this leadership style adopts a realistic approach to governance, mitigating unrealistic expectations and minimizing disappointment when goals cannot be fully realized. Moreover, the leader's commitment to serving the community and fulfilling their elected responsibilities ensures that collaborative governance remains on track and advances towards shared objectives, even when confronted with competing interests among stakeholders. This approach helps maintain a steadfast focus on serving the public interest, a fundamental goal of collaborative governance within the integrated governance framework.

6.2.2 Fostering Community Engagement and Co-Production: Navigating Challenges and Building Trust in Healthcare Service Delivery

Local political leaders face the challenge of meeting the increasing demand for public services with limited budgetary resources (Lowndes and Gardner, 2016; Leach, Stewart and Jones, 2017). To address this challenge, they are exploring innovative approaches to better serve their local communities. One such approach is the shift of care responsibility from statutory services to community organizations and individuals, aiming to reduce the burden on statutory services and to promote community involvement in service provision. However, this strategic shift brings its own set of challenges that local political leaders must carefully consider. They need to assess the implications of this approach on the affected communities and ensure transparent and honest communication about these changes. Failure to do so may lead to public mistrust and resistance. As highlighted by F (2022) it is crucial for leaders to navigate these challenges and ensure effective community engagement in order to implement equitable and efficient healthcare services within the H&SC system.

“Treating people who are ill against a rising demand and potentially stable or decreased funding requires doing things differently. This includes reducing demand on statutory services by encouraging greater involvement of community organizations and individuals. However, this approach is still in its early stages, and there are concerns about placing too much demand on voluntary organizations and individuals for cost-cutting purposes. The staff is currently exploring this approach, and they have presented some initial ideas to the IJB. However, there is a need for honest communication with the public about what this approach entails, as the current messaging is filled with jargon and lacks transparency. Therefore, there is a need to provide real-life case studies that illustrate the impact of this approach on people's lives.” (Interviewee F, 2022).

The local political leader is taking a participatory and transparent approach to governance by acknowledging the challenges of providing healthcare services with limited resources. These efforts of this IJB shifting demand from statutory to community organisation has been evidenced through documentary analysis as well (IJB F minutes, 21 Jun 2017). However, they do express concerns about the demands placed on voluntary organizations and whether one of the reasons they are being considered is because they are cost effective. Recognizing the importance of honesty and transparency, F (2022) emphasizes the need to communicate openly with the public, ensuring they understand the implications of changes and involving them in decision-making processes. Effective communication and collaboration are crucial to the success of this approach, as the involvement of community organizations and individuals requires careful co-ordination and oversight by local political leader (Ansell, and Torfing, 2021). F (2022) also considers the potential impact on vulnerable groups and takes appropriate measures to ensure that services are not disrupted or compromised. This reflects the complexities of collaborative governance as leaders attempts to balance the needs of

various stakeholders. The leadership style can build public trust and support for changes, but it requires significant time, resources, and effort to engage and collaborate with multiple stakeholders (Ansell and Gash, 2008). The complexity lies in finding a balance between reducing demand on statutory services and not overburdening voluntary organizations.

Furthermore, F (2022) is concerned about the lack of clear communication about the issue and the use of jargon, indicating a desire for transparency and accountability (Douglas et al., 2020). The complexity is further highlighted by the need for case studies to illustrate what this approach means in real life. The local political leader is grappling with finding solutions to address the challenges of providing healthcare services while balancing the needs of various stakeholders and being transparent and honest with the public. The leader's participatory and transparent approach, effective communication and collaboration, and careful consideration of vulnerable groups can build public trust and support for changes.

Against this background, within the domain of local Health and Social Care planning, local political leaders proactively engage with their respective communities, demonstrating an acute awareness of the fundamental role of co-production. By actively soliciting the perspectives and insights of "community members, encompassing patients, caregivers, and local healthcare professionals" (H, 2022), these leaders obtain invaluable information to ensure that decisions closely align with the distinct needs and priorities of the community. The arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic has notably underscored the criticality of effective leadership in addressing the needs of constituents. In this regard, the case of H (2022) stands as an embodiment of such leadership through their active involvement in volunteer endeavours, thereby exemplifying the core principles of co-production and the ensuing metamorphosis of civic engagement. H's experiences serve as a testament to the potential dividends yielded by the active engagement of local political leaders, including the cultivation of trust, the nurturing of community spirit, and the promotion of astute governance practices.

"You know, during COVID, I was really blessed to be fit and healthy and able to help out by volunteering. I would pick up prescriptions for people in need and deliver food to those who were shielding. It was a positive experience for me, as it allowed me to get out and about in my area and be a practical help to people, while fostering a community spirit. People were helping each other out all over the place. So, I have always tried to apply that principle to everything that I do." (Interviewee H, 2021)

Further B, (2022) shared their experience of involving communities when local services were closing down:

"I said earlier that my background was community campaigning and I campaigned against closer of my own community hospitals and it's one of the reasons I ended up in the position, so really difficult and you know, that gets brought up now. For example, we had to close a

community hospital in one of the locality, which was a tough decision. Unfortunately, the consultation process was flawed, and we acknowledge our failure in communication. We took responsibility, apologized, and actively listened to the public, ensuring them that the new services would be an improvement. It is challenging to handle lobbying from local members and colleagues, but I strive to navigate through these difficulties.” (Interviewee B, 2022)

These local political leaders’ statements underline the importance of their physical presence and active involvement within their communities, particularly during times of crisis and when local services are facing crisis of unsustainability. By participating in practical and hands-on initiatives, the leader showcases their dedication to serving the needs of their constituents and fostering a positive community environment. This prioritisation of community needs and incorporating them in decision making has been appreciated and highlighted by senior officials in these areas, where senior official (B1, 2022) said, “I have seen politicians leaving their political parties division of Conservative and left politics behind and listening and promoting their communities’ interests in the IJB”.

This approach can bolster trust and strengthens relationships between the political leaders and their constituents, which is crucial for the success of integrated governance. Both leaders acknowledge the critical role of the community in overcoming governance challenges and recognizes that co-operation and support from community members and stakeholders can facilitate the identification and implementation of effective solutions. This approach embodies the principles of co-production, where political leaders collaborate with their constituents to address community problems and meet community needs. It is important to note here a shift in the perception of traditional civic engagement as well from being seen as an end in itself, to being seen as a means of strengthening and democratizing political leadership. This new understanding recognizes that by providing input to elected politicians, civic engagement can help them to better understand and address pressing societal problems (Lees-Marshment 2015). Through interaction with various constituents and stakeholders, elected politicians can lead the local community more effectively.

The concept of co-production of public value outcomes, which was previously only thought of as a tool for administrators, can now also seen as a useful tool for elected politicians. These politicians previously found themselves in a difficult position of needing to provide political leadership for integrated policy governance, but also risking losing influence on public policy making (Sullivan, 2011). By engaging in co-production, elected politicians can more effectively address policy problems, improve policy outcomes, and avoid being side-tracked from their goals. Interaction with different kinds of citizens and stakeholders can help elected politicians to lead the local community.

6.2.3 Challenges in Creating a Transparent and Accountable Environment

In the domain of governance, transparency and accountability are fundamental principles that underpin effective leadership (Erkkilä, 2007; Emerson et al., 2012). These principles are especially critical in the complex sector of H&SCI, where the accountability of local political leaders within the context of IJBs is multi-dimensional (See figure 6.3). The democratic mandate begins this accountability: political leaders derive their authority from the electorate, to whom they are ultimately accountable (Joint Act, 2014). This translates into a responsibility to deliver on campaign promises, address public concerns, and ensure equitable access to healthcare services, thereby upholding public trust (Powell, 2020). Furthermore, structured institutional accountability mechanisms exist. National ministers oversee IJBs, demanding accountability in the form of strategic commissioning plans that guide integrated functions and budgets (Joint Act, 2014). Political leaders within IJBs are also accountable to Health Boards and Local Authorities, which delegate functions and resources, thus shaping the nature of service delivery (Audit Scotland 2018).

Moreover, professional accountability is integral to the governance structure. Leaders must align with the ethos of integrated governance, adhering to standards and maintaining effective collaboration with peers within the political and administrative domains (Interviewee B, 2022; Interviewee H1,2022; Interviewee H, 2022). Public engagement adds another layer of accountability. Through consultations and participatory processes, leaders actively solicit feedback from citizens, patients, and stakeholders, fostering collective responsibility and integrating a spectrum of viewpoints into policymaking (Interviewee C1, 2022; Interviewee B, 2022; Interviewee E, 2022). Community forums serve as venues for leaders to justify their decisions, solicit public input, and exhibit adaptability to civic concerns.

Figure 6.3: the Accountability mechanism in the IJB

(Source: Audit Scotland report on integration, 2018).

In essence, political leaders operating within the IJB framework navigate a complex web of accountability channels. The Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014 has been instrumental in establishing this framework, ensuring that leaders remain focused on public well-being and the provision of equitable, high-quality healthcare services. Establishing a conducive environment for accountability and transparency is vital to this goal. Research indicates that such an environment is essential for the effective leadership and governance in the integration of health and social care services, as it directly impacts the quality of care and service delivery (Crocker et al., 2020).

This entails fostering a setting where inquiry and dialogue are encouraged without fear of reprisal or judgment. Local political leaders emphasize the role of top bureaucratic leadership in creating this environment while setting the tone and culture of the organization (Interviewee F, 2022). Transparent and accountable organizations work openly, honestly, and fairly to ensure that information is available to the public and interested parties. This requires a culture that values transparency and accountability,

and leaders need to take the initiative to set that tone. Building an open and supportive environment involves building trust and relationships with employees, stakeholders and the public through effective communication, consultation, and collaboration. Stakeholders should be encouraged to provide feedback on policies and practices to build this environment.

“I put a lot of effort into creating an environment where people felt safe to ask questions. You know that there's no such thing as a ‘daft’ question. And the chief financial officer and the chief officer were super in terms of how they responded to those questions. Nobody felt defensive, they were open to challenge. They spent time explaining how things worked to people.” (Interviewee H, 2022).

This reflects the importance of leadership styles that give priority to transparency, co-operation, and inclusiveness. These values are essential in creating a trusting environment and promoting a culture of co-operation in governance. This type of approach encourages the participation of different stakeholders and ensures that everyone has a say in the decision-making process. The interview data show that H (2022) focused on creating a safe environment for questions by emphasizing there is no ‘daft’ question and to be willing to discuss issues non-defensively in order to build trust among stakeholders. This style helps to promote the participation of diverse stakeholders and ensures that everyone has a voice in the decision-making process. The leader's focus on creating a safe environment for questioning and the willingness of leaders to engage with questions in a non-defensive manner is essential for building trust among stakeholders.

Furthermore, the approach of H (2022) in creating an open and supportive environment can also help to promote innovation and creativity, as individuals are more likely to contribute their ideas and expertise in a supportive and safe environment. This leads to better decisions and outcomes, as different perspectives are discussed, and creative solutions explored (Heikkila and Isett, 2011). However, creating this environment is not always easy. This requires leaders to prioritize transparency and accountability. They must listen and respond to stakeholder needs and foster a culture of continuous improvement. Policies and practices that promote transparency, such as regular reporting and publication, are essential. In addition, fostering a culture of continuous learning and development ensures that people have the skills and knowledge to participate fully in decision-making (Bryson and Crosby, 2006).

In this context, it can be argued that in integrated governance, local political leaders have a crucial role in representing their constituents and working alongside diverse stakeholders to achieve effective outcomes. Effective communication with stakeholders is vital as it ensures that everyone is working towards shared goals and objectives. The establishment of clear lines of communication enables local political leaders to co-ordinate their efforts and avoid miscommunication, which can lead to ineffective

decision-making. This communication also allows leaders to gain a comprehensive understanding of the roles, responsibilities, and perspectives of each stakeholder involved. Such understanding is vital because it helps leaders to make informed decisions that consider the needs and interests of all parties involved (O'Leary and Bingham, 2008). For example, if a local political leader is aware of the concerns and perspectives of officers in their team, they can work to address these concerns in a way that is beneficial to both the team and their constituents.

The interview data reveal such complex decision-making process related to charges for health and social care toilet service. One instance highlights the divergent perspectives and interests of stakeholders, including the local elected member, the chief financial officer (CFO), and the IJB. Specifically, a local elected member challenged a charge linked to the closure of a toilet, "which had significant personal and community implications" (Interviewee B, 2022). The CFO and the IJB opposed removing the charge, creating a challenging decision for the council. The local political leader was tasked with navigating the intricacies of collaborative governance and arriving at a decision that considered the community's interests while balancing financial constraints.

"I made the decision that I would remove this, I supported this elected member in removing the charge. So that was a difficult decision, a discussion to have with my chief financial officer. Maybe she felt a little bit let down, it has been really difficult. Chief financial officer understood why I chose to do it. But it was first time I'd probably given into, that kind of feeling quite personally responsible. It was a difficult one." (Interviewee B, 2022)

This approach highlights the importance of being responsive to community needs and concerns, a critical element of integrated governance. However, it also reveals the different perspectives and interests of stakeholders, specifically the local elected member, the CFO, and the IJB. The elected member challenged a charge based on its emotional and sensitive impact on the affected community, while the CFO and IJB were concerned about its financial implications. This demonstrates how competing priorities can challenge local political leaders to balance the needs of multiple stakeholders.

Effective communication and decision-making are vital for integrated governance (O'Leary and Bingham, 2008; Emerson et al., 2012), as the leader had to navigate a difficult discussion with the CFO about the charge's removal. This required careful consideration of stakeholders' perspectives and interests, and clear communication to ensure that everyone understood the reasoning behind the decision. The CFO's possible feelings of let-down illustrate the challenges in managing stakeholder relationships in integrated governance to make difficult decisions and reach consensus. Finally, this emphasizes the emotional toll of local political leadership and decision-making in collaborative governance. The leader's sense of personal responsibility and the decision's difficulty suggest significant burdens on individuals in these roles that can complicate governance.

As local political leaders navigate the complex landscape of governing, managing budget/financial matters is often a challenge that requires trust, effective communication, and transparency. According to B,

“In managing economic matters, you just have to absolutely trust your chief financial officer. And you're assured that the information that they're giving because it is very important for everything, we can do to make that the delivery as lean and effective as it possibly can be. but it is difficult. It's difficult to come back to your elected member and colleagues to say we've overspent again.” (2022)

This approach highlights the complexities of integrated governance for local political leaders in several ways. The leader emphasizes the importance of trust in working with their chief financial officer to manage economic matters. However, this also underscores the difficulty of having to rely on others in decision-making processes and being accountable for their actions. Relying on senior officers to manage financial matters can be challenging, as it may result in overspending that the leader has to explain to elected members and colleagues. This situation shows that there can be a delicate balance between relying on experts and being held accountable for the decisions made. The leader must navigate this complexity in a manner that is both transparent and effective, while ensuring resources are allocated efficiently. Furthermore, this sheds light on the challenge of communicating about financial overspending with elected members and colleagues. This showcases the need for clear and open communication among stakeholders, as well as the challenges in managing competing interests and priorities. It also emphasizes the importance of ensuring the delivery of services is efficient and effective, which requires balancing the needs and perspectives of multiple stakeholders.

Integrated governance refers to a co-operative approach to address complex issues through the participation of various stakeholders, such as politicians, bureaucratic actors, community leaders, and civil society organizations (Ansell and Gash, 2008; Bryson and Crosby, 2006). However, maintaining a trustful relationship among these stakeholders as mentioned in the case of the toilet charge, can pose significant challenges for local political leaders. One of the main difficulties in that case was the differing goals and interests of the local political leaders and senior official. Each stakeholder tried to advance their own priorities, which can result in potential conflicts with the others. Therefore, local political leaders must navigate between these competing interests and find ways to balance the needs and demands of various stakeholders to maintain co-operation.

Power dynamics is another crucial challenge in any integrated governance arrangement. The power dynamics refer to the unequal distribution of power and influence among different stakeholders. In such arrangements, some stakeholders may have more power or influence than others. Local political leaders may hold significant authority over decision-making processes, which can result in tensions

with other stakeholders. They may feel that their voices are not being heard, and their needs are not being adequately addressed. A recent challenge faced by a local political leader in the context of Scottish H&SC context tells the same story of maintaining trust and power dynamics. The issue at hand is that some members of the IJB are required to stand down after serving two terms of three years, in accordance with the board's policy. The policy aims to bring new members onto the board to encourage fresh ideas and ways of thinking. However, the unions (one of the stakeholders) have complained about this policy, arguing that they should have the freedom to choose who sits on the board. According to local political leader (E, 2022):

“We had a recent instance where, from an IJB perspective, we followed the NHS board policy of serving two terms of three years, after which you stand down as an IJB member. We adopted that policy early on, and it is now time for some of these members to step down and make way for new members. This encourages new ideas, turnover on the board, fresh ways of thinking, and so on. However, we were challenged by the unions, who said that we cannot dictate who they put on the board.” (Interviewee E, 2021).

This illustrates a classic case of power dynamics and competing interests in collaborative governance. The IJB's policy on term limits for board members reflects a set of norms that prioritizes a regular turnover of the board, promotes diverse perspectives, and prevents the concentration of power among a few individuals. However, the unions contested this policy and argued that they should have the freedom to appoint who they wanted to the board. This highlights the tension that often exists between democratic values, such as participation and representation, and procedural rules designed to ensure effective and efficient decision-making.

Moreover, this situation illustrates the political nature of integrated governance, where stakeholders with different levels of power and interests compete to advance their agendas. The unions' challenge to the IJB policy reflects their desire to protect their interests and influence the governance process. Meanwhile, the local political leaders (who have voting power to transform the norm into law) insistence on enforcing the policy suggests that they are committed to upholding the rules of the game and ensuring that the board operates within a structured and transparent framework. According to E,

“We’ve reached an absolute agreement on this one. In June of this coming year, we will do a whole board review of the integration scheme, the scheme of delegation, the governance structure and all that kind of stuff. I will now bring it back into June for a talk review, but you will abide by that review. And the option would say that it applies to everyone, me included as chair. It wasn’t exclusive of anybody, that policy included everyone on the board apart from the full-time employees. So, any member of the board that was elected voluntarily by choice has to go through that process. These are the rules that you are abiding by, and if you don’t want to abide by these rules, that is a choice for you to make. It was a difficult

conversation because they saw me as being a bit dictatorial and coercing them to do this. I said, it's written down, these are the rules that we engage by." (Interviewee E, 2022)

Tensions between the unions and the IJB are evident regarding the policy enforced by the local political leader. The unions saw the leader's actions as dictatorial and coercive while the IJB believed that they were merely abiding by the agreed rules. This situation highlights the potential for conflict when elected officials hold significant decision-making authority, which may leave other stakeholders feeling unheard or their needs unmet. Being democratically elected, local political leaders are responsible for decisions that can impact the lives of many community members. In this case, some stakeholders perceive the leader's authority as stifling the input and influence of others, particularly the trade unions with conflicting perspectives and interests. The leader is enforcing a policy mandating term limits for members of an IJB, which is causing tensions with union representatives seeking more influence. Although the political leader is acting within the bounds of the policy to maintain a fair process, it is viewed as dictatorial and coercive by some stakeholders. The leader's authoritative and assertive approach is evident as they have a clear understanding of the term limits policy and are willing to enforce it despite pushback from the unions. Moreover, the leader is committed to reviewing and adapting the policy to ensure that it is equitable and applicable to all members. The local political leaders have advantage of being voting member of the IJB who can amend the rule as compared to trade unions (as stakeholder) which is not.

It is important to note here that the conflict between the unions and the local political leader highlights the significance of accountability and legitimacy in integrated governance. For the political leader (E, 2022) commitment to fairness and equality is evident in their argument that everyone, including themselves, must follow the rules. However, the analysis of the union's challenge to the policy reveals the need for effective mechanisms of the accountability that allow stakeholders to express their concerns and grievances in a fair and transparent manner. Such mechanisms are critical in ensuring that all stakeholders have a meaningful role in the decision-making process and that the governance system remains legitimate and trustworthy. Therefore, this example stresses the importance of establishing clear and agreed-upon policies and guidelines for all stakeholders involved in integrated governance. While conflicting opinions and interests may arise, having established guidelines can help to minimize conflicts and provide a framework for decision-making. In complex governance settings, collaboration among stakeholders is necessary for achieving effective and sustainable solutions to community issues. This often involves balancing competing interests and finding common ground, which can be challenging when power imbalances exist. Therefore, local political leaders are expected to listen to diverse perspectives and

work collaboratively with stakeholders to find mutually beneficial solutions that serve the community as a whole.

Conclusion

Local political leaders in Health and Social care face a range of challenges that require them to be adaptable and flexible in their leadership style to respond to varying political contexts. The dynamic nature of politics requires leaders to have situational awareness and the ability to modify their leadership style to meet the needs of the situation at hand. The situational leadership style acknowledges that there is no one-size-fits-all approach to leadership and that effective leaders must assess the situation and the skills and capabilities of the individuals involved before deciding on the most appropriate leadership style to adopt. In the political context of Health and Social Care, local political leaders possess situational leadership skills that enable them to navigate the complex governance and regulatory constraints that are inherent in the system. They are also expected to balance limited resources with the diverse needs of their constituents, which requires them to employ a range of leadership styles and approaches. Local political leaders are found to be using different leadership approaches in varying degrees, depending on the situation i.e., dealing with structures, agendas, committees, institutionalization of leadership, power imbalances and competing interests among others.

Therefore, local political leaders in Health and Social care are versatile in their leadership style, adjusting it to the situation at hand. During a crisis such as a pandemic, leaders may choose a co-producing approach, involving the community and other stakeholders in the decision-making process to tackle the most important concerns of the community. Alternatively, when time is of the essence, and quick action is necessary, leaders may adopt a more direct style. Transparency and accountability are encouraged, and inclusivity is promoted to achieve consensus and demonstrate commitment. In most cases, the leaders interviewed indicated that they prioritize service delivery and adopt a supportive approach to guide and motivate IJB team members. Their strategies further empower others by creating a sense of shared responsibility and a more inclusive decision-making process. As such, situational leadership has become an essential part of the Health and Social Care system, allowing local political leaders to address complex problems and work towards effective solutions. To fully comprehend situational political leadership in Health and Social Care, it is crucial to examine how it relates to contextual factors that can impact the approach of local political leaders. By taking into account five varying contextual factors, namely economy and finance, political-administrative relationship, partisanship, geographical considerations (such as the size of

the IJB area and its urban or rural nature) and the expectations of the frontline workforce, a more nuanced understanding of situational leadership strategies can be achieved, of including democratic, servant, transformational, facilitative, and laissez faire.

Chapter 7

Contextual Analysis of Local Political Leadership in Scottish Health and Social Care

Introduction

Chapter 6 explored the complex and dynamic Health and Social Care Integration system in Scotland, emphasizing the crucial role of situational leadership strategies employed by local political leaders to overcome challenges. The chapter explored the many and different leadership styles, strategies, and characteristics that local political leaders use when navigating the complexities of integrated governance.

This chapter builds on that analysis and highlights the impact of contextual factors on the situational leadership approach of local political leaders in the H&SCI system. Five contextual factors were identified: economy and finance, political-administrative relationship, partisanship, geographical characteristics of the local authority (urban/rural, population size of the local authority area) and the expectations of the frontline workforce. The analysis evaluates how each of these factors can influence situational leadership style, such as how economic and financial factors can impact decision-making or how the expectations of frontline workforce can shape the leadership approach. The aim of this chapter is to provide a nuanced understanding of situational leadership strategies in the H&SCI system and identify which leadership styles are most effective in different political contexts and situations.

This chapter utilises evidence from two sources including documents and interviews. The documentary evidence is used to complement and triangulate the interviews. The documents provide much of evidence for the relevance of the contextual factors on the IJBs, such as economy and finance, political-administrative relationship, partisanship, geographical considerations (such as the size of the IJB area and its urban or rural nature) and the expectations of the frontline workforce. The documents show how these factors were manifested and experienced in different IJBs, and how they posed challenges and opportunities for the IJBs. The interviews capitalized on this evidence and explored how the local leaders perceived and responded to these factors, and how they exercised their leadership roles and styles in the IJBs. The interviews provided more depth and detail into the phenomenon and revealed the diversity and richness of the responses and experiences of the local leaders. By merging the documents and interviews data, the research aimed to provide a comprehensive and in-depth analysis of the phenomenon, and to address the research objectives and questions. Ultimately, this thesis contributes to the fields of public administration, leadership, and situational leadership theory.

7.1 The influence of financial and economic conditions

The IJB's financial governance is complex, involving multiple funding sources with their own rules and limitations. The Scottish Government is the primary funder, allocating funds to health boards and a proportion of funds to social care for local councils, who then allocate funds to the IJB. IJBs possess full authority over resource allocation and deliver delegated services. Their dual accountability to the council and NHS board is enforced through voting membership and transparent public reporting (Joint Act, 2014; Audit, 2020). Mandated by the Joint Act (2014), IJBs annually prepare audited accounts, ensuring financial sustainability and ongoing service transformation amidst fiscal pressures across Scotland. For instance, the financial pressures faced by the IJB area F, as documented in meeting minutes and audit reports, are evident in the predicted overspend for Social Care and the underspend for health in 2015/16 (IJB area F minutes, 8 Feb 2016) and with planned savings of £19.555 million for 2019/20. These financial difficulties have prompted councillors to engage with the Scottish Government to secure additional funding and revisit budget allocations (IJB area F minutes, 15 Mar, 2017). The content analysis reveals that councillors are aware of the challenges posed by limited resources and are actively seeking solutions to maintain service provision (IJB area F minutes, 15 Mar, 2017; Audit Scotland, 2020 c).

Echoing the concerns raised in the documentary evidence, local political leader (F, 2022) from the mixed deprived IJB area F highlights the impact of the government's funding allocation practices on the IJB's ability to provide integrated care. The interviewee notes that 'the government's increased funding for health and decreased funding for councils has restricted council's choices in allocating funds.' One of the key objectives of the IJBs' establishment was to merge Health and Social Care budgets to achieve more integrated care (Joint Act 2014). However, despite the efforts by local partners, Health and Social Care budgets remain separate, leading to limited choices in fund allocation. According to the same political leader (F, 2022)-

"The other issue on the budget is that it still largely operates separately, as you know, that the council gives money for the things the Council delivers on behalf of the IJB, and the Health Board gives money for the things the Health Board delivers on behalf the IJB. Those budgets are still effectively separate." (Interviewee F, 2022)

The division of funding in the Health and Social Care system can lead to challenges in integrated governance, such as fragmentation of services, difficulty in co-ordination and inefficiencies, ultimately resulting in poorer outcomes for service users. Audit Scotland (2015) have identified this as a key issue. However, local political leaders (e.g., F, 2022) highlight the attempts being made to merge these budgets by examining unscheduled care and reducing unnecessary hospital admissions. Despite attempts to merge budgets, the budgets for health and social care remain separate. Most of the Health

Board's funding is still directed and ringfenced by the Scottish Government, reducing flexibility in how funds are spent (Interviewee F, 2022).

Furthermore, Interview analysis reveals that Local councils in Scotland face financial difficulties in providing social care services due to their reliance on central government funds (Interviewee C, 2022; Interviewee F, 2022, Interviewee A, 2021). Despite being the primary funder, this often falls short, leading to significant financial pressures on councils (Interviewee C, 2022). The documentary evidence confirmed these issues, as it showed that the IJB C area had experienced a significant funding gap and a high level of overspending, and that it had developed a financial recovery plan and a medium-term financial strategy to address them. The IJB's financial woes have been widely documented by several sources, including Audit Scotland's report (2020), IJB minutes from 2016 and 2018, and Azets' report (2020). For instance, Audit Scotland's report (2020) states: "The IJB has reported a deficit in each of the four years since it was established". This persistent financial strain has also been echoed in the IJB minutes, which reveal that councillors have consistently raised concerns about the IJB's precarious financial situation and demanded transparency. In addition to concerns about the IJB's financial situation, the IJB minutes (20 January 2017) documented that councillors have consistently raised concerns about the financial arrangements and demanded transparency. They noted the alarming financial position as of November 2016, indicating a substantial overspend of £5.4 million. Recognizing the potential for further financial turmoil, the minutes noted that "NHS would cover the projected overspend, based on the assumption that NHS would achieve financial stability within the current fiscal year" (IJB area C minutes, 20 Jan 2017 p., 3). This conditional arrangement underscored the councillors' awareness of the inherent risks and challenges associated with the IJB's financial reliance on NHS and their determination to hold NHS accountable for their commitments. Moreover, the councillors demanded that "NHS conduct a comprehensive review of prescribing practices at the local level to address the underlying causes of the IJB's financial troubles" (p., 3).

Local political leaders are thus expected to balance limited resources with increasing demand for social care services, while navigating a complex landscape. For instance, the local council receiving the highest per capita funding still struggles with an underlying structural deficit of £15 to 20 million each year. This situation puts pressure on local political leaders to balance limited resources with increasing demand for social care services. Local political leader (C, 2021) from mixed deprived area noted the difficulty of navigating this complex landscape:

"The financial challenges are a restriction. Someone mentioned yesterday that they would rather spend more time agonizing over how to balance the budget rather than how to invest in available services. I would add to that. Our local council receives the most per capita of any council in Scotland, but the Scottish government continues to squeeze services, creating

an underlying structural deficit. The health and social care budget consistently have a gap of £15 to 20 million pounds per year, which remains a challenge to balance.” (Interviewee C, 2022).

The limited resources available to local political leaders may impact their leadership approach, as the government's continuous reduction of services suggests limited autonomy. The statement from C (2022) "balancing the budget remains a challenge no matter what measures are taken" indicates that the local council lacks control over its financial resources and cannot manage the funding shortfall independently. The local council's reliance on the Scottish Government for social care funding restricts the local political leadership's ability to manage finances and limits their decision-making aligned with community needs. Evidence from this study suggests that the persistent gap in the Health and Social care budget poses a significant challenge for leaders in balancing the budget and delivering essential services. For example, C (2022) notes these difficulties:

“Last year, we didn't set a balanced budget because of the finances, but because we were not willing to make cuts. Through working with the council and NHS, we managed to plug the gap through the year through other means. We have every likelihood that this will happen again this year. However, the ironic thing is that because we have come through COVID, we have had a bit of a crisis in terms of staffing. The funding allocated to us is one-off funding, which limits our ability to do something sustainable in the long term. We may get one-off fixes over the next 12 months or so, and we can use them well by investing in new technology, training staff, or hiring temporary or fixed-contract staff. However, we won't be able to start up a new service that will last forever.”

These insights reveal a pragmatic and cautious leadership approach towards managing financial constraints. The leader acknowledges the challenge of balancing the budget while delivering necessary services and recognizes the limitations of budgetary constraints. They also point out the central government's role in providing one-off funding, indicating a need for a more sustainable approach to funding H&SCI. Collaboration with other actors, such as the council and NHS, is emphasized for integrated governance, but one-off funding for COVID-related crisis management limits sustainable changes. Interviewee C (2022) also raised concerns about outsourcing service delivery, suggesting the need for improvement in health and social care matters.

“From my personal perspective, more of our services need to be hosted with the council instead of external providers. Our IJB heavily relies on external providers who may abandon services, leaving the council to take over. We need a balance of in-house services, but we cannot afford to recruit staff long-term. This limits us and makes us vulnerable to market failures, where companies go bust or cease assets, leaving people without services. We have to pick up on that burden.” (Interviewee C, 2022).

The local political leader's innovative approach to integrated governance is as a result of the financial constraints and dependence on the Scottish Government. They propose alternative solutions such as shifting towards more in-house services, despite financial constraints, challenging

the status quo and demonstrating determination and vision. By advocating for a balance between in-house and external services, the leader also demonstrates a commitment to improving service quality and public experience while recognizing the risks of relying solely on external providers. However, financial constraints limit the ability to recruit staff on a long-term basis, indicating an understanding of the practical realities of integrated governance. One senior official C1, (2022) has witnessed this leader's knowledge and commitment to H&SCI. The Scottish Government's uneven distribution of resources between the health sector and local councils exacerbates the funding challenges for integrated governance making it difficult to achieve a balance between in-house and external services. Therefore, while the establishment of IJBs is a step towards integrated governance, it may not fully address the challenges of separate funding.

Moving from the innovative approach of the local political leader to the practical realities of the IJB, it is important to note that the IJB's financial dependence on the Scottish Government means that they are expected to identify a plan for making efficiency savings. While the IJB has an obligation to "break even," the Health Board approach differs in that they do not need to agree on all efficiency savings before setting their budget. This difference in approach can cause uneasiness among elected members who are used to different ways of doing things within the local authority and the IJB setting. For example, one senior official G1, (2021) from a deprived area highlighted the need for effective communication and collaboration between the IJB and the local authority to address these differences and ensure a smooth and effective approach to financial planning and decision-making.

"As an IJB, we have a duty to break even, but there are challenges with our and financial planning and efficiency arrangements that differ from the local authority's processes. The local authority sets its budget and efficiency savings first, while we identify a plan for making savings afterwards. This can make some elected members uncomfortable as they are used to starting with a balanced budget. The demand pressures and challenges we face within the partnership can lead to tensions and frustrations from elected members, who receive complaints from constituents about delays in treatment and other issues." (Interviewee G1, 2021).

This statement highlights the complexity of financial management in integrated governance, particularly the differences in financial planning and efficiency planning arrangements between the local authority and the IJB. These differences can create tensions between elected members and lead to challenges around the IJB table, causing complaints from constituents about treatment delays because of financial pressures and leading to political frustrations. The documentary analysis paints a stark picture of the IJB's dire financial situation and corroborates the concerns expressed in the interview analysis regarding the service users' demand challenges faced by the IJB area G. The IJB's annual report and accounts for 2019/20 reveal that the IJB is grappling with "extremely

challenging financial conditions". These challenges are exacerbated by the IJB's reliance on non-recurring in-year savings, which are unsustainable in the long run. The IJB's financial pressures are also exacerbated by the financial struggles of its partner organizations, which are unable to provide the IJB with the support it needs (Thornton, 2020). In 2020/21, the IJB was forced to deliver £22.6 million in savings, and the NHS was required to contribute an additional £4.774 million following a budget overspend. Elected members will face difficult decisions about services in this challenging context (Audit Scotland, 2018 b). These financial constraints are compounded by high expectations from service users and citizens, as well as a national shortage of social workers.

However, the senior official's willingness to engage in open communication and collaboration demonstrates a commitment to dealing with the complexities of integrated governance. Moreover, their emphasis on breaking even and finding ways to address financial gaps indicates a commitment to responsible financial management. Therefore, integrated governance requires effective communication, collaboration, and financial management strategies to address these complexities and deliver high-quality services.

In this context, responsible stewardship is a critical concern for local political leaders in integrated governance, as emphasized by a leader from a less deprived IJB area. Healthcare services are vulnerable to budgetary constraints, making effective budget optimization and resource allocation essential for quality service delivery and a positive working environment for healthcare professionals (Buck et al., 2013). Interviewee A (2022) recognizes this importance, advocating for responsible financial management and resource optimization. Thus, prioritizing efficient service delivery over increasing funding is crucial for sustainable financial management in integrated governance.

"The economy plays a significant role in controlling finances in healthcare facilities. Budget cuts can lead to limiting the use of expensive drugs or changes in healthcare practices due to a shortage of doctors or nurses. There are primary care practices that are closed because they haven't got enough doctors basically, but they've probably got enough budget to hire in locums probably, but you can't run a primary care service support with locums. Can you, it just doesn't work. However, optimizing spending is critical for good feedback from doctors so that they would like to work in the area and improving the quality of healthcare service. Running a surplus in the contingency fund is a positive sign. To make the best use of limited resources, healthcare facilities need to think creatively and redirect resources efficiently. For example, repurposing an old people's hospital as a facility for mental and other health issues or providing respite for those with dementia. Efficiently redirecting resources requires thinking outside the box." (Interviewee A, 2021).

The above statement highlights some of the important leadership choices, the amount of work or the approach to playing around with priorities to manage H&SC services. Interviewee A (2021)

demonstrates the knowledge and importance of continuous strategic thinking to lead trade-offs between staffing levels, budgets and limited drug usage. The reputation of the IJB area is critical for retaining and recruiting staff, and A (2021) recognises the interconnectedness of stakeholders in the healthcare system and the importance of collaboration and co-ordination to address economic challenges. Feedback loops ensure informed decisions that consider the needs of all parties involved and the leader understands the significance of stable economic and financial conditions to retain skilled professionals and maintain a positive reputation, which requires strategic thinking and planning. Economic stability may contribute to the leader's ability to think strategically. Without it, leaders may lack resources and the flexibility to focus on retaining skilled professionals and maintaining a positive reputation.

Further, this research suggests that local political leaders in less, mixed, and more deprived IJBs heavily rely on skilled officers to navigate complex fiscal landscapes and deal with financial constraints (Interviewee I, 2022; Interviewee B, 2022; Interviewee H, 2022). This trend is likely to be prevalent across Scotland, where Health and Social Care public bodies must oversee finances and spending. The officers play a critical role in examining quarterly spending on Health and Social care and raising concerns if necessary, underscoring the importance of transparency and accountability in integrated governance (Scottish Government, 2019). Effective collaboration and communication between stakeholders are essential for addressing emerging issues and challenges. Local political leader A (2021) recognizes the importance of officers in ensuring responsible financial management and emphasizes the need for stakeholders to work together to overcome financial constraints and improve service delivery.

“The chief officer is responsible for looking at finances, examining quarterly spending on drugs and other aspects of care, and raising red flags if things don't look right. The IJB then needs to adjust how they perform their services. At the end of the day, this is always about money, but it's also about providing the best and most efficient service. Simply throwing money at a problem is not the most effective approach.” (Interviewee A, 2022).

This style of leadership could be seen as one that is willing to work collaboratively with stakeholders to find solutions to complex issues. The data show that the role of the chief officer in examining finances and raising red flags if necessary, indicates a willingness to engage in open and transparent dialogue about the challenges faced by the Health and Social care system, further suggesting a willingness to listen to and act on feedback from their Integrated Joint Board team.

In the context of integrated governance, the “trust” (Interviewee B, 2022) that local political leaders place in officers to deliver on their financial goals suggests that officers are seen as important intermediaries who translate political priorities into practical and actionable strategies (Interviewee

H, 2022). It suggests further that the leadership styles of these leaders are more collaborative and co-operative. This is because the leaders are relying on officers with professional expertise in financial matters to help achieve their political goals, rather than trying to micromanage or take control of the economic decision-making process themselves. According to I (2021)-

“You need to rely on officers, that’s their job. Sometimes you got a criticism that officers running council. I don't know one councillor I would prefer to be the chief social work officer or one I'd prefer to be the head of finance. That’s the officer’ job, they have been doing it for thirty years.” (Interviewee I, 2021).

The reliance of local political leaders on their officers in less, mixed, and more deprived IJBs for maintaining good economic conditions indicates a decentralized leadership approach. This approach leads to more efficient decision-making processes, as officers are equipped to handle complex financial landscapes and constraints (Scottish Government, 2019). However, this does not imply a passive role for local political leaders in financial matters. Instead, they play an active role in scrutinizing decisions made by officers, ensuring transparency and accountability. The documentary analysis of IJB area (I) audit reports and meeting minutes provides evidence of effective financial management by IJB political leaders. For instance, the IJB's positive overall balance forecast by the end of March 2020 stands as a testament to the careful monitoring and stewardship of finances by IJB leadership (Audit Scotland, 2018). The content analysis further reveals that local political leaders have proactively sought clarity on responsibility for overspending. In a notable instance, one councillor questioned officers about the inconsistencies in the budget report, while another highlighted the need to review the £2 million overspend caused by outfit placements, which are placements of patients outside the IJB area (IJB area I minutes, 13 June 2018 p., 512).

This emphasis on accountability is further evident in their request for information on economic decisions from stakeholders, such as the impact of changes in Alcohol and Drugs Prevention targets on the IJB's spending budgets (IJB area I minutes, 20 Mar, 2015). However, critiques may still argue that this relationship is not without its challenges, as officers may have considerable influence over policy decisions, potentially leading to a conflict of interest. To ensure transparency and accountability in decision-making, political leaders might be expected to develop and maintain a financially critical attitude towards the financial decisions and recommendations provided by officers.

In addition, the commitment of the IJB leadership to maintain good economic conditions and find innovative ways to deliver services without compromising patient care suggests a willingness to adapt, experiment, take calculated risks, and continuously evaluate. According to H (2022)

“Good economic conditions are the result of having an excellent chief financial officer and real commitment to and no surprises agenda. Better economic conditions are the result of hardworking diligence by the senior team and looking at as many ways as possible, but don't impact patient care or redesigning services.”

The collaborative efforts of the CFO driving cost reduction initiatives and the senior team focusing on service delivery redesign highlight the importance of working together to address economic challenges. The emphasis on the "no surprises" agenda shows that local political leaders in Scotland prioritize avoiding unforeseen financial shocks that could disrupt service delivery or lead to budget shortfalls. Therefore, ongoing monitoring, evaluation, and learning are essential for maintaining stable economic conditions and delivering quality health and social care services. According to H (2022) "looking at different ways of delivering services based in people's homes rather than in old expensive hospitals, and spending less on building maintenance, for example," is critical for improving economic conditions without negatively impacting patient care.

7.2 The Influence of Partisanship

The findings of the study suggest that the situational leadership style adopted by local political leaders in the Health and Social Care sector are shaped by their responsibilities towards their political parties. This understanding of the interplay between political party responsibilities and leadership styles has implications for policy implementation, especially in the context of the National Care Service in Scotland. The National Care Service (NCS) is a proposed reform of the social care system in Scotland, which aims to ensure everyone has access to consistently high-quality care and support across the country. The NCS will be established by the National Care Service (Scotland) Bill (forthcoming), which will make Scottish Ministers accountable for adult social care and transfer some responsibilities from local authorities to a new national body. Given the concerns about its impact on localism, local political leaders face the challenge of reconciling support for a national policy with the need to protect the interests of their community. Balancing these competing demands require local political leaders to navigate complex political landscapes and make difficult decisions. According to local political leader (B, 2022)-

“You are a member of political party; you believe their ethos. National Care service, I suppose, regular example, something that I am very invested in, and I believe absolutely is the right direction for health and social care in Scotland. But it has been contentious for a lot of people. I think a lot of people feel, NCS have issues with localism and that is well founded. I am very supportive of my priority and, the direction is taking health and social care in, but also very aware of any protective. when it comes to my locality and showing exactly that, get it right from my community. So that has been difficult because, I agree in a lot of the proposals on a national level, like workforce planning, training etc. but I absolutely agree with

issues related localism, because we get that all the time here, it's that central built bias." (Interviewee B, 2022).

Interviewee B (2022) acknowledges the tension between supporting the NCS and protecting the interests of their local community, demonstrating an inclusive leadership style that prioritizes community needs. The need to balance national and local priorities is a common challenge in integrated governance, which requires strategic decision-making. The documentary analysis of the IJB B area revealed a tumultuous past, marked by political instability and a lack of direction. These challenges had hindered progress and placed a heavy burden on senior officers (Audit Scotland, 2020 d). However, the analysis also uncovered a glimmer of hope: the emergence of a more strategic and collaborative leadership style among the IJB B area's political leaders. This new approach enabled them to unite across party lines, gain support for key decisions, and reduce the administrative burden on senior officers (Audit Scotland, 2020 d).

In addition, Local political leader E (2022) adopts a non-partisan approach that prioritizes the well-being of individuals and the population despite political pressures surrounding funding.

"I suppose from my perspective with the board, I try to make it non-political. And again, it does get political, and usually that is around funding. But I try to say to people, this is not about politics. This is about what is good for the population, for the individual, with a people focused organization. It is what is best for them with yes, sometimes it does ground against the political view. I think we have just got to work that one through from my old party perspective." (Interviewee, E, 2022).

The SNP leader's commitment to achieving the IJB's goals and clarity in defining objectives highlights their leadership prowess. By emphasizing the people-focused approach and the importance of making decisions based on what is best for them, local political leader E aims to build trust and common ground among different political parties. Furthermore, their willingness to work through political differences and find a way forward suggests a collaborative and inclusive approach, which is crucial when different political parties may have divergent views and priorities. Through constructive dialogue and finding common ground, local political leaders can work towards achieving shared goals and outcomes, transcending party-political divides to emerge as inspirational leaders. Such leadership indicates a situational leadership phenomenon, adapting leadership style to the situation to manage competing interests and achieve successful outcomes. Effective leadership is crucial for achieving collective goals in politics, where conflicting interests are at play, and cultivating relationships across party lines is paramount to achieving meaningful progress (Elgie, 2015). The senior official D1 (2021) from IJB D area has expressed similar views in terms of achieving the best result from establishing political consensus particularly regarding financial issues. Furthermore, the IJB Area D's documentary analysis painted a picture of unity and

collaboration, as its members transcended political boundaries in their commitment to serving their communities (IJB area D minutes, 16 Nov 2016), which indicates that they had a leadership, which emphasizes the vision, values, and culture of the organization (Bolman and Deal, 2017). They also demonstrated that they were able to reverse decisions on cuts and minimize savings, which indicates that they had a s leadership, which emphasizes the goals, roles, and policies of the organization (IJB area D minutes, 2 May 2018).

The ability of local political leaders to transcend party-political divides is particularly relevant when analysing the influence of political parties on local political leaders, as discussed in the evidence provided by Interviewee (F, 2022). The interview data sheds light on the ideological similarities and differences between the Scottish National Party and the Labour Party, with the latter highlighting the former's social democratic tendencies and fundamental disagreement on independence. Though differences may exist in resource allocation, there may not be significant differences in approach to health and social care. The importance of understanding the broader political landscape and party ideologies when analysing the decisions and actions of local political leaders is underscored by the following quote. It highlights the challenges of navigating party politics while also working towards common goals, particularly in contexts where effective governance requires the formation of coalitions and alliances.

“I think one has to remember anyway, some of my colleagues might not like me saying this, but the Scottish National Party is broadly, not wholly broadly a social democratic party, as is the Labour Party, disagree fundamentally on an issue of independence. I think some parts of the SNP nationally may pay more attention to rural issues, for example, or at least to spread money more in that direction. But I'm not convinced that there are big differences between the parties in approach to health and social care.” (Interviewee F, 2022)

Interviewee F (2022) acknowledges political differences and tensions, especially in the context of party politics and ideological beliefs, indicating a situational leadership style. The interviewee also demonstrates an inclusive leadership style by recognizing different perspectives and finding common ground. They suggest that leaders can prioritize the community's needs over partisan politics by acknowledging that there may not be significant differences in the approach to health and social care between political parties. This approach emphasizes the importance of building relationships and trust across party lines and finding ways to work constructively through disagreements, essential when different parties have different priorities and interests. The IJB's consistent demonstration of effective leadership through constructive relationships between officers and elected members since 2014 was supported by the content analysis data (Audit, 2018). However, the data also highlighted the challenges posed by changes in councillor engagement and scrutiny, stemming from shifts in political control and the election of new councillors. Despite these

challenges, senior staff had adapted to the change and relationships between councillors and senior staff remained positive through regular engagement (Audit Scotland, 2018). This implies that the senior staff also adopted a flexible and adaptive leadership style, which enabled them to cope with the changes in political membership and maintain positive relationships.

Focusing on policy similarities and goals can help identify areas of potential agreement and collaboration, leading to more effective decision-making and policy implementation by building on shared interests and priorities rather than differences (Hallsworth, 2011). However, collaborative governance presents challenges, and local political leaders need to navigate complex political terrain while balancing competing priorities and interests when working towards shared goals. For instance, while the interviewee acknowledges the potential differences in attention given to rural issues, they suggest that funding decisions and other constraints may limit the extent to which parties can prioritize specific areas.

Despite the potential for collaboration and finding common ground, conflicting views between political parties remain a challenge for local political leaders. Political parties often have different priorities and interests and navigating these differences can be difficult when working towards shared goals. Funding decisions are particularly contentious, with parties favouring different areas and communities. For instance, the SNP local political leader, H, (2022) provided evidence of political party influence on decision-making, discussing COVID relief funding allocation by the Scottish Government to the Integrated Joint Board. The Conservative and Independent leadership at the council made the ultimate decision to allocate the funds, with the SNP leader expressing dissatisfaction at the way it was handled. This shows how political ideologies and priorities can play a significant role in shaping how parties approach policy issues, which can create further obstacles to collaboration. According to H,

“The last couple of years we have had a lot of investment for the Scottish government in terms of COVID money. The Cabinet Secretary for Finance gave just over one and a half million pounds, additional funding to the IJB, but that was funnelled to council administration. And the Conservative and Independent leadership at the Council decided in its infinite wisdom, to keep just over a million of it. And the IJB only got half a million and that is why the Cabinet Secretary ended up ring fencing money to go to IJB. I was really upset about the way council spent money, and I got my MSP to raise it in parliament and it was raised at COSLA as well. Now, local authorities moan about that but it's a way of protecting that funding to make sure that it goes to the people who need it most.” (Interviewee H, 2022).

Interviewee H (2022) exhibits a proactive approach to dealing with conflicting views among political parties in integrated governance. Despite expressing dissatisfaction with the funding decisions made by the Conservative and Independent leadership at the council, the leader did not just

complain or criticize their actions. Instead, they raised the issue with their MSP and brought it to the attention of the Scottish Parliament and COSLA. This shows how local political leaders can leverage their positions of influence to advocate for their communities' interests and hold other parties accountable for their decisions. H's approach further highlights the significance of prioritizing the needs of the community over partisan politics. They emphasize how the council's decision to retain a significant portion of the COVID funding for themselves, rather than allocating it to the IJB, hindered the necessary relief to those in need. Interviewee H's (2022) actions to encourage ring-fence funding for the IJB, despite local authorities' complaints, illustrate how leaders can take bold measures to ensure funding is utilized for its intended purpose of benefiting the community.

In contrast, a local political leader's approach also promotes centralization in dealing with conflicting views between political parties in integrated governance. They expressed dissatisfaction with the Conservative and Independent leadership at the council, who kept over £one million of funding intended for the IJB, creating tensions and disagreements between political parties. To address this issue, the leader raised the matter with their MSP and brought it to the attention of Parliament and COSLA. By referring the matter to national authorities, they attempted to centralize decision-making and promote accountability in the allocation of funds, ensuring that the money benefits the community. This approach may promote collaboration and common ground between political parties by setting clear guidelines and standards for decision-making. However, it may be perceived as encroaching on local political leaders' autonomy and risk alienating other political parties, creating divisions. While it is important to address issues and protect community interests, it is also crucial to maintain positive relationships and foster collaboration with other political parties.

Despite the contested benefits of centralization in governance, some Scottish local political leaders strongly oppose central government interference in planning and delivering Health and Social Care services at the local level. They argue that central government policies fail to account for their unique communities' needs and circumstances, resulting in ineffective or inefficient service delivery. One growing concern for policymakers and healthcare providers is the provision of care homes; as the elderly population increases, demand for high-quality care grows, putting significant pressure on local primary care services. In this context, Interviewee A (2021) highlights how some care homeowners in Scotland leverage their political connections to secure planning permission, despite objections from local authorities. This is exemplified in the case of a care homeowner who overturned a local planning committee's decision to deny permission to build a new care home because of concerns about the impact on local primary care.

“The issue with care homes is that they require a significant amount of primary care. There is a particular care home that is being constructed, whose owner, he is big mates with Scottish Government. He believes in Independence. The local planning department, planning group, and planning committee initially rejected the proposal for the new care home due to concerns about the strain it would put on local care facilities. The proposal involved the construction of 80 additional rooms, accommodating more elderly residents who would have added to the burden on local primary care services. The owner appealed to the Scottish government's reporter's department, which subsequently approved the proposal without any issues. However, the care home was not able to be delivered as doctors were not available.” (Interviewee A, 2021).

In this case the local political leader adopts an assertive leadership style by expressing strong opposition to the construction of a new care home, citing concerns about the potential impact on local primary care. They also draw attention to the influence of political connections on the decision-making process, as the owner of the care home in question is "big mates with Scottish government" and "believes in independence" indicating that the local political leader may be facing the influence of the SNP, and that the care homeowner secured planning permission through connections with the Scottish Government, despite objections from the local council. This highlights how power dynamics and political alliances outside formal structures may pose a challenge to the local political leader's emphasis on local autonomy and can affect integrated governance. The leader emphasizes the unique needs and circumstances of their community, indicating a focus on local autonomy and control. However, local leaders' focus on their communities may clash with the SNP's centralized approach, potentially hindering collaboration. Integrated governance necessitates working with multiple stakeholders, including local planning and the Scottish Government, to balance competing interests. The growing demand for accessible care for older people and concerns over new care homes' impact on primary care services present challenges. Achieving an optimal outcome requires careful negotiation and compromise.

In conclusion, partisanship has a significant influence on local political leadership, shaping the way leaders exercise their leadership. The findings suggest that the influence of political parties can be manifested in different ways, including the distribution of resources, the framing of issues, and the shaping of policy priorities. While local political leaders may have some discretion in how they exercise their leadership, their actions are ultimately constrained by the expectations and demands of their party affiliations. This reality can create challenges for local political leaders who may need to balance the competing demands of their party, their constituents, and the broader community.

7.3 The Influence of Political-administrative Relationships

This theme highlights the crucial role of quality of relationship in fostering positive or nuanced (challenging) relationships between local political leaders and senior officials in the Health and Social Care sector. The quality of the relationship between political leaders and officers can significantly influence the leadership style of the former. Trust, respect, transparency, polite behaviour clear communication and acknowledgement of strengths are factors that facilitate positive relationships, resulting in a collaborative and participative leadership style. This case suggests that the chief officer's approach is significant in shaping this relationship, with mutual respect, openness, discussion, and constructive criticism being crucial. Trust with officers is also essential in making better-informed decisions and navigating the complexities of the decision-making process. Interviewee F (2022) experienced this first-hand, with their relationship with the second chief officer being better than the first due to their openness to discussion.

“The chief officer's role is important. The first and second chief officers were different, with the second being better as they were more open to discussion. The first chief officer was focused on making progress, but sometimes this made discussions difficult. The current chief officer may expect agreement with proposed plans, which is not unusual. The relationship with officers is good, and there is no perceived tension at meetings.” (Interviewee F,2022).

Local political leader A (2021) confirms that building trust with officers is essential for effective decision-making.

“The relationship with officers is based on teamwork and polite behaviour. It's a good working relationship and that's the way I have always worked, my professional life in the oil industry, and now in the council, trust is built over time, leading to a good working relationship where information is freely shared than, otherwise. There are challenges as well. There are challenges with how you actually manual your primary care functions, where you get the doctors from to run infirmary. There are challenges where you get, other professional staff, and how you actually physically run the practices, but we don't tend to see that, we just see the higher level, but sometimes a high level can be quite useful.” (Interviewee A, 2022).

The local political leader makes the case that building trust with officers by demonstrating polite behaviour and promoting teamwork, leveraging their prior experience in both the oil industry and council is important. The senior official A1 (2022) also shared similar views about their constructive and positive relationships with local political leaders. This aligns with the principles of collaborative governance, which emphasizes cultivating positive relationships with local senior officials (Rhodes, 1997, 2017; Fenwick, Miller, and McTavish, 2012). While policy implementation can involve obstacles such as manual primary care functions, securing medical professionals for the hospital and recruiting qualified staff, such challenges are often overlooked in favour of higher-level concerns. Neglecting these challenges can lead to significant issues, conflict, and strained

relationships, resulting in a shortage of healthcare providers and undermining the policy's effectiveness. Therefore, it is critical to prioritize both higher-level issues and lesser challenges in policy implementation, necessitating careful attention to detail and a willingness to engage with the practical complexities of governance.

Once stakeholders understand the challenges facing the H&SC policy process, they can work collaboratively to overcome them. Local political leader B (2022) demonstrates this collaborative leadership style by prioritizing positive relationships and regular communication with senior officials. Academics highlight the importance of prioritizing both relationship-building and challenge-addressing in collaborative governance (Rhodes, 2017), which the leader embodies. The leader adapts to changing circumstances such as the pandemic by emphasizing the role of a new chief officer in driving successful collaboration and positive relationships with the Integrated Joint Board, showing an adaptive leadership style. Good governance and staying informed about the IJB are acknowledged as important by the leader, who recognizes the practical complexities of governance. Neglecting minor challenges in a strategic plan can result in less interaction between actors and strained relationships, underscoring the importance of addressing both higher-level and smaller issues.

“We have a positive working relationship with the new chief officer appointed a couple of years ago, who has been incredible during the pandemic. We also meet with the council's chief executive and IJB's chief financial officers every six weeks, which has been really helpful during difficult financial times. This provides good governance for the two main partners to be updated and well-informed about everything happening within the IJB. This collaborative approach has been brilliant and has developed significantly from the pandemic. The council is now heavily investing in health and social care. As a management team, I feel like we absolutely get it and understand the huge positives of working together to maintain this kind of work.” (Interviewee B, 2022).

The local political leader prioritizes building partnerships and recognizing interdependence to achieve common goals in the Health and Social care sector, as demonstrated through regular meetings and good governance practices. Collaborative leadership is crucial for effective governance, requiring input and participation from multiple stakeholders and building trust (Bianchi et al., 2021). The leader's proactive and collaborative approach fosters trust, collaboration, and shared goals transparently and inclusively. This leadership style encourages open communication and collaboration with senior officials to achieve IJB goals. The appointment of a new chief officer during the pandemic and shared purpose brought about by difficult financial times underscore the importance of local political leaders in the Health and Social care agenda.

The effective collaboration of senior officials and local political leaders in Scottish health and social care is crucial in achieving successful governance. Interviewee B (2022) has demonstrated how prioritizing transparency and collaboration in their leadership style can foster trust and achieve shared goals transparently and inclusively. While each leader may adopt a unique approach to managing relationships with senior officials, building positive relationships with officers is a top priority for all. Local political leaders E (2022) and I (2022) value collaboration and mutual respect, treating their officers as equals and respecting their expertise, which fosters positive working relationships that lead to better outcomes. On the other hand, H (2022) recognizes the importance of maintaining a good relationship with officers while also being willing to encourage a different approach if necessary. These leaders' approaches may differ, but they all prioritize building positive relationships with officers and other bureaucratic actors, recognizing this as essential to successful collaboration in local governance.

Despite the importance of building positive relationships, building these partnerships is not always easy, and conflicts or challenges can arise that can hinder the success of the collaborative efforts. Interviewee B (2022) has experienced such challenges in their partnership with the Integrated Joint Board. Despite their commitment to good governance, regular communication and transparency, conflicts have arisen, highlighting the importance of addressing such challenges in a timely and effective manner.

“One challenge has been around budgets, as the NHS is not as limited as councils in terms of delivering a balanced budget. A deficit within the Integrated Joint Board (IJB) could potentially have a more significant impact on a local authority than on the NHS. Working with our senior leadership team and chief financial officer at the council has been challenging, as they are responsible for certain services like economic development, and it's difficult for them to see their services being impacted by overspending.” (Interviewee B, 2022).

According to the identified challenges, it is clear that financial arrangements and constraints have created significant tension in the relationship between the council, the Health Board, and the IJB, which has had a direct impact on the quality of healthcare services provided. To address these issues, senior officials have called for more flexible funding arrangements and streamlined decision-making processes (C1, 2022; G1, 2021). However, the high turnover of members on the IJB, which is an essential component of integrated Health and Social Care governance, poses another significant challenge that must be addressed. This turnover can impede relationship-building efforts and make collaboration and co-ordination more difficult. In addition, the impact of digital platforms on relationship-building and the need for additional guidance for newer members have been highlighted as areas that require further attention. Failure to address these challenges could further

exacerbate the strained relationship and create more difficulties in working together effectively.

According to a senior official (G1, 2022)-

“Relationships can lead to some challenges because local political leaders become accustomed to the way things work in the local authority setting, and then it may work slightly differently at the IJB table. This can take some getting used to. The turnover of members, whether elected members around the IJBs or NHS non-executive members around the IJBS, also presents difficulties in terms of building relationships. We've implemented development programmes, training sessions, and learning opportunities for our IJB members, and we've nearly achieved a working board. However, when an election or change in NHS non-executive members occurs, we have to start over again. It's easier to build relationships when you're in the same room as someone, having a cup of coffee and working together, compared to building relationships over a digital platform. For newer members, they may not have as deep an understanding or grasp of the bigger picture as others. This doesn't mean they are less supported, but they may require more guidance. Overall, I think the chair and vice chair has been effective.” (Interviewee G1, 2022).

The challenges faced by local political leaders in adapting to different settings and frameworks while working across various organizations are significant (Audit Scotland, 2022). They are expected to be adaptable and work within different frameworks as situations require, which can be a struggle. This adjustment struggle can result in communication breakdowns, delays in decision-making, and conflicts in priorities, leading to negative impacts on service delivery and patient outcomes (Cejundo and Terin, 2023). Moreover, local political leaders may feel overwhelmed or disempowered by the unfamiliar environment, resulting in a lack of engagement and participation in the integration process. This lack of engagement can lead to missed opportunities for innovation and improvement.

To address these challenges, senior officials have implemented training and development programmes to achieve a working board (Audit, 2022), but relationship-building remains an ongoing process that requires continuous effort and attention. Establishing personal relationships over digital platforms is challenging, and in-person engagement opportunities, such as meetings and events, are vital for fostering trust and collaboration. Moreover, the turnover of IJB members poses an additional challenge, and senior officials have called for mentorship and support from local political leaders to newer IJB members. This approach can facilitate their growth and development within the governance structure, enhance their understanding of the local political environment, and strengthen their ability to work effectively with other bureaucratic actors.

In this context, the senior official's ability to navigate challenges and maintain good relationships with local political leaders is a testament to the importance of personal relationships in integrated governance.

“I know all the political members on the council, and I brief them on ongoing progress. Since we are local, I am known to them all. Overall, I have a good relationship with them, but it can be extremely challenging at times and needs revision, particularly when some matters are not personal but are core business. For example, political leaders were upset that GPs weren't vaccinating homebound patients. I explained that it was a regional programme and suggested they speak with GPs about individual cases who cannot go to the centre, and I will see what I can do to arrange transport. Despite challenges, I focus on finding solutions and some political members indulge themselves in blame games or political discussions but as an officer, I do not rise to it. As a strong leader, I deal with these challenges my way.” (Interviewee H1, 2021).

The interview with the senior official highlights the crucial role of relationship-building in the effective functioning of integrated governance structures. Building positive relationships is a challenging task for senior officials and local political leaders, especially when dealing with core business matters. Nonetheless, adopting a solution-focused approach and a strong leadership style can facilitate the avoidance of blame games and political discussions, enabling leaders and actors to work through challenges and find solutions. The effectiveness of this approach is evident in the positive experience of local political leader H, who worked with a senior official. Interviewee H's (2022) endorsement of the official's competence suggests that this approach can yield positive outcomes and is replicable by other local senior officials. The official's views, when combined with H's interview data, further emphasize the importance of prioritizing relationships and solutions in collaborative governance.

Moreover, effective integrated governance necessitates building and sustaining robust relationships both locally and nationally. Interviewee I (2022) suggest that effective integrated governance involves leveraging relationships at a national level to achieve local goals:

“I have really good relationships with all of the political parties and independent candidates. We have no issues. I think we have a really good, trusted relationship locally amongst ourselves, but the SNP representatives have a good, trustworthy relationship at a national level as well. Some of the things we want to do, we used our good working relationships locally to enable us to go back to national colleagues and say, "We're going to try something different here. It may be out of alignment with what you're doing nationally, but it's the right thing to do." That's not about me having relationships; that's about them having really good relationships at a national level. And, as I said, that works really well.” (Interviewee I1, 2022).

The analysis highlights the importance of building alliances and partnerships in the context of integrated governance, and the value of trust and strong relationships among local and national leaders. The success of the official in implementing innovative approaches to H&SC was largely due to the leverage of these relationships, underlining the importance of collaboration and trust among all parties involved. This approach is in contrast to confrontational political styles that prioritize individual interests over those of the community can hinder effective integrated governance.

The significance of building strong relationships between local political and bureaucratic leaders in integrated health and social care initiatives has implications for the traditional dichotomy concept in public administration. While this concept emphasizes the separation of politics and administration, the evidence suggests the interdependence of these roles and the need for effective relationships and communication for effective governance. This indicates that the dichotomy concept may need re-evaluation in modern governance, where collaboration and communication are essential to achieving positive outcomes.

7.4 Geographical Considerations

The geographical considerations in this research are broadly divided into two categories: the size of the IJB area and urban/rural community needs.

7.4.1 The influence of the size of an IJB

IJBs have been established in Scotland to lead the integrated governance of Health and Social Care services. The size and composition of IJBs have become a topic of interest among researchers and policymakers (Joint Act, 2014; Scottish Government, 2015). Specifically, the impact of IJB membership size on the leadership style of local political leaders has been explored in this theme, along with the representation of different sectors on the leadership style and effectiveness of integrated governance. Drawing from the interviews conducted with local political leaders and senior officials, it can be contended that the size of the IJB membership has not impacted on their efficient functioning. Although the extent and composition of IJBs have been a matter of interest, there are scant instances where local actors have emphasized the impact of IJBs' size on their operations within these boards. Therefore, while examining the influence of IJB size and representation on the leadership approach of local political leaders is crucial, the dimensions of these boards have been deemed routine and effective throughout Scotland.

In this context, Interviewee F (2022) suggests that the size of IJB can limit the role of local political leaders in integrated governance. The boards' extensiveness makes it challenging for them to explore vital topics during meetings, especially with a large number of agenda items. Members may face difficulty presenting concerns or engaging in substantial deliberation. The IJB F Minutes from February 15, 2017, revealed a debate among IJB members regarding the potential expansion of the IJB to include unions representing the voluntary sector. While some members expressed concerns about the impact on workflow and the IJB's already large size, (IJB area F Minutes, 15 Feb 2017). In such circumstances, it is essential to have a robust and effective leadership structure that can

facilitate efficient communication and ensure that important concerns are addressed. These challenges seem to be systemic and inherent to the structure of integrated health and social care governance, rather than resulting from individual actors' actions or decisions. According to F,

“I think sometimes it's quite difficult in a meeting that has a board of 20 and you're moving through an agenda of perhaps 20 items that if I have an issue that I think merits real probing, this is an issue for the chair as to how far and in what depths you can pursue a particular issue. If you are one of 20 people and this is one of 20 agenda items, and that I think is a problem. But that's a problem with the way the piece is set up that you're trying to have often a very important discussion with a very big board and a very long agenda. And that, I think, is the major failing of the piece.” (Interviewee F, 2022).

This perspective highlights the potential limitations of large IJBs in enabling effective collaboration and decision-making, especially for local political leaders who represent their communities' interests but the leadership style of local political leaders in the context of IJBs appear to be prioritizing proactive involvement in identifying and addressing issues while acknowledging the limitations imposed by the integrated governance structure. It additionally exhibits a pragmatic strategy towards leadership that prioritizes the efficient functioning of the board and the accomplishment of its objectives over individual concerns or preferences.

The relationship between IJB size and leadership style is a topic of debate, with some suggesting that larger boards may be less conducive to effective scrutiny, while others argue that larger boards can facilitate a more diverse range of perspectives and ideas (Interviewee A, 2022). However, in the case of the IJB, a member from a large IJB area argued that a large board would be optimal for effective problem-solving, as it accommodates a variety of voices and experiences. In this context, local political leadership plays a crucial role in navigating political rivalries and gaining the trust of stakeholders who may have divergent interests and views.

“I think the size is very optimal because in the political scene, you clearly have lines, you are whipped to vote in a particular direction, but that isn't the case on the IJB. it's just bringing different experiences from our different parties. It functions very well, if it's too small, then the pool of thought is too small. If it's too big, then there's too many diverging ideas. I think ours works very well. it's important to accommodate all these voices that you've got on the board. In a good-sized board, the key skill is having competent officers who can provide well-prepared reports. These reports are managed by a healthcare professional who ensures their quality. Usually, the reports are refined and may undergo some changes before they are presented to any committee. If effective people are handling this process, then it works smoothly.” (Interviewee A, 2022).

The leadership style of the local political leader reflects a collaborative and inclusive approach valuing diverse perspectives and avoids overwhelming decision-making. A balanced board size is crucial for adequate representation, promoting constructive dialogue and working across party

lines. The analysis emphasizes the importance of well-prepared reports managed by skilled officers to ensure quality and efficiency in large structures of integrated governance. Furthermore, this research suggests that the complexities of integrated governance require balanced decision-making and effective delegation, particularly in a challenging political environment. The political leader's style, which reflects a commitment to collaboration and inclusivity, is particularly crucial in this context.

However, Interviewee B (2022) suggests that working in a smaller area can have benefits in building relationships based on trust and familiarity, contributing to a more collaborative and cohesive decision-making process. On the other hand, this can also lead to potential conflicts of interest or biases. Additionally, a smaller board may lack the diverse perspectives necessary for comprehensive decision-making. Thus, finding a balance between the advantages of a smaller board and the need for diverse representation can be challenging in achieving effective decision-making in integrated governance. Nevertheless, the input of local political leaders, such as B, can provide valuable insights into the nuanced and complex decision-making processes involved in integrated governance.

“In the small size area, you know everybody, there's no anonymity, everybody knows everybody else. And most of the people on the board, I've worked with in one capacity or another, I know their children. I think that it can be seen that positive or negative, I suppose for me, it's positive because, these are real relationships I had prior to becoming a councillor, it's been a great opportunity to kind of build these relationships, and I suppose I've kind of used those relationships to just, ensure sort of smooth sailing. so incredibly important relationships here are trustful relationship incredibly important.” (Interviewee B, 2022).

The data from this thesis highlights the benefits of a small-scale governance structure that prioritizes personal relationships, which can enhance collaborative governance (Ansell & Gash, 2007). The leader also acknowledges the potential positive and negative implications of pre-existing relationships, indicating an understanding of the complexities of integrated governance in this context. In this type of setting, the leader's approach of building and maintaining trustful relationships with board members can foster collaborative governance, aligning with the collaborative governance model that stresses the significance of mutual trust and respect in achieving shared goals (Emerson et al., 2012).

Moreover, the use of personal connections can help to overcome challenges in integrated governance, such as communication barriers and divergent interests. However, this leadership style may not be suitable for larger governance structures where anonymity is more prevalent (B1, 2022). Over-reliance on personal connections can also undermine transparency and accountability, which are essential for effective governance. Therefore, this sheds lights on the situational phenomena of

local political leadership where leaders are expected to be attuned to the complexities and nuances of integrated governance, adapting their leadership style to suit the specific context or situation in which they operate. The size of the area and the IJB team impact the members' respect and trust, as highlighted by the leader's experience with opposing political groups.

“I know all our members even if they are from the opposition. I built up relationships with them and those relationships have helped. The example I gave earlier about the GP closures, I spent years working with them building up trust with those opposition members because some of them are quite suspicious of my party and it's taken a lot of work to kind of make sure they trust me. And that time I've invested over these years, I thought it's starting to pay off. The opposition member supported the closure of GP surgeries.” (Interviewee B, 2022).

In their interview B (2022) discussed the challenge of gaining the trust of opposition parties and the effort required to build trust over time. This demonstrates that integrated governance requires leaders to navigate political rivalries and build trust with stakeholders who have divergent interests and views. It also suggests that effective integrated governance involves sustained effort that requires patience and perseverance. The example of GP closures highlights how difficult decisions and trade-offs may be necessary in modern governance that may not be popular with all stakeholders.

The leader's experience shows that the small size of the IJB team and area can facilitate interaction and relationship-building, promoting effective problem-solving. This is supported by a senior official B1, (2022) who also emphasized the benefits of working closely with others to build trust and mutual respect. However, in larger IJBs or local authorities, building the same level of trust and understanding could be more challenging.

“I do think that helps in terms of building trust, when you work closely with people on it, both on a day to day basis, within formal committee structures, I do think it helps to build a degree of under mutual understanding respect and like you say trust, whereas once you're into a bigger, a bigger IJB, and in a larger local authority and health system, it can't feel. This small IJB which was open to ideas, which sought to achieve consensus and strategic leadership by consensus.” (Interviewee B1, 2022).

7.4.2 Influence of Geography (Urban/rural)

The impact of whether the local authority's territory is either rural or urban has a significant impact on the local political leadership approaches. Studies show a close relationship between leaders' style and the features and needs of the communities they represent (Xu et al., 2021). Rural and urban communities have different strategic needs that affect leadership styles in integrated governance. Therefore, this theme focuses on examining instances where local political leaders have made decisions based on the needs of their rural or urban communities and how these

decisions reflect their leadership styles. The interview evidence shows that rural areas are often better serviced by a more community-based approach, while urban areas tend to benefit more from a structured approach to accommodate complex urban dynamics. Thus, understanding the needs of these communities is crucial in determining the appropriate leadership style.

To meet the needs of rural communities, local political leaders adopt a more community-based approach to decision-making, as demonstrated by local political leader E (2022). By engaging with communities through events such as community lunches, leaders can gain valuable insights into challenges such as poor transportation or limited healthcare access. This knowledge can inform decision-making and lead to better outcomes for constituents.

“We are getting more tuned to what communities need from us, which could be as simple as having a district nurse available at a local centre once a week. I always use an example, and I've used it for many years now that if we have got a lunch club in the village and there's lunch clubs and stuff like that in many villages, if you sent a district nurse, a doctor, a health worker to join them at lunch, you would get more intelligence from that lunch, than any appointment from any doctor, because they will tell you about how crap the bus service is. They can't get an appointment with a cooperative. They can't get the eyes tested. The dentist days, they'll tell you all that over lunch. They would never tell you that in a face-to-face appointment. So, I'm a great advocate of going into community lunch.” (Interviewee E, 2022).

For local political leader E, public opinion is very relevant, particularly when recognising their work or getting public support. This is not presented as a legitimisation strategy; on the contrary, it is justified as the necessary strategy to understand and convey people's interests, in order to represent them as best as they can. Such an approach can necessitate flexibility and adaptability in collaborating with stakeholders in the community. Developing ties with community members and collaborating with them to address their concerns are essential components of integrated governance (Ansell and Torfing, 2021). In addition, the interview evidence highlights the importance of leaders being innovative in addressing community needs. The leader's suggestion to join community lunches and advocate for a district nurse to visit the local centre once a week demonstrates a proactive approach to governance and a willingness to prioritize community engagement and feedback. The IJB's commitment to service user engagement is further corroborated by the Audit Scotland report on the IJB from 2020, which highlights the IJB's efforts to gather feedback from service users and incorporate their perspectives into its decision-making processes (Audit, 2020e). This emphasis on user engagement aligns with the IJB's mission to provide high-quality services that meet the needs of its users.

The significance of understanding and addressing community needs, which E (2022) highlights, is supported by the experiences shared by both B (2022) and H (2022) in their respective interviews.

Both leaders recognize the challenge of balancing community preferences with the need for efficient healthcare services but stress the importance of involving stakeholders in the decision-making process and ensuring inclusivity in the consultation process. This aligns with E's emphasis on adaptability, flexibility, and community involvement in governance. By prioritizing community feedback and collaborating with stakeholders, leaders can effectively address community needs and promote integrated governance. B (2022) outlines potential problems.

"We have a situation at the moment where we will potentially be closing some GP surgeries. The decision is not ours as the practice is making that decision, but obviously they're looking for support from us because we have oversight for assurance purposes of GPs. We're leading the consultation on that. It's incredibly difficult because, as you said, it's a really weird area and there are huge issues for transport. But we've made sure that at every activation, we've involved the local members. They've been invited along, allowed to speak, and members of the public have been invited as well. We've ensured that the consultation is as good as it can be, and every single stakeholder has the opportunity to respond to that. It's difficult, always closures are terrible. These community hospitals are often an identity. It means so much, it's where you perhaps lose a parent, or your auntie works. It's really difficult." (Interviewee B)

And H (2022) added,

"Sometimes, an old hospital may no longer be needed, or it may be necessary to concentrate staff in one particular location. It can be difficult for people to understand why they are losing their hospital, but ultimately, those who receive care prefer to have it in their own home or a local community setting. While people are attached to their local services and hospitals, it may not be the most effective way to deliver care to the wider population. This has been a challenging conversation for the past 20-25 years as we strive to shift the balance of care." (Interviewee H, 2022).

This analysis presents two contrasting leadership styles of local political leaders in the context of integrated governance. The first leader (B, 2022) takes a consultative and responsive approach, acknowledging the emotional attachment of community members to local healthcare services and the challenges of decision-making in a rural area with transportation issues. This leader emphasizes involving stakeholders in the decision-making process, promoting collaboration. The IJB B area's commitment to community engagement is evident in the documentary analysis, which reveals that local political leaders actively seek feedback from the public on ongoing H&SC infrastructure projects (IJB area B minutes, 29 June 2017). This approach underscores the IJB B area's dedication to involving the community in decision-making, ensuring that the needs and preferences of residents are considered in shaping local services. In contrast, the second leader (H, 2022) adopts a more directive and top-down leadership style, prioritizing effective care delivery to the wider population over maintaining attachment to local services and hospitals. This leadership style is focused on outcomes and may be less consultative. The quotes demonstrate how different

leadership styles can impact decision-making processes in integrated governance contexts, and the importance of balancing community needs with broader healthcare delivery goals.

The nature of leadership styles in the context of integrated governance is complex, with both advantages and disadvantages to consultative and directive approaches. Consultative styles foster trust, but can be unwieldy, while direct approaches are efficient but may not always consider community concerns and could generate opposition. In this case of rural IJBs facing unique challenges such as transportation issues and limited healthcare access, requiring leaders to use a consultative and responsive approach to decision-making. This ensures that decisions reflect local needs and priorities, leading to greater acceptance of healthcare delivery changes. However, the need to deliver effective health and social care to the broader population must also be considered, and a more mandate approach may be required at times.

As discussed previously, the rural areas face unique challenges when it comes to delivering healthcare services in Scotland. Local leaders across IJB areas face difficulties in providing adequate and equitable services to the dispersed rural population due to a lack of skilled workforce and politicization of service delivery. The documentary data from the IJB are G provided evidence for the relevance of this factor. For example, the IJB minutes from 29 Oct 2020 reported concerns about the non-engagement of elected members in decision-making for a special locality project. The IJB minutes from 27 September 2018 revealed that members showed selectivity in strategic priorities based on the immediate needs of the dispersed rural population. The IJB minutes from 31 May 2018 identified staff recruitment challenges in remote areas.

The interview data from the local leaders complemented and enriched the documentary data, by providing insights into how the local leaders perceived and addressed the challenges and opportunities arising from rural nature of the area. For example, the workforce shortage is recognized as a significant issue by both local political leaders and senior officials, as "it results in increased workloads and pressures on frontline workers" (Interviewee B,2022). The immense pressure on H&SC services frustrates local political leaders due to their constituents' pressure, and they prioritize their individual concerns in the IJB (G1, 2021). This, in turn, affects the ability of the Integrated Joint Board to deliver its strategic commissioning plan and intentions effectively, which requires "a skilled, qualified, motivated, and well-resourced workforce" (Interviewee G1,2022). G1 (2021) added,

"The IJB has made several decisions, including the development of integrated community teams in local communities, called 'homes', which aim to support individuals in their own homes, reduce unnecessary hospital admissions, facilitate faster hospital discharge, and provide rehabilitation, enablement, palliative care, and social care services. These teams are

composed of multi-professional and multidisciplinary staff. The IJB has commissioned and expects the delivery of these services, which require a properly skilled and qualified workforce, including care workers. However, in rural areas, the recruitment of care workers presents a significant challenge. Therefore, the IJB cannot direct the health board and local authority to ensure the delivery of these services unless we have a workforce.” (Interviewee G1,2021).

The IJB demonstrates a proactive leadership style by making decisions and commissioning services that benefit local communities. This approach reflects a desire to address community needs and take initiatives, such as developing integrated community teams that require collaboration across different professions and disciplines. However, recruitment of care workers in rural areas presents a significant challenge, adding complexity to integrated governance. The content analysis of IJB area E provides compelling evidence of the persistent workforce challenges that have hindered service delivery and patient choice, particularly in rural areas. The documentary data from IJB minutes and audit reports reveals a series of concerns raised by councillors and stakeholders, including the future risk of care homes, the resourcing of care packages, the lack of carer availability, travel difficulties, and national recruitment issues involving COSLA (IJB area E minutes, 4 Mar 2015; IJB area E minutes, 13 May 2015; IJB area E minutes, 30 Aug 2017). These challenges underscore the complex factors that contribute to service delays and the need for innovative solutions. Against this background, Interviewee E (2022) suggested a potential solution to this challenge, demonstrating the understanding of local problems and complexities.

“I believe we're failing to address the geographical challenges holistically. If we employed staff who work from home within a 10–15-mile radius, we could provide them with an electric vehicle, grant funding for a charging point, and cover their patch. This could be a cheaper solution than what we currently offer to providers.” (Interviewee E, 2022).

In urban IJBs, local political leaders face many challenges when addressing health inequalities and societal issues similar to their rural counterparts, but the nature of those challenges is slightly different. To effectively prioritize the well-being and independence of vulnerable communities, these leaders meticulously examine deprivation levels and make strategic investments in order to address this issue e.g., they invest in accessible and affordable housing among others. Interviewee F (2022) emphasizes the significance of understanding the impact of income and historic family backgrounds on people's health. Instead of focusing solely on the urban/rural divide, local political leaders recognize deprivation as a critical lens in urban areas to address health and social care problems. The documentary data from IJB area F supports this finding. The documentary analysis of IJB area F sheds light on the council's commitment to addressing the needs of deprived communities. The IJB minutes reveal that councillors' decision-making on infrastructure development projects, such as the homelessness assessment centre, was guided by the specific

needs of these underserved areas (IJB area F minutes, 21 Mar 2017; IJB area F minutes, 6 Feb 2019). This focus on equity is further underscored by discussions surrounding resource allocation to GPs, where concerns were raised about potential disparities in funding and suggestions made to prioritize funding based on the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) (IJB area F minutes, 24 Jan 2018).

However, alongside these efforts, it is important to consider the process of consensus building to tackle deprivation levels within the IJB. The senior official (F1, 2021) reveals that, while local political leaders are keen on discussing funding allocation for their deprived communities within the IJB territory, there is a broader recognition of the need to balance the distribution of resources. This approach aims to avoid excessive spending on severely disadvantaged communities while still addressing their needs. The common pool of money allocated for the fiscal year is guided by a consensus-driven approach that acknowledges the challenges faced by different communities and localities.

“It's not like other areas where you've got pockets, and local areas where there's high deprivation, and you can say let's target these guys, because it's huge, and it's very difficult, and the level of need is very difficult to meet everyone's aspirations or the needs they have in terms of services.” (Interviewee F1, 2022).

This strategic approach showcases a complexity and deep understanding of one of the potential root causes of social and economic inequality, aiming to enhance the quality of life for urban populations. These challenges seem closely knitted and related to the principles of integrated governance that expect stakeholders to build consensus in decision making processes. This could lead to a situation where deprived communities do not receive the resources they need to address their challenges. For example, they may not have access to affordable housing, which can have a significant impact on their quality of life.

Affordable housing is one of the most important resources that urban communities need. However, limited financial means present a challenge in making a meaningful difference. Local political leader (C,2022) emphasizes this point.

“Our commitment to investing in new and affordable housing is not delivering fast enough, so we must continue to prioritize this as a key part of contributing to people's wellbeing and independence.” (Interviewee C,2022)

The senior official C1, (2022) further sheds light on the details of these dynamics of urban challenges, particularly those neighbourhoods and localities that experience high levels of deprivation, visible through poor housing estates and other indicators. The urban landscape also includes hinterland areas resembling the countryside, posing challenges in delivering services

effectively across the city. One area where these dynamics manifest prominently is in the “composition of the Third Sector, comprising community groups and services” (C1, 2022). Local actors strive to maintain a balanced approach, demonstrated through initiatives such as the grants programme, which distributes substantial funds, ranging from £10 million to £40 million.

While the grants programme initially faced criticism as it was perceived as a money-grabbing exercise, a rigorous and fair process was implemented to address concerns of fairness. The allocation of grants was scrutinized in terms of distribution between the north and south of the city and its equitable allocation to areas of deprivation and minority groups. According to C1 (2022), the board dedicated significant attention to these considerations, reflecting its commitment to fairness. Moving forward, the strategic plan and locality plans aim to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how this work is carried out at the local level. To achieve this, operational and organizational restructuring is being undertaken to ensure the availability of appropriate resources at the local level for officers to effectively address community needs.

“Community representatives play a crucial role, representing diverse groups and raising important voices. The challenge lies in representing all carers and people with lived experiences in health and social care. To address this, we seek advice from individuals with personal experiences. We actively engage with various groups, including care centres, care groups, and individual carers. Through co-production, our carer strategic plan and thrive programme involve carers and those with lived experiences.” (Interviewee C1, 2022).

These insights reveal a leadership style that prioritizes community engagement, inclusivity, collaboration, and a focus on personal experiences. The leaders acknowledge the challenge of representing all groups and perspectives while valuing the input of individuals with personal experiences. They actively engage with stakeholders, including care centres, groups, individual carers, and providers, through co-production and collaboration. The argument of an interviewee C1 was also affirmed by the documentary analysis of the IJB area C. For instance, documentary analysis provides evidence that local leaders are crucial in appointing service user and carer representatives on the IJB Partnership, highlighting their close connection to the public and communities they represent. The specific needs of the communities are recognized, with decisions made based on population-specific criteria (IJB area C minutes, 11 March 2016; IJB area C minutes, 26 January 2018). This ensures that decision-making involves diverse perspectives, leading to more inclusive outcomes. By involving community members in initiatives like the carer strategic plan and thrive programme, the leaders foster ownership and shared responsibility. They actively seek and involve a diverse range of stakeholders, going beyond token representation. This commitment allows them to understand and address community needs comprehensively and stay connected to their priorities.

In addition, the documentary analysis of urban IJB area F reveals a complex and somewhat contradictory picture of community engagement. On the one hand, there is evidence of a genuine commitment to open engagement with local communities and interest groups, particularly through initiatives like the Thriving Places program (IJB area F minutes, 9 Dec 2016). Additionally, the council's efforts to ensure inclusive engagement through a communication plan that encompasses various groups and builds community capacity for meaningful participation are commendable (IJB area F minutes, 31 Oct 2016). However, this commitment to community involvement seems to be undermined by instances where the local community and elected members were not consulted on preferred H&SC infrastructure (IJB area F minutes, 9 May 2018). This discrepancy raises concerns about the gap between the professed commitment to community engagement and the actual practice in this urban area. The council should strive to bridge this gap by ensuring that its actions align more closely with its stated values and priorities.

7.5 Influence of Frontline- workforce' expectations

Frontline workforce expectations exert a complex influence with the leadership styles of local political leaders. These expectations depend on work culture, IJB policies, and the socio-economic context, and shape the relationship between frontline workers and IJB leaders. The data from IJB areas show how local political leaders responded differently to these expectations and challenges. They acknowledged the frontline workforce's importance and difficulties and tried to engage and support them. For instance, in IJB area B, the local political leaders emphasized the need to ensure that staff have the confidence and skills to effectively implement the IJB policy and provided targeted logistical support to deliver services in remote rural area (IJB area B minutes, Nov 2016; IJB area B minutes 28 Nov 2019). They also proposed a recognition program to recognize, celebrated, and affirmed their dedication (IJB area B minutes, 14 Dec 2017).

In IJB area (I), local leaders also showed responsiveness to the needs and expectations of the frontline workforce, who faced poor working conditions and a substandard physical environment. The leaders raised concerns and advocated for their HR and job security and prepared them for changes with updated information (IJB area I minutes, 12 Oct 2017; 17 June 2020). These actions showed they valued their input, feedback, trust, and loyalty. However, they also failed to address some of the underlying issues that caused dissatisfaction among some frontline staff, such as lack of resources, capacities, and training (IJB area I minutes, 25 Jan 2017). The data also show that they emphasized the need to significantly increase placements for students hosted by the Health and Social Care Partnership to enhance their practical capacities (IJB area I minutes, 26 Mar 2019). Thus,

the local political leaders in IJB area I demonstrated both sensitivity and pragmatism in responding to the needs and expectations of the frontline workforce.

Furthermore the data show that healthcare contexts, such as rural or urban areas, affect local political leaders' leadership styles and frontline workers' needs and concerns in H&SCI. A directive leadership approach may achieve specific outcomes, but it may also ignore frontline staff's concerns and priorities, causing resistance and disengagement among stakeholders (Wimmelmann et al., 2018). A leadership approach that engages and responds to stakeholders can foster trust, collaboration, and better decision-making, improving job satisfaction, performance, and patient care (Innes and Booher, 2010). This is particularly evident in rural areas like IJB area G, where a critical shortage of healthcare professionals has led frontline staff and stakeholders to strongly advocate for changes to service delivery, including a reduction in geographical boundaries or even the closure of certain locations (IJB area G minutes, 22 Sep 2016). These proposals require a complex leadership decision that considers stakeholder needs and service priorities. In rural areas where it is hard to recruit and retain skilled healthcare professionals, a consultative and responsive leadership style can build trust, engagement, and collaboration among stakeholders, leading to more effective and sustainable H&SCI.

Therefore, effectiveness of local political leaders' leadership styles and their stakeholder management abilities, including those of the frontline workforce, are crucial to the success of integrated governance (Lipsky, 2010). Moreover, the expectations of frontline workers, who are integral to the healthcare sector, are particularly vital in shaping the direction of integrated governance. As F (2022) suggests, "frontline workers expect the board to collectively take responsibility and demonstrate a clear view of direction". Thus, it is important to understand team members' expectations and how they influence local political leadership choices.

An informal conversation between a political leader and a mental health team sheds light on the significance of such collaboration. It had no agenda, which allowed for free-flowing dialogue and helped the leader to gain valuable insights into the team's challenges and needs. Such conversations can aid in strategic planning and addressing the concerns of various teams, as highlighted in the mental health team's example. E (2022) explained,

"In a mental health project, the council withdrew its funding because it didn't fit their criteria. But frontline said that they use a triangle to address social work issues and currently, they bring people to the apex of the triangle. However, the aim is to bring them down to the base to reduce costs for early intervention and officer visits. Frontline workers missed a project where they could have directed people to gardening or cooking clubs instead of needing their assistance. And I used one example as I was struggling at one point just to put my shoes on due to my hip replacement. They sent out an occupational therapist (OT) to basically say,

what you need is a long-handled shoehorn apparently, a visit from an OT to provide a long-handled shoehorn cost £300, but a simple phone call could have resulted in sending a shoehorn in the post, cutting £299 worth of costs, and allowing the frontline staff to focus on more pressing interventions.” (Interviewee E, 2022).

The local political leader's approach seems to be pragmatic and result-oriented, providing clear guidance to address social work issues within financial constraints. However, they also demonstrate attentiveness to the needs of frontline workers by redirecting resources to more pressing issues, indicating a consultative and responsive leadership style. The leaders' first-hand experience echoes the workforce challenges that the IJB formally acknowledges in its meeting minutes, such as capacity issues and difficulties in engaging the workforce in the process of decision-making. This consistency between the leaders' perspectives and the documented evidence lends credibility to the concerns raised. The IJB's gratitude for the workforce's dedication and service shows the value of their contributions. For instance, the minutes of the IJB meetings held on November 27th, 2019, and November 25th, 2020, state: "The IJB recognizes the workforce challenges they face, such as capacity constraints and challenges in engaging the workforce in the decision-making process, which can hinder their ability to achieve their goals (IJB area E minutes, 27 Nov, 2019; 25 Nov, 2020)." Additionally, the minutes convey the IJB's appreciation for the workforce's dedication and service provision: "The IJB expresses gratitude to all members of the workforce for their unwavering commitment and service delivery" (IJB area E minutes, 25 Nov 2020).

In contrast, the interview evidence from A (2021) highlights a past decision by the IJB to move forward with converting a public practice into a private one despite the majority of staff and patients expressing their opposition in a survey. The leader expresses regret for voting in favour of the decision, emphasizing the importance of standing by convictions and prioritizing the needs and preferences of those receiving care. This example underscores further the importance of listening to and valuing the input of frontline workers and patients in decision-making processes to ensure that the needs and interests of those impacted by decisions are prioritized. A (2021) explained,

"Let's go back to the old city practice. They conducted a survey among all the staff, including patients and student professionals, and about 120 people participated. The majority of the respondents did not want to convert the practice into a private one. However, the IJB decided to go ahead with it. Although I had some questions and concerns, I ultimately voted in favour of their decision, even though I now realize it was a complete disaster. Looking back, I should have stood by my conviction and said no, even if I would have been outvoted. It's unfortunate that situations like this can arise." (Interviewee A, 2022).

Interviewee A (2021) expressed reservations about converting the practice into a private one, demonstrating thoughtfulness and analytical decision-making. Despite these concerns, they ultimately voted in favour of the decision, potentially indicating a willingness to compromise or

defer to authority or majority opinions. Moreover, the leader's subsequent regret for not standing by their conviction and opposing the decision highlights the importance of principles and integrity in leadership. This preference for a more principled or idealistic leadership style may be suggested by the leader's statement.

Although the local political leader expressed concerns and regrets about a decision made in the past, they also have a track record of advocating for the well-being of frontline staff, both within the council and the Integrated Joint Board. As a former employee and health and well-being advisor, H (2022) has connections within the workforce that allow them to stay informed and address issues such as domestic abuse.

“I still have connections within the workforce, both within the IJB, and the council that allows me to take a temperature check. None of it is a surprise, it was entirely predictable. I knew that domestic abuse would go up and I asked the council to tighten up its domestic abuse policy for employees, and the IJB as well. I was involved in that and that's distribution sadly, but there was, there was sort of extra levels of support for our employee who were having to work at home who might be exposed to greater levels of domestic abuse. so, you know, People in the council and IJB know me well enough, from my past lives to be able to come to me about issues.” (Interviewee H, 2022).

Interviewee H (2022) highlights a leadership style that prioritizes the wellbeing of the frontline workforce. Their ability to maintain regular communication with the workforce and use their connections to address issues such as domestic abuse demonstrate a leadership style that is empathetic and considers the needs of others. They anticipate challenges, implement proactive solutions, and consider external factors such as COVID-19 to protect and support the workforce. Their strategic and empathetic leadership style is forward-looking and inclusive.

The senior official (H1, 2022) endorses the local political leader's approach of leveraging her expertise to benefit the frontline workforce and she acknowledge the political leader's effective participation in debates and positive relationships with colleagues, indicating that her leadership style is well-regarded. This proactive leadership aligns with the senior official's perception of the leader as supportive and effective in promoting progress. Moreover, the official suggests that the leader's support is also associated with the advantages of projects that benefit their electoral wards and political jurisdiction, as noted in Interviewee F1's 2021 statement.

However, this leadership approach can also present challenges. For instance, the proactive approach of the leader may be seen as intrusive or assertive by other partners, leading to tension and conflict. In addition, the leader's personal connections with the workforce may create perceptions of favouritism or bias, eroding trust, and collaboration among partners.

Conclusion

This chapter aimed to uncover local leaders' prevalent styles across diverse political contexts. The chapter has revealed that the leadership styles of local leaders are diverse and dynamic, highlighting the complexity and uncertainty of the issues they face. The analysis of Scottish H&SC leadership identified five significant contextual factors affecting local leaders' decision-making. These include economic and financial considerations, partisanship, political-administrative relationships, geographical influence (urban/rural, area size), and frontline workforce expectations. However, some factors hold greater sway in local leadership. Among these, Chapter 8 provides sufficient data to assert that the most influential are economic and financial factors, partisanship, political-administrative relationships, and urban/rural community needs. These factors have a direct and significant impact on the resources, priorities, and relationships of local leaders..

For example, IJB areas characterized by economic prosperity tend to facilitate effective resource optimization, while areas grappling with economic deprivation and financial challenges often contend with communication challenges and working relationship difficulties among leaders and their diverse array of stakeholders. The exigencies of financial constraints in mixed-deprived area often necessitate a more hands-off leadership approach. In addition, the contours of political-administrative relationships were revealed to be complex and multifaceted. The Chief Officer, occupying a leading role within the IJB, emerges as a one of a central figure in shaping these relationships. Elements such as politeness, trust, respect, teamwork, transparency, and collaboration were underscored as pivotal for fostering and maintaining these relationships. Nevertheless, the intricacies of navigating work culture disparities among stakeholders can introduce their own set of challenges. Personal relationships, while potentially advantageous, may not be without complications when fundamental business matters come into play. The local political leaders rely on officers to navigate the financial landscape and challenging financial and economic conditions can strained the relationships between these two groups.

Furthermore, partisanship, as another fundamental contextual factor, assumes a critical role. National-level policies significantly Mold the strategic choices of local leaders, sometimes harmonizing with local concerns, but at other times, diverging significantly. The dynamics among different political groups at the local level are instrumental in channelling energies towards community-centric issues. Occasionally, limited political consensus provides a fertile ground for collaborative work, even in the face of underlying political discord. Robustly challenging the priorities of disparate political parties can contribute to enhanced accountability mechanisms.

Although collaboration between different political parties can promote effective policy implementation, the cross-party representation can also lead to politicization of decision-making processes. Moreover, the urban or rural nature of the area undeniably leaves its imprint on leadership perspectives. Rural leaders strongly assert their intimate proximity to the immediate needs of local communities, advocating for innovative and community-specific engagement strategies. These leaders also faced with workforce challenges to realise their political ambitions. Conversely, urban leaders underscore the significance of addressing deprivation levels and urban housing challenges as primary determinants in decision-making processes, while concurrently advocating for heightened public participation.

Furthermore, the other factors, such as IJB team size and expectations of frontline workers, are also relevant, but they have a more indirect and moderate impact on the actions and outcomes of local leaders. For instance, the scale of the team or board emerged to be a topic of discussion. Some local leaders conveyed that large teams can potentially hinder effective scrutiny, often owing to time constraints. Nevertheless, some argue that the efficacy of larger teams can be accentuated when complemented by competent supporting officers. Conversely, a number of leaders attested to the efficiency of smaller boards, where close-knit familiarity among members ensures a higher degree of accountability. Finally, the expectations of the frontline workforce emerged as a contextual factor of significance, albeit with a somewhat lower prevalence in the examples collected in this study when compared to other factors. This suggests that while it certainly holds importance, it may not be as paramount for local political leaders as some of the other contextual elements. Nonetheless, it remains indisputable that the workforce's insistence on clear strategies and straightforward communication avenues with leaders is an unequivocal necessity. Local leaders have consistently emphasized the invaluable nature of the insights gained through informal engagements with frontline personnel. They recognize that adaptability and responsiveness constitute pivotal aspects of effective leadership.

Chapter 8

Main discussion and Conclusions

Introduction

This chapter evaluates the role of local political leadership in the strategic decision-making of Health and Social Integration areas in Scotland. It also explores the local political leadership styles in relation to their political context and the role they play in H&SCI. The chapter presents the findings of the data analysis conducted in Chapter 6 and 7. The chapter also discusses the findings in relation to the existing literature on integrated/collaborative governance and the research objectives and questions. The chapter aims to answer the following questions:

- What is the role of local political leaders, particularly IJB members, in the strategic decision-making process for H&SCI service delivery within Scotland?
- How do the following contextual factors influence the leadership styles employed by local political leaders in H&SCI decision-making processes:

1. Economic and financial landscape

2. Partisanship

3. Political-administrative relationships

4. Geographical considerations (rural vs. urban, size of the IJB area)

5. Frontline workforce expectations in health and social care.

The findings revealed that the local political leaders' role is far from over, and they have a significant contribution to make in strategic decision making. They are responsible for setting the vision and priorities for H&SCI in their communities, and they have the power to allocate resources and ensure that H&SCI initiatives are implemented effectively. However, the role of local political leaders is often constrained by their political context. They may be facing pressure from different stakeholders, such as political parties, community members, senior officials, and other elected officials. They may also be limited by the availability of resources. Therefore, local political leaders need to be adaptable and flexible in order to be effective. When they were influenced by their surrounding political context, they needed to have situational awareness to carry out their duties. Finally, they need to be supported by their senior officials, particularly in matters such as the economy and finance.

These findings have important implications for integrated/collaborative governance literature, as well as for the future of the H&SCI agenda. They can help to inform the development of the new theoretical frameworks for integrated governance. For example, the study has the potential to suggest new ways to conceptualise the nature of accountability mechanisms, the role of power imbalances, institutionalised leadership, and political contextual factors that contribute to the effectiveness of integrated initiatives. By understanding the role of local political leaders in the integrated governance of H&SCI, the findings can be used to develop new guidance for practitioners working in the field of integrated governance. For example, policymakers and local authorities can develop strategies to ensure that these leaders are well equipped for the potential situational dynamics and challenges. This can be done by providing them with the resources they need, by giving them a clear mandate, and by creating a supportive political environment (see section 8.2).

8.1 The Role of Local Political Leadership in Strategic Decision Making

In recent years, integrated governance has gained prominence as a tool for tackling complex social issues, including those related to Health and Social Care (Connolly et al., 2020). In response to this growing trend, the Scottish Government established Integration Joint Boards to enhance local policy development and implementation. These IJBs serve as platforms that bring together a diverse array of stakeholders, including elected local political leaders, senior officials, citizen representatives, care providers, and clinical professionals (Joint Act, 2014). By fostering collaboration between these actors, IJBs aim to collectively address health and social care issues within their respective communities.

8.1.1 The Advantages and Power Imbalances in Integrated Governance

These findings suggest that one of the primary strengths of integrated governance lies in its capacity to foster a holistic comprehension of local health and social care concerns. The integrated framework facilitates the convergence of diverse stakeholders possessing first-hand experience in the domains of health and social care, enabling them to collectively shape policies that are potentially more closely attuned to the exigencies of the local community. This observation aligns with prior research on collaborative governance, emphasizing the importance of involving a heterogeneous group of stakeholders in the decision-making process to enhance policy quality and legitimacy (Bingham & O'Leary, 2014; Emerson et al., 2012). However, the task of reconciling diverse interests, values, and perspectives in integrated governance poses challenges such as governance inertia, deadlock, or the need for compromise (Bodin, 2017). Further, ensuring

adequate representation, participation, and empowerment of all stakeholders in integrated governance, especially marginalized and underprivileged groups lacking resources or authority, presents additional obstacles (Larsen, 2008; Arai et al., 2021; Bianchi et al., 2021). For example, this is often the case with IJB members, who do not have voting powers as compared to local political leaders and senior officials who have voting powers. IJBs have a statutory duty to staff members who come from these marginalised groups, but they may not have the power to make decisions that reflect the needs of those groups. This raises concerns about the representativeness and legitimacy of policies developed within the integrated governance approach. Hence, this research contends that power imbalances in integrated governance may have negative effects on the process and outcomes of the H&SCI agenda.

However, there have been concerns raised by local actors who possess voting powers regarding the efficacy of citizen representation mechanisms. These concerns revolve around the observation that these representatives often fail to adequately address and represent the diverse needs of the entire community they are meant to serve. To address this issue, suggestions have been put forward to encourage more direct involvement of community members in the decision-making process, thereby promoting the adoption and promotion of co-production practices (Interviewee C1, 2022). Although existing research recognizes the challenges of citizen representation in local collaborative governance initiatives, civil society groups face constraints such as the lack of an institutional arena for co-production, limited resources, communication issues, and inadequate community engagement, hindering their ability to gather comprehensive community feedback (Flemig and Osborne, 2019; Ansel and Torfing, 2021). This research did not imply the exhaustive examination of this issue. Hence, it is important to thoroughly examine the shortcomings and underlying reasons for the failure of current citizens' representation mechanisms in the case of IJBs. This analysis is of importance as any future system implemented is likely to encounter similar challenges that are present in the current system. By understanding the specific issues faced by the existing representation mechanisms, it might become possible to make progress in this regard and overcome these challenges in the design and implementation of future systems e.g., a National Care Service Bill. Such an approach has the potential to ensure that the lessons learned from the current system inform the development of a more effective and robust framework for citizens' representation in the context of IJBs.

Moreover, the influence and authority of local political leaders in the IJBs can vary depending on their position within the governance structure. There are variations in the ways local political leaders play their role in the IJBs. For instance, the evidence suggests that local political leaders who chair the IJBs tend to have greater influence and decision-making power compared to those

who are board members. This difference in influence can impact the dynamics of integrated decision-making processes, as the chair's position often grants them more visibility, control over the agenda, and the ability to shape discussions and outcomes. As a result, the perspectives, and priorities of local political leaders in the chair may hold more weight and sway over the direction of the integrated governance initiative compared to their board member counterparts (Ansell et al., 2020). This shows decision-making power is often not distributed equally among various stakeholders, which can lead to conflict and inefficiency. This power imbalance within the local setting can have implications for inclusivity, representation, and the overall effectiveness of the collaborative governance process (Sørensen et al., 2020). On the one hand, this illustrates the influential role of local political leaders as an IJB chair in shaping integrated governance as compared to local political leaders serving as a board member, but on the other hand, this stresses the need for stakeholders to collaborate while being sensitive to power dynamics and conflicting interests (Farr, 2018). This research indicates that by addressing these challenges, stakeholders can work towards more effective and equitable governance processes, both in the Scottish Health and Social Care context and beyond. Therefore, there are opportunities in the integrated system to explore strategies to mitigate power imbalances, such as promoting inclusive participation, providing training on equitable decision-making, and enhancing accountability mechanisms.

8.1.2 The Benefits, Drawbacks, and Remedies for Information Flow

The establishment of committees within IJBs is recognized as a notable strength, facilitating collaboration, decision-making and policy discussions. These sub-committees, as a part of IJBs' institutional design, not only alleviate the workload of the main board but also bring together individuals with specialized knowledge and skills, ensuring a comprehensive approach to governance (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Ansell et al., 2020). However, there are potential limitations related to the resource availability and the number of committees within the integrated governance approach. Insufficient resources or a limited number of committees can restrict the effectiveness of IJBs and create a gap between policy and implementation. The resource-intensive and time-consuming nature of the integrated approach may hinder the ability of IJB members to focus on policy development and implementation. Therefore, addressing these limitations by providing adequate resources and support is crucial to ensure effective policy development and implementation within the integrated governance approach.

However, some evidence from this thesis does suggest that there are ways to enhance the integrated governance approach. One way is to better prepare for meetings. This includes providing

written materials that are clear and concise, as well as allowing time for active engagement, questioning, and understanding different perspectives (Interviewee E, 2022; Interviewee A, 2022). Local political leaders gain valuable insights and promote informed decisions through these activities. The findings demonstrate an enhancement of the integrated governance approach through a strategic refinement of documentation practices employed by local political leaders. Specifically, the study highlights the successful reduction of unnecessary agenda repetition, as local leaders direct senior officials to prioritize focused material pertaining to the current issue at hand, instead of duplicating all details from previous meetings. However, they still managed a large volume of papers and size can pose challenges in providing proper scrutiny and meaningful discussions (Agranoff and McGuire, 2001; O'Leary and Bingham, 2008; Emerson et al. 2012).

This shows that integrated governance is a complex process that requires careful attention regarding workload and committee concerns (Emerson & Nabatchi, 2015). Here evidence indicates the tensions in one of the suggested solutions to managing the workload and community leadership approach in IJBs; local political leaders practising community-based leadership approaches at the cost of bureaucratic constraints. As highlighted in this study, local political leaders can prioritize public service and community needs over bureaucratic constraints, but there are also potential challenges, such as overlooking existing bureaucratic procedures. Although, adding more committees can help to address workload issues, it can also lead to resource constraints and bureaucratic complexity (Ansell & Gash, 2008). It can undermine the potential benefits of community leadership that can enhance accountability, trust, and unity within the community (see Chapter 7). Therefore, it is important to consider that any modifications to the committee structure are carefully evaluated to ensure they enhance this workload aspect without increasing bureaucratic complexity and compromising community-based leadership approaches. Future studies could explore innovative approaches to optimizing committee structures. For example, allocating adequate resources and developing effective prioritization systems could help reconcile bureaucratic constraints and manage the workload faced by IJB members. This could enable more efficient policy development and implementation processes.

8.1.3 Bureaucratic Constraints and Community Engagement: A Double-edged Sword

While there is a recognized need to improve bureaucratic constraints in integrated governance, it is important to acknowledge the benefits that bureaucratic restrictions bring to the overall governance framework. Integrated governance is intended to establish fairness, equity, and compliance with moral and legal standards by imposing bureaucratic regulations (Emerson et al.,

2012). On the one hand, this research reveals the key role of local political leaders in reconciling political priorities with bureaucratic objectives. They attempt to navigate the complexities of addressing specific ward concerns while operating within the bureaucratic limitations to foster collaboration and accomplish collective objectives (Interviewee F, 2022). There is sufficient evidence to argue that when local political leaders adeptly handle these intricacies, they have the potential to significantly enhance the effectiveness of integrated decision-making processes and contribute to their overall success (Ansel and Gash, 2008).

However, it is important to recognize that these bureaucratic restrictions e.g., ward issues and red tape, can inadvertently hinder community involvement and participation (Interviewee G1, 2021). In this context, Klijn and Koppenjan (2015) and Douglas et al., (2020) argue that decision-making in integrated governance structures can be hindered by bureaucratic procedures and the dominance of technical experts. These studies suggest that a narrow focus on technical expertise and rigid bureaucratic procedures may actually hinder the agility and adaptability required for effective decision-making in integrated governance structures. For instance, local political leaders in the Integrated Joint Boards (IJBs) of Scotland face constraints within this framework and have difficulties in adopting the comprehensive approach of the IJBs, as they tend to represent their individual constituents' interests in the IJB meetings. This leads to constrained relationships with senior officials. This tension between addressing community concerns and maintaining bureaucratic constraints does not go down very well in areas where the communities are going through immense pressure on the H&SC system. Bureaucratic concerns are often focused on efficiency and cost effectiveness, while community concerns are often focused on equity and justice (Brodkin, 2011; Lipsky, 2010). The deprived economic conditions facing an IJB can exacerbate this tension. The evidence suggests when IJBs are under financial pressure, they may be more likely to make decisions that prioritize efficiency over equity (Interviewee G1, 2022), even if those decisions have negative consequences for some communities. Consequently, there is a need to strike a balance between following rules and regulations while effectively addressing constituent concerns for local actors. To achieve successful collaborative governance, it becomes crucial to navigate the complexities of community-based leadership, reconcile conflicting priorities and direct involvement of communities in decision making (Ansell and Gash, 2008; Douglas et al., 2020).

This study provides strong evidence that community engagement and collaboration are essential for effective integrated governance. The evidence demonstrates that political leaders who engage in practical initiatives, such as volunteering for communities, actively involving them in important decisions, and providing direct assistance, have a potential to foster community spirit, build trust, and promote successful integrated governance, thereby promoting the effectiveness of the

integrated governance approach (Interviewee H, 2022; Interviewee H1, 2021) In contrast, the study also found that the presence of politicians in decision-making processes to represent their communities can prioritize their individual community interests, introduce political ideologies or party agendas, which can potentially influence policy outcomes.

To mitigate this, this research suggests that it becomes crucial to prioritize the autonomy and unity of the IJB. This emphasis on autonomy serves the purpose of preventing local political leaders from politicizing decision-making and enables the board to make difficult decisions that benefit the collaborative setting as a whole, even if they may have an impact on their constituents. Cross-party representation does help to prevent single party influence to push an IJB in a specific direction based on political agenda (Interviewee F, 2022). From a bureaucratic standpoint, maintaining autonomy and unity within the IJB helps to ensure that decision-making reflects a shared understanding of roles and responsibilities among all parties involved (Interviewee C1, 2022).

It is essential to acknowledge that, while maintaining autonomy and unity within the IJB is crucial, it is equally important for local political leaders to have a voice in the collaborative process. Political differences are inherent in democratic governance, and diverse perspectives and healthy debates can lead to better decision-making outcomes (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Klijn and Koppenjan, 2015). However, it is necessary to hold individual political influence accountable to prevent them from hindering the effectiveness of the decision-making procedure. This study emphasizes the importance of consistent and clear communication in building and maintaining trust with stakeholders. This research indicates that, by actively engaging in discussions and empowering others to ask questions, consideration of other perspectives by political leaders are crucial in identifying and addressing community issues and maintaining trust with stakeholders.

This is particularly important given that lack of trust, suspicion, or a perception by political opponents that some stakeholders are not interested in working collaboratively can all hinder integration efforts. This study suggests that personal relationships with opposition political leaders can help to gain support for collaborative initiatives, but it is essential for local political leaders to genuinely engage in collaborative efforts and work towards achieving shared goals, rather than using collaboration as a means to avoid the need to make difficult decisions. The politicization of decision-making is identified as a significant hindrance to the effectiveness of collaborative governance, as it can lead to a breakdown in trust and co-operation (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Klijn and Koppenjan, 2015). Building on these challenges, the strong leadership (who do not indulge in political blame games) of senior officials is suggested as an important factor in promoting a collaborative spirit, building trust, and avoiding politicization to improve the effectiveness of

collaborative governance (Interviewee H1, 2021; Interviewee F, 2022). The commitment of IJBs to avoiding politicization and investing in education and training demonstrates their dedication to addressing challenges and political sensitivity while promoting a shared understanding of roles and responsibilities among stakeholders (Interviewee A1, 2022).

In summary, this section has explored the effectiveness of collaborative governance in Health and Social Care Integration areas in Scotland, with a specific focus on the role of local political leaders. The study's findings suggest that collaborative governance involving diverse stakeholders in decision-making processes helps to understand local health and social care issues. The committees play a crucial role in supporting IJBs ensuring their effectiveness in H&SCI. Clear roles and responsibilities are essential in achieving successful collaborative governance as well as adopting participatory, flexible, and proactive approaches that facilitate the integration process. However, the detrimental impact of politicization on collaborative governance effectiveness and trust is reiterated.

8.2

Assessing the Contextual Role of Local Political Leadership in Integrated Governance: A Typology Based on Political Context

This section builds on the preceding discourse regarding the role of local political leaders in the strategic decision making of Health and Social Care Integration, specifically examining the influence of the political contextual factors on the leadership styles of these leaders. It aims to explore how these leaders adjust their leadership strategies in response to varying political circumstances, demonstrating a situational response to the challenges and opportunities presented in the integrated governance. This transition signifies a shift from an emphasis on structural elements, roles, and institutional factors to a deeper exploration of the local political landscape. It aims to uncover how the effectiveness of H&SCI and its local actors are intricately intertwined with the political challenges specific to Scottish localities.

The aim of this discussion is twofold; to first demonstrate the impact of contextual factors (economy and finance, partisanship, political administrative relationships, geographical considerations (such as the size of the IJB area and its urban or rural nature), and the expectation of frontline workforce) on local political leadership, and secondly, to present situations and corresponding leadership styles, concluding each subheading with a table consisting of political context and corresponding leadership style. The tables aim to paint a clear picture of the relationship between political contextual factors and leadership styles found in this research to answer the Research Question: What local political leadership styles are evident in the different political contexts of H&SCI processes? These tables are systematically discussed throughout the narrative or discussion of each factor, and they follow the same sequence as the narrative, including material from Analysis Chapters 7 and 8. This practice helps maintain focus on the Research Questions.

8.2.1 Economic and Financial Context

The economic and financial circumstances of integrated governance play a vital role in shaping the leadership dynamics of Scottish H&SC. This section examines how economic and financial governance influences the role of local political leaders and their leadership styles in integrated governance. It highlights the specific leadership approaches best suited to address the challenges and opportunities of this context. While collaborative governance is often known for its advantages,

academic research also underscores its difficulties, especially under economic and financial pressures (Emerson et al., 2012; Grootjans et al 2022). To provide specific insights into financial context and corresponding leadership styles, the section concludes with Table 8.2.1 that summarizes the combinations this research found. The table will provide a visual representation of the relationship of economic and financial factors and will help us to understand how they can impact leadership. Consequently, through this discussion section, this research aims to understand the dynamic relationship between context and leadership in these settings.

The evidence finds that the complex financial governance structure of the IJBs and the division of funding in the H&SCI system pose significant challenges to integrated governance. These difficulties lead to fragmentation of services and inefficiencies, requiring an integrated approach that emphasizes shared decision-making (Audit Scotland, 2018; Debie et al., 2022). Local political leaders face constraints imposed by the ring-fencing of funds by the national government. This limits their ability to actively adopt collaborative approaches and hampers efforts to dismantle inefficient political structures.

The ring-fencing of funds has emerged as a significant challenge in the financial governance of IJBs, as highlighted by local actors. A substantial amount of funding is ringfenced within the healthcare sector, in particular where the NHS assumes greater responsibility for service delivery (Scottish Government, 2018; Interviewee F, 2022). The ring-fencing of funds restricts the opportunities for collaboration between local political leaders and NHS voting members within the IJB, as these funds have already been allocated by the Scottish Government for specific aspects of healthcare e.g., mental health, leaving limited room for local deliberation (Interviewee F, 2022). In response to this context, local leaders often adopt a partially integrated leadership approach (see Table 8.2.1), emphasizing collaboration and shared decision-making. Yet, they face a significant challenge in effectively communicating and navigating this complex financial environment as a result of the uncertainty created by ring-fenced resources. This effective communication is a crucial factor in navigating complex financial environments, particularly when different budgets are involved (Emerson et al., 2012; Bianchi et al., 2021). The potential conflict between national government's directives concerning ring-fencing and guidelines accentuating the need to collaborate worsens the situation for IJBs, as it might create a potential confusion, sense of power imbalance and limited autonomy among local actors, which can lead to frustrations and strained relationships. Although, the recent development in Scottish politics, including the new agreement between the Scottish Government and local authorities, demonstrates a renewed commitment to eliminate ring-fencing of funds by the Scottish Government, and grant local authorities greater flexibility to allocate resources according to their locally determined needs. This agreement, signed on June 30th, 2023,

represents a significant step towards empowering local authorities to invest in their communities using local discretion (COSLA, 2023). Still, as this is a recent development, its full implications and outcomes are yet to be observed and assessed.

Moreover, local elected members often encounter challenges aligning their preferences with stakeholders' budgets due to differing financial frameworks and decision-making processes. These challenges can lead to inefficiency, lack of transparency, and conflicts (Emerson et al., 2012; O'Leary & Bingham, 2008). This indicates the need to increase collaboration and implement integrated governance approaches in its full spirit (Good Governance Institute, 2016). This approach has the potential to address the fragmentation and inefficiencies observed in the system (Frazer, 2022). The Scottish Government has legislation in place that mandates or encourages the merger of budgets among key stakeholders in order to facilitate greater co-ordination and alignment of financial resources (Joint Act, 2014). However, the objective of merging local authority and NHS budgets has not yet been achieved, and the various challenges and complexities make it difficult to do so. Despite these challenges, there is a need to continuously realize the potential benefits of merging NHS and local authorities' budgets. For example, merging budgets could lead to improved co-ordination of services, reduced costs, or better outcomes for service users (Good Governance Institute, 2016; Audit, 2018). The Scottish Government's guidelines, regulations, and mechanisms for merging budgets are important, but they will only be effective if stakeholders are held accountable for following them.

Meanwhile, it must be acknowledged that the realization of fully operational integrated structures may require additional time, as previous representative democratic structures and organizational cultures might take some time to gradually transform their working patterns (UNDP, 2016). Nonetheless, it is worth noting that the Scottish H&SCI system has been in place since 2016, following its transitional period that commenced in 2014 (Joint Act, 2014). Therefore, if stakeholders continue to face basic challenges in merging these budgets or fail to make significant progress in this regard, this highlights a potential failure in the implementation of integrated ideas in Scotland (Audit Scotland, 2018). Consequently, there are opportunities for future research to examine the measures taken to enhance budget mergers since the inception of Integrated Joint Boards and the challenges encountered e.g., power imbalances and accountability in achieving this crucial strategic objective within the integrated agenda.

Furthermore, the limited control over funding and dependence on national government creates uncertainty and instability in the long-term sustainability of integrated governance efforts (Interviewee A, 2022). Crisis funding allocations, like those during the COVID response, can disrupt

initiatives and hinder effective governance mechanisms (Peters, 2021). This constraint impacts the leadership approach of local political leaders, requiring a cautious and pragmatic strategy to manage limited resources (Interviewee C, 2022). Table 8.2.1 shows that cautious and pragmatic leadership style is a suitable approach in times of financial constraints. This is because it allows leaders to navigate challenging circumstances with a realistic and thoughtful approach (Crayne and Medeiros, 2021), while still being able to get business going and achieve goals. The funding unpredictability also deters local actors from making long-term commitments or investing in building the necessary capacities for integrated governance, leaving them with no choice but to adopt a 'hands off' approach (Laissez-faire leadership style). Therefore, this research highlights the need for increased dialogue and collaboration between national and local actors. The evidence suggests that local political leaders were able to get extra funding from national government by advocating for local innovative strategies to improve H&SC (Interviewee I1, 2022). Thus, local political leaders who actively engage in advocacy efforts are important to influence national funding priorities and promote a more participatory and responsive approach to integrated governance.

This discussion highlights the uncertain condition of H&SCI, but it also suggests that there are many opportunities for improvement and further research. One area of interest is that providing adequate resources and support to local actors is essential for navigating financial constraints effectively (Bianchi et al., 2021). For instance, studies have indicated that mayoral leadership can influence local government resource allocation decisions by shaping the agenda, framing the issues, mobilizing support, and negotiating with other actors (Heinelt et al., 2018). By exercising different types of leadership styles and strategies, collaborative governance initiatives can leverage the political capital and legitimacy of mayors to advance local interests and achieve desirable outcomes. To make this happen, there is a need to promote more devolution and empowerment approaches on local decision-making and accountability in H&SCI. Research has shown that these approaches can improve service quality and outcomes when they are implemented effectively against centralised influences (McKenna and Dunn, 2015; Dickinson et al., 2012). However, there are also challenges associated with devolution and empowerment, such as the need for strong leadership and effective coordination.

While situational leadership, devolution, and empowerment can be effective strategies for improving H&SC services, the evidence indicates that they may not be sufficient in deprived economic conditions. In such challenging economic circumstances, local political leaders may face frustrations and complaints from constituents, potentially leading to domineering leadership styles in their desire to address their constituents' immediate needs that might lead to undermine transparency, accountability, and stakeholders' participation (Ansell and Gash, 2008). The direct

leadership style adopted by local political leaders highlights the difficulty of balancing competing priorities in integrated governance. The evidence highlights the key challenges of balancing the needs of constituents with the need to maintain efficiency savings. In this context, a collaborative leadership style, effective mechanisms for stakeholder engagement, information sharing, and decision-making can help to address these challenges and promote more inclusive and effective governance (Ansell & Gash 2008; Douglas et al., 2020). However, emphasis collaboration can also be more decentralized and result in blurred accountability lines. To navigate these contrasting perspectives, a nuanced and context-specific approach to leadership in integrated governance might be needed. Local actors can balance competing priorities by developing a flexible leadership style that suits the changing contexts.

Furthermore, the effective financial management of the H&SC system involves optimizing budgets, and employing a cooperative leadership approach that integrates diverse perspectives and delegates power to professional stakeholders (Interviewee A, 2022; Interviewee I, 2022). Strategic thinking is essential for resource optimization, balancing priorities related to staffing, medication provision, and patient care (see Table 8.2.1). Therefore, this study highlights the importance of careful resource allocation in improving healthcare access and outcomes, and acclaims the collaboration with officers, professionals, and frontline workforce as a potentially effective strategy to achieve this goal. This co-operative approach has the potential to promote transparency and accountability in financial management across Scotland. A key element of this approach is its reliance on skilled officers to navigate complex fiscal landscapes and constraints, with a focus on teamwork and integration of diverse perspectives and expertise. Existing literature supports the importance of leadership and teamwork in financial management, particularly in healthcare management, where collaborative leadership styles are associated with positive outcomes such as improved efficiency, reduced costs, and enhanced service quality (West et al., 2015; Moore, Elliott, and Hesselgreaves, 2023).

However, delegating too much authority to officers could undermine the role of local political leaders in financial decision-making. While relying on skilled professionals for financial management is important, it is also important for local political leaders to understand financial matters to make informed decisions and ensure transparency and accountability. Training programmes can equip them with financial knowledge and skills (Audit, 2022; Interviewee A1, 2022). Therefore, there is a need to have that balance in a local approach that fosters collaboration with senior officials and keeps necessary check and balances. According to the Local Government Association (2023), sector-led improvement is based on the principles of strong political and managerial leadership, peer support and challenge, benchmarking performance, using comparable

data, and sharing good practice. This approach can help local actors to improve their services and outcomes, learn from each other, and balance competing priorities.

As representatives of their communities, local political leaders have a duty to review, evaluate, and provide oversight of the financial plans and proposals presented by senior officials (Interviewee F, 2022; Interviewee I, 2022; Interviewee E, 2022). For example, in the case of IJBs, they can use their oversight powers to ensure that the work of officers is in line with political priorities and that any potential concerns are addressed. The preparation of plans is usually the domain of the officers, but they have to finalise them with the consultation of local political leaders (Interviewee I1, 2021; Interviewee F1, 2021). One of the reasons for more officer involvement in these matters could be that political leaders may not have the time or bandwidth to handle all financial matters. Therefore, it is crucial to balance delegating authority to skilled professionals and ensuring sufficient knowledge and oversight of local political leaders. Clear guidelines and protocols for financial decision-making, with regular reporting and oversight mechanisms, can help achieve this balance. This ensures decisions are transparent and accountable, while allowing skilled professionals to handle day-to-day financial management.

Therefore, this study highlights the need of compliance with IJB guidelines which are critical for segregated budget mergers. This research also highlights the importance of collaborative, pragmatic, strategic, delegated and co-operative leadership that has a potential to enable effective financial management, transparency, and accountability. It emphasizes investing in skilled officers and fostering a decentralized approach that integrates diverse perspectives and expertise, in particular related to economy and financial governance. Effective financial management requires strategic thinking and planning that considers the needs and priorities of stakeholders such as healthcare professionals, patients, and policymakers. Therefore, a multi-disciplinary approach to integrated governance is necessary to address complex challenges and integrate diverse perspectives and expertise.

In this section, this research has discussed the different leadership styles that local political leaders adopt in response to economic and financial challenges. Table 8.2.1 below summarizes these styles.

Table 8.2.1: Relationship between Economic and Financial Governance and Leadership Styles.

Economic and Financial Context	Leadership Approach	Example
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Segregated funding streams	Partially integrated leadership approach	A local political leader (F, 2022) emphasizes the importance of collaboration and partnership building in financial decision-making, have identified attempts to merge budgets through initiatives such as examining unscheduled care and reducing unnecessary hospital admissions, but ring-fencing of funds leads to ineffective communication.
Resource limitations	Pragmatic and cautious leadership approach	Local political leader (C, 2022) acknowledges the budgetary challenge in delivering essential services, recognizing the constraints, and emphasizing collaboration with other actors for integrated governance.
Financial constraints	Limited autonomy, Laissez-faire leadership	Local political leader (C, 2022) highlights the difficulties faced by local political leaders in balancing the budget within the complex landscape and their limited control over financial resources. These constraints contribute to limitations in decision-making aligned with community needs.
Economic deprivation	Domineering leadership approach	Senior official (G1, 2021) acknowledges that when constituents express complaints and frustrations towards them, it can potentially prompt local political leaders to adopt an authoritarian leadership style.
Financial stewardship	Strategic thinking, planning and	Local political leader (A, 2022) emphasizes the necessity of making informed decisions and adjustments in allocating financial resources, emphasizing the importance of avoiding wasteful expenditure. They

	contingency reserves	propose the strategic redistribution of healthcare burdens to areas with available capacity as a means of managing the healthcare system effectively.
Managerial dependence	Collaborative, co-operative, decentralized approach	According to the local political leader (Interviewee I, 2022), the reliance on skilled officers is essential as it aligns with their designated roles and expertise. The leader acknowledges that officers have extensive experience in managing the council, such as the chief social work officer and the head of finance, and their expertise is valuable for effective governance.

8.2.2: Partisanship

In the dynamic landscape of the Scottish Health and Social Care sector, the complex interplay between partisanship, leadership, and policy implementation has garnered considerable attention in academic literature (Cairney and McGarvey, 2013; Connolly et al., 2021). This scholarly scrutiny underscores the pivotal role played by effective leadership in attaining collective objectives amidst the presence of conflicting interests. Notable academics, including Elgie (2015) and Hlepas et al., (2018), emphasize the significance of comprehending how partisanship shapes leadership styles and decision-making processes in this domain. Building on these findings, it becomes imperative to investigate the practical implications of effective leadership in the Health and Social Care sector in relation to partisanship, particularly by means of a participatory, inclusive, and collaborative approach that has a potential to address the needs of the community and aligns with local concerns in modern governance (Huxham & Vangen, 2005; Brookers and Grint, 2010). The subsequent section delves into this multi-faceted relationship, thereby illuminating the nuanced dynamics confronted by local political leaders amidst the sprawling expanse of Scotland's health and social care political landscape. Table 8.2.2 indicates the correspondence between the leadership styles and partisanship as a contextual factor.

The complex task of navigating the political landscape and reconciling competing interests within the H&SC sector poses a substantial challenge for local political leaders (Wolak, 2020; Waring et al., 2022; Steel, 2022). As shown in Table 8.2.2 partisanship is a potent factor in influencing leadership in H&SC in Scotland, and it can significantly impact leadership styles in a number of ways. For example, one leader commends the importance of adopting an impartial and cross-party collaborative approach that places priority on the welfare of individuals and the broader population to facilitate the successful implementation of policies over political party responsibilities (Interviewee E, 2022). Conversely, another leader illustrates the inherent tensions between fulfilling party responsibilities and protecting local interests, especially when reconciling support for national policies with the preservation of local concerns indicating a strategic and inclusive approach (Interviewee B, 2022). The first approach is promising in terms of leading to more equitable healthcare outcomes, but it is also challenging to implement, as it requires consensus from all stakeholders (Bodin, 2017). It is important that local political leaders prioritise community voices above all else, but it is also important that they take pragmatic steps to receive support from other stakeholders, such as party groups and senior officials (Ansel and Gash, 2008; Bianchi et al., 2021). Further, only emphasising local concerns and needs can also lead to a situation where affluent communities may be more successful at getting their priorities met than deprived communities (Interviewee I, 2022). The second approach also indicates difficulties for local actors to manage competing priorities that may lead to inequities in healthcare outcomes, as disagreeing with national government agenda may have consequences in terms of getting reduced funding from national accounts given the dependence of IJBs on national government finances, because the evidence indicates the good relationship with national level which enabled local actors to get extra funding for their innovative initiatives (Interviewee I1, 2021).

Therefore, one of the best approaches to implementing healthcare policies may depend on the specific context. In some cases, it may be necessary to adopt a more impartial approach, while in other cases, it may be necessary to reconcile national party responsibilities with local concerns. Ultimately, the decision of which approach to take can be made on a situation-by-situation basis. The impact of partisanship on integrated governance and local political leadership style underscores the importance of enhanced collaboration and co-operation among different tiers of government as well as flexibility in leadership approaches. This research indicates that by fostering dialogue and co-operation between national, and local levels, the challenges posed by partisanship can be effectively addressed.

Furthermore, as highlighted, collaboration among different political parties has the potential to facilitate effective policy implementation. The Scottish Conservatives and Labour Party leaders were

more likely to support local autonomy and more decentralized approach to funding (Interviewee F, 2022; Interviewee A, 2022), whereas the SNP local political leaders were likely to be less critical to centralised funding for H&SC programmes (Interviewee H, 2022), but the SNP and Labour have the same approach to H&SCI because they have similar ideological beliefs that help them to work together (Interviewee F, 2022). This indicates a situational leadership style as political leaders agree and disagree on various issues depending on the subject at hand (see Table 8.2.2). Existing literature also substantiates this; for instance Sørensen et al., (2020) examine how political boundary-spanning - the ability of politicians to operate at the interface between collaborative governance and representative policy making - can foster trust, legitimacy and accountability in collaborative governance processes. However, cross - party co-operation in healthcare is not always effective or desirable, as it may create conflicts of interest and undermine the impartiality and neutrality that is crucial for effective collaborative governance. When politicians are involved in both collaborative governance and representative policy making, there is a risk of prioritizing their political agenda and party interests over the broader goals of collaboration and public interest. This can lead to biased decision-making and erode the trust and legitimacy of the integrated governance process. For instance, a study by Wonka (2022) highlights that political parties and interest groups use policy frames and constituency frames to advocate their positions in legislative policymaking, and that the use of these frames varies between radical and moderate parties.

While ideological differences and different political agendas can impede collaboration and consensus-building, situational and inclusive leadership styles can facilitate these processes (see Table 8.2.2). To surmount these obstacles, local political leaders can benefit from adopting adaptive leadership styles, forge relationships and foster trust across party lines, and actively seek common ground to effectively navigate through disagreements (Leach and Wilson, 2002). Finding common ground out of disagreements can be a useful strategy to keep the business going (Wolak, 2020) and this can be achieved through creating more opportunities for collaboration, such as joint committees, task forces, and working groups, to facilitate information-sharing and decision-making (Bryson et al, 2006; Hudson et al., 2019), which can help to bridge ideological differences (Elgie, 2017). Therefore, cross-party co-operation in H&SCI should be approached with caution and evaluated on a case-by-case basis.

Furthermore, the encroachment of power and political interference in local governance is a vexing issue with detrimental consequences in Scotland. It was suggested that political connections had been used to influence the decision-making process (Interviewee A, 2022), potentially compromising local autonomy and control. For example, a care home proposal rejected by the IJB due to resource strain was approved through national political connections, undermining

local directives and autonomy. This exemplifies how political connections beyond formal structures can influence decision-making, potentially compromising local autonomy and leaving local actors with hands off approach (Laissez-faire leadership style) as shown in Table 8.2.2.

This is not an isolated incident. A recent study by DLHUC (2020) found that ineffective political leadership and political interference is a widespread problem in local governance in the UK. This can manifest itself in a number of ways, such as: lack of strategic direction; poor decision making; inability to challenge or scrutinise performance; lack of accountability; and inappropriate interference in operational matters. These behaviours can undermine the confidence and morale of officers, create confusion and conflict, and damage the reputation and credibility of the council. Nevertheless, political interference is not necessarily always a problem for local governance, as it may reflect the legitimate interests and preferences of the electorate, enhance the responsiveness and accountability of local officials (Interviewee H, 2022), or facilitate the co-ordination and co-operation between different levels of government (Mfuru et al., 2018; Interviewee H, 2022). Therefore, to address the problem of political interference, it is important to strike a delicate equilibrium between centralized authority and local autonomy. There is the potential to find ways to empower local actors while also ensuring that decisions are made in the best interests of the community as a whole (Ansell and Gash, 2008). One way to do this is to increase transparency and accountability in decision-making. This can be done by publishing more information about decision-making processes e.g., how certain issues has been prioritised over others, the difficulty of reaching consensus among a diverse group of people and by giving the public a greater say in how decisions are made.

Another way to address the problem of political interference is to strengthen the capacity of local integrated H&SC services. In the Scottish context political interference arose from capacity issues at a local level regarding primary care for the elderly (Interviewee A, 2022). It is very important to continuously evaluate the capacities of H&SCI and introduce improved changes. The integrated system has the capacity to address these issues and improve health outcomes. Goodwin and Smith, (2011) substantiated this approach, revealing that the adoption of the integrated primary care model yields notable benefits, including improved care quality, enhanced patient outcomes, and reduced healthcare costs. Moreover, political interference may not have a significant impact on local governance outcomes, as other factors such as institutional capacity, civic engagement, or socio-economic conditions may be more important (Copus et al., 2021). Therefore, political interference in local governance can be understood as a complex and context-dependent phenomenon that may have positive or negative effects depending on the situation.

In conclusion, the presence of partisanship within the Scottish local political landscape presents formidable hurdles in achieving efficient policy implementation and enhancing social care services. Nonetheless, through the adoption of a more inclusive and collaborative leadership and governance approach, local political leaders can effectively confront these challenges and ensure the provision of exceptional healthcare services to their respective communities. This research indicates that by amalgamating the imperative for a consensual approach to governance, the resolution of power dynamics, and the adoption of innovative care models, local leaders can adeptly navigate the complexities associated with encroaching power, political interference, and resource limitations. The adoption of this approach engenders a climate of collaboration, bolstering the collective efforts of stakeholders.

Table 8.2.2 summarizes the different combinations of partisanship context and leadership styles that have been found in research. The table also includes supporting evidence for these findings.

Table 8.2.2: Relationship between Responsibilities Towards Political Party and Leadership styles.

Political context	Leadership style	Example
Cross-partisan collaboration	Collaborative and inclusive leadership approach	Local political leader E (2022) builds trust and common ground with different political parties by emphasizing the organization's people-focused approach and the importance of making decisions based on what is best for them despite political pressures surrounding funding.
'Balancing' support for a national policy with the local needs.	Inclusive and strategic leadership style	Local political leader (B, 2022) acknowledges the tension between supporting the National Care Service and protecting the interests of their local community.
Ideological dynamics	Situational leadership	The local political leader (F, 2022) acknowledges political differences and tensions, especially in the context of party politics and ideological beliefs. They

		recognize that there may not be significant differences in the approach to Health and Social Care between political parties and prioritize the community's needs over partisan politics.
Shadow alliances	Hands off approach or lassies fare leadership	Local political leader (A, 2022) alleges that the care home owner obtained planning permission through political connections with the Scottish Government, disregarding objections from the local council. The local political leader expresses opposition to the construction of a new care home, citing concerns about its potential impact on local primary care.

8.2.3 Political-Administrative relationship

Political-administrative networking is an important factor in the governance of H&SCI as it has an impact on the course of the direction that the IJB agenda and leadership takes. These relationships generally are described as helpful but open to political and bureaucratic influences thereby determined by the varying situations. Therefore, with a specific focus on decision-making, collaboration, and leadership, this section seeks to discuss valuable insights into the interplay of trust, respect, transparency, in fostering effective connections between political leaders and senior officials. Moreover, the evidence highlights the key challenges i.e., competing priorities, budgetary conflicts, and IJB members turnover that strain these relationships. These strengths and challenges are presented in Table 8.2.3 in the form of combinations of political- administrative contexts and their relationship with different leadership styles. The existing literature that highlights the significance of collaboration among stakeholders in enhancing health and social care outcomes was helpful in building evaluating arguments, as evidenced by Bianchi et al., (2021), Nabatchi & Leighninger (2015) and Alderwick et al., (2021).

In the Scottish H&SC sector, positive relationships between local political leaders and senior officials are vital for effective governance. Trust, respect, transparency, polite behaviour, clear

communication, and acknowledgement of each other's strengths are identified as key factors that often facilitate positive relationships, ultimately leading to a collaborative and participatory leadership styles (Table 8.2.3). The evidence suggests that the positive nature of relationships has a potential to facilitate teamwork, support, and consensus-building, which are all essential for delivering high-quality services to the public (Audit, 2018). For example, the relationships built on trust and respect can create an environment conducive to collaboration, where different stakeholders can come together, share ideas, and work towards common goals (Interviewee E, 2022; Interviewee F, 2022; Interviewee B1, 2021; Interviewee C1, 2022). Clear communication and transparency further enhance the quality of relationships, ensuring that information is shared openly in mutually reliant environments, and decision-making processes are inclusive (Interviewee B, 2022; Interviewee H, 2022; Zeffane et al., 2011). As shown in Table 8.2.3, by recognizing interdependency and leveraging the expertise and contributions of all stakeholders, local political leaders can often harness the collective intelligence and experiences of the team, leading to more informed and effective decision-making (Interviewee A, 2022; Interviewee I, 2021; Interviewee B, 2022; Interviewee E, 2022; Interviewee H, 2022). For example, local political leader B (2022) reveals that, by utilizing good relationships, they can often effectively pool their resources, share expertise, and develop more comprehensive plans.

However, previous research suggests that an excessive emphasis on collaboration may not always yield positive outcomes, particularly when there is a need to challenge unwise political decisions with bureaucratic resistance. In such scenarios, a more assertive leadership style may become crucial to ensure independent advice and resist undue political pressure (Hecl, 1977; Hecl, 2011). In this study, the findings converge with this existing literature, while also offering a slightly different perspective. The evidence indicates that the local political leader in question prioritized the interests of the local communities when making decisions, often at the expense of adhering to bureaucratic constraints (Interviewee B, 2022). This implies that under certain circumstances or situations, community needs and preferences can supersede the established bureaucratic processes and considerations (see table 8.2.3). It highlights a form of resistance to the intentions of senior officials, indicating a tension between bottom-up community-driven decision-making and top-down bureaucratic control. This resulted in a strained relationship between political actors and senior officials. One way to address this is to encourage more communities to participate (co-production) in decision-making processes (Interviewee C1, 2022). This approach could entail communities taking on a greater share of the responsibility for decisions currently made by local political leaders on their behalf, granting them a more substantial role in shaping the governance of their communities. This would be a more democratic and equitable approach to decision making

(Interviewee C1, 2022) and it would assist in reducing political-administrative relationship challenges. These ideas also align with modern debates around citizen assemblies that encourage greater role and direct involvement of communities in a decision-making process. However, the citizen representation in policy spaces comes with its own challenges, prominently accountability measures and ensuring balanced contributions from all walks of life (Bussu, 2022).

The evidence suggests that the senior officials play a critical role in shaping political-administrative relationships as shown in table 8.2.3. These officials can foster a climate of transparency, mutual respect, and constructive exchange of ideas, which can create an empowering environment for local political leaders and officers to freely share invaluable information and insights (Interviewee F, 2022; Interviewee H1,2021). This finding aligns with existing literature on leadership and organizational culture, which consistently emphasizes the indispensable role of leadership in cultivating effective relationships among key stakeholders (Northouse, 2018). However, the chief officer's ability to influence political-administrative relationships is not absolute. The findings of this research also indicates that there are other factors that can influence these relationships, such as the IJBs rules and procedures, the finances, and stakeholder's cultural considerations. For instance, there are situations when stakeholders deviate from collaborative norms which are stated in a IJB rule book and in these situations local political leaders may need to assert their authority to ensure adherence (Interviewee E,2022). This might sometimes lead to tensions between them. Further, the relationships are affected by the pervasive challenges inherent in governance system, encompassing issues such as budgetary conflicts and the frequent turnover of Integration Joint Board (IJB) members. While budgetary conflicts can certainly be a source of tension between senior official sand local political leaders (Fisher et al.,2020), they have a potential to be an opportunity for the parties to find a common ground. Current H&SCI is in a need of more collaboration and co-operation between parties to find a solution to financial governance problems. When local political leaders and senior officials are able to work together to resolve budgetary conflicts, it can actually strengthen their relationships and can make the financial governance more effective in the long run as suggested by the Scottish Government and Audit Scotland (Joint Act, 2014; Audit 2018). As shown in Table 8.2.3, in the face of dealing with economic and financial challenges there are opportunities for local political leaders to negotiate extra funding for their innovative projects using their trust-based relationships with national levels (Interviewee I1, 2022).

In addition, the study's findings on the IJB members turnover are open to interpretation, as they can be seen to support both positive and negative views on the issue. Local political leaders are concerned that the policy of trade unions of not replacing members every three years prevents

new ideas from coming in to the IJB. Senior officials, on the other hand, are concerned that the turnover of new members impedes the relationship between the IJB and the senior officials because the new members are not aware of, or equipped well enough, to work with the IJB teams. These insights add complexity to the understanding of decision-making dynamics in the context of IJBs' local governance. While transparency, collaboration, and inclusivity are vital qualities (Emerson & Nabatchi, 2015; Bianchi et al., 2021), they require a careful balance with the judicious exercise of situational leadership for effective governance. In response to these challenges, this research posits a series of strategic interventions that place a premium on cultivating robust relationships, offering training and resources to facilitate fruitful collaboration (Audit, 2022), and nurturing a supportive work environment characterized by teamwork and civility (Interviewee A, 2022). In addition, this stresses the pivotal role of mentorship and guidance from local political leaders in empowering new IJB members, augmenting their comprehension of the local political landscape, and fortifying their collaborative engagement with other senior officials. Through harnessing relationships at both local and national levels, initiatives centred around integrated governance hold the potential to yield favourable outcomes (Interviewee I1, 2021). These recommendations align with prior scholarship, which underscores the salience of organizational culture in fostering effective relationships and decision-making processes (Denison and Mishra, 1995; Weare et al., 2014; Aydin 2018)

Moving forward, these findings align with recent scholarship suggesting a more nuanced and blurred distinction between local political leaders and senior officials in the context of H&SCI (Forbes, 2008; Emerson and Nabatchi, 2015; Clarke et al., 2021). Rather than a clear separation, there is a sense of collaborative and interdependent work between these actors. They recognize the importance of working together and acknowledge the value of each other's strengths, expertise, and knowledge. There is a growing recognition that administrative leadership and political leadership are interconnected and that both roles contribute to the overall governance and functioning of the health and social care system (Clarke et al., 2021). This recognition challenges the traditional separation between public politics and public administration. While the majority of local political leaders and senior officials maintain a distinction between the roles of elected politicians and appointed administrators, there is a conscious effort to foster collaboration and maintain open lines of communication (e.g., Åström et al., 2022). This suggests a shift towards a more integrated approach, where administrative leaders actively engage with political leaders and vice versa, recognizing the importance of collective decision-making and shared responsibilities. This recognition of shared goals and mutual reliance contributes to a more cohesive and effective leadership dynamic.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that this study's findings are based on a specific context and may not be directly applicable to other health and social care systems. Future research could explore how political-administrative relationships vary across different contexts and examine the factors that facilitate or hinder their effectiveness. In addition, studies could explore the long-term outcomes of positive political-administrative relationships on health and social care governance and performance.

Table 8.2.3: Relationship between Political-Administrative Context and Leadership Styles.

Context	Leadership style	Example
Mutually reliant	Teamwork and polite behaviour	Local political leader A (2022) prioritizes building trust with officers by demonstrating polite behaviour and promoting teamwork to get information to make informed decisions, leveraging their prior experience in both the oil industry and council. Local Political Leaders E (2022) and I (2022) appreciate and respect the professional expertise of senior officers.
Interdependency	Collaborative and participatory leadership style	The local political leader B ((2022) prioritizes building partnerships and recognizing interdependence to achieve common goals in the health and social care sector, as demonstrated through regular meetings and good governance practices.
Negotiating	Adaptive leadership	Local political leader B (2022) experienced a strained relationship as they had to navigate the tension between community demands and bureaucratic constraints. Ultimately, the leader prioritized addressing the needs

		of the community over conforming to bureaucratic requirements.
Chief Officer-mediated relationship dynamics	Collaborative and participative	Local political leader F (2022) experienced a better relationship with the second chief officer, who was open to discussion and constructive criticism, compared to the first chief officer who was focused on making progress, making discussions difficult.
Networking	Trust-based approach	Senior official I1 (2021) acknowledges the beneficial relationship between local political leaders and the national government, enabling them to secure additional funding and implement innovative approaches.

8.2.4: The Influence of IJB's Size

Building upon the continuing discourse surrounding local political leadership in integrated governance and the influence of political context, this discussion continues to explore the complex relationship between the size of IJBs and the leadership style employed within them. As shown in Table 8.2.4, the local political leaders face varying influences working in different board sizes including small, large, and optimal. These mixed teams' conditions in different IJB areas enable local political leaders to be adaptable and flexible, which can often be a huge advantage in complex and rapidly changing environments. By shedding light on the complexity of these processes, this study presents unparalleled insights into the dynamic interplay between board size, leadership style, and the resultant effectiveness of decision-making mechanisms.

Large, IJBs represent a paradox in the context of effective governance. On one hand, they encompass a broad spectrum of expertise and viewpoints, which promotes a more inclusive leadership style and could potentially yield more resilient decision-making processes (Interviewee A1, 2022; Interviewee C1, 2022; Interviewee A, 2022). On the other hand, the extensive size of IJBs may pose logistical and operational challenges. Local stakeholders in H&SCI have voiced

apprehensions regarding the impediment larger boards may pose to the detailed scrutiny of agendas, as illustrated in Table 8.2.4. They indicate a likelihood of escalated time commitments and bureaucratic obstacles. This observation is consistent with the findings of Goodstein et al. (1994), which posit that although larger and heterogeneous boards enhance governance, they often encounter difficulties in executing strategic changes.

However, the study also identified effective practices that can mitigate these challenges. Competent officers, clear roles and responsibilities, sub-committees, consensus-building mechanisms, and consistent communication can all contribute to a well-functioning large board (Interviewee A, 2021; Interviewee C1, 2022). When large boards are supported by these elements, they operate optimally (Interviewee A, 2021). These findings are consistent with the Scottish Government's 2015 policy recommendation to ensure stakeholder and community diversity in IJB composition. Interestingly, this study shows that local political leaders within large boards adopt a pragmatic leadership approach that focuses on improving board performance and achieving goals, rather than worrying too much about large board size. This adaptive and flexible leadership style is often helpful in navigating the complexities of IJBs for local political leaders and is consistent with previous studies in complex healthcare settings (Yukl and Mahsud, 2010; Ramadas et al., 2018), which confirms the importance and relevance of the current study's empirical findings.

Furthermore, decision-making processes in integrated governance structures are multi-faceted and require a nuanced approach. While large boards have their advantages and disadvantages, collaborative leadership styles can also be beneficial. As Table 8.2.4 shows, local political leaders have suggested that working in a smaller area can also have advantages, such as building relationships based on trust and familiarity with senior officials and political opposition indicating collaborative leadership approach (Interviewee B, 2022). As shown in Section 7.4, small boards often contribute to improved collaboration and good governance practices (Interviewee B, 2022). This perspective highlights the importance of contextual factors in decision-making processes and finds its relevance in existing literature. For instance, the first study, conducted by Bianchi et al. (2021), found that smaller groups were more effective in reducing transaction costs in an inter-agency collaborative governance initiative in New Zealand. The second study, conducted by van der Jagt et al., (2017), which focused on urban gardens in the Netherlands, found that small core groups of volunteers were essential for sustainability. This research also indicated that, in these small intimate settings, members were more likely to engage in constructive dialogue, share diverse perspectives, and work collaboratively towards common goals. Nevertheless, it is important to consider the potential conflicts of interest or biases that may arise in smaller boards, as well as the potential limitation of diverse perspectives. Comprehensive decision-making requires input from

various stakeholders, and a smaller board may have limitations in providing this diversity. Therefore, a balanced approach to board size and representation in integrated governance is needed.

In conclusion, this study has found that board size has a significant impact on leadership practices in integrated governance. Boards with smaller sizes tend to be promoting trust and collaboration, while boards with larger sizes tend to be more inclusive but lacking effective scrutiny. This study emphasizes the need for an optimal approach to board size and composition in integrated governance. It provides valuable insights into the benefits of both larger and smaller boards, depending on the context and stakeholder dynamics. Table 8.2.4 summarizes the key findings of this study.

Table 8.2.4: Relationship between IJB’s Size as Contextual Factor and Leadership Styles.

Context	Leadership styles	Example
Optimal boards	Inclusive leadership	Local political leader (Interviewee A, 2022) argues a large board to be optimal for effective problem-solving, as it accommodates a variety of voices and experiences. It is important to be supported by competent officers.
Large Board Size leads to overwhelming workload	Pragmatic and proactive approach	Local political leader (F, 2022) suggests that the large size of IJBs can limit the role of local political leaders in integrated governance and can hinder effective scrutiny.

Small board size	Collaborative, trust-based and promote personal relationships	Leader (B,2022) emphasizes the importance of building trustful relationships and working in a small area with pre-existing relationships, which can foster collaborative governance.
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8.2.5: The influence of geography (Rural/urban)

The evidence related to geographical considerations suggests that urban and rural contexts can have a significant influence on local actors’ leadership styles and approaches in H&SCI. Table 8.2.5 summarizes the key evidence of the section. This evidence contributes to the discourse surrounding the influence of urban/rural context on local political leadership styles in a number of different ways. First, it provides empirical support for the idea that, in Scottish H&SCI, there is a difference between urban and rural leadership styles. Secondly, it suggests that specific challenges and opportunities of rural and urban H&SC governance shape the way that local leaders approach their role in IJBs. Thirdly, this uncovers diverse leadership approaches, including participatory, collaborative, innovative, directive, and community-based paradigms. Furthermore, it sheds light on the intricate challenges prevalent in urban/rural healthcare provision, including limited funding streams, workforce scarcities, and deprivations levels. These insights augment the existing knowledge by providing a nuanced understanding of the strategies and considerations necessary for delivering healthcare services effectively in urban/rural settings.

Local political leaders in rural areas are often more closely connected to their communities than their urban counterparts. One of the reasons is that the rural communities tend to be smaller and more tightly knit, and local political leaders often have a long history of involvement in the community (Downes, 1968; Love and Powe, 2020). Rural communities are often more dependent on local government for services and face more problems than their urban counterparts (Nuffield Trust, 2020), which means that local political leaders have a greater role to play in the lives of their constituents. As a result, it can be argued that local political leaders in rural areas are often more aware of the needs of their constituents. This study also observed this trend in Scotland, as local political leaders from rural areas spoke more about the challenges and interactions with their

communities and their problems as compared to urban areas (Interviewee E, 2022; Interviewee I, 2022; Interviewee H, 2022; Interviewee, G1, 2021).

As shown in Table 8.2.5, the evidence displays that, through active engagement with rural communities, local leaders can acquire first-hand knowledge of the specific challenges faced, including transportation limitations and limited healthcare access in H&SCI. The methods encouraged by local actors to collaborate effectively with rural communities are unconventional and innovative instead of traditional ones e.g., lunch clubs. These advanced methods have the potential to be effective for a number of reasons. First, they are often more flexible and responsive to the needs of specific rural communities; for instance, when local actors go to informal places such as a lunch club, the evidence suggests that community members share their problems more comfortably than formal surgery appointments (Interviewee E, 2022). Secondly, they can be more inclusive, as they can help to build relationship between local actors and rural residents. Thirdly, this consultative and community-oriented approach of local actors aligns with the importance of community inclusion highlighted in previous studies (Ansell et al., 2020; Bianchi et al., 2021), particularly in the context of Scottish rural areas where community attachment to local services and hospitals is very strong (interviewee B, 2022; Interviewee H1, 2022). This research indicates that by actively involving stakeholders and allowing community members to voice their concerns, local leaders have the potential to foster trust, transparency, and a sense of ownership, enabling decision-makers to make more informed and contextually appropriate decisions in rural context (Interviewee B, 2022).

These findings make a meaningful contribution to the scholarly discourse on leadership and governance by emphasizing the need for leaders to transcend traditional roles and engage with community members through unconventional means e.g., lunch club interactions and continuous citizens' involvement thereby promoting co-production. This departure from top-down decision-making and formal communication channels has the potential to recognize the unique needs of rural communities more effectively. By embracing participatory and inclusive leadership practices, leaders can bridge the gap between the government and the rural population, leading to more effective representation and governance (Interviewee E, 2022; Interviewee B, 2022; Ansell and Torfing 2021).

However, critics argue that community-based approaches may be time-consuming and resource-intensive, potentially leading to inefficiencies and delays in decision-making processes (Del Gaudio et al., 2017). Margerum (2007) highlighted that practical challenges, such as time constraints and varying community interests, can hinder decision-making efficiency. These complexities necessitate

a delicate balance between involvement and expediency, especially in resource-constrained rural areas. They contend that traditional top-down leadership styles and formal communication channels ensure a more efficient and streamlined governance system (Matshabaphala, 2017). This is evident in the way that some local leaders in Scottish H&SCI often adopt a directive and top-down style that prioritizes efficient care delivery. Critics such as Sanga et al., (2022) caution against exclusive top-down decision-making, emphasizing the importance of community buy-in and inclusivity. These rebuttals shed light on the trade-offs between efficiency and inclusivity, underscoring the significance of situational leadership styles. Therefore, these insights resonate with academics such as Khanal et al., (2023), who underscore the importance of context-specific leadership approaches in addressing the distinct challenges encountered by rural communities.

While top-down approaches can be effective in certain situations, they can also have negative consequences, especially in Scottish rural areas. The problems faced by the workforce in rural areas can make it difficult for leaders to adopt a top-down approach, as they need to be aware of the challenges facing their workforce and develop strategies to address them (Interviewee G1, 2021; Interviewee B, 2022). The lack of available healthcare professionals creates a major barrier for local political leaders and senior officials in achieving their strategic commissioning plan and goals (Interviewee G1, 2021; Skills for Care, 2017; Abelsen et al., 2020). This implies a laissez-faire approach where local leaders have less control over their strategic plans because of workforce uncertainty (Table 8.2.5). However, workforce resourcing is not the only or the most important factor for collaborative governance and rural workforce stability. Other factors, such as the impact of limited infrastructure, geographic isolation, community engagement and underfunding on healthcare delivery, may have a greater impact on the success and sustainability of collaborative initiatives and rural health services. Research conducted by the House of Lords Library, (2023) underscores the significance of these challenges, expanding the discussion beyond workforce shortages. These complexities highlight the need for comprehensive strategies that address not only the workforce aspect but also the broader infrastructure and funding issues. Therefore, workforce resourcing should be considered as one of many elements in a holistic and context-specific approach to collaborative governance and rural workforce development.

In line with this broader perspective, the evidence reveals that some local leaders are often found to be adopting innovative and collaborative approaches offering solutions that address rural healthcare challenges through suggesting the employment of local staff working from home within a specific radius, along with the provision of electric vehicles and grant funding for charging points that might help to reduce the cost. This approach not only offers solution to overcome geographical barriers, but it is, in fact, a cost-effective solution. By leveraging technology and innovative

strategies, this solution aligns with the literature's exploration of alternative workforce models and emphasizes the importance of optimizing resources to meet the specific needs of rural communities (The Local Government Association and Public Health England, 2017). However, it is important to acknowledge that implementing such innovative workforce models may face resistance and practical challenges. Research (NHS England and NHS Improvement, (2019) highlights the need for careful consideration of logistical issues, cost-effectiveness, regulatory frameworks, and stakeholder buy-in when introducing new workforce models in healthcare. In addition, the long-term sustainability and scalability of these models require further investigation and evaluation and the cultural and contextual factors specific to each rural area may influence the feasibility and acceptance of these models, necessitating tailored approaches.

In contrast, local actors in urban IJB areas did not emphasize the ongoing community discussions related to local issues. Instead, they were more inclined to discuss their consideration of broader societal issues such as income disparities, housing challenges, and community engagement to fulfil their commitments (Interviewee F, 2022; Interviewee C, 2022; Interviewee C1, 2022). As shown in Table 8.2.5, they did not view their priorities as being shaped by the rural-urban divide; rather, they perceived local issues as closely tied to family income levels and the underlying factors contributing to these challenges. This perspective and the associated evidence differ from the issues discussed earlier in this section, which highlighted rural problems related to workforce, funding, transportation, and healthcare access. This shift in leadership orientation could be attributed to several factors. For instance, Kenny and Luca (2021) argue that that urban and rural areas have different political and socio-economic attitudes, and that these differences are influenced by both composition and contextual effects. They suggest that urban areas tend to have more cosmopolitan, and progressive views, while rural areas tend to have more nationalist, conservative views. They also claim that urban areas are more exposed to the challenges of globalization, such as immigration, diversity and inequality, while rural areas are more affected by the decline in traditional industries, public services and social capital. These factors may shape the preferences and expectations of local political leaders in different ways. Therefore, local political leaders in urban areas may adopt a more open or strategic approach that prioritizes addressing overarching societal challenges rather than delving into the minutiae of community-level issues, as observed among their rural counterparts.

Nonetheless, the strategic thinking of urban local leaders is not without its challenges. Their approach, which considers issues at a broader level, often necessitates the negotiation of priorities related to deprivation with a wide array of stakeholders involved in the IJBs (Ansell and Gash, 2008). Making decisions based on such a wide consensus has both advantages and disadvantages, as

outlined in the collaborative governance literature. On one hand, it ensures inclusivity, a critical factor for the success of collaborative policy spaces. On the other hand, it can introduce complexities when making a case within the expansive network of integrated governance (Interviewee F1, 2021; Bodin, 2017). However, this research has documented instances where local leaders have argued that success of integration process lies in listening to communities and prioritizing the needs of deprived communities. They have worked to establish transparent distribution systems and accountability mechanisms for allocating grants to these communities. With transparency and accountability in place, there may be increased opportunities to garner support from other stakeholders (Interviewee C1, 2022). Against this backdrop, one common thread identified in both urban and rural areas' leadership is the emphasis on community engagement to solicit input on local priorities and needs in the decision-making process thereby promoting co-production in H&SC sector in Scotland.

Table 8.2.5: Relationship between IJB's Geography (rural/urban) and leadership styles.

Context	Leadership styles	Example
Community-centred Rurality	Community-based leadership approach	Local political leader E (2022) suggest engaging with rural communities through events like community lunches to gather information about their specific needs.
Small nature of Rural area	Consultative and responsive leadership	Local political leader B (2022) emphasizes involving communities as a stakeholder in decision-making processes and ensuring inclusivity in the consultation process. They contend that the small rural nature of the area facilitates that.
		Local political leader H (2022) adopts a more directive

Rural Standardization	Directive and top-down	leadership style, prioritizing effective care delivery to the wider population over maintaining local community attachment to local services and hospitals.
Rural healthcare disparities	Innovative and collaborative approach	Local political leaders E (2022) propose employing local staff who work from home within a 10-15-mile radius, providing them with electric vehicles and grant funding for charging points to save money and retain workforce.
Urban conditions	Strategic leadership focusing on wider problems	Interviewee F (2022) emphasizes the significance of understanding the impact of income and historic family backgrounds on people's health. Instead of focusing solely on the urban/rural divide. Local leaders (C1, and F) recognize deprivation levels, housing problems as a critical lens in urban areas to address health and social care problems (Interviewee F, 2022; Interviewee C1, 2022).

8.2.6: The influence of Frontline Workforce Expectations

The leadership of the H&SCI agenda is shaped by a range of factors, including the expectations of frontline workers. Frontline workers are the backbone of the H&SCI agenda, and their expectations are essential to its success. This study brings to the forefront the critical role played by frontline workers in shaping the trajectory of integrated governance. It unveils their substantial influence on decision-making processes and local political leadership style choices. In this context, the findings align with prior research emphasizing the importance of stakeholder engagement in public policy decision-making (Møller, 2022; Lee, 2022; Bianchi et al., 2021). However, this study extends the existing literature by providing empirical evidence of the specific mechanisms through which frontline workers' input is woven into the fabric of governance frameworks and shapes the leadership styles of local leaders as shown in Table 8.2.6.

In parallel with the prevailing literature on leadership in public policy, this study indicates that local political leaders in Scotland recognize the significant role played by the frontline workforce in achieving their political ambitions. Leaders, on the one hand, acknowledge that frontline workers expect direction from the collective leadership of the board (Interviewee F, 2022). On the other hand, these leaders also value the knowledge and expertise of frontline workers regarding the realities of health and social care at the grassroots level, actively seeking their input and striving for consensus in the decision-making processes as shown in Table 8.2.6 (Interviewee E, 2022; Interviewee H, 2022; Interviewee H1, 2022). While not always immediately embracing frontline approaches, the local leaders can be convinced through open discussions and deliberations. At times local political leaders may decline frontline proposals, exercising their authority (Interviewee E, 2022). This aligns with research that acknowledges the challenges of accommodating all frontline workers and stakeholders' preferences in decision-making processes. Public policy decisions involve complex trade-offs and competing interests, making it difficult to incorporate every perspective. According to this argument, collaborative governance involves too many actors with diverse and conflicting interests, values, and perspectives, which makes it difficult to reach consensus and coordinate actions (Bodin, 2017). Therefore, striking a balance between stakeholder input and efficient decision-making is a key consideration for policymakers.

There are many potential leadership styles that can be used to manage frontline stakeholders. In this study, some of these are characterized by a consultative, principled, responsive, and result-oriented, empathetic and strategic approach, that facilitates the frontline workforce during the implementation of H&SC policies (see Table 8.2.6). This research indicates that leaders can benefit

by adopting such a style to address the needs and challenges faced by frontline workers, recognizing their crucial role in achieving effective governance outcomes. These findings build upon previous research which emphasizes the significance of engaging with diverse stakeholders and frontline workers comprehending their perspectives to facilitate effective decision-making and implementation. For instance, Lipsky (2010) and Kalkman & Groenewegen (2019) note that frontline workers can play a crucial role in implementing collaborative governance initiatives, as they are often the ones who interact directly with citizens and stakeholders. They suggest that involving frontline workers in the design and implementation of collaborative governance initiatives can help to build trust and legitimacy among stakeholders. These findings are also consistent with the recent report by Walsh and de Sarandy (2023), who define an effective leadership in collaborative governance as something which can create a safe, inclusive, and trusting environment in which all can contribute fully and openly to achieving an agreed shared goal. Their identified key areas, such as building relationships and managing power dynamics, empower frontline workers to drive coordinated care across health and social services.

However, this research indicates that some local leaders regret ignoring the voices of frontline workforces, and that regret is understandable. Frontline workforces are often the ones who are closest to service users (Lipsky, 2010), and they have valuable insights into what is needed to improve the service. If a leader does not listen to their frontline workforce, they are potentially missing out on a valuable source of information. Nevertheless, it is important to consider that the influence of the democratic process, which typically follows majority rule in decision-making, may have pressured the leader in this instance to make the decision despite not listening to their frontline workers (Interviewee A, 2022). For instance, in this case the majority of IJB members decided to ignore the feedback gathered from frontline staff, and perhaps the local leader was under pressure to make this decision. In these cases, it is possible that leader made the best decision they could in the situation that they were facing at the time. But it still raises questions about how leaders balance their personal principles with broader decision-making dynamics and organizational pressures. This also opens up a discussion about the relevance of principled or idealistic leadership styles in decision-making processes (Moore and Bazerman, 2022). The leaders expressed concerns and regrets, which highlight their commitment to learning from mistakes and prioritizing the well-being of frontline staff.

In contrast to the leader who regretted not listening to their frontline workforce, another leader managed the expectations using empathy and strategy. This approach led to proactive measures to address frontline workforce issues like domestic abuse (see Table 8.2.6). There are two factors that helped this leader to achieve this. First, the leader's previous work experience in the sector gave

them a deep understanding of the challenges frontline workforce face. This understanding allows the leader to empathetically understanding the frontline workers' needs (Interviewee H, 2022). Secondly the leaders' proactive thinking is an important asset in mitigating challenges. By thinking ahead, the leader can identify potential problems and develop strategies to address them. This can help prevent problems from occurring in the first place, or it can help to minimise the impact of problems if they do occur. This finding contributes to the existing literature by emphasizing the significance of prioritizing the well-being of frontline workers through an empathetic and strategic leadership approaches. According to Crayne and Medeiros (2021), compassion is a key leadership skill that goes beyond empathy and involves understanding and acting to alleviate the suffering of others. However, it is crucial to acknowledge and critically engage with the counterarguments raised against integrating frontline workers' input into decision-making processes. Academics contend that frontline workers, while possessing valuable on-the-ground knowledge, may lack the broader strategic perspective necessary for making high-level decisions that align with organizational goals. Moreover, within the hierarchical structure of public organizations, power dynamics and entrenched bureaucratic procedures can present formidable challenges in effectively integrating frontline workers' input (Bianchi et al., 2021). Reflections of this are evident in the comments of local political leader E (2022). They implemented their Social Work plan without following frontline guidelines due to broader financial constraints, as illustrated in Table 8.2.6.

Nevertheless, this study maintains that a nuanced examination of the benefits and challenges is imperative. While acknowledging these potential hurdles, it asserts that the advantages of involving frontline workers in decision-making outweigh the potential drawbacks. By actively considering and incorporating the perspectives and expertise of frontline workers, leaders can tap into a wealth of contextual knowledge, gaining invaluable insights into the operational realities, diverse needs, and potential implications of policy decisions. This participatory approach not only enhances the legitimacy, relevance, and effectiveness of policies and practices but also promotes inclusivity and shared ownership, contributing to a more democratic and responsive governance framework (Bradely and Schneider, 2004; Sørensen and Torfing, 2011).

By critically analysing these findings and their implications, this research contributes to the existing literature on the influence of the frontline workforce and highlights the significance of engaging with diverse stakeholders, considering their perspectives, and acting in the best interest of the public. This comprehensive approach to decision-making helps ensures that the needs and interests of those impacted by decisions are adequately addressed, leading to more effective and ethical governance.

Table 8.2.6: Relationship between Frontline workforce expectations and leadership styles.

Context	Leadership styles	Example
Frontline-centric governance	Consultative, accountability-oriented and responsive approach	Interviewee F (2022) suggests that frontline workers expect the board to collectively take responsibility and demonstrate a clear view of direction. Local political leader (E, 2022) demonstrates attentiveness to the needs of frontline workers and on their advice they redirect resources to more pressing issues.
Frontline resource optimization	Result-oriented and pragmatic approach	The local political leader (E, 2022) emphasizes clear guidance on addressing social work issues within financial constraints. They aim to reduce costs for early intervention and officer visits by redirecting people to gardening or cooking clubs instead of needing assistance. This approach was taken in contrast to the current practices continued by the frontline workforce, who were instructed to be costing more money.
Frontline Workforce related Decision-making dilemma	Principled or idealistic approach	The local political leader A (2022) expressed regret for voting in favour of converting a public practice into a private one, despite the majority of staff and patients opposing it. The leader acknowledged the importance of standing by convictions and prioritizing the

		needs and preferences of those receiving care.
Frontline Domestic abuse advocacy	Empathetic and strategic approach	Local political leader H (2022) addressed domestic abuse issues and advocated for the well-being of frontline staff. In this context, the local political leader leveraged their extensive experience working closely with the frontline workforce for a long time.

8.3 Concluding reflections

This final section reflects upon the dynamic interplay between local political leadership, their leadership styles, and political contexts, examining how these factors influence strategic decision-making within Scotland’s Health and Social Care system. The study’s implications extend to public policy, leadership theory, and the practice of new public governance, focusing on two pivotal questions: the role of local political leaders in H&SC strategic decisions, and the influence of political contexts on their leadership styles. Addressing these questions has revealed insights that enhance our understanding of local governance dynamics, thereby facilitating informed decision-making and policy formulation in the realm of integrated healthcare services. This section will discuss the implications of these findings, providing valuable guidance for practitioners, policymakers, and scholars. It will explore and interpret the significance of the most important findings, demonstrating their potential to inform future research endeavours.

8.3.1 The Role of Local Political Leaders in the Public Service Reform of H&SCI

This study reveals the nuanced and dynamic role of local political leadership in Health & Social Care Integration. Local political leaders are pivotal in shaping strategic decision-making processes. Their responsibilities transcend mere representation; they encompass establishing strategic directions, managing resource allocations, and aligning services with the needs of the community. This emphasis on strategic influence aligns with Connolly et al. (2022), who highlight the importance of local leadership in H&SCI. However, their work primarily focuses on administrative leadership within H&SCI. This research complements that perspective by shedding light on the distinct and influential role of political leaders. For instance, the findings illustrate that local political leaders are instrumental in

fostering collaboration among healthcare providers, social care agencies, and community organizations. This collaborative approach facilitates stakeholder involvement within Integration Joint Boards (IJBs), ultimately contributing to the successful integration of health and social care services (Audit Scotland, 2018).

It is crucial to recognize that the interpretation and impact of local political leaders' roles can vary significantly. These variations hinge on whether they serve as elected members participating as board members in Integration Joint Boards (IJBs) or assume the pivotal role of board chair. As board members, they contribute to decision-making; however, as board chairs, they have the opportunity to drive the agenda and shape outcomes more directly. This finding underscores the critical importance of understanding leadership dynamics within IJBs and contributes to broader debates on New Public Governance (NPG), emphasizing the need for diverse leadership styles within these governance structures. NPG advocates for adaptive, collaborative, and community-oriented approaches to public administration, challenging traditional hierarchical models (Osborne, 2010). The research reinforces this notion by demonstrating how local political leaders, particularly those serving as board chairs, can leverage their positions to prioritize community needs and foster collaboration across stakeholders. This focus on collective well-being aligns with the principles of NPG and challenges earlier assumptions about the diminished role of local leaders during the New Public Management (NPM) era (Dunleavy et al., 2005; El-Ghalayini, 2016). Contrary to the NPM focus on efficiency and market-driven reforms, these reinvigorated local leaders place communities at the forefront of their leadership ethos. Their commitment to community well-being transcends bureaucratic boundaries, reinforcing the transformative potential of NPG in contemporary democratic governance.

This focus on community well-being calls for an expanded conceptualization of accountability, one that may transcend conventional frameworks to include greater responsiveness to the needs of the local population (Erkkilä, 2007). Such an expanded view is not merely theoretical but rooted in the tangible shifts witnessed by this research, where leaders prioritize responsiveness to the local population's needs over rigid adherence to procedural mandates. Consequently, redefining accountability within local governance structures becomes a central tenet of this transformative governance paradigm and leadership model. The study advocates for a dynamic accountability framework that goes beyond traditional electoral duties, underscoring the need for a holistic approach that integrates both horizontal and vertical accountability mechanisms (Lührmann, Marquardt, & Mechkova, 2020).

The proposed dynamic accountability framework is born out of a synthesis of this research's findings and the existing body of knowledge. While vertical accountability remains crucial in ensuring leaders are answerable to the national government for resource allocation, this study underscores the

burgeoning need for robust horizontal accountability. This form of accountability, where leaders are answerable not only to their peers but also to the community at large, is essential in the evolving governance landscape (Erkkilä, 2007).

This paradigm shift towards a more integrated and responsive governance structure aligns with the principles of New Public Governance (NPG). NPG champions adaptability and responsiveness to the diverse needs and interests of stakeholders (Hood, 1991; Liddle, 2021), which resonates with the findings of this research. Effective leadership requires sustained engagement and a dedicated focus on community needs. It is this kind of leadership that can truly transform governance and create a model that is as dynamic and multifaceted as the communities it serves. However, integrated settings in Scotland reveal a critical tension: third sector and private stakeholders, despite making significant contributions to social care service delivery, lack voting rights (Feeley et al., 2021). Reflecting on this, this research argues that there is a need to bolster horizontal accountability mechanisms to ensure that such contributions are not only recognized but also influential (Scottish Government, 2019). Such reinforcement would not only acknowledge these contributions but also empower them to shape outcomes effectively.

Local political leaders, vested with voting rights, play a crucial role in maintaining strong vertical accountability to higher authorities (Scottish Government, 2015). The study calls for the implementation of proactive measures within Integration Joint Boards (IJBs) to address potential power imbalances. Leaders with greater authority have a responsibility to foster inclusive governance, which involves enhancing transparency, empowering all stakeholders, and ensuring their voices are heard in the decision-making process (Joseph-Williams et al., 2014). It is imperative for leaders with voting rights to use their influence to create a just and inclusive environment, rather than marginalizing or overlooking non-voting groups, such as citizen representatives and third sector organizations (Scottish Government, 2022).

Recognizing the necessity for a balanced approach to governance, this research suggests a path forward—one that lies not only in adjusting the scales of power but also in redefining the very nature of decision-making processes (Kaplan et al., 2003). Such a shift compels a move towards co-production, a cooperative and inclusive model that bridges the accountability-engagement gap (Evans et al., 2016). This research highlights the significance of co-production in enhancing governance efficacy (Mukoro, 2023), emphasizing the need for local political leaders to actively involve communities and integrate their perspectives into the decision-making framework. This approach fosters community spirit and trust, challenging the conventional perception that decision-making is a domain solely for administrative authorities (Howlett et al., 2017). By embracing co-production, anchored in the

principles of New Public Governance (NPG), leaders can dismantle entrenched power dynamics and cultivate a governance structure that is transparent, accountable, and reflective of the diverse needs of stakeholders (Howlett et al., 2015; Liddle, 2021). This collaborative approach not only strengthens the legitimacy and effectiveness of governance systems but also paves the way for sustainable and equitable outcomes (Sorrentino et al., 2018).

Co-production offers numerous benefits, yet its practical application comes with inherent challenges. Local political leaders encounter the challenging task of balancing individual community interests, which may at times be at odds with the collective welfare (Fusco et al., 2020). In Scotland, for example, this research suggests that the cultural attachment to local hospitals, notwithstanding their underutilization, presents a dilemma against the need for efficient healthcare resource allocation. This calls for a thoughtful approach to co-production, where leaders must weigh community engagement against the necessity for broader systemic transformations. This requires a deep understanding of local contexts and their impact on broader community health (Evans et al., 2016). The study suggests that decision-making must consider both the immediate and long-term effects on community well-being, necessitating that leaders possess situational awareness and flexibility in their leadership approach (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007).

Furthermore, it is a widely recognized principle that effective leadership often involves driving and facilitating change. Notable sources such as Kotter (2008), Kanter (2007), and Bridges (2009) emphasize that leadership in contemporary governance contexts necessitates a willingness to embrace change. Resistance to change is frequently viewed as incongruent with effective leadership in the modern governance landscape.

8.3.2 The contextual role of local political leaders

This research highlights the significant role of political context in shaping leadership styles within the integration agenda. The manner in which leaders enact their role is subject to change, contingent upon the specific contextual factors they confront. This underscores a central argument that has been consistently highlighted throughout this thesis; namely, that leadership is inherently a contextual process.

In terms of explaining this contextual process, this chapter has shown that the categorisation of political contextual factors is relevant for understanding the role of local political leaders in strategic decision-making. Notably, factors such as economic and financial conditions, political party affiliations, geographical considerations (including the size of an area and urban/rural dynamics),

as well as interactions with senior officials and frontline expectations, have exerted significant influence on the strategic perspectives of local political leaders within the IJBs. However, what emerges from this exploration is a nuanced leadership dynamic within H&SC that defies easy categorization into a singular leadership style, be it trait-based or collaborative. Instead, it portrays local political leaders who adopt a situational leadership approach, demonstrating a capacity to adapt their leadership style to the specific circumstances they encounter. They exhibit an acute awareness of the need for leadership traits such as inclusivity, collaboration, participation, consultation, pragmatism, innovation, and strategic thinking, particularly in response to the ever-evolving political landscapes they navigate. Their varied responses to financial constraints, political partisanship, and geographical considerations highlight the intricate nature of political leadership.

This finding, that leadership within H&SCI is situational, aligns well with contemporary leadership theories that emphasize adaptability and responsiveness (Van Wart, 2013; Boyar et al., 2023). In the dynamic political landscape of Scottish Health and Social Care, leadership is not about possessing inherent traits but rather about effectively navigating complex situations. This study challenges the traditional heroic leadership model, advocating instead for a situational leadership approach. This approach, initially described by Fiedler (1967), and further elaborated by Hersey and Blanchard (1969), acknowledges the fluid nature of leadership and underscores the need for leaders to adjust their style to the prevailing context. The findings of this research suggest that local political leaders in Scotland demonstrate this very approach. This is indicative of a shift from rigid leadership categorizations towards a more flexible and responsive leadership paradigm, aligning with contemporary theories that critique the static nature of traditional leadership categories and emphasize the importance of nimbleness in leadership practice (Stoker, 2017; Cloutier and Barling, 2020; Northhouse, 2021).

Against this background, this study does not present an alternative perspective but rather emphasizes the importance of aligning contemporary leadership styles with the diverse political contexts of today. In response, it proposes an additional leadership style category, specifically designed for local political leaders operating within the complex and contemporary environment of Scottish Health and Social Care. This perspective complements, rather than conflicts with, the established literature that underscores the importance of adapting to prevailing situations as a fundamental aspect of effective leadership (Fiedler, 1967; Hart and Rhodes, 2014). The contribution of this research expands upon this well-established proposition by introducing a nuanced category/typology of leadership styles that are relevant to local political leadership in modern integrated governance (Hartley, 2018). This category, termed the 'integrative leader,' is characterized by vision, inclusivity, participation, pragmatism, cautiousness, engagement, empowerment, laissez-faire leadership, and innovation (Emerson et al.,

2012). It aligns with recent literature that underscores the importance of diversity and inclusion in leadership (Allen, 2017). By incorporating more relevant political contextual factors and leadership styles into the practices of modern local political leaders, this research acknowledges the significance of the prevailing political situations and contexts. This category broadens the current understanding of political leadership, particularly its adaptability to diverse situations, and underscores the potential for local leaders to effect positive change in H&SCI (Moore & MacKenzie, 2020). Rather than viewing context and leadership style as opposing forces, this perspective suggests that they can be effectively exercised in tandem to navigate the complexities of collaborative/integrated governance. This enriches the existing understanding of political leadership by demonstrating how leaders can adapt their styles to situational demands (Hartley, 2018). By leveraging various approaches tailored to specific contexts, leaders can navigate the multifaceted challenges of integrating health and social care in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2019).

This thesis contributes to the literature on situational leadership in three distinct ways. First, it develops and applies a framework that integrates political context and leadership styles (Fiedler, 1967; Tosun et al., 2022) to examine how local political leaders lead in various health and social care settings. Second, it explores the challenges and opportunities that local political leaders encounter, offering suggestions for their learning, governance, and collaboration, as highlighted by the significant challenges facing health and care in England (Dunn et al., 2023). Third, it demonstrates how this research can benefit stakeholders of H&SCI by providing them with valuable insights and tools that can enhance policy, governance, and service delivery in Scotland. Moreover, the contributions of this research to the discourse on collaborative and inclusive leadership are substantial. By proposing a new typology of leadership styles suited to contemporary governance challenges (Filgueiras et al., 2023), the study addresses the gap in the literature regarding the practical application of leadership theories in H&SCI settings.

8.3.3 Policy and Practice Implications

This research offers valuable insights that translate into practical recommendations for leadership development within Scottish H&SCI. A thorough understanding of how political contexts and leadership styles interact is critical for shaping policy and practice (Foley, 2013). The findings provide guidance for local authorities and organizations such as Convention of Scottish Local Authorities' (COSLA) in creating leadership programs for political leaders.

Specifically, the findings can inform local authorities during the nomination process of leaders for IJBs, ensuring that the selected individuals possess the necessary leadership qualities to foster effective

governance (Scottish Government, 2019). Additionally, these insights support COSLA's proactive investments in leadership development programs for local political leaders (COSLA, 2023). The study's identification of the 'integrative leader' style category, which emphasizes inclusivity, collaboration, and situational awareness, suggests a valuable framework for COSLA's leadership development programs, looking ahead to 2024. By incorporating training modules on these key competencies, these programs can equip local political leaders with the skills necessary to navigate the complexities of collaborative governance. Ultimately, this approach can lead to more effective decision-making and improved public service delivery in Scottish H&SCI (Audit Scotland, 2018).

However, the path from national policy pronouncements to successful implementation within the H&SCI agenda is not always smooth. Conflicting directives and constrained fiscal autonomy can impede local stakeholders' efforts to enact these policies effectively (Interviewee A, 2021; Interviewee F, 2022; Interviewee C, 2022; Department of Health & Social Care, 2021; Shanske, D., 2014). To address these challenges, it is recommended that local leaders be obligated not only with participatory roles but also with substantial decision-making power and fiscal authority (UK Government, 2022). This empowerment would necessitate a thorough review of funding structures, aiming to facilitate significant reforms that align with the integration objectives.

Similarly, the issue of local autonomy further complicates this landscape. Certain planning laws in Scotland, such as those governing primary care and care home planning, empower national intervention in local affairs (Scottish Parliament, 2019). While this may be intended to ensure alignment with national goals, it can also diminish the autonomy of local authorities. These trade-offs highlight the need for policymakers to acknowledge the realities of local implementation. The ongoing transformation of H&SCI requires consistent and well-coordinated support, acknowledging the complexities faced by local authorities and developing structures to navigate these challenges (Audit Scotland, 2022).

One of the solutions to address this issue is to establish a central coordinating body within the Scottish Government responsible for regulating national policy pronouncements related to H&SCI. This body could ensure policy coherence and provide clear guidance to local stakeholders (Audit Scotland, 2022). Additionally, fostering a more collaborative approach to policy development would be beneficial. By giving local stakeholders, a greater voice in shaping national policy, the gap between national goals and local implementation realities can be bridged (Feeley et al., 2021). Only through a collaborative and supportive approach, alongside well-coordinated national policies, can the H&SCI agenda achieve sustainable long-term success.

While achieving significant change in public policy and practice can be a gradual process, the Scottish Government and local authorities can leverage these findings to initiate a conversation on leadership development for H&SCI. By acknowledging the need for long-term investment in leadership skills (Kaplan et al., 2003) and fostering a culture of continuous improvement (Baxter et al., 2018), stakeholders can embark on a journey towards more effective and impactful H&SC services for Scottish communities. The impact of leadership on H&SC services in Scotland has been recognized as a key factor in the success of integration efforts (Baylis and Trimble, 2018).

Furthermore, this study has also enhanced our understanding of the various perspectives on leadership in modern governance, particularly collaborative governance (Ansell and Gash, 2008; Emerson and Nabatchi, 2015). These perspectives acknowledge the dynamic and complex nature of contemporary governance, where leadership is not confined to traditional hierarchical structures but rather dispersed across networks, partnerships, and collaborative initiatives (Kooiman, 2003). However, there are variations in how local political leaders operate across Europe and United Kingdom, especially in collaborative policy spaces or modern forms of governance. For instance, this thesis shows that local political leaders in Scotland adopt a situational leadership style, adapting their approaches to address the unique challenges and opportunities of H&SCI reform. This flexibility and responsiveness are crucial in navigating the complexities of cross-sector collaboration, requiring leaders to foster consensus, build trust, and manage diverse stakeholder interests (Huxham & Vangen, 2005). This situational leadership style stands in contrast with the more personalized, politically driven, and territorial leadership style of Southern Europe. It claims that local power in Southern Europe is still legitimized by vote-catching (clientelism) and 'caciquismo', a form of local bossism (Genieys, Ballart, and Valarié, 2004; Steyvers, Reynaert and Valcke, 2012). The political leadership is not only centered on the administrative and sectorial management of public services, but rather on political decisions aimed at governing territories.

Southern Europe and Northern Europe have different models of local government and leadership. Southern Europe follows a strong mayoral model, where leadership is vested in the office of the mayor, who is usually elected directly and leans on majoritarian principles of decision-making. This model is rather presidential and oriented towards the role of a local notable (Steyvers, Reynaert and Valcke, 2012; Copus and Leach, 2014). It is also characterized by a dualistic conception of legislative-executive relations, where leadership dominates the council and the administration. This model tends to be more politicized, where local government was the expression of a political community rather than an instrumental device to deliver services (Steyvers, Reynaert and Valcke, 2012). Northern Europe follows a collective leadership model, where leadership is shared by a collective that is appointed or indirectly elected, and whose powers are often embedded in the

legislative. This model nurtures a parliamentary and consensus-oriented style of decision-making. Leaders in this model are *primus inter pares*, and the model is traditionally associated with Northern Europe. This model is also influenced by the autonomous tradition of local government, which created what Page (1991) calls a more 'soft' and more 'efficient' form of leadership. This style of Nordic local political leadership is characterized by a more participatory and collaborative approach to decision-making. This style of leadership emphasizes the importance of building consensus and involving citizens in the decision-making process. It also highlights the importance of trust and social capital in local political leadership (Steyvers, Reynaert, and Valcke, 2012; Copus and Leach, 2014). This study indicates that local political leadership in Scottish health and social care exhibits leadership characteristics unique to northern Europe. Unlike the hierarchical systems often observed in Southern Europe, Scottish leadership is marked by its collaborative, participatory, facilitative, and inclusive nature. These characteristics resonate strongly with the principles of the Nordic model of local government, which emphasizes the autonomous tradition and active engagement of local authorities and communities.

These distinct leadership approaches that emerge across Europe stem from diverse historical, institutional, cultural, and social contexts (Copus and Leach, 2014). These varying leadership styles reflect the changing dynamics of European integration and ongoing public service reforms (Stoker, 2006), which necessitate adaptability in leadership approaches. In the context of increasing cross-border collaboration, leaders need to build consensus and manage competing interests from diverse stakeholders, requiring leaders with the ability to adapt, negotiate, and bridge cultural differences (Ansell and Torfing, 2016). This recognition is imperative for developing effective leadership training and education programs that equip leaders with the skills and knowledge to navigate the intricacies of collaborative governance and deliver effective public services in an increasingly interconnected world (Emerson et al., 2012).

8.3.4 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

In this section, the limitations of the study are discussed. Considering the intrinsic nature of the topic, specifically focusing on leadership and the selected research methodology has led to the identification of certain limitations, which have been duly acknowledged. The literature review section of this thesis previously highlighted the elusive nature of leadership. While this research has contributed to knowledge and deepened our understanding of leadership in integrated governance context, it is important to recognize the limitations in claiming a definitive and exhaustive exploration of the leadership phenomenon. Leadership, as a situational and context-dependent phenomenon, remains subject to constant change and adaptation, aligned with the

evolving values and dynamics of society over time. Thus, while this research has made valuable contributions to theoretical knowledge with potential timeless value, it is important to recognize that its practical contributions may have a more limited shelf life, given the rapidly changing social environment in which leadership operates.

Although this research has classified, or focused on, specific aspects of the contextual factors deemed most relevant to local political leaders in the modern policy space, it is essential to acknowledge the presence of other contextual elements that could be incorporated in future research endeavours. For instance, considering the broader UK-level government context, where local authorities in Scotland receive direct funding from Westminster or Whitehall, recent initiatives such as the levelling-up agenda of the current Conservative government has emerged as a potential example to support local initiatives throughout the UK (Connolly, Pyper, and van der Zwet, 2021). These initiatives allocate funding to different local areas to address deprivation levels through various local projects. The implementation and impact of such developments take place in the H&SC sector as well; therefore, it would be interesting to map out the impact or influence of this important contextual factor on the leadership practices of local actors involved in delivering Health and Social Care services in the future research. This thesis has provided evidence that the relationship between local leadership and national leadership facilitate the local IJBs to get extra funding and facilitate their innovative initiatives. The study has also evidenced that local political leadership has prioritised the smooth relationship at national levels, although sometimes the national level guidance contradicted with their personal belief regarding localism. This could be because of the financial dependence on the national government. There is a much scope, therefore, for developing the analysis of the dynamics of IJB leadership in multi-level governance. Thus, there is a need to investigate how the multilevel relationship between the UK government, the Scottish Government, and local government affects the dynamics of leadership in the healthcare and social care sector.

Moreover, this research focuses primarily on the role of local political leaders within the Integration Joint Boards. Therefore, it is important to acknowledge that some of the significant work carried out by local political leaders also takes place in IJBs' sub-committees which provide tremendous support to the IJBs. These committees serve as platforms for detailed debates on various topics and these discussions within the committees often involve governance arguments and conflicting ideas, providing valuable insights into the approaches adopted by local political leaders. The members of these committees are comprised of local political leaders who serve on the IJBs, as well as a wider political membership representing the local authority or council and it is important to note that, although not all local political leaders in these committees are part of the IJBs, their

contributions remain highly relevant to the Health and Social Care agenda, as their roles primarily involve supporting the IJBs. Recognizing the significance of these committees and their potential to provide further understanding of the intricacies of Scottish Health and Social Care politics, it is recommended that future research includes local elected members who participate in these committees. Incorporating their perspectives and experiences would contribute to a deeper understanding of the multifaceted dynamics of Scottish health and social care governance. Expanding the research approach would offer insights into collaborative efforts and decision-making processes of local political leaders, enhancing understanding of the complexities in shaping integrated health and social care policies. This will be an important step forwards for this research in terms of exploring more local dynamics of H&SCI in Scotland.

Furthermore, the thesis has operationalised the situational leadership theory arguing that local political leaders are influenced by the stakeholders they collaborate with including senior officials and the frontline workforce. Chapters 7 mapped out that the leadership style of local political leaders is determined by the expectations and needs of stakeholders they collaborate with. These chapters provided evidence that these leaders are influenced by the expectations and needs of the frontline workforce and local stakeholders involved in the decision-making process. However, due to time limitations inherent in a PhD project, this thesis did not include the frontline workforce in the sampling strategy, but interviews were conducted with local stakeholders, specifically senior officials, to gather evidence of the existence of these expectations and how they shape the leadership approaches of local political leaders in the Scottish H&SC. In the light of these findings, it is recommended that future research includes the frontline workforce in its sampling strategy when researching modern integrated or collaborative settings. Research such as this would allow for analysis of the expectations of frontline workforce. By exploring how local political leaders respond to these expectations, further insights can be gained to refine the understanding of leadership styles in relation to varying frontline workforce expectations or political situations.

Finally, this research has relied primarily on document analysis and interviews. While these methods have provided valuable insights, they also have some inherent limitations. Document analysis, by its very nature, offers a static snapshot of leadership, capturing only what has been documented or recorded. Interviews, while offering a deeper understanding of individuals' perceptions and experiences, are susceptible to selective recall and self-presentation biases (Yin, 2018). Therefore, there are opportunities to utilise observation as a complementary data collection method. Observation provides researchers with a direct and ongoing view of leadership behaviours in real-world settings (Bryman, 2016). It allows for the capture of subtle nonverbal cues,

interactions with stakeholders, and the broader context of decision-making processes (Patton, 2015).

To conclude, this thesis has addressed the research question of how local political leaders enact their roles in the Scottish public sector reform landscape, with a focus on the complex area of health and social care integration. It reveals that local leadership is not a static entity, but a dynamic force that adapts and responds to the specific contextual challenges encountered. For instance, the thesis shows how local leaders use various strategies, such as cooperation, vision, teamwork, strategic thinking, inclusivity, result orientation, direction, and initiative, to contribute to policy and organizational outcomes in H&SCI. This work fills a critical gap in public policy and administration research, where previous studies have mainly examined bureaucratic mechanisms of reform (Harris et al., 2020; Connolly et al., 2020; Connolly et al., 2022). By exploring the context of H&SCI, the thesis demonstrates the crucial role of local political leaders in shaping and delivering public services in the 21st century, which are characterized by complexity and uncertainty. This contribution extends to the broader fields of public administration, political leadership, and health and social care integration, deepening our understanding of the intricate and paradoxical nature of public service delivery. In closing, this thesis offers a rich and original account of local political leadership in Scottish reform and suggests some implications and recommendations for future research and practice. The journey has just begun.

Bibliography

Abelsen, B., Strasser, R., Heaney, D., Berggren, P., Sigurðsson, S., Brandstorp, H., Wakegijig, J., Forsling, N., Moody-Corbett, P., Akearok, G.H. and Mason, A., (2020). 'Plan, recruit, retain: A framework for local healthcare organizations to achieve a stable remote rural workforce'. *Human resources for health*, 18(1), p.1-10.

Adamson, D. & Bromiley, R., (2013). 'Community empowerment: Learning from practice in community regeneration '. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 26(3), p.190-202.

Agranoff, R. & McGuire, M., (2001). 'Big questions in public network management research '. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 11, p.295-326.

Albert, A. and Passmore, E., (2008). 'Public value and participation [electronic resource]: A literature review for the Scottish Government '. Scottish Government.

Alderwick, H., Hutchings, A., Briggs, A. and Mays, N., (2021). 'The impacts of collaboration between local health care and non-health care organizations and factors shaping how they work: A systematic review of reviews '. *BMC Public Health*, 21, p.1-16.

Alford, J., (2002). 'Defining the client in the public sector: A social-exchange perspective '. *Public administration review*, 62(3), p.337-346.

Allen, P. (2017). 'D&I and Leadership in Organizations. In: Aquino, C., Robertson, R. (eds) *Diversity and Inclusion in the Global Workplace*'. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.

Allmendinger, P., (2003). 'Integrating planning in a devolved Scotland ' '. *Planning Practice & Research*, 18(1), p.19-36.

Allmendinger, P., (2010). 'Integrating planning in a devolved Scotland ': *Planning Practice & Research*, 18(1), p.19-36.

Alsharari, N.M., (2022). 'Institutionalization of results-based budgeting in the public sector: Political and economic pressures '. *Asian Review of Accounting*, 30(3), p.352-377.

Amanchukwu, R.N., Stanley, G.J. and Ololube, N.P., (2015). 'A review of leadership theories, principles and styles and their relevance to educational management '. *Management*, 5(1), p.6-14.

Ansell, C. & Gash, A., (2008). 'Collaborative governance in theory and practice '. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), p.543-571.

Ansell, C. & Torfing, J., (2021). 'Co-creation: The new kid on the block in public governance '. *Policy & Politics*, 49(2), p.211-230.

Ansell, C., Doberstein, C., Henderson, H., Siddiki, S. and 't Hart, P., 2020. 'Understanding inclusion in collaborative governance: a mixed methods approach'. *Policy and society*, 39(4), pp.570-591.

Antonakis, J. & Day, D.V. (Eds.), (2018). 'Leadership: Past, present, and future. In: The nature of leadership '. Sage Publications, Inc, p.3-26.

Antonakis, J. & House, R.J., (2014). 'Instrumental leadership: Measurement and extension of transformational-transactional leadership theory '. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 25, p.746-771.

Arai, Y., Oktoriana, S., Suharyani, A. and Inoue, M., (2021). ' How can we mitigate power imbalances in collaborative environmental governance? Examining the role of the village facilitation team approach observed in West Kalimantan, Indonesia '. *Sustainability*, 13(7), p.3972.

Arnott, M. (2020). '*Missing Links: Past, Present and Future Interparliamentary Relations in the devolved UK* '. Institute of Welsh Affairs.

Asencio, H. & Mujkic, E., (2016). ' Leadership behaviours and trust in leaders: Evidence from the US federal government '. *Public Administration Quarterly*, p.156-179.

Åström, J., Freschi, A-C. and Montin, S., (2010). 'Electronic and representative democracy: A happy couple? Comparing online dialogues in the UK, Sweden and Italy. ' In: E. Amnå, ed. *New forms of citizen participation: Normative implications*. Baden-Baden: Nomos verlag.

Åström, J., Olsson, J. and Hysing, E., (2022). 'Does policy influence hollow out public managers' political neutrality? ' *Administration & Society*, 54(6), p.1019-1044.

Audit Scotland, (2010). 'An overview of local government in Scotland '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2015). 'Health and social care integration faces major challenges '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2016). 'Changing models of health and social care. Health and social care series '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2018). 'Best Value Assurance Report: East Ayrshire Council '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2018). 'Review of health and social care integration in Scotland: Progress and next steps '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2018c). 'Health and social care integration: Update on progress '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2018d). 'Best Value Assurance Report: Dumfries and Galloway Council '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2019). 'Moray Integration Joint Board 2018/19 Annual Audit Report Prepared for Moray Integration Joint Board and the Controller of Audit '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2020). 'West Dunbartonshire Integration Joint Board Annual Audit Plan 2019/20 Prepared for West Dunbartonshire Integration Joint Board '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2020a). 'Best Value Assurance Report: The City of Edinburgh Council '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2020b). 'Best Value Assurance Report: East Lothian Council '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2020c). 'Glasgow City Integration Joint Board 2019/20 Annual Audit Report '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2020d). 'Best Value Assurance Report: Moray Council. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland '.

Audit Scotland, (2020e). 'Clackmannanshire and Stirling Integration Joint Board 2019/20 Annual Audit Report '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2020f). 'West Dunbartonshire Integration Joint Board 2019/20 Annual Audit Report '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2021). 'Angus Integration Joint Board 2020/21 Annual Audit Report – DRAFT Prepared for Angus Integration Joint Board and the Controller of Audit '. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland, (2022). 'Integration Joint Boards: Financial analysis 2020/21'. Edinburgh: Audit Scotland.

Audit Scotland. (2018). 'Health and social care integration: progress review'. audit. Scot:<https://audit.scot/publications/health-and-social-care-integration-update-on-progress>.

Audit Scotland. (2024). 'NHS in Scotland 2023'. audit.scot: <https://audit.scot/publications/nhs-in-scotland-2023> .

Avery, G.C., (2009). 'Understanding leadership: Paradigms and cases '. London: Sage.

Avolio, B.J. & Bass, B.M., (2004). 'Multifactor leadership questionnaire (MLQ) '. Palo Alto, CA: Mind Garden.

Avolio, B.J. & Gardner, W.L., (2005). 'Authentic leadership development: Getting to the root of positive forms of leadership '. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 16(3), p.315-338.

Avolio, B.J., (2009). ' Leadership: Current theories, research, and future directions '. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 60, p.421.

Avolio, B.J., Walumbwa, F.O. & Weber, T.J., (2009). 'Leadership: Current theories, research, and future directions '. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 60, p.421-449.

Aydin, B., (2018). 'The role of organizational culture on leadership styles '. *MANAS Sosyal Arařtırmalar Dergisi*, 7(1), p.267-280.

Banfield, E., (1961). 'Una comunit del Mezzogiorno [The moral basis of backward society] '. Nuova edizione, a cura di D. De Masi. Milano: Feltrinelli.

Bao, G., Wang, X., Larsen, G.L. and Morgan, D.F., (2013). 'Beyond new public governance: A value-based global framework for performance management, governance, and leadership '. *Administration & Society*, 45(4), p.443-467.

Bapuji, A., (1989). 'Public administration and management: A comparative perspective '. London: Macmillan.

Bass, B.M. & Avolio, B.J., (1994). 'Transformational leadership: Improving organizational effectiveness'. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Bass, B.M., (1985). 'Leadership and performance beyond expectations '. New York, NY: Free Press.

Bass, B.M., (1990). 'Bass and Stogdill's handbook of leadership: A survey of theory and research '. New York, NY: Free Press.

Baxter, P. & Jack, S., (2008). 'Qualitative case study methodology: Study design and implementation for novice researchers '. *The Qualitative Report*, 13(4), p.544-559.

Baxter, S., Johnson, M., Chambers, D., Sutton, A., Goyder, E., and Booth, A. (2018) 'Understanding new models of integrated care in developed countries: a systematic review', *Health Services and Delivery Research*, 6(29).

Baylis, A. and Trimble, A., (2018). 'Leading across health and social care in Scotland: Learning from chief officers' experiences, planning next steps'. London: The King's Fund.

- BBC News, (2015). 'The fall of Labour in Scotland - in their own words' [online].
- Beerbohm, E., (2015). 'Is democratic leadership possible?' *American Political Science Review*, 109(4), p.639-652.
- Beiten, B.K., (2012). 'Interviewing and sampling: How many and whom'. In: J.F. Gubrium, J.A. Holstein, A.B. Marvasti and K.D. McKinney, eds. *The Sage handbook of interview research: The complexity of the craft* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Bennett, M., Fairley, J. and McAteer, M., (2002). 'Devolution in Scotland: The impact on local government'. York: York Publishing Services Limited.
- Bernard, H.R., (2000). 'Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches'. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Bevir, M., Rhodes, R.A. and Weller, P., (2003). 'Comparative governance: Prospects and lessons'. *Public Administration*, 81(1), p.191-210.
- Bianchi, C., Nasi, G. and Rivenbark, W.C., (2021). 'Implementing collaborative governance: Models, experiences, and challenges'. *Public Management Review*, 23(11), p.1581-1589.
- Bingham, L.B. & O'Leary, R., (2008). 'Big ideas in collaborative public management'. Armonk, NY: M.E. Sharpe.
- Bingham, L.B. and O'Leary, R., 2014. '*Big Ideas in Collaborative Public Management*'. Routledge.
- Bloomberg, L.D. & Volpe, M., (2012). 'Completing your qualitative dissertation: A road map from beginning to end'. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Bochel, H. and Bochel, C., (2010). 'Local political leadership and the modernisation of local government'. *Local Government Studies*, 36(6), p.723-737.
- Bodin, Ö., (2017). 'Collaborative environmental governance: Achieving collective action in social-ecological systems'. *Science*, 357(6352), p. eaan1114.
- Bolden, R., (2011). 'Distributed leadership in organizations: A review of theory and research'. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 13(3), p.251-269.
- Bolman, L.G. & Deal, T.E., (2017). 'Reframing organizations: Artistry, choice, and leadership'. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bowen, G.A., (2009). 'Document analysis as a qualitative research method'. *Qualitative Research Journal*, 9(2), p.27-40.

Boyar, S.L., Savage, G.T. and Williams, E.S., (2023). 'An adaptive leadership approach: The impact of reasoning and emotional intelligence (EI) abilities on leader adaptability'. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 35(4), pp.565-580.

Bradley, D. and Schneider, H., (2004). 'Participatory approaches: A facilitator's guide' [online]. VSO. Available from: [2](#) [Accessed 10 July 2012].

Braithwaite, J. & Lyall, C., (2016). 'Leadership for integrated health and social care: A review of the literature'. London: King's Fund.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V., (2019). 'Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis: Qualitative research in sport, exercise and health', 11(4), p.589-597.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V., 2006. 'Using thematic analysis in psychology'. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), pp.77-101.

Bray, D.W., Campbell, R.J. & Grant, D.L., (1974). 'Forming a leadership style from behavioural incidents'. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(1), p.168-177.

Breaugh, J.A., (2006). 'Behavioural interview questions'. In: J.A. Breaugh, ed. *Handbook of employee selection*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.

Bridges, W., (2009). '*Managing transitions: Making the most of change*'. Da Capo Press.

Bridges, W., 2009. '*Managing transitions: Making the most of change*'. Da Capo Press.

Brodkin, E.Z., (2011). 'Policy work: Street-level organizations under new managerialism'. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 21(suppl_2), p.i253-i277.

Brookes, S. & Grint, K., (2010). 'The new public leadership challenge'. Basingstoke, UK: Palgrave Macmillan.

Bryman, A., (2016). 'Social research methods'. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Bryson, J.M., Crosby, B.C. and Bloomberg, L., (2014). 'Public value governance: Moving beyond traditional public administration and the new public management'. *Public Administration Review*, 74(4), p.445-456.

Bryson, J.M., Crosby, B.C. and Stone, M.M., (2006). 'The design and implementation of cross-sector collaborations: Propositions from the literature'. *Public Administration Review*, 66, p.44-55.

Buck, D. and Dixon, A., (2013). 'Improving the allocation of health resources in England'. London: King's Fund.

- Burns, J.M., (1978). 'Leadership. New York: Harper and Row'.
- Bussu, S. & Bartels, K.P., (2014). 'Facilitative leadership and the challenge of renewing local democracy in Italy'. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 38(6), p.2256-2273.
- Bussu, S., Bua, A., Dean, R. and Smith, G., (2022). 'Introduction: Embedding participatory governance'. *Critical Policy Studies*, 16(2), p.133-145.
- Cairney, P. and McGarvey, N., (2013). '*Scottish politics*'. London: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Cairney, P., (2012). 'The Scottish political system since devolution: From new politics to the new Scottish government'. Luton: Andrews UK Limited.
- Cardno, C., (2018). 'Policy document analysis: A practical educational leadership tool and a qualitative research method'. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 24 (4), 623-640.
- Cejudo, G.M. and Trein, P., (2023) `.'Policy integration as a political process'. *Policy Sciences*, 56(1), p.3-8.
- Chambers, S., (2006). 'Mayors and schools'. Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
- Chapman, C., (2018). 'Glasgow: What works Scotland' [online]. Available from: [2](#) [Accessed 21 February 2024].
- Child, J., (1984). 'Organization'. Cambridge: Harper and Row.
- Christensen, T. and Laegreid, P., eds., (2007). 'Transcending new public management: The transformation of public sector reforms'. Aldershot: Ashgate.
- Christie, C., (2011). 'Commission on the future delivery of public services'. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.
- Clarke, J.M., Waring, J., Bishop, S., Hartley, J., Exworthy, M., Fulop, N.J., Ramsay, A. and Roe, B., (2021). 'The contribution of political skill to the implementation of health services change: A systematic review and narrative synthesis'. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21(1), p.1-15.
- Cloutier, A. and Barling, J., 2020. 'Leadership in flexible work systems'. In *Flexible Work* (pp. 79-97). Routledge.
- Community Planning Working Group, (1998). 'Report of the Community Planning Working Group'. Edinburgh: Scottish Office.

Connolly, J. and Pyper, R., (2020). 'The leadership and management of public services reform in Scotland'. In: G. Hassan and R. Shaw, eds. *The Oxford handbook of Scottish politics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Connolly, J. and Van der Zwet, A. eds., (2021). *'Public value management, governance and reform in Britain'*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.

Connolly, J., (2009). 'British crisis management and the dynamics of change: The case of the veterinary disease policy sector 2001-2007'. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. University of Birmingham.

Connolly, J., (2022). 'Integrating health and social care: Seven steps for success'. *The Conversation*.

Connolly, J., Pyper, R. and van der Zwet, A., (2021). 'Governing 'levelling-up' in the UK: Challenges and prospects'. *Contemporary Social Science*, 16(5), p.523-537.

Copus, C. and Leach, S., (2014). 'Local political leaders. In: C. Skelcher, H. Sullivan and S. Jeffares, eds. *Hybrid governance in European cities: Neighbourhood, migration and democracy'*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.

Copus, C., (2003). 'Re-engaging citizens and councils: The importance of the councillor to enhanced citizen involvement'. *Local Government Studies*, 29(2), p.1-24.

Copus, C., Jones, A. and Wall, R., (2021). 'Too big to be local: Local and national elite complicity in the narrative of English council mergers'. In: *Local government in Europe*. Bristol: Bristol University Press, p.18-38.

Cox, B., (2008). 'Systematic sampling'. In: P. Lavrakas, ed. *Encyclopedia of survey research methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, p.872-873.

Cozby, P.C. & Bates, S.C., (2012). *'Methods in behavioural research (11th ed.)'*. New York, NY: McGraw Hill.

Crasnow, S., (2012). 'The role of case study research in political science: Evidence for causal claims'. *Philosophy of Science*, 79(5), p.655-666.

Crayne, M.P. and Medeiros, K.E., (2021). 'Making sense of crisis: Charismatic, ideological, and pragmatic leadership in response to COVID-19'. *American Psychologist*, 76(3), p.462.

Creswell, J.W., (2003). *'Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches'*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

- Creswell, J.W., (2007). 'Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches'. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Creswell, J.W., (2009). 'Mapping the field of mixed methods research'. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 3(2), p.95-108.
- Creswell, J.W., (2013a). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Creswell, J.W., (2013b). 'Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches'. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Crosby, B. & Bryson, J., (2005). 'Leadership for the common good: Tackling public problems in a shared-power world'. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Dahl, R.A., (1961). 'Who governs? Democracy and power in an American city'. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Dahl, R.A., (2005). 'Who governs? Democracy and power in an American city'. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Dalton, R.J. and Welzel, C., eds., (2014). 'The civic culture transformed: From allegiant to assertive citizens'. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- De Groot, M., Denters, B. and Klok, P-J., (2010). 'Strengthening the councillor as a representative and scrutiniser: The effects of institutional change on councillors' role orientations in the Netherlands'. *Local Government Studies*, 36(3), p.317-332.
- Debie, A., Khatri, R.B. and Assefa, Y., 2022. 'Successes and challenges of health systems governance towards universal health coverage and global health security: a narrative review and synthesis of the literature'. *Health research policy and systems*, 20(1), p.5
- Del Gaudio, C., Franzato, C. and de Oliveira, A.J., (2017). 'The challenge of time in community-based participatory design'. *Urban Design International*, 22, p.113-126.
- Denhardt, R.B. & Denhardt, J.V., (2015). 'The pursuit of significance: Public service and democracy in the 21st century'. Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press.
- Denhardt, R.B. and Denhardt, J.V., (2003). 'The new public service: An approach to reform'. *International Review of Public Administration*, 8(1).

Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities & Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government (2020). 'Addressing cultural and governance failings in local authorities: lessons from recent interventions'. London: DLUHC & MHCLG. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/addressing-cultural-and-governance-failings-in-local-authorities-lessons-from-recent-interventions/addressing-cultural-and-governance-failingsin-local-authorities-lessons-from-recent-interventions> .

Department of Health and Social Care, (2021). 'Integration and innovation: Working together to improve health and social care for all. The Department of Health and Social Care's Legislative Proposals for a Health and Care Bill'. London: Department of Health and Social Care.

Dewar, D., (1999). 'Statement by the First Minister, Donald Dewar MSP, Legislative Programme and Priorities'. 16 June, Scottish Parliament, Official Report, 1(9), p.16.

Diamond, J., (1996). 'The roots of radicalism'. *The New York Review of Books*, 43(18), p.4-6.

Dickinson, H., Allen, K., Alcock, P., Macmillan, R. and Glasby, J., (2012). 'The role of the third sector in delivering social care'. Birmingham: Third Sector Research Centre.

Dinh, J.E. & Lord, R.G., (2012). 'Implications of dispositional and process views of traits for individual difference research in leadership'. *Leadership Quarterly*, 23(4), p.651-669.

Dion, L., (1968). 'The concept of political leadership: An analysis'. *Canadian Journal of Political Science/Revue canadienne de science politique*, 1(1), p.2-17.

Douglas, S., Ansell, C., Parker, C.F., Sørensen, E., 'T Hart, P. and Torfing, J., (2020). 'Understanding collaboration: Introducing the collaborative governance case databank'. *Policy and Society*, 39(4), p.495-509.

Downes, B.T., (1968). 'Municipal social rank and the characteristics of local political leaders'. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. University of Chicago.

Dunleavy, P., Margetts, H., Bastow, S. and Tinkler, J., 2006. 'New public management is dead—long live digital-era governance'. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 16(3), pp.467-494.

Dunn, P., Ewbank, L. and Alderwick, H., 2023. 'Nine major challenges facing health and care in England'.

Dyhrberg-Noerregaard, N. & Kjær, U., (2014). 'Non-zero-sum leadership games: Is facilitative leadership a win-win? ' *International Journal of Public Administration*, 37(4), p.249-258.

Eisenhardt, K.M., (1989). 'Building theories from case study research'. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), p.532-550.

- El-Ghalayini, Y., 2016. 'New public management: An assessment of impact and the influence on Public Administration'. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 6(12), pp.18-22.
- Elgie, R. (2017). 'Political Leadership: A Pragmatic Institutional Approach'. New York.
- Elgie, R., 1995. '*Political leadership in liberal democracies*'. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Elliott, I.C., Fejszes, V. and Tàrrega, M., (2019). 'The Community Empowerment Act and localism under devolution in Scotland: The perspective of multiple stakeholders in a council ward'. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 32(3), p.302-319.
- Ellis, P., (2015). 'The different approaches to leadership'. *Wounds UK*, 77(1), p.65-67.
- Elo, S., Kääriäinen, M., Kanste, O., Pölkki, T., Utriainen, K. and Kyngäs, H., (2014). 'Qualitative content analysis: A focus on trustworthiness'. *SAGE Open*, 4(1), p.2158244014522633.
- El-Zayaty, N., (2016). 'An exploration of leadership styles and motivation in Egyptian business organizations'. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. Walden University.
- Emerson, K. and Nabatchi, T., 2015. '*Collaborative governance regimes*'. Georgetown University Press.
- Emerson, K., Nabatchi, T. and Balogh, S., (2012). 'An integrative framework for collaborative governance'. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 22(1), p.1-29.
- Ensley, M.D., Hmieleski, K.M. and Pearce, C.L., (2006). 'The importance of vertical and shared leadership within new venture top management teams: Implications for the performance of startups'. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 17(3), p.217-231.
- Erkkilä, T., (2007). 'Governance and accountability-A shift in conceptualisation'. *Public Administration Quarterly*, p.1-38.
- Erkkilä, T., 2007. 'Governance and accountability-A shift in conceptualisation'. *Public Administration Quarterly*, pp.1-38.
- Evans, M. and Terrey, N., 2016. 'Co-design with citizens and stakeholders'. *Evidence-based policy making in the social sciences*, pp.243-262.
- Fairhurst, G.T., (2009). 'Considering context in discursive leadership research'. *Human Relations*, 62(11), p.1607-1633.
- Farr, M., (2018). 'Power dynamics and collaborative mechanisms in co-production and co-design processes'. *Critical Social Policy*, 38(4), p.623-644.
- Fawcett Society. (2019). 'Councillors' Census (2018) '. Fawcett Society.

- Fawcett, P., Flinders, M.V., Hay, C. and Wood, M., eds., (2017). *'Anti-politics, depoliticization, and governance'*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Feeley, D., Chisholm, M. and Dixon, A., 2021. 'Independent review of adult social care in Scotland'. *Edinburgh: The Scottish Government*.
- Feldman, M.S. and Khademian, A.M., (2001). 'Principles for public management practice: From dichotomies to interdependence'. *Governance*, 14(3), p.339-361.
- Fenwick, J., Miller, K.J. and McTavish, D., (2012). 'Co-governance or meta-bureaucracy? Perspectives of local governance 'partnership' in England and Scotland'. *Policy & Politics*, 40(3), p.405-422.
- Fiedler, F., (1967). *'A theory of leadership effectiveness'*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Fiedler, F.E. & Chemers, M.M., (1984). *'Improving leadership effectiveness: The leader match concept (2nd ed.)'*. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
- Filgueiras, F., Palotti, P. and Testa, G.G., 2023. 'Complexing Governance Styles: Connecting Politics and Policy in Governance Theories'. *SAGE Open*, 13(1), p.21582440231158521
- Fisher, J., Stutzman, H., Vedoveto, M., Delgado, D., Rivero, R., Quertehuari Dariquebe, W., Seclén Contreras, L., Souto, T., Harden, A. and Rhee, S., (2020). 'Collaborative governance and conflict management: Lessons learned and good practices from a case study in the Amazon Basin'. *Society & Natural Resources*, 33(4), p.538-553.
- Flemig, S.S. & Osborne, S., (2019). 'The dynamics of co-production in the context of social care personalisation: Testing theory and practice in a Scottish context'. *Journal of Social Policy*, 48(4), p.671-697.
- Fleurke, F. and Willemse, R., (2004). *Approaches to decentralization and local autonomy: A critical appraisal*. *Administrative Theory & Praxis*, 26(4), p.523-544.
- Flyvbjerg, B., (2006). 'Five misunderstandings about case-study research'. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(2), p.219-245.
- Foley, M., 2013. 'Doing leadership: Types, styles, and contingency'. *Political Leadership*, pp.31-57.
- Foley, M., 2013. 'Doing leadership: Types, styles, and contingency'. *Political Leadership*, pp.31-57.
- Forbes, T. and Evans, D., (2008). 'Health and social care partnerships in Scotland'. *Scottish Affairs*, 65(1), p.87-106.

- Forester, J., (2009). 'Community planning: A comprehensive guide to theory and practice'. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Forester, J., (2019). 'Ecological wisdom through deliberative improvisation: Theory and practice in challenging cases'. *Journal of Urban Management*, 8(1), p.12-19.
- Frazer, S., Granius, M., Brinkerhoff, D.W. and McGregor, L., (2022). 'Integrated Governance: Achieving governance results and contributing to sector outcomes'. RTI Press, p.35782.
- Frederickson, H.G., (1997). 'The spirit of public administration'. San Francisco City: Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- Frederickson, H.G., Smith, K.B., Larimer, C. and Licari, M.J., 2018. '*The public administration theory primer*'. Routledge.
- Friedrich, C. J. and Mason, E. S., (1940). '*Public policy: a yearbook of the graduate school of public administration, Harvard University*'. Harvard University Press.
- Friedrich, C.J. (1935), 'Problems of the American Public Service', McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
- Fusco, F., Marsilio, M. and Guglielmetti, C., 2020. 'Co-production in health policy and management: a comprehensive bibliometric review'. *BMC health services research*, 20, pp.1-16.
- Gastil, J., (1994). 'A definition and illustration of democratic leadership'. *Human Relations*, 47(8), pp.953-975.
- Genieys, W., Ballart, X. and Valarié, P., (2004). 'From 'great' leaders to building networks: The emergence of a new urban leadership in southern Europe? '. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 28(1), pp.183-199.
- Genieys, W., Ballart, X. and Valarié, P., 2004. 'From 'great' leaders to building networks: The emergence of a new urban leadership in southern Europe? '. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 28(1), pp.183-199.
- Gerring, J., (2004). 'What is a case study and what is it good for? '. *American political science review*, 98(2), pp.341-354.
- Getimis, P. and Hlepas, N.-K., (2006). 'Aspects of leadership styles: An interaction of context and personalities'. In: H. Heinelt and D. Kübler, eds. *Urban governance in Europe: Multi-level dynamics, co-operation and conflict*. Campus Verlag, pp. 163-184.

- Geurtz, C. and Van de Wijdeven, T., (2010). 'Making citizen participation work: The challenging search for new forms of local democracy in the Netherlands'. *Local Government Studies*, 36(4), pp. 531-549.
- Gill, R., (2011). '*Theory and practice of leadership*'. 2nd ed. Sage.
- Givens, R. J., (2008). 'Transformational leadership: The impact on organizational and personal outcomes'. *Emerging Leadership Journeys*, 1(1), pp. 4-24.
- Glasby, J. and Dickinson, H., (2014). '*Integrated care: A guide for commissioners, providers and practitioners*'. Policy Press.
- Goldstein, A. E. and Reiboldt, W., (2004). 'The multiple roles of low income, minority women in the family and community: A qualitative investigation'. *The Qualitative Report*, 9(2), pp. 241-265.
- Good Governance Institute (GGI). (2016). 'The new integrated governance handbook 2016: Developing governance between organisations (GBO)'. Available at: <https://www.good-governance.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/The-new-Integrated-Governance-Handbook-2016.pdf>.
- Goodwin, N. and Smith, J., (2011). '*The evidence base for integrated care*'. King's Fund and the Nuffield Trust.
- Goodwin, V. L., Whittington, J. L., Murray, B. and Nichols, T., (2011). 'Moderator or mediator? Examining the role of trust in the transformational leadership paradigm'. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 23(4), pp. 409-425.
- Gordon, C., (2002). 'From war of attrition to roller-coaster ride: Local and central government in Scotland'. *Public Money & Management*, 22(2), pp. 6-8.
- Gortner, H. F., Mahler, J. and Nicholson, J. B., (1997). '*Organization theory: A public perspective*'. 2nd ed. Harcourt Brace College.
- Granberg, M. and Åström, J., (2010). 'Civic participation and interactive decision-making: A case study'. In: E. Amnå, ed. *New forms of citizen participation: Normative implications*. Nomos, pp. 131-150.
- Gray, J., (1996). '*After social democracy: politics, capitalism and the common life*'. Vol. 18. Demos.
- Greenleaf, R., (1995). 'Reflections from experience. In: L. C. Spears, ed. *Reflections on leadership: How Robert K. Greenleaf's theory of servant leadership influenced today's top management thinkers*'. John Wiley & Sons, pp. 22-36.
- Grint, K., (2000). '*The arts of leadership*'. OUP Oxford.

- Grint, K., (2005). 'Problems, problems, problems: The social construction of 'leadership''. *Human relations*, 58(11), pp. 1467-1494.
- Groenewald, T., (2004). 'A phenomenological research design illustrated'. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 3(1), pp. 1-26.
- Gronn, P., (2002). 'Distributed leadership as a unit of analysis'. *The leadership quarterly*, 13(4), pp. 423-451.
- Grootjans, S.J., Stijnen, M.M.N., Kroese, M.E.A.L., Ruwaard, D. and Jansen, M.W.J., 2022. 'Collaborative governance at the start of an integrated community approach: a case study'. *BMC Public Health*, 22(1), p.1013.
- Guzzini, S., (2022). 'Power in World Politics'. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics*.
- Hall, S., (2011). 'The neo-liberal revolution'. *Cultural studies*, 25(6), pp. 705-728.
- Hallingberg, B., Turley, R., Segrott, J., Wight, D., Craig, P., Moore, L., Murphy, S., Robling, M., Simpson, S. A. and Moore, G., (2018). 'Exploratory studies to decide whether and how to proceed with full-scale evaluations of public health interventions: a systematic review of guidance'. *Pilot and feasibility studies*, 4, p. 104.
- Hallsworth, M., (2011). 'Policymaking in the real world'. *Political Insight*, 2(1), pp. 10-12.
- Hambleton, R., Sweeting, D. and Oliver, T., (2022). 'Place, power and leadership: Insights from mayoral governance and leadership innovation in Bristol, UK'. *Leadership*, 18(1), pp. 81-101.
- Hannah, S. T., Uhl-Bien, M., Avolio, B. J. and Cavaretta, F. L., (2009). 'A framework for examining leadership in extreme contexts'. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 20, pp. 897-919.
- Hargrove, E. C., (1989). 'Two conceptions of institutional leadership'. In: B. D. Jones, ed. *Leadership and politics: New perspectives in political science*. University Press of Kansas, pp. 3-24.
- Harris, R., Fletcher, S., Sims, S., Ross, F., Brearley, S. and Manthorpe, J., 2020. 'Understanding key mechanisms of successfully leading integrated team-based services in health and social care: protocol for a realist synthesis'. *BMJ open*, 10(7), p.e038591.
- Hart, P.T. and Rhodes, R.A., (2014). 'Puzzles of political leadership'. *The Oxford handbook of political leadership*, p.3.
- Hartley, J. and Benington, J., (2011). '*Recent trends in leadership thinking and action in the public and voluntary service sectors*'. The King's Fund.

Hartley, J. and Rashman, L., (2018). 'Innovation and inter-organizational learning in the context of public service reform'. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 84(2), pp. 231-248.

Hartley, J., Alford, J., Hughes, O. and Yates, S., (2015). 'Public value and political astuteness in the work of public managers: The art of the possible'. *Public Administration*, 93(1), pp. 195-211.

Haus, M. and Sweeting, D., (2006). 'Mayors, citizens and local democracy'. In: H. Bäck, H. Heinelt and A. Magnier, eds. *The European mayor: Political leaders in the changing context of local democracy*. VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, pp. 151-175.

Haymond, S., (2017). 'Enhance your leadership through influence'. *The Journal of Applied Laboratory Medicine*, 1(5), pp. 598-599.

Hecl, H., (2011). *A government of strangers: Executive politics in Washington*. Brookings Institution Press.

Heifetz, R. A., (1994). *Leadership without easy answers*. Harvard University Press.

Heifetz, R. A., (2009). *The practice of adaptive leadership: Tools and tactics for changing your organizational world*. Harvard Business Press.

Heinelt, H. and Hlepas, N. K., (2006). 'Typologies of local government systems'. In: H. Bäck, H. Heinelt and A. Magnier, eds. *The European mayor: Political leaders in the changing context of local democracy*. VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, pp. 21-42.

Heinelt, H., Hlepas, N., Kuhlmann, S. and Swianiewicz, P., (2018). 'Local government systems: Grasping the institutional environment of mayors'. In: H. Heinelt, N. Hlepas, S. Kuhlmann and P. Swianiewicz, eds. *Political leaders and changing local democracy: The European mayor*. Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 19-78.

Helms, L., (2012). 'The importance of studying political leadership comparatively'. In: L. Helms, ed. *Comparative political leadership*. Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 1-24.

Hendriks, F. and Karsten, N., (2014). 'Theory of democratic leadership'. In: P. 't Hart and R. Rhodes, eds. *Oxford handbook of political leadership*. Oxford University Press, pp. 41-56.

Hermann, M. G., (2010). 'Assessing leadership style: A trait analysis'. In: J. M. Post, ed. *The psychological assessment of political leaders: With profiles of Saddam Hussein and Bill Clinton*. University of Michigan Press, p. 178.

Hermann, M., (2013). 'Political psychology and the study of political leadership'. In: P. 't Hart and R. Rhodes, eds. *Oxford handbook of political leadership*. Oxford University Press, pp. 25-39.

- Hermann, M., ed., (2003). *The next generation of world leaders*. Central Intelligence Agency.
- Hersey, P. and Blanchard, K. H., (1969). *Management of organizational behaviour: Utilizing human resources*. Prentice Hall.
- Hesse-Biber, S., (2010). 'Qualitative approaches to mixed methods practice'. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 16(6), pp. 455-468.
- Hirst, P., (2000). 'Democracy and governance'. In: J. Pierre, ed. *Debating governance: Authority, steering and democracy*. Oxford University Press, pp. 13-35.
- Hlepas, N., Chantzaras, T. and Getimis, P., (2018). 'Leadership styles of European mayors: How much have they changed over the past 12 years?'. In: H. Heinelt, N. Hlepas, S. Kuhlmann and P. Swianiewicz, eds. *Political leaders and changing local democracy: The European mayor*. Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 209-241.
- Hockin, T. A., (1977). *Apex of power: The prime minister and political leadership in Canada*. Prentice-Hall of Canada.
- Hollis, M., (1994). *The philosophy of social science: An introduction*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hood, C., (1991). 'A public management for all seasons?'. *Public administration*, 69(1), pp. 3-19.
- Hood, C., (1995). 'The "new public management" in the 1980s: Variations on a theme'. *Accounting, organizations and society*, 20(2-3), pp. 93-109.
- House of Lords Library, (2023). *Health care in rural areas*. In Focus. [Online]. Available at: <https://lordslibrary.parliament.uk/health-care-in-rural-areas/>.
- House, R. and Mitchell, R., (1974). 'Path-goal theory of leadership'. *Journal of Contemporary Business*, 3, pp. 81-97.
- House, R. J. and Aditya, R. N., (1997). 'The social psychology of leadership: Theory and research'. In: R. P. Vecchio, ed. *Leadership: Understanding the dynamics of power and influence in organizations*. 2nd ed. University of Notre Dame Press, pp. 181-218.
- House, R. J. and Aditya, R. N., (1997). 'The social scientific study of leadership: Quo vadis?'. *Journal of Management*, 23, pp. 409-473.
- House, R., (1971). 'A path goal theory of leader effectiveness'. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 16(3), p. 321-339.

Howlett, M., Kekez, A. and Poocharoen, O.O., (2017). 'Understanding co-production as a policy tool: Integrating new public governance and comparative policy theory'. *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, 19(5), pp.487-501

Howlett, M., Koštro, A.K. and Poocharoen, O.O., 2015. 'Co-production as a Policy Tool: Merging Policy and Management Thinking to Advance Policy Theory'. In *International Conference on Public Policy*, Milan, Italy.

Hudson, B., Hunter, D. and Peckham, S., (2019). 'Policy failure and the policy-implementation gap: can policy support programs help? '. *Policy Design and Practice*, 2(1), pp. 1-14.

Huxham, C. and Vangen, S., (2005). '*Managing to collaborate: The theory and practice of collaborative advantage*'. Routledge.

Hyde, K. F., (2000). 'Recognising deductive processes in qualitative research'. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 3(2), pp. 82-90.

Illsley, B. and Coles, E., (2009). 'Putting communities in control: A Scottish perspective'. *Planning Practice & Research*, 24(3), pp. 363-378.

Innes, J. and Booher, D., (2010). '*Planning with complexity: An introduction to collaborative rationality for public policy*'. Routledge.

Innes, J. E. and Booher, D. E., (2004). 'Reframing public participation: strategies for the 21st century'. *Planning Theory and Practice*, 5, pp. 419-436.

Insch, G. S., Moore, J. E. and Murphy, L. D., (1997). 'Content analysis in leadership research: Examples, procedures, and suggestions for future use'. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 8(1), pp. 1-25.

Integration Joint Board (2014, January 31). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 31, 2014. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2014, March 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 28, 2014. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2014, May 23). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, May 23, 2014. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2014, November 10). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 10, 2014. Area D Council Archive, Area D.

Integration Joint Board (2014, November 17). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 17, 2014. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2014, November 7). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 7, 2014. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2015, August 27). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, August 27, 2015. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2015, August 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, August 28, 2015. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2015, February 3). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, February 3, 2015. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2015, July 1). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, July 1, 2015. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2015, July 1). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, July 1, 2015. Area D Council Archive, Area D.

Integration Joint Board (2015, May 13). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, May 13, 2015. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2015, November 26). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 26, 2015. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2015, October 29). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, October 29, 2015. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2015, September 25). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, September 25, 2015. Area B Council Archive, Area B.

Integration Joint Board (2016, April 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, April 28, 2016. Area B Council Archive, Area B.

Integration Joint Board (2016, December 9). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, December 9, 2016. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2016, February 8). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, February 8, 2016. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2016, January 15). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 15, 2016. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2016, January 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 28, 2016. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2016, January 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 28, 2016. Area G Council Archive, Area G.

Integration Joint Board (2016, March 11). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 11, 2016. Area C Council Archive, Area C.

Integration Joint Board (2016, March 17). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 17, 2016. Area G Council Archive, Area G.

Integration Joint Board (2016, November 16). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 16, 2016. Area D Council Archive, Area D.

Integration Joint Board (2016, November 29). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 29, 2016. Area G Council Archive, Area G.

Integration Joint Board (2016, November 4). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 4, 2016. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2016, October 31). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, October 31, 2016. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2016, September 16). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, September 16, 2016. Area C Council Archive, Area C.

Integration Joint Board (2016, September 22). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, September 22, 2016. Area G Council Archive, Area G.

Integration Joint Board (2017, August 24). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, August 24, 2017. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2017, August 30). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, August 30, 2017. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2017, December 12). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, December 12, 2017. Area B Council Archive, Area B.

Integration Joint Board (2017, December 14). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, December 14, 2017. Area B Council Archive, Area B.

Integration Joint Board (2017, February 1). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, February 1, 2017. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2017, February 15). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, February 15, 2017. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2017, January 20). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 20, 2017. Area C Council Archive, Area C.

Integration Joint Board (2017, January 25). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 25, 2017. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2017, June 14). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 14, 2017. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2017, June 21). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 21, 2017. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2017, June 29). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 29, 2017. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2017, June 29). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 29, 2017. Area B Council Archive, Area B.

Integration Joint Board (2017, June). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 2017. Area B Council Archive, Area B.

Integration Joint Board (2017, March 1). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 1, 2017. Area D Council Archive, Area D.

Integration Joint Board (2017, March 15). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 15, 2017. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2017, March 15). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 15, 2017. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2017, March 21). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 21, 2017. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2017, March 22). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 22, 2017. Area D Council Archive, Area D.

Integration Joint Board (2017, November 8). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 8, 2017. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2017, October 12). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, October 12, 2017. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2017, September 25). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, September 25, 2017. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2018, December 13). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, December 13, 2018. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2018, January 24). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 24, 2018. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2018, January 26). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 26, 2018. Area C Council Archive, Area C.

Integration Joint Board (2018, January 3). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, January 3, 2018. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2018, June 20). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 20, 2018. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2018, June 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 28, 2018. Area B Council Archive, Area B.

Integration Joint Board (2018, June 3). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 3, 2018. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2018, March 26). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 26, 2018. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2018, March 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 28, 2018. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2018, May 2). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, May 2, 2018. Area D Council Archive, Area D.

Integration Joint Board (2018, November 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 28, 2018. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2018, September 27). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, September 27, 2018. Area G Council Archive, Area G.

Integration Joint Board (2019, February 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, February 28, 2019. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2019, February 6). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, February 6, 2019. Area F Council Archive, Area F.

Integration Joint Board (2019, March 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, March 28, 2019. Area H Council Archive, Area H.

Integration Joint Board (2019, November 27). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 27, 2019. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2019, November 28). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 28, 2019. Area B Council Archive, Area B.

Integration Joint Board (2019, November 6). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 6, 2019. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2019, October 9). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, October 9, 2019. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2019, September 27). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, September 27, 2019. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2020, February 6). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, February 6, 2020. Area G Council Archive, Area G.

Integration Joint Board (2020, July 31). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, July 31, 2020. Area J Council Archive, Area J.

Integration Joint Board (2020, June 17). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, June 17, 2020. Area I Council Archive, Area I.

Integration Joint Board (2020, May 21). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, May 21, 2020. Area G Council Archive, Area G.

Integration Joint Board (2020, November 25). Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, November 25, 2020. Area E Council Archive, Area E.

Integration Joint Board (2020, October 29). ' Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, October 29, 2020'. Area G Council Archive, Area G.

Integration Joint Board (2020, September 23). 'Minutes of the Integration Joint Board, September 23, 2020'. Area D Council Archive, Area D.

Interviewee A. (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 11 April, Scotland.

Interviewee A1 (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 5 Jan, Scotland.

Interviewee B (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 4 June, Scotland.

Interviewee B1 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 1 Dec, Scotland.

Interviewee C (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 4 March, Scotland.

Interviewee C1 (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 11 Feb, Scotland.

Interviewee C2 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 16 Dec, Scotland.

Interviewee D1 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 4 Nov, Scotland.

Interviewee E (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 11 March, Scotland..

Interviewee F (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 8 March, Scotland.

Interviewee F1 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 3 Dec, Scotland.

Interviewee G (2022 Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 23 March, Scotland.

Interviewee G1 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 17 Nov, Scotland.

Interviewee H (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 4 March, Scotland.

Interviewee H1 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 6 Dec, Scotland.

Interviewee H2 (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 29 March, Scotland.

Interviewee I (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 16 March, Scotland.

Interviewee I1 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 23 Nov, Scotland.

Interviewee I2 (2022). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 18 March, Scotland.

Interviewee J1 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 8 Dec, Scotland.

Interviewee K1 (2021). Interviewed by A. Mashkoor. 2 Dec, Scotland.

Ivanišević, S., (1987). *Izvršni sloj u lokalnoj upravi*. Pravni fakultet.

Jackson, M., (2009). 'Responsibility versus accountability in the Friedrich-finer debate'. *Journal of Management History*, 15(1), pp. 66-77.

Jackson, W., Gillis, A. and Verberg, N., (2011). 'Qualitative research methods'. In: M. Eid, ed. *Research methods in communication*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 97-120.

James, K. T., (2011). 'Leadership in context lessons from new leadership theory and current leadership development practice'. In: S. Alimo-Metcalfe and J. Alban-Metcalfe, eds. *The new public leadership challenge*. Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 57-76.

Jick, T. D., (1979). 'Mixing qualitative and quantitative methods: Triangulation in action'. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24(4), pp. 602-611.

Jogulu, U. D. and Wood, G. J., (2006). 'The role of leadership theory in raising the profile of women in management'. *Equal Opportunities International*, 25(4), pp. 236-250.

John, P. and Cole, A., (1999). 'Political leadership in the new urban governance: Britain and France compared'. *Local Government Studies*, 25(4), pp. 98-115.

John, P. and Cole, A., (2014). 'Political leadership in the new urban governance: Britain and France compared'. In: D. Sweeting, ed. *Renewing local democracy?*. Routledge, pp. 98-115.

John, P., (2010). 'Local government reform and political leadership'. In: S. Brookes and K. Grint, eds. *The new public leadership challenge*. Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 85-98.

Jones, B. D., (1985). 'The impact of party and ideology on urban service delivery'. In: J. P. Crecine, ed. *Research in urban policy: A research annual*, vol. 1. JAI Press, pp. 3-36.

Joseph-Williams, N., Edwards, A. and Elwyn, G., 2014. 'Power imbalance prevents shared decision making'. *Bmj*, 348.

Judd, D., (2000). 'Strong leadership'. *Urban Studies*, 37(5-6), pp. 951-961.

Kalkman, J.P. and Groenewegen, P., 2019. 'On frontline workers as bureau-political actors: The case of civil-military crisis management'. *Administration & Society*, 51(7), pp.1148-1170.

MacQueen, K. M. and Namey, E. E., (2012). *Applied thematic analysis*. Sage Publications.

Kane, J. and Patapan, H., (2009). 'The democratic legitimacy of bureaucratic leadership'. In: J. Kane, H. Patapan and P. T. Hart, eds. *Dispersed democratic leadership*. Oxford University Press, pp. 119-139.

- Kane, J., Patapan, H. and Hart, P. T., (2009). 'Dispersed democratic leadership'. In: J. Kane, H. Patapan and P. T. Hart, eds. *Dispersed democratic leadership*. Oxford University Press, pp. 1-12.
- Kanter, R.M., 2007. 'The enduring skills of change leaders'. *NHRD Network Journal*, 1(5_Special_Issue), pp.53-59.
- Kaplan, R.S., Palepu, K. and Hollis, H., 2003. 'Boards and corporate governance: a balanced scorecard approach'. *Harvard Business School Working Knowledge*, pp.1-4.
- Kareem, J., (2016). 'The influence of leadership in building a learning organization'. *IUP Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 15(1), pp. 7-18.
- Karlsson, M., (2012). 'Participatory initiatives and political representation: The case of local councillors in Sweden'. *Local Government Studies*, 38(6), pp. 795-815.
- Kasapović, M., (2004). Lokalno izborno pravo u Hrvatskoj u komparativnoj perspektivi. In: Z. Petak, M. Kasapović and D. Lalić, eds. *Lokalna politika u Hrvatskoj*. Faculty of Political Science, Zagreb, pp. 29-54.
- Kearney, C., (2020). 'Entrepreneurial leadership and its impact on the emergence of entrepreneurial ventures'. In: R. Ramadani and V. D. Bexheti, eds. *Organizational mindset of entrepreneurship: Exploring the co-creation pathways of structural change and innovation*. Springer, pp. 9-24.
- Keating, M., (2010). *Government of Scotland: Public Policy Making after Devolution*. Edinburgh University Press.
- Keating, M., ed., (2020). *The Oxford handbook of Scottish politics*. Oxford University Press.
- Keiser, L. R. and Soss, J., (1998). 'With good cause: Bureaucratic discretion and the politics of child support enforcement'. *American Journal of Political Science*, 42(4), pp. 1133-1156.
- Kelly, J., (2007). 'The missing ingredient: Inter-municipal co-operation and central–local relations in the UK'. In: R. Hulst and A. van Montfort, eds. *Inter-municipal co-operation in Europe*. Springer, pp. 193-210.
- Kenny, M. and Luca, D., (2021). 'The urban-rural polarisation of political disenchantment: an investigation of social and political attitudes in 30 European countries'. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 14(3), pp. 565-582.
- Kerley, R., (2000). *The report of the renewing local democracy working group [the Kerley report]* '. Stationery Office.

Khanal, J., Rana, K., Sharma, L., Whybrow, N. and Ghimire, S., (2023). 'Context-specific leadership practices: An examination of evidence of successful community school headteachers in Nepal'. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 22(1), pp. 200-224.

Kickert, W. J. M. and Koppenjan, J. F. M., (1997). 'Public management and network management: An overview'. In: W. J. M. Kickert, E.-H. Klijn and J. F. M. Koppenjan, eds. *Managing complex networks: Strategies for the public sector*. Sage, pp. 35-61.

Klijn, E. H. and Koppenjan, J. F., (2000). 'Politicians and interactive decision making: Institutional spoilsports or playmakers'. *Public Administration*, 78(2), pp. 365-387.

Klijn, E. H. and Koppenjan, J., (2015). *Governance networks in the public sector*. Routledge.

Knight, K., 2017. 'Exploring leadership conceptualisations in semi-structured interviews from multiple perspectives'. In: M. C. Nussbaum and J. E. Reeser, eds. *Challenging leadership stereotypes through discourse: Power, management and gender*. Springer, pp. 119-145.

Kooiman, J., 2003. *Governing as governance*. Sage.

Kotter, J. P. and Lawrence, P. R., 1974. *Mayors in action*. Wiley & Sons.

Kotter, J.P., (2008). *Force for change: How leadership differs from management*. Simon and Schuster.

KPMG, 2020. *Annual audit report to the members of Perth and Kinross Integration Joint Board and the controller of audit for the year ended 31 March 2020*. KPMG.

Kuckartz, U., 2019. 'Qualitative text analysis: A systematic approach. In: G. Kaiser and N. Presmeg, eds. *Compendium for early career researchers in mathematics education*'. Springer, pp. 181-197.

Langbein, L. I., 2000. 'Ownership, empowerment, and productivity: Some empirical evidence on the causes and consequences of employee discretion'. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 19(3), pp. 427-449.

Larsen, G. L., 2008. *Emerging governance at the edge of constrained federalism: Public administrators at the frontier of democracy*. Doctoral dissertation. Portland State University.

Lather, P., 1993. 'Fertile obsession: Validity after poststructuralism'. *The sociological quarterly*, 34(4), pp.673-693.

Leach, S. and Wilson, D., 2000. *Local political leadership*. The Policy Press.

Leach, S. and Wilson, D., 2002. 'Rethinking local political leadership'. *Public Administration*, 80(4), pp.665-689.

Leach, S., Stewart, J. and Jones, G., 2017. '*Centralisation, devolution and the future of local government in England*'. Routledge.

Lee, S., 2022. 'When tensions become opportunities: Managing accountability demands in collaborative governance'. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 32(4), pp. 641-655.

Lees-Marshment, J. (2016). 'Deliberative political leaders: The role of policy input in political leadership'. *Politics and Governance*, 4 (2), pp. 25-35.

Liddle, J., 2021. 'New public governance'.

Liden, R. C. and Antonakis, J., 2009. 'Considering context in psychological leadership research'. *Human Relations*, 62, pp. 1587-1605.

Linden, R. M., 2002. '*Working across boundaries: Making collaboration work in government and nonprofit organization*'. Jossey-Bass.

Lipsky, M., (2010). '*Street-level bureaucracy: Dilemmas of the individual in public service*'. Russell Sage Foundation.

Local Government Association (2019) National census of local authority councillors 2018. London: Local Government Association. Available at: <https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/Councillors%27%20Census%202018%20-%20report%20FINAL.pdf>

Local Government Association and Public Health England, 2017. Health and wellbeing in rural areas. Available at: https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/1.39_Health%20in%20rural%20areas_WEB.pdf.

Local Government Association, 2023. Sector-led improvement in 2020/21. London: LGA. Available at: <https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/sector-led-improvement-pr-75b.pdf>.

Lonsdale, J., (2009). 'Managing performance: International comparisons - by Geert Bouckaert and John Halligan'. *Public Administration*, 87(3), pp. 702-704.

Love, H. and Powe, M., (2020). 'Building resilient rural places: Strategies from local leaders to strengthen rural assets, diversity, and dynamism'. Brookings institutions.

Lowndes, V. and Gardner, A., (2016). 'Local governance under the conservatives: Super-austerity, devolution and the 'smarter state''. *Local Government Studies*, 42(3), pp. 357-375.

Lowndes, V. and Leach, S., (2004). 'Understanding local political leadership: constitutions, contexts and capabilities'. *Local Government Studies*, 30(4), pp. 557-575.

Lührmann, A., Marquardt, K.L. and Mechkova, V., 2020. 'Constraining governments: New indices of vertical, horizontal, and diagonal accountability'. *American Political Science Review*, 114(3), pp.811-820

Lupton, R., (2003). '*Case brief 25 - Poverty street: The dynamics of neighbourhood decline and renewal*'. Centre for Analysis of Social Exclusion, London School of Economics.

Margerum, R. D., (2007). 'Overcoming locally based collaboration constraints'. *Society & Natural Resources*, 20(2), pp. 135-152.

Marsh, D. and Stoker, G., eds., (1995). *Theory and methods in political science*. Macmillan.

Masciulli, J., Molchanov, M. A. and Knight, W. A., (2009). 'Political leadership in context'. In: J. Masciulli, M. A. Molchanov and W. A. Knight, eds. *The Ashgate research companion to political leadership*. Ashgate, pp. 3-27.

Masciulli, J., Molchanov, M. A. and Knight, W. A., (2016). 'Political leadership in context'. In: J. Masciulli, M. A. Molchanov and W. A. Knight, eds. *The Ashgate research companion to political leadership*. Routledge, pp. 3-27.

Matshabaphala, M. D. J., (2017). 'Traditional leadership and a simpler way to accountability in local government'. In: *International Conference on Public Administration and Development Alternatives (IPADA)*. University of Limpopo, pp. 1-10.

Mawhinney, T. C. and Ford, J. D., (1977). 'The path goal theory of leader effectiveness: An operant interpretation'. *Academy of Management Review*, 2(3), pp. 398-411.

May, P. J. and Winter, S. C., (2009). 'Politicians, managers, and street-level bureaucrats: Influences on policy implementation'. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 19(3), pp. 453-476.

McConnell, A., (2004). '*Scottish local government*'. Edinburgh University Press.

McGarvey, N. and Cairney, P., (2008). '*Scottish politics*'. Palgrave.

McGarvey, N., (2002). 'Central–local relations in Scotland post devolution'. *Local Government Studies*, 28(3), pp. 29-48.

McGarvey, N., (2012). 'Expectations, assumptions and realities: Scottish local government post-devolution'. *The British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 14(1), pp. 153-174.

McGowan, V.J., Buckner, S., Mead, R., McGill, E., Ronzi, S., Beyer, F. and Bambra, C., (2021). 'Examining the effectiveness of place-based interventions to improve public health and reduce health inequalities: an umbrella review'. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), pp.1-17.

McIntosh, N. (1999) 'Local Government and the Scottish Parliament'. Edinburgh: The Stationery Office.

McKenna, H. and Dunn, P., (2015). '*Devolution: What it means for health and social care in England*'. The King's Fund.

McMillan, J., (2021) . 'Public Value Leadership in the Context of Outcomes, Impact and Reform'. Public Value Management, Governance and Reform in Britain, pp.173-200.

Meier, K. J., O'Toole Jr, L. J. and Nicholson-Crotty, S., (2004). 'Multilevel governance and organizational performance: Investigating the political-bureaucratic labyrinth'. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 23(1), pp. 31-47.

Merriam, S.B., 2015. 'Qualitative research: Designing, implementing, and publishing a study'. In *Handbook of research on scholarly publishing and research methods* (pp. 125-140). IGI Global.

Mfuru, A. W., Sarwatt, A. C. and Kanire, G., (2018). 'The impact of political interference in public administration in Kibaha town council'. *Global Journal of Political Science and Administration*, 6(4), pp. 21-31.

Michael, A., (2010). 'Leadership style and organizational impact'. Online: <http://www.ala.apa.org/newsletter>). Retrieved April, 10, p.2015.

Miles, M. B. and Huberman, A. M., (1994). '*Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*'. Sage.

Miller, S. I. and Fredericks, M. A., (1994). '*Qualitative research methods: Social epistemology and practical inquiry*'. Peter Lang.

Mills, J., Bonner, A. and Francis, K., (2006). 'The development of constructivist grounded theory'. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 5(1), pp. 25-35.

Møller, A. M., (2022). 'Mobilizing knowledge in frontline work: A conceptual framework and empirical exploration'. *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance*, 5(1), pp. 50-62.

Mongkol, K., (2011). 'The critical review of new public management model and its criticisms'. *Research Journal of Business Management*, 5(1), pp. 35-43.

Moore, A. and MacKenzie, M.K., 2020. 'Policy making during crises: how diversity and disagreement can help manage the politics of expert advice'. *Bmj*, 371.

Moore, D. A. and Bazerman, M. H., (2022). '*Decision leadership: Empowering others to make better choices*'. Yale University Press.

Moore, J., Elliott, I. C. and Hesselgreaves, H., (2023). 'Collaborative leadership in integrated care systems: Creating leadership for the common good'. *Journal of Change Management*, pp. 1-16.

Moore, M. H., (1995). '*Creating public value: Strategic management in government*'. Harvard University Press.

Morais, F., Kakabadse, A. and Kakabadse, N., (2020). 'Leading through discontinuous change: A typology of problems and leadership approaches in UK boards'. *Long Range Planning*, 53(2), p. 101870.

Morgan, D. and Cook, B., (2015). '*New public governance: A regime-centered perspective*'. Routledge.

Morrell, K. and Hartley, J., (2006). 'A model of political leadership'. *Human Relations*, 59(4), pp. 483-504.

Morse, R. S., (2010). 'Integrative public leadership: Catalysing collaboration to create public value'. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 21(2), pp. 231-245.

Mukoro, F., 2023. 'How co-production is used to improve the quality of services and peoples experience of care: A literature review'. *NHS England*. Available online at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/long-read/how-co-production-is-used-to-improve-the-quality-of-services-and-peoples-experience-of-care-a-literature-review/#point-of-care-requirementscreating-the-conditions-for-genuine-co-production-at-point-of-care>.

Myers, G., (2020). 'Urban politics and policy in a southern urban planet'. In: J. Rokem and C. Boano, eds. *Rethinking urbanism*. Bristol University Press, pp. 155-178.

Nabatchi, T. and Leighninger, M., (2015). '*Public participation for 21st century democracy*'. John Wiley & Sons.

National Committee for Research Ethics in the Social Sciences and the Humanities (NESH). (2021). *Guidelines for Research Ethics in the Social Sciences and the Humanities* (5th ed.)

National Records of Scotland, (2021). 'Mid-2020 Population Estimates, Scotland'. Edinburgh: National Records of Scotland. Available at: <https://www.nrscotland.gov.uk/files//statistics/council-areadata-sheets/angus-council-profile.html>.

Neuendorf, K. A., (2017). '*The content analysis guidebook*'. Sage.

- Neuman, W. L., (2011). 'Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches'. In: M. Eid, ed. *Research methods in communication*. Pearson, pp. 341-377.
- NHS England and NHS Improvement. (2019). 'Innovative workforce models'. [Online] Available at: URL (Accessed: Rapid response: the role of the ambulance sector in transforming services and coping with the long-term impact of COVID-19 (nhsproviders.org)).
- NHS Scotland. (2022). '*Blueprint for Good Governance: Second Edition*'. [Online]. Available at: NHS Scotland Publications.
- Norris, N., (1997). 'Error, bias and validity in qualitative research'. *Educational Action Research*, 5(1), pp. 172-176.
- Northouse, P. G., (2007). '*Leadership: Theory and practice*'. 4th ed. Sage.
- Northouse, P. G., (2010). '*Leadership: Theory and practice*'. 5th ed. Sage.
- Northouse, P. G., (2013). '*Leadership: Theory and practice*'. 6th ed. Sage.
- Northouse, P. G., (2021). '*Leadership: Theory and practice*'. Sage.
- Nunes, F. J. C. T., (2010). '*The analysis of political will and its role in leadership: a study of Portuguese mayors*'. Doctoral dissertation'. Universidade de Aveiro.
- Nye, J. S., (2010). 'Power and leadership. In: N. Nohria and A. Khurana, eds. *Handbook of leadership theory and practice*'. Harvard Business Press, pp. 305-332.
- O'Flynn, J., (2007). 'From new public management to public value: Paradigmatic change and managerial implications'. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 66(3), pp. 353-366.
- O'Toole, L., (2010). 'The ties that bind? Networks, public administration, and political science'. *Political Science & Politics*, 43, pp. 7-14.
- Orr, K. and McAteer, M., (2010). 'The modernisation of local decision making: Public participation and Scottish local government'. *Local Government Studies*, 36(1), pp. 25-44. doi: 10.1080/0300393042000267209.
- Osborn, R. N., Hunt, J. G. and Jauch, L. R., (2002). 'Toward a contextual theory of leadership'. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 13, pp. 797-837.
- Osborne, S. P., 2010. '*The new public governance*'. Routledge.
- Page, D. and Wong, T. P. (1998). 'A conceptual framework for measuring servant leadership'. Langley, , Canada: Trinity Western University. Unpublished manuscript.

- Page, E.C., 1991. *'Localism and centralism in Europe: The political and legal bases of local self-government'*. Oxford University Press.
- Pandey, S. K. and Moynihan, D. P., (2006). 'Bureaucratic red tape and organizational performance: Testing the moderating role of culture and political support'. In: G. A. Boyne, K. J. Meier, L. J. O'Toole Jr and R. M. Walker, eds. *Public service performance: Perspectives on measurement and management*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 130-151.
- Patton, M. Q., (1990). *'Qualitative evaluation and research methods'*. 2nd ed. Sage.
- Patton, M. Q., (2002). *'Qualitative research & evaluation methods'*. 3rd ed. Sage.
- Patton, M. Q., (2014). *'Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice'*. 4th ed. Sage.
- Pearce, C. L. and Conger, J. A., (2003). All those years ago: 'The historical underpinnings of shared leadership'. In: C. L. Pearce and J. A. Conger, eds. *Shared leadership*. Sage, pp. 1-18.
- Pearce, C. L., Conger, J. A. and Locke, E. A., (2008). 'Shared leadership theory'. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 19(5), pp. 622-628. doi: 10.1016/j.leaqua.2008.07.005.
- Pearson, C. and Watson, N., (2018). 'Implementing health and social care integration in Scotland: Renegotiating new partnerships in changing cultures of care'. *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 26(3), pp. e396-e403.
- Pestoff, V., (2011). 'Co-production, new public governance and third sector social services in Europe'. *Ciências Sociais Unisinos*, 47(1), pp. 15-24.
- Peters, B. G. (2021). 'Governing in a time of global crises: the good, the bad, and the merely normal'. *Global Public Policy and Governance*, 1, 4–19.
- Peters, B. G. and Pierre, J., (2016). *'Governance, politics and the state.'* Macmillan International Higher Education.
- Peters, B. G., (2017). 'What is so wicked about wicked problems? A conceptual analysis and a research program'. *Policy and Society*, 36(3), pp. 385-396.
- Pollitt, C. and Bouckaert, G., (2011). *'Continuity and change in public policy and management'*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Porter, L. W. and McLaughlin, G. B., (2006). 'Leadership and the organizational context: like the weather?'. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 17(6), pp. 559-576.

- Powell, G.B., 2020. 'Mandate Versus Accountability'.
- Pratchett, L., (2004). 'Local autonomy, local democracy and the 'new localism''. *Political Studies*, 52(2), pp. 358-375.
- Preston, T. and 't Hart, P., (1999). 'Understanding and evaluating bureaucratic politics: The nexus between political leaders and advisory'. *Political Psychology*, 20(1), pp. 49-98.
- Price-Dowd, C. F. J., (2020). 'Your leadership style: why understanding yourself matters'. *BMJ Leader*, 4(4).
- Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act (2014). Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2014/9/contents/enacted>.
- Pugh, M. and Connolly, J., (2016). 'A review of contemporary linked challenges for Scottish local government'. *Scottish Affairs*, 25(3), pp. 317-336.
- Pugh, M., (2014). 'Centralism versus localism? Democracy versus efficiency? The perennial challenges of Scottish local government organisation'. *Scottish Affairs*, 23(4), pp. 483-507.
- Ramadass, S. D., Sambasivan, M. and Xavier, J. A., (2018). 'Collaboration outcomes in a public sector: impact of governance, leadership, interdependence and relational capital'. *Journal of Management and Governance*, 22, pp. 749-771.
- Rhodes, R. A. W., (1997). '*Understanding governance: Policy networks, governance, reflexivity and accountability*'. Open University Press.
- Rhodes, R. A., (2017). '*Network governance and the differentiated polity: Selected essays*'. Vol. 1. Oxford University Press.
- Rhodes, R.A.W. and Hart, P.T. eds., 2014. *The Oxford handbook of political leadership*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Ridder, H. G., (2017). 'The theory contribution of case study research designs'. *Business Research*, 10, pp. 281-305.
- Ridley, N., (1988). '*The local right*. Centre for Policy Studies'. Sharpe, J., 1970. Theories and values of local government. *Political Studies*, 18(2), pp. 153-174.
- Ritchie, B. and Haggith, M., (2012). 'The push-me, pull-you of forest devolution in Scotland'. In: J. Lidström and L. E. Loughlin, eds. *The politics of decentralization*. Routledge, pp. 212-228.

Robert, V. and Vandenberghe, C., (2021). 'Laissez-faire leadership and affective commitment: The roles of leader-member exchange and subordinate relational self-concept'. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 36, pp. 533-551.

Rossman, G. B. and Rallis, S. F., (1998). '*Learning in the field: An introduction to qualitative research*'. Sage.

Rost, J. C., (1991). '*Leadership for the twenty-first century*'. Praeger Publishers.

Sancino, A., (2021). 'Local political leadership: from managerial performances to leaders-hip hop on social media? '. *International Journal of Public Leadership*, 17(3), pp. 283-297.

Sanga, N., Gonzalez Benson, O. and Josyula, L., (2022). 'Top-down processes derail bottom-up objectives: a study in community engagement and 'Slum-Free City Planning''. *Community Development Journal*, 57(4), pp. 615-634.

Scholz, J. T., Twombly, J. and Headrick, B., (1991). 'Street-level political controls over federal bureaucracy'. *American Political Science Review*, 85(3), pp. 829-850.

Scotland, A., (2018). '*Glasgow City Council best value assurance report*'. Audit Scotland.

Scottish Executive, (1999). '*The report of the commission on local government and the Scottish Parliament*'. Scottish Executive.

Scottish Executive, (2001a). '*Scottish local government's self-review of its political management structures*'. Scottish Executive.

Scottish Executive, (2001b). '*Framework document defining working relationships and consultation arrangements*'. Scottish Executive.

Scottish Executive, (2001c). '*The future of strategic planning*'. Scottish Executive.

Scottish Executive, (2002). '*Local government bill*'. Scottish Executive.

Scottish Government, (2009). '*Scottish community empowerment action plan*'. Scottish Government.

Scottish Government, (2015). '*Directions from integration authorities to health boards and local authorities: statutory guidance*'. Scottish Government.

Scottish Government, (2017). '*Mental Health Strategy 2017-2027*. Scottish Government'. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/mental-health-strategy-2017-2027> .

Scottish Government, (2019). '*Directions from integration authorities to health boards and local authorities: statutory guidance*'. Scottish Government.

Scottish Government, (2023 a). 'New Deal with Local Government – Verity House Agreement'. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/new-deal-local-government-partnership-agreement/>.

Scottish Government, (2023 b). 'Reprioritising £38m in the mental health budget: FOI release'. Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/foi-202200328373/>.

Scottish Government. (2015). 'Integration Joint Board: Roles, Responsibilities and Membership'. [Online Document]. Available at: Scottish Government - Integration Joint Board.

Scottish Government. (2016). 'Improving Public Services: A Guide to Better Outcomes'. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/policies/improving-public-services/>.

Scottish Government. (2018). 'Health and Social Care: Medium Term Financial Framework'. [Online]. Available at: Health and Social Care: medium term financial framework - gov.scot (www.gov.scot).

Scottish Government. (2022, June 27). 'Equality evidence strategy 2023 to 2025: engaging with stakeholder organisations [Strategy/plan]'. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/equality-evidence-strategy-2023-to-2025-engaging-with-stakeholder-organisations/>.

Scottish Office, (1997). 'Local government finance in Scotland'. Cmnd 6811. HMSO.

Scottish Parliament. (2019). Planning (Scotland) Act 2019 (ASP 13). Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2019/13/2021-04-01>.

Selznick, P., (1957). 'Leadership in administration: A sociological interpretation'. Happer & Row.

Shamir, B., (2012). 'Leadership in context and context in leadership studies'. In: D. V. Day and J. Antonakis, eds. *The nature of leadership*. 2nd ed. Sage, pp. 129-158.

Shanske, D., 2014. 'Local fiscal autonomy requires constraints: the case for fiscal menus'. *Stan. L. & Pol'y Rev.*, 25, p.9.

Sharpe, M., (2008). 'Styles of large group leadership'. *Group*, 32(4), pp. 289-301.

Silvia, C. and McGuire, M., (2010). 'Leading public sector networks: An empirical examination of integrative leadership behaviours'. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 21(2), pp. 264-277.

Sinclair, D., (1997). 'Local government and a Scottish Parliament'. *Scottish Affairs*, 19, pp. 1-12.

Smith, G., (2009). 'Democratic innovations: Designing institutions for citizen participation'. Cambridge University Press.

Social Research Association. (2021). 'Research Ethics Guidance'.

Sørensen, E. and Torfing, J., (2015). 'Enhancing public innovation through collaboration, leadership and new public governance'. In: A. Nicholls, J. Simon and M. Gabriel, eds. *New frontiers in social innovation research*. Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 145-169.

Sørensen, E. and Torfing, J., (2016). 'Political leadership in the age of interactive governance'. In: J. Edelenbos and I. van Meerkerk, eds. *Critical reflections on interactive governance*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 444-466.

Sørensen, E., (2006). Meta governance: 'The changing role of politicians in processes of democratic governance'. *American Review of Public Administration*, 36(1), pp. 98-114.

Sørensen, E., Hendriks, C. M., Hertting, N. and Edelenbos, J., (2020). 'Political boundary spanning: politicians at the interface between collaborative governance and representative democracy'. *Policy and Society*, 39(4), pp. 530-569.

Sorrentino, M., Sicilia, M. and Howlett, M., 2018. 'Understanding co-production as a new public governance tool'. *Policy and Society*, 37(3), pp.277-293.

Spears, L. C., ed., (1995). *Reflections on leadership: How Robert K. Greenleaf's theory of servant-leadership influenced today's top management thinkers*. John Wiley & Sons.

Springer.

Stebbins, R. A., (2001). *Exploratory research in the social sciences*. Vol. 48. Sage.

Steele Gray, C., (2022). 'Overcoming political fragmentation: The potential of meso-level mechanisms; Comment on "Integration or fragmentation of health care? Examining policies and politics in a Belgian case study"'. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 11(1), pp. 1-4.

Steger, M. B. and Roy, R. K., (2010). *Neoliberalism: A very short introduction*. Vol. 222. Oxford University Press.

Stewart, J. and Walsh, K., (1992). 'Change in the management of public services'. *Public Administration*, 70(4), pp. 499-518.

Stewart, J., (1995). 'A future for local authorities as community government'. In: J. Stewart and G. Stoker, eds. *Local government in the 1990s*. Macmillan, pp. 249-268.

Steyvers, K., Reynaert, H. and Valcke, T., (2012). 'Army of One or Join the Club'? Comparing local political leadership in Europe'. In: L. Helms, ed. *Comparative political leadership*. Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 227-248.

- Steyvers, K., Reynaert, H., Valcke, T. and Verhelst, T., (2008). 'From Princeps to President? Comparing local political leadership transformation'. *Local Government Studies*, 34(2), pp. 131-146. doi: 10.1080/03003930701852179.
- Stogdill, R. M., (1974). '*Handbook of leadership: A survey of theory and research*'. Free Press.
- Stoker, G., (1996). 'The struggle to reform local government: 1970–95'. *Public Money & Management*, 16(1), pp. 17-22.
- Stoker, G., (2000). '*The new politics of British local governance*'. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Stoker, G., (2006). 'Public value management: A new narrative for networked governance? '. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 36(1), pp. 41-57.
- Stoker, G., (2017). '*Why politics matters: Making democracy work*'. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Stoker, G., ed., (1999). '*The new management of British local governance*'. Macmillan.
- Stolzenberg, P., Terizakis, G., Hlepas, N. and Getimis, P., (2016). '*Cities in times of crisis: Fiscal consolidation in Germany and Greece*'. Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft.
- Stone, A. G., Russell, R. F. and Patterson, K., (2004). 'Transformational versus servant leadership: A difference in leader focus'. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 25(4), pp. 349-361. ISSN 0143-7739.
- Sullivan, H., (2010). 'Governing the mix: how local government still matters. ' In: J. Diamond, A. Southern and I. Liddle, eds. *From recession to renewal*. Policy Press, pp. 179-196.
- Suresh, D., (2015). 'Case study: Research method for social sciences. ' Available at SSRN 2684644.
- Svara, J. H. and Associates, (1994). '*Facilitative leadership in local government: Lessons from successful mayors and chairpersons*'. Jossey-Bass.
- Svara, J. H., (2003). 'Effective mayoral leadership in council-manager cities: Reassessing the facilitative model'. *National Civic Review*, 92(2), pp. 157-172. doi: 10.1002/(ISSN) 1542-7811.
- Svara, J. H., (2007). '*The ethics primer for public administrators in government and nonprofit organizations*'. Jones & Bartlett.
- Svara, J., (1990). '*Official leadership in local government: Patterns of conflict and cooperation*'. Oxford University Press.
- Swianiewicz, P., ed., (2001). '*Public perception of local governments*'. OSI/LGI.

- Tabner, K., (2020). '*Narratives of empowerment in Scottish community development policy: a multi-level, critical analysis of the design and implementation of the Community Empowerment (Scotland) Act (2015)*'. Doctoral dissertation. University of the West of Scotland.
- Tan, M., Fatt Hee, T. and Yan Piaw, C., (2015). 'A qualitative analysis of the leadership style of a vice-chancellor in a private university in Malaysia'. *SAGE Open*, 5(1), p. 2158244015577665.
- Teles, F., (2013). 'Facilitative mayors in complex environments: Why political will matters'. *Local Government Studies*, 39(4), pp. 465-482. doi: 10.1080/03003930.2013.801835.
- Teorell, J., (2006). 'Political participation and three theories of democracy: A research inventory and agenda'. *European Journal of Political Research*, 45(5), pp. 787-810.
- Theakston, K., (2011). 'Gordon Brown as prime minister: Political skills and leadership style'. *British Politics*, 6, pp. 78-100.
- Thomas, E. and Magilvy, J. K., (2011). 'Qualitative rigor or research validity in qualitative research'. *Journal for Specialists in Pediatric Nursing*, 16(1), pp. 151-155.
- Torfin, J. and Ansell, C. K., eds., (2016). '*Handbook on theories of governance*'. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Torfin, J., (2012). '*Interactive governance: Advancing the paradigm*'. Oxford University Press.
- Torfin, J., Andersen, L. B., Greve, C. and Klausen, K. K., (2020). '*Public governance paradigms: Competing and co-existing*'. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Torfin, J., Bentzen, T. Ø. and Winsvold, M. S., (2022). 'How institutional designs condition perceived local political leadership'. *Local Government Studies*, 48(3), pp. 341-366.
- Torfin, J., Peters, B. G., Pierre, J. and Sørensen, E., (2012). '*Interactive governance: Advancing the paradigm*'. Oxford University Press.
- Torrance, D., (2006). '*The Scottish secretaries*'. Birlinn Publishers.
- Tosun, J., Galanti, M.T. and Howlett, M., 2022. 'The significance of leadership in the evolution of policy styles: reconciling policy-making in the short and long term'. *Politische Vierteljahresschrift*, 63(2), pp.337-358.
- Trottier, T., Van Wart, M. and Wang, X., (2008). 'Examining the nature and significance of leadership in government organizations'. *Public Administration Review*, 68(2), pp. 319-333.
- Uhl-Bien, M. and Marion, R., eds., (2007). '*Complexity leadership: part 1: conceptual foundations*'. IAP.

UK Government. (2022). 'Build Back Better: Our Plan for Health and Social Care'. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/build-back-better-our-plan-for-health-and-social-care>.

Ulrich, D. and Smallwood, N., (2012). 'What is leadership? '. In: W. H. Mobley, Y. Wang and M. Li, eds. *Advances in global leadership*. Vol. 7. Emerald Group Publishing, pp. 9-36.

United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2016). 'Integrated Framework to Support Local Governance and Local Development'. Available at: <https://www.undp.org/publications/integrated-framework-support-local-governance-and-local-development>.

van der Hoek, M., Groeneveld, S. and Beerkens, M., (2021). 'Leadership behaviour repertoire: An exploratory study of the concept and its potential for understanding leadership in public organizations'. *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance*, 4(4), pp. 363-378.

van der Jagt, A. P., Szaraz, L. R., Delshammar, T., Cvejić, R., Santos, A., Goodness, J. and Buijs, A., (2017). 'Cultivating nature-based solutions: The governance of communal urban gardens in the European Union'. *Environmental Research*, 159, pp. 264-275.

Van Wart, M., (2003). 'Public sector leadership theory: An assessment'. *Public Administration Review*, 63(2), pp. 214-228.

Van Wart, M., (2013). 'Lessons from leadership theory and the contemporary challenges of leaders'. *Public Administration Review*, 75(4), pp. 553-565.

Verity House Agreement signed by First Minister and COSLA President (30th June 2023). Available at: <https://www.cosla.gov.uk/news/2023/a-new-deal-with-local-government-30th-june-2023>.

Wadhams, C., (2007). 'The end of the affair? '. *New Start*, 26(January), pp. 14-15.

Waldo, D., (1948). *The administrative state*. Ronald Press.

Walker, D., (2002). 'In praise of centralism. In: *A critique of the new localism*'. Catalyst Forum Working, pp. 1-18.

Walsh N, de Sarandy S (2023). 'The practice of collaborative leadership: Across health and care services'. London: The King's Fund. Available at: https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/sites/default/files/2023-07/The_practice_of_collaborative_leadership.pdf.

Walsh, K. and Walsh, K., (1995). 'The traditional model of public service provision'. In: K. Walsh, ed. *Public services and market mechanisms: Competition, contracting and the new public management*. Macmillan, pp. 3-28.

- Waring, J., Bishop, S., Clarke, J., Exworthy, M., Fulop, N. J., Hartley, J., Ramsay, A. I., Black, G. and Roe, B., (2022). 'Acquiring and developing healthcare leaders' political skills: an interview study with healthcare leaders'. *BMJ Leader*, 6(1), pp. 1-9.
- Weare, C., Lichterman, P. and Esparza, N., (2014). 'Collaboration and culture: Organizational culture and the dynamics of collaborative policy networks'. *Policy Studies Journal*, 42(4), pp. 590-619.
- Weller, P. and Stevens, B., (2015). 'When counting is over, can governments govern? *Social Alternatives*, 34(3), pp. 52-58.
- West, M., Armit, K., Loewenthal, L., Eckert, R., West, T. and Lee, A., (2015). '*Leadership and leadership development in health care: the evidence base*'. The King's Fund.
- Wimmelmann, C. L., Vallgård, S. and Jensen, A. M., (2018). 'Meet the local policy workers: Implementation of health promotion guidelines in Denmark'. *Public Policy and Administration*, 33(1), pp. 66-87.
- Winther, S.C. and Nielsen, V.L., (2008). 'Implementering af politik. 1. udg., 1. opl. *Academica, Århus*.
- Wolak, J., (2020). '*Compromise in an age of party polarization*'. Oxford University Press.
- Wondolleck, J. M. and Yaffee, S. L., (2000). '*Making collaboration work: Lessons from innovation in natural resource management*'. Island Press.
- Wonka, A., (2022). 'Policy and constituency frames in the advocacy of political parties and interest groups in policymaking'. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 29(1), pp. 1-22.
- Woodrow, W. (1887), "The study of administration", *Political Science Quarterly*, Vol. 2 No. 2, pp. 197-222.
- Woolpert, S., Slaton, C. D. and Schwerin, E. W., eds., (1998). '*Transformational politics: Theory, study, and practice*'. SUNY Press.
- Xu, H., Luke, N. and Short, S. E., (2021). 'Women's political leadership and adult health: Evidence from rural and urban China'. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 62(1), pp. 100-118.
- Yin, R. K., (1994). '*Case study research: Design and methods*'. 2nd ed. Sage.
- Yin, R. K., (2003). '*Case study research design and methods*'. 3rd ed. Sage.
- Yin, R. K., (2009). '*Case study research: Design and methods*'. 4th ed. Sage.
- Yin, R. K., (2014). '*Case study research: Design and methods*'. 5th ed. Sage.

Yin, R. K., (2018). '*Case study research and applications*'. 6th ed. Sage.

Yukl, G. A., (2006). '*Leadership in organizations*'. 6th ed. Prentice Hall.

Yukl, G. and Mahsud, R., (2010). 'Why flexible and adaptive leadership is essential'. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 62(2), pp. 81-93.

Yukl, G., (1989). 'Managerial leadership: 'A review of theory and research'. *Journal of Management*, 15, pp. 251-289.

Zaccaro, S. J. and Klimoski, R. J., eds., (2002). '*The nature of organizational leadership: Understanding the performance imperatives confronting today's leaders*'. Vol. 12. John Wiley & Sons.

Zeffane, R., Tipu, S. A. and Ryan, J. C., (2011). 'Communication, commitment & trust: Exploring the triad'. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(6), pp. 77-87.

Zelikow, P. and Rice, C., (1995). '*Germany unified and Europe transformed: a study in statecraft*'. Harvard University Press.

Appendix A: List of interviewees.

IJB Area	Role	Interview date	Code
Urban A	Political leader	Apr 2022	A
Urban A	Senior official	Jan 2022	A1
Rural B	Political leader	Jun 2022	B
Rural B	Senior official	Dec, 2021	B1
Urban C	Political leader	Mar 2022	C
Urban C	Senior official	Feb, 2022	C1
Urban C	Senior official	Dec 2021	C2
Urban D	Senior official	Nov 2021	D1
Rural E	Political leader	Mar 2022	E
Urban F	Political leader	Mar 2022	F
Urban F	Senior official	Dec 2021	F1
Rural G	Political leader	Mar 2022	G
Rural G	Senior official	Nov 2021	G1
Rural H	Political leader	Mar 2022	H
Rural H	Senior Official	Dec 2021	H1
Rural H	Political leader	Mar 2022	H2
Rural I	Political leader	Mar 2022	I
Rural I	Senior official	Nov 2021	I1
Rural I	Political leader	Mar 2022	I2
Rural J	Senior official	Dec 2021	J1
Rural K	Senior Official	Dec 2021	K

Rationale for selecting interviewees:

- LPL A:** A local political leader serving in the IJB as a board member. He was chosen because he represents the Urban Area A, which has less challenging conditions in terms of health and social care integration, compared to other areas. He also has experience of working in the oil sector before becoming a member of the IJB, which gives him a unique perspective on the economic and environmental issues affecting the area. He represented Conservative party.
- SO A1:** A senior official working as the Chief Officer of the IJB. She was chosen because she holds a leading position in the IJB and works closely with the local political leaders serving in the board. Her position allows her to take actions such as determining the direction of health and social care integration initiatives, for example, introducing training and education for IJB members to improve governance practices.
- LPL B:** A local political leader serving in the IJB as a board member. She was chosen because she represents the Rural Area B, which has more challenging conditions in terms of health and social care integration, due to its geographical remoteness, and limited resources. She also has a background as a nurse and community activist before being elected as a councillor and IJB member, which gives her a strong connection to the local community and its needs. She represented SNP.

- **SO B1:** A senior official working as a senior bureaucratic position in one of the regions of Scottish health and social care. He was chosen because he serves as an IJB member in Rural Area B. He is also an academic, which adds a unique perspective to the discussion.
- **LPL C:** A local political leader serving as the IJB Chair in one of the largest health and social care areas in Scotland, which has challenging economic conditions. He was chosen because he has been an elected member since 1995 and has been part of the previous model of health and social care delivery before the IJB. His experience and evolutionary understanding of health and social care integration delivery was important in shedding light on structural problems embedded in H&SC approach. He represented Labour Party.
- **SO C1:** A senior official working as the Chief Officer of Urban Area C IJB. She was chosen because she is one of the involved actors who directly contributed to the health and social care integration reforms and has experience of running multiple IJB areas as Chief Officer.
- **SO D1:** A senior official working as the Chief officer of Health and Social Care in Urban Area D. She was chosen because she belongs to one of the stable economic and financial condition areas, which is a small urban area. She has a strategic role in planning and implementing health and social care integration initiatives in the area.
- **LPL E:** A local political leader serving as the IJB Chair in Rural Area E. He was chosen because he has been an experienced politician serving local communities. He is also SNP local group leader, which gives him influence and authority in the IJB.
- **LPL F:** A local political leader serving as a board member in the IJB of Urban Area F. She was chosen because she represents a mixed challenging economic and financial condition area, which has a high demand for health and social care services. She belongs to the Labour party, which gives her a different political orientation from other interviewees.
- **SO F1:** A senior official working as the Assistant Chief Officer in one of the largest IJB areas in Scotland. He was chosen because he has more interaction with IJB members and is involved in detailed implementation of projects at the ground level, as compared to Chief Officers. He has a practical role in facilitating and coordinating health and social care integration activities in the area.
- **LPL G:** A local political leader serving as a board member in the IJB of Urban Area G. She was chosen because she represents an area that is going through immense financial challenges and pressures on health and social care services, which gives her a different orientation from other interviewees.
- **SO G1:** A senior official working as the Chief Officer in the IJB of Rural Area G. She was chosen because she represents a rural deprived area, with tough financial conditions and political instability. she has a challenging role in handling and dealing with all the pressures that affect the leadership who is responsible for effective delivery of health and social care integration.
- **LPL H:** A local political leader serving as a board member in the IJB of Rural Area H. She was chosen because she represents a small rural IJB that is one of the most effective in Scotland, with stable economic conditions and high performance in health and social care integration. She also has experience working in health care before getting elected as a political member and serving in the IJB, which gives her deep understanding of the health and social care sector.

- **SO H1:** A senior official working as the Chief Officer in the IJB of Rural Area H. She was chosen because she has had her career built locally in the local health and social care sector. This experience of working in the same area in different health and social care officer capacities brings a unique perspective related to health and social care delivery.
- **LPL I:** A local political leader serving as a board member in the IJB of Urban Area I. He was chosen because he represents a mixed economic and financial condition area, which has a moderate demand for health and social care services. He belongs to the Labour party.
- **SO I1:** A senior official working as the Chief Officer in the IJB of rural Area I. He was chosen because he represents a leadership position of the IJB, which is unique in a way that he also leads a regional health and social care program that combines two IJB areas to deliver services with collaboration. This puts him in a unique position in providing wider insights into the regional issues facing structural inequalities.
- **LPL I2:** A local political leader serving as a board member in the IJB of Urban Area I. He was chosen because he represents a mixed economic and financial condition area, which has a moderate demand for health and social care services. He belongs to the Conservative party, which gives him a different political orientation from other interviewees.
- **SO, J:** A senior official working as the Chair of Health and Social Care in Rural Area J, which gives him a leadership role and a strategic vision for health and social care integration. He was chosen because he represents an area that is facing challenging economic and financial conditions, which affect the quality and availability of health and social care services.

Appendix B: A copy of Consent form.

School of Education and Social Science

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: The role of local political leaders in Shaping the planning and Implementation of Health and social care integration: A case study of Scotland

Ethics Approval Number: 16144

Investigators names: Awais Mashkoor

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

The purpose of this research is to understand political leadership within health and social care integration as a major area of public sector reform in Scotland. The primary focus of the research includes understanding the leadership styles exhibited by local councillors in Integrated Joint Boards (and the factors which shape approaches to local leadership in this context).

I would like to request an interview with you and hope that you will be willing to offer some of your time. I know that you will be very busy so I will work around your diary if you are able to contribute to the study. The interview will last approximately no more than 45 minutes (but I would be grateful for any time you can spare if it is difficult for you to accommodate this time). The interview questions aim to understand the relationship between political representatives and Chief Officers and planners.

By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after completing the study without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (<i>age, sex, and contact details</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	

I agree to have my voice/likeness digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: ess.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE.

School of Education and Social Science

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals): (Interviewee, D1,2021)
capitals):

Name of researcher (block

Date: 04/11/2021

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

Appendix C: A Copy of Ethical approval.

Dear Awais Mashkoor,

Your application 16144: The role of local political leaders in Shaping the planning and Implementation of Health and social care integration c. 2014-2019: A case study of Scotland, submission 13367, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. We see no ethical issues; however, the application has been reviewed acknowledging that English is not the first language of the applicant. You may now proceed with your study, after you have improved the documents prior to collecting data. Please allow your supervisors check your PIS and CS in relation to the following comments from the reviewers. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

05/03/2021

Appendix D: A Copy of Invitation email.

Dear Councillors,
I hope you are well.

I'm a researcher at UWS and I am contacting you in your capacity as a health and social care leader in Scotland in the hope that you will be willing to be interviewed for my study. I am researching the role of local political leadership in the decision making of the health and social care integration (H&SCI) processes in Scotland. My study aims to understand the leadership approaches and styles (the way you work) exhibited by local political leadership while working in the IJBs.

Being a member of the IJB as elected member, I believe that you would be in the ideal position to give me valuable insights based on your experience. During the interview, you will be asked about the leadership approaches and styles exhibited by you as part of IJB processes, and you will also be asked about the role of contextual political factors, such as economic conditions, affiliation with a political party, the rural / urban nature of the area and the relationship with other stakeholders, such as the Chief Officer, in establishing your approach to leadership.

The interview takes around no more than 45 minutes and is very informal. Your responses to the questions will be kept confidential. Each interview will be assigned a number and alphabetical code to help ensure that personal identifiers are not revealed during the analysis and write up of findings.

If you are willing to participate, please suggest a day and time that suits you and I'll make myself available. As a research participant you have a choice between having the interview online or face to face. I am pleased to attach the participant information sheet, research informed consent form and brief questions for interview. Interview questions are examples of questions I will ask you, but I would also like to explore few related questions as well.

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask.

Looking forward to hearing from you.

Yours faithfully,

Awais

Appendix E: A Copy of Freedom of Information (FOI) request.

Hello there,

My name is Awais Mashkooor, and i am a doctoral student at university of the west of Scotland (UWS). I am conducting research on Health and social care integration in Scotland.

I am writing to you under the Freedom of Information Act 2002 to request the following information from *IJB area H*. Please may you provide me with:

Meeting minutes of shadow integrated joint board arrangement 2014-2016.

Please provide the information in the form soft copy.

If you can identify any ways that my request could be refined I would be grateful for any further advice and assistance.

If you have any queries please don't hesitate to contact me via email and I will be very happy to clarify what I am asking for and discuss the request.

Thank you for your time and I look forward to your response.

Best wishes,

Awais Mashkooor

Appendix F: A Sampling of Documents.

Documents selected	Documents analysis
Christie Commission (2011)	<p>This document offers a comprehensive overview of Scotland's recent public service delivery agenda, shedding light on the underlying principles and motivations driving the ongoing reforms in H&SCI. This thesis looked at this document in relation to H&SCI. It indicates the expected key characteristics of involved stakeholders, structures, and decision-making processes. The Christie Commission's work has challenged local political leaders to evolve new leadership practices that align with flatter, more collaborative, and less regulated public service organizations. In short, it outlines the initial scheme of the current reforms which empowers researchers to grasp the responsibilities, goals, objectives, stakeholder interactions in the context of local political leaders operating in H&SCI. By aligning with the research purpose, it will provide the necessary confidence to ask targeted and specific questions.</p>
<p>Public Bodies Joint Act (PBJA) (2014)</p> <p>Community Empowerment (Scotland) Act 2015 (Part 2) (CEA, 2015)</p>	<p>PBJA (2014) is a regulatory framework legislated to administer H&SC IJBs and is a Scottish law that allows two or more public bodies to work together to deliver public services more effectively and efficiently. The Act sets out a framework for joint working, including how decisions are made, how resources are shared, and how the public is consulted.</p> <p>CEA (2015) lawfully connect local communities to IJBs. IJBs are underpinned by Community Planning Partnerships (CPPS) to cater for local needs, and the CEA focuses on reforming CPPS. This legislation establishes a clear purpose for community planning, aiming to enhance local outcomes and reduce inequalities. CPPS contribute to IJBs' decision making by providing information on the needs of immediate communities, for instance their deprivation levels, their specific health and social care needs by involving communities in decision making process.</p>

	<p>The impact of community considerations on the role of local political leaders is one of the key focuses of this research. It helps to craft interview questions, particularly in exploring how community participation influences the roles and preferred leadership styles of local political leaders.</p>
<p>Health and Social Care Integration (2015)</p> <p>Health and Social Care series Social Work in Scotland (2016)</p> <p>Changing Models of Health and Social Care (2016)</p> <p>Health and Social Care Integration (2018)</p> <p>Published by Audit Scotland</p>	<p>These documents consist of reports prepared by Audit Scotland, which is an independent body that audits public bodies in Scotland to ensure that they are using public money effectively and efficiently. These reports are useful in understanding the relevance of political contextual factors as they report IJBs performance including the role of stakeholders, politicization of agenda, overall processes and funding mechanisms, as well as other key barriers.</p> <p>This means they presents an overview of current H&SCI efforts and how the local political actors and the political contextual factors interface in these. Further, these documents emphasize the importance of senior officials, enabling this study to ask local political leaders about the kind of responsibility they and other leaders have for H&SCI. This also leads to a question about the relationship with other actors (e.g., chief officers) which is one of the contextual factors in this study. This information is deemed important to understand the role of local political leaders in relation to their political context because it provides information to explore their behaviours in through specific situation aligned with conceptual framework of this study.</p>
<p>Local Government Benchmarking Framework National Benchmarking Overview Report 2018-19</p>	<p>This document also complements the contextual information observed in the Audit Scotland reports. It explains the level of variation across councils and factors shaping these trends including physical geography, population distribution, size of council and the impact of economy. Graphs are presented showing the level of variation across councils for each area benchmarking measure. This allows the researcher to ask specific questions from local political leaders in their particular local authority context, helps to ask relevant questions, and</p>

	facilitates conversation in order to obtain data that fits the conceptual construction of this study.
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Appendix G: IJBs reviewed meeting minutes.

IJB area B meeting minutes references.

References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 Apr 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 25 SEP, 2015).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 12 DEC, 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 June 2018).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board June 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 29 June 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 NOV 2019).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 14 DEC 2017).

IJB area C meeting minutes references.

(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 11 March 2016)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 26 January 2018)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 16 September 2016)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 20 Jan, 2017).

IJB area D meeting minutes references.

References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 10 NOV 2014).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 23 SEP 2020).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 22 Mar 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 1 July, 2015).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 1 MAR 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 16 Nov 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 2 May 2018).

IJB area E meeting minutes references.

References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 3 Feb 2015).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 27 Nov 2019).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 25 Nov 2020).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 30 Aug 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 25 Sep 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 13 May 2015).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 Aug 2015).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 3 FEB, 2015).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 1 FEB 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 Mar 2018).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 Nov 2018).

IJB area F meeting minutes references.

References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 17 NOV 2014).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 9 DEC, 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 31 OCT, 2016).

References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board, 21 MAR, 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 6 FEB 2019).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 8 NOV 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 20 JUN 2018).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 21 JUN, 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 24 Jan 2018).).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 8 FEB 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 15 MAR, 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 15 February 2017).

IJB area G meeting minutes references.

References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 21st May, 2020).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 17 MAR 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 22 SEP, 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 Jan 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 29 NOV 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 17 Mar 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 29 OCT 2020).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 27 SEP 2018).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 6th FEB 2020).

IJB area H meeting minutes references.

(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 26 NOVEMBER, 2015)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 27 AUGUST, 2015).
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 29 OCTOBER, 2015).
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 1 JULY, 2015).
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 FEB, 2019).
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 29 JUN, 2017).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 13 DEC, 2018).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 MAR, 2019).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 26 NOV, 2015).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 JAN 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 24 AUG 2017).

IJB area I meeting minutes references.

(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 9 October 2019)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 14 June 2017)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 15 March 2018)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 9 October 2019).
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 3 June 2018)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 25 January 2017)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 12 October 2017)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 26 March 2019)
(References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 17 June 2020)

IJB area J meeting minutes references.

References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 4 Nov 2016).

References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 15 Jan 2016).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 28 MAR 2014).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 31 Jan 2014).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 7 NOV 2014).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 6 NOV, 2019).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 27 Sep 2019).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 31 July 2020).
References – minutes of the Integration Joint Board 23 May 2014

Appendix H: NVivo Screenshot.

The screenshot displays the NVivo 12 Pro interface. The main window shows a hierarchical tree of nodes on the left and a detailed table of nodes on the right. The table columns are: Name, File, References, Created On, Created By, and Modified By. The nodes are organized into several levels, including 'IB area G', 'IB area B', 'IB area C', 'IB area D', 'IB area E', 'IB area F', 'IB area H', 'IB area I', 'IB area J', and 'West dumbertonshire'. Each node is associated with a specific file and a set of references.

Name	File	References	Created On	Created By	Modified By
IB area G		31	07/15/04/2021 14:44	AWAS	30/12/2023 13:47
Economy and Finance		6	16/14/11/2023 13:26	AWAS	14/11/2023 13:54
Frontline workforce expectations		5	7/14/11/2023 13:26	AWAS	14/11/2023 14:06
Geographical consideration		9	10/14/11/2023 13:26	AWAS	14/11/2023 13:46
Partnership		5	5/14/11/2023 13:27	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:43
Relationship		2	2/14/11/2023 13:31	AWAS	14/11/2023 13:35
IB area B		21	65/16/04/2021 14:19	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:28
Economy and finance		0	0/30/12/2023 14:31	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:31
IB area C		28	84/16/04/2021 12:15	AWAS	30/12/2023 13:49
Economy and finance		0	0/30/12/2023 14:31	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:31
IB area D		25	100/16/04/2021 11:56	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:29
Economy and Finance		0	0/30/12/2023 14:31	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:31
IB area E		24	78/15/04/2021 12:57	AWAS	14/11/2023 13:11
Economy and Finance		13	25/14/11/2023 13:02	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:12
Geographical consideration		10	16/14/11/2023 14:05	AWAS	30/12/2023 13:59
Partnership		2	5/14/11/2023 14:05	AWAS	30/12/2023 13:55
Relationship		6	8/14/11/2023 14:05	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:13
IB area F		40	136/16/04/2021 14:03	AWAS	30/12/2023 13:49
Community needs		11	19/30/12/2023 14:23	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:26
Economy and Finance		19	44/14/11/2023 14:03	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:26
Frontline Workforce		8	10/14/11/2023 14:01	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:26
Partnership		1	3/14/11/2023 14:04	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:20
Relationship		5	11/14/11/2023 14:04	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:23
Size		1	2/14/11/2023 14:04	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:21
IB area H		23	103/15/04/2021 13:18	AWAS	14/11/2023 13:10
IB area I		39	128/15/04/2021 15:52	AWAS	30/12/2023 13:48
IB area J		30	103/16/04/2021 14:47	AWAS	30/12/2023 14:30
Polarization		2	2/02/04/2021 13:13	AWAS	28/06/2021 14:34
Relationship between stakeholders		8	14/02/04/2021 13:54	AWAS	18/04/2021 13:57
West dumbertonshire		22	71/16/04/2021 15:16	AWAS	21/06/2021 13:23

This screenshot illustrates the hierarchical node structure of documentary analysis.

Appendix I: Interview Schedules.

Questions for Local Political Leaders.

1. Please explain how you view your own leadership style being part of IJB?
2. Have there been occasions when you have adjusted your leadership approach in light of the nature of the meetings?
3. To what extent does responsibilities towards your party shape how you engage in H&SC deliberations?
4. To what extent does the geographical, and economic context have implications for how you approach your role within the IJB?
5. How do you regard your relationship with officials and other agencies within the IJBs, including the chief officer? Is it positive, negative, or perhaps this is more nuanced?
6. Do you ever get a sense of how other stakeholders react to how you approach deliberations in the IJBs as a local political leader?

Questions with Senior Officials.

1. How do you regard your working relationship with local political elected members serving in the IJB?
2. To what extent do you feel supported by local political leaders in your position?
3. As a chief officer of an IJB, how would you describe the leadership style qualities and approaches of your local elected members serving with you in IJB?
4. To what extent does the political, geographical, and economic context have implications for how you approach your relationship with political leaders within the IJB?

Appendix J: NVivo Screenshot.

The screenshot shows the NVivo software interface with the following components:

- Top Menu:** File, Home, Import, Create, Explore, Share.
- Left Panel:** Quick Access (Files, Memos, Nodes), Data (Files, File Classifications, Externals), Codes (Nodes, Relationships, Relationship Types), Cases, Notes, Search, Maps, Output.
- Main Window:**
 - Nodes:** A hierarchical tree structure. The top-level node is "Governance structure and membership of IIBs". Below it are sub-nodes like "Committees", "IIB board", "Partner organisation", "Responsibility", and "Stakeholders". Other top-level nodes include "Institutionalisation of the role of local political leaders", "The influence of financial and economic conditions on leadership style choices", "The influence of frontline workforce expectations", "The influence of geographical considerations", "The influence of partnership on leadership style choices", "The influence of political-administrative relationship on leadership style choice", and "Acknowledgement of skills".
 - References Table:**

Name	Files	References
Governance structure and membership of IIBs	3	4
Committees	1	1
IIB board	3	8
Partner organisation	3	3
Responsibility	2	3
Stakeholders	3	5
Institutionalisation of the role of local political leaders	4	10
Navigating governance regulations, constraints and limited resources in local political leadership within integrated governance	7	12
Role and challenges of local political leaders	9	17
The influence of financial and economic conditions on leadership style choices	8	15
Budget pressure	4	4
Challenge status quo	1	1
Effective communication among partners	3	3
Financial dependency	3	3
Financial challenge	4	6
Financial constraint	3	3
Financial optimisation	2	4
Funding model	3	3
Lack of coordination	1	1
Separate budgets	2	3
The influence of frontline workforce expectations	5	9
The influence of geographical considerations	12	29
The influence of partnership on leadership style choices	7	17
The influence of political-administrative relationship on leadership style choice	9	22
Acknowledgement of skills	3	3
Collaboration	5	5
Constructive	2	2
Cooperation	6	7
Mutual respect	6	6
Organisational culture	5	7
Personal relationships	3	3
Polite behaviour	1	1
 - Right Panel:** A preview of a reference snippet with a coverage percentage of 2.84%. The text reads: "They don't really they don't, I don't fur the interaction with the director, as planning partnership, and doing oth them, but they don't come to me v discussions or emailing me or writr chief executive they do they they w".

This screenshot illustrates the hierarchical node structure of interview analysis.

Appendix K: Themes, descriptions, and codes of the interview qualitative data analysis (Chapter 6).

Theme	Description	Codes
Governance structure and membership of IJBs	This theme referred to the organisational and institutional arrangements and processes that governed the H&SCI policy area, such as the roles, responsibilities, and relationships of the IJB board members, the partner organisations, and the other stakeholders.	"IJB board", "partner organisation", "stakeholder role", "responsibility", strengths, "committees" "political parties".
Role and challenges of local political leaders	This theme referred to the role and function of the local political leaders in the H&SCI policy area, such as setting the representation, the scrutiny, and the accountability. This theme also included the challenges they faced, such as, the uncertainty, the conflict, and the workload.	"Strategic direction" "Autonomy", "representation", "advocacy", "scrutiny", "accountability", "workload" "Questioner" "transformation"
Institutionalisation of the role of local political leaders	This theme referred to the process and outcome of establishing and embedding the role of local political leaders in the H&SCI policy area, such as the recognition, the legitimacy, the influence, and the impact of the local political leaders. This theme also included strategies that facilitated or hindered the institutionalisation of the role of local political leaders.	"Board member" "IJB chair legitimacy," "limited role" "authority" "recognition", "influence", "facilitator" "diverse perspective" "consensus" "communication".
The politics of depoliticization: balancing neutrality and constructive political engagement	This theme referred to the dilemma and paradox of the local political leaders in the H&SCI policy area, which required them to balance between being neutral and apolitical and being engaged	"depoliticization", "constructive role" "bureaucratic-political understanding" "community's needs" "accountability" "trust" "blame game".

	and political. This theme also included the benefits and risks of the depoliticization and politicisation, such as the consensus, the cooperation, the trust, and the transparency, or the disagreement, the opacity.	
Navigating governance regulations, constraints, and limited resources in local political leadership within integrated governance	This theme referred to the challenges and opportunities, which involved navigating the complex and changing governance regulations, constraints, and limited resources that affected the H&SCI policy area. This theme also included the responses and strategies of the local political leaders to cope with the governance challenges and opportunities, such as complying, adapting, resisting, or, constraints, and limited resources.	<p>“Political budget priorities”</p> <p>“Collective decision making”</p> <p>“Inclusivity”, “Democratic”,</p> <p>“limited resource”,</p> <p>“Compliance”, “Strategic thinking”, “resisting” “limited autonomy” “flexibility”.</p> <p>“Community preference”.</p>
Fostering community engagement and co-production: navigating challenges and building trust in healthcare service delivery	This theme referred to the role and function, which involved fostering community engagement and co-production in the H&SCI service delivery. This theme also included the challenges and opportunities of the community engagement and co-production, such as the participation, the empowerment, or disempowerment, the alienation, and the dissatisfaction.	<p>“Community organisations”</p> <p>“community engagement”,</p> <p>“innovation” “Honesty”</p> <p>“participation”, “volunteering”,</p> <p>“ownership”, “Activism”</p> <p>“Trust”</p>
Challenges in creating a transparent and accountable environment	This theme referred to the challenges and opportunities, which involved creating a transparent and accountable environment for the H&SCI service delivery. This theme also included the factors and	<p>“Bureaucratic leader role”,</p> <p>“communication” “inclusive environment” “competing priorities” “feedback”, “trust”</p> <p>“power dynamics”</p>

	strategies that facilitated or hindered the transparency and accountability, such as the information, the communication, the feedback, and the evaluation.	“accountability” “Comfortable environment for participation”
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Appendix L: Themes, descriptions, and codes of the interview qualitative data analysis (Chapter 7).

Theme	Definition	Codes
The influence of financial and economic conditions on leadership styles	This theme referred to the influence of the financial and economic conditions and constraints on the role and leadership styles of the local political leaders in the H&SCI policy area. This theme included the perceptions and experiences of the local political leaders and the senior officials on the financial and economic challenges and opportunities.	“Financial pressure”, “Separate budgets” “lack of funding” “financial dependency”, “lack of coordination”, “challenge status quo” “efficiency planning management”, “budget optimization” “commitment” “communication” “Funding model” “Strategic thinking” “Officers dependency” “acknowledgement of skills” “accountability”. “Family background and income level”.
The influence of partisanship on leadership styles	This theme referred to the influence of the political affiliation and ideology on the role and leadership styles in the H&SCI policy area. This theme also included the perceptions and experiences of the local political leaders and the bureaucratic leaders on the partisanship and its consequences.	“Political competing priorities” “Nonpartisan” “inclusiveness”, “ideological similarities”, “adaptive”, “political conflict”, “political accountability” “political interference” “limited autonomy” “political compromise” “common ground” “Centralisation”.
The influence of political-administrative relationship on leadership styles	This theme referred to the influence of the relationship between the local political leaders and the bureaucratic leaders on their role and leadership styles. This theme also included the perceptions and experiences of the local political leaders and the bureaucratic leaders on the political-administrative relationship and its dynamics.	“Senior official key role”, “personal relationships” “Trust”, “mutual respect”, “transparency”, “organisational culture” “polite behaviour” “clear communication” and “acknowledgement of strengths” “technology hinder relationship building” “collaboration”, “cooperation”, “tension”, “turnover of members”, “Constructive”.

<p>The influence of geographical considerations on leadership styles</p>	<p>This theme referred to the influence of the geographical characteristics and diversity of urban/rural community needs on the role and leadership styles. This theme also included the perceptions and experiences of the local political leaders and the bureaucratic leaders on the geographical considerations and their implications, such as the accessibility, the availability, the quality, and the integration of the H&SCI services.</p>	<p>“Large boards” “optimal boards” “Scrutiny” “deliberations”, “supporting officers” “inclusiveness” “familiarity” “personal relationships” “political harmony”” mutual understating “ “innovative community engagement” “collaboration” “strong feeling for community hospitals” “Community consultation” “direct approach” “proactive approach “ “lack of workforce” “innovative approach” “Deprivation levels” “ co-production” “ lack of consensus building” “Innovative approach” “Transport issues”.</p>
<p>The influence of frontline workforce expectations on leadership styles</p>	<p>This theme referred to the influence of the expectations and demands of the frontline workforce on the role and leadership styles. This theme also included the perceptions and experiences of the local political leaders and the bureaucratic leaders on the frontline workforce expectations and their feedback, such as the satisfaction, the dissatisfaction, the complaint, and the compliment.</p>	<p>“Expect clear leadership ““expect direction” “informal discussions”, “feedback”, “compliment”, “Disagreement” “Strategic consultation” “Result oriented direction” “Lack of consultation” “not valuing frontline voices” “principle leadership” “personal relationship” “local workforce” “personal connections” “Empathy”.</p>